

Understanding the social stresses affecting the families of Algerian students and students of these families during the period of their PhD studies in the UK in the context of family separation.

HOUDA AGGOUN

Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements
of the University of the West of Scotland
for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

Declaration

I hereby declare that this thesis is resulted from my own original work, but for the acknowledged quotations and citations. I also confirm that this Ph.D. thesis has not been previously and is not being currently submitted for the reward of any other academic degree at the University of West of Scotland or any other institution.

Name: Houda AGGOUN.

Signature: Personal details withheld.

Date: 15 November 2023

Dedication

I dedicate this thesis to:

My family, the most important of my life, who has always supported me throughout this journey.

My dearest parents *Fatima* and *Chaabane*.

My beloved sisters: *Amina* and *Asma*.

My beloved brothers: *Imed Eddine*, *Abdesslem* and *Amar*.

My cute niece *Miral* and lovely nephew *Yazen*.

My grandfather's memory, *Mouhammed*, who passed away the end of this thesis.

My closest friend who was always by my side throughout this journey.

All my loved family and friends.

Acknowledgments

I express my gratitude to the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research for funding this study.

I would like to thank my supervisors, Dr Chris Holligan, Dr Susan Henderson-Bone, and Dr Conny Gollek for their support, patience, and academic guidance throughout my PhD journey. Special thanks go out to Chris for helping me become the autonomous researcher I am today and for kindly understanding my circumstances.

My gratitude also goes to all staff in the university of the West of Scotland who assisted me throughout this journey.

I am also thankful to the participants who took part in this research; without their thoughts and views, this thesis would not have been made.

Many thanks to my dearest family for believing in me and encouraging me to start off this learning experience, thank you for your prayers.

Abstract

This research study aims to understand the social stressors impacting families of these Algerian students and students themselves during the period of their doctoral journey in the UK. It explores how students, and their families perceive social stress and conceptualize family separation. It also aims at learning about the coping strategies they use to cope with family separation and social stress. The research is constructivist, and a descriptive multiple-case study design has been used. Data have been collected using qualitative semi-structured interviews with 18 students (90-180 mins) and 11 family members (60- 120 mins). Thematic analysis has been used to analyse the collected data. Findings showed that social stress for Algerian students and their families is originated from separation and study where all the stressors they came across were separation-related and study-related. With reference to the impact of COVID pandemic in intensifying these stressors, participants expressed the psychological and emotional impacts of separation on their mental health. Participants' conceptualizations of family separation were related to physical and emotional absence and presence. Algerian PhD students and family members pointed out to their use of social media, religious, emotional coping, and positive thinking to cope with separation and stress.

Keywords: social stress, family separation, family members, Algerian students.

Table of Contents

Declaration.....	2
Dedication.....	3
Acknowledgments.....	4
Abstract.....	5
Table of Contents.....	6
List of Tables.....	13
List of Figures.....	14
List of Abbreviations.....	15
Chapter One: General introduction.....	16
1.1. Personal experience and motivation.....	16
1.2. Statement of the problem/ Rationale.....	17
1.3. Research questions.....	21
1.4. Research aim and objectives.....	21
1.5. Structure of the thesis.....	22
Chapter Two: Context of the study.....	24
2.1. Introduction.....	24
2.2. Algeria: general overview.....	24
2.3. The educational system in Algeria.....	25
2.3.1. Basic education phase.....	25
2.3.2. Higher education phase.....	26
2.4. The educational reforms in Algeria.....	26
2.4.1. Higher education reforms.....	26
2.4.2. The Bologna process and Algeria.....	27

2.5. The status of English in Algeria.....	28
2.6. Family in Algeria.....	28
2.7. Chapter summary.....	30
Chapter Three: Theoretical Framework.....	31
3.1. Introduction.	31
3.2. Stress as a concept.....	33
3.3. Sociology and stress.....	34
3.4. Theories of stress.....	36
3.4.1. Psychological stress and coping theory.....	36
3.4.2. Selye's theory of systemic stress.....	38
3.4.3. Social stress theory.....	38
3.5. Social stress theory and the current study.....	40
3.6. Chapter summary.....	42
Chapter Four: Literature review.....	44
4.1. Introduction.....	44
4.2. Studying abroad.....	44
4.3. Transition and migration.....	46
4.3.1. Transition.....	46
4.3.2. Migration.....	49
4.4. International Students' Experiences of Studying Abroad	50
4.4.1. International students' challenges in study abroad context.....	50
4.4.2. International students' benefits of study abroad.....	53
4.5. International students and social support.....	54
4.6. Globalization and internationalization.....	55

4.7. Students' mobility.....	56
4.7.1. Purposes of students' mobility.....	59
4.8. Family.....	60
4.8.1. Definition of family.....	60
4.8.2. Types of family.....	61
4.8.2.1. Nuclear family.....	62
4.8.2.2. Joint family.....	62
4.8.3. Family relationships.....	62
4.8.4. Impact of family separation on mental health.....	64
4.9. Social media.....	66
4.9.1. Definition of social media.....	66
4.9.2. Types of social media.....	66
4.9.2.1. Collaborative projects.....	67
4.9.2.2. Blogs.....	67
4.9.2.3. Content communities.....	68
4.9.2.4. Social networking sites.....	68
4.9.2.5. Virtual game worlds.....	69
4.10. Chapter summary.....	69
Chapter Five: Research methodology.....	70
5.1. Introduction.....	70
5.2. Research approach.....	70
5.3. Research paradigm.....	71
5.3.1. Interpretivist / Constructivist paradigm.....	72
5.3.1.1. Ontology.....	73

5.3.1.2. Epistemology.....	73
5.4. Research method.....	74
5.4.1. Qualitative research method.....	75
5.5. Research design.....	76
5.5.1. Case study design.....	76
5.6. Data collection.....	79
5.6.1. Pilot study.....	79
5.6.2. Semi-structured interviews.....	81
5.6.3. Online interviewing.....	82
5.6.4. Sampling strategies.....	83
5.6.5. Sample dimensions.....	85
5.7. Data analysis.....	88
5.7.1. Thematic analysis.....	89
5.7.2. Transcription.	89
5.7.3. Translation.....	91
5.7.4. Coding process.....	92
5.7.4.1. Codes generation.	92
5.7.4.2. Themes formation.....	94
5.8. Trustworthiness of the research.....	94
5.8.1. Credibility.....	94
5.8.2. Dependability.....	95
5.8.3. Transferability.....	96
5.8.4. Confirmability.....	96
5.9. Reflexivity and researcher positionality.....	96

5.10. Ethical considerations.....	99
5.11. Chapter summary.....	101
Chapter Six: Perceptions of social stress.....	102
6.1. Introduction.....	102
6.2. Participants’ conceptualizations of social stress.....	102
6.2.1. Separation-related stress.....	104
6.2.1.1 El Ghorba – feeling alienated.....	105
6.2.1.2. Being perfectly responsible.....	109
6.2.2. Study-related stress.....	112
6.2.2.1. Taking PhD in Algeria.....	116
6.3. Chapter summary.....	121
Chapter Seven: Social stressors impacting students in the UK and their families in Algeria during separation.....	122
7.1. Introduction.....	122
7.2. Separation-related stressors.....	122
7.2.1. Losing a family member.....	122
7.2.2. Health issues.....	127
7.2.3. Racism and discrimination.....	133
7.3. Study-related stressors.....	143
7.3.1. Students’ perspective.....	144
7.3.1.1. Meeting deadlines.....	144
7.3.1.2. PhD completion and securing a job.....	146
7.3.1.3. Lack of Data.....	148
7.3.1.4. Supervision-related issues.....	149
7.3.1.5. The weather.....	153

7.3.2. Families’ perspective.....	155
7.4. The COVID-19 pandemic.....	158
7.5. Chapter summary.....	164
Chapter Eight: Perceptions of family separation.....	166
8.1. Introduction.....	166
8.2. Participants’ conceptualizations of family separation.....	166
8.3. Impacts of family separation on mental health.....	176
8.4. Family separation and family relations.....	184
8.5. Family separation and family support.....	192
8.6. Family separation and gender.....	200
8.7. Missing a family member VS missing a family.....	204
8.8. Chapter summary.....	210
Chapter Nine: Coping strategies Algerian students and their families use to cope with family separation and social stress.....	211
9.1. Introduction.....	211
9.2. Religious coping.....	211
9.3. Emotional coping.....	217
9.4. Avoidance coping.....	225
9.5. Positive thinking.....	228
9.6. Social media.....	239
9.7. Chapter summary.....	249
Chapter Ten: General conclusion.....	250
10.1. Introduction.....	250
10.2. Summary of the study.....	250
10.3. Contribution of the study.....	252

10.4. Limitations of the study.....	253
10.5. Implications of the study.....	256
10.5.1. Implications for universities.....	256
10.5.2. Implications for Algerian students studying abroad.....	257
10.5.2. Implications for families of Algerian students studying abroad.....	258
10.6. Further research.....	258
References.....	260
Appendices.....	291

List of Tables

Table: 5.1. Different Types of Case Studies.

Table: 5.2. Algerian PhD students' background.

Table: 5.3. Family members background.

List of Figures

Figure: 5.1. Transcription with Arabic and Latin letters of Alphabets.

Figure: 5.2. Transcription with Arabic letters of Alphabets.

Figure: 5.3. Back translation sample.

Figure: 5.4. Coding process using Microsoft Word Document.

List of Abbreviations

FOI: Freedom of Information.

BEM: Brevet d'Enseignement Moyen (certificate of intermediate education).

MENA: Middle East and North Africa.

OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development.

ONS: Office for National Statistics.

HE: Higher Education.

BERA: British Educational Research Association.

Chapter one: General introduction

1.1. Personal experience and motivation:

After completing my master's degree in Didactics of Foreign Languages and Cultures at Khenchela University, Algeria, I was among the 100 chosen candidates, in March 2017, for the government scholarship to take postgraduate research in the UK. My journey started when I first departed to the UK to study a pre-sessional course in the English university of Canterbury Chris Church (Guerriche, 2020).

During the pre-sessional course, I noticed that students were different in coping with living abroad; some have easily managed to live alone with other Algerian colleagues under the same programme, while others found it very difficult to cope with life in the UK alone and were eager to go back to Algeria to join their families. I had a pre-conception that students gender played a critical role in their extent of coping with living alone in the UK, although there were not many male Algerian students. I even thought that the ethnic group Algerian students belong to in Algeria might have an impact on their ability to live alone away from family. I, myself, found it very challenging to live in the UK away from my family, especially for the first time, and I felt so lonely although I was surrounded by many Algerian students. The ideas I had, raised my interest in the experiences of international students and Algerian students in the UK and led me to have a mind conception that students' identity changes differently from one student to another in study abroad contexts. Thus, my first research proposal for the PhD was intended to research "the cultural identity changes of Algerian postgraduate research students studying/ studied abroad in the UK and the impact of the British culture and highly enriched environment on their cultural identity". The following year, I started my PhD course at the university of the West of Scotland researching this topic, which turned later into this thesis.

As an Algerian PhD student in the UK, I have always reflected on Algerian students' experiences and how different they are from my experience, and whether a given situation, a social event for example, would be experienced differently by each one of us, as we are all Algerian students and came from the same cultural background; and so is the case for families in Algeria, I wondered whether all students' families struggled in the same way and to the same extent to cope with the absence of their adult children.

My experience of separation because of studying in the UK presents a starting point in conducting this study. It is crucial to note here, however, that I had to be consciously aware and pay attention to the potential impacts of my experience and pre-assumptions on the interpretations of qualitative data. Therefore, I had always to be cautious about my opinion and not to prioritise it over that of the participants because the study aims to primarily promote the perspectives of the participants. So, my experience helped me in this study to get an insider position at some points throughout the course of the research because of my familiarity of the research context, which allowed me to build rapport with the participants as I approached the topic from within since I am one of the Algerian students in the UK before being the researcher of the study. However, I make no claims here that such a topic should be researched from the same context of the research, yet approaching the topic by researchers outside of the box could opt for a different research design and build different findings and interpretations. Also, if I am to research Algerian students taking doctoral research in another destination country other than the UK, my approach, position, and interpretations could be different than this thesis and this would result in a different thesis.

1.2. Statement of the problem/ Rationale:

In recent years, there has been a dramatic increase in the movement of migration and people's mobility over the world. International migrants' global number increased to reach 272 million in 2019 up from 50 million in 2010 to represent 3,5 per cent of the world's global population (United Nations, 2019). People decide to migrate to a foreign country for several reasons, which can be classified under economic, political, social, or academic factors that affect people's lives (World Migration Report, 2018; Lundholm, Garvill, Malmberg and Westin, 2004). This is because: some people migrate to another country as refugees to run away from their country's political situation, some may migrate to settle in the host country, others tend to migrate to pursue their studies. Although people migrate for different reasons and pass through different experiences in migration settings, they still share a common factor that they experience and might suffer from which is the separation from their families and relatives. Family separation is seen as the hardest part of the migration journey (Suárez-Orozco, Bang, and Kim, 2011). Additionally, separation of family members in situations of migration can result in psychological, educational, social, and emotional hardships on children as well as their parents (Giannelli and Mangiavacchi, 2010). That is, family separation is an unavoidable aspect of migration (Moskal and Tyrrell, 2015).

Family separation can have negative results on both members of the family: the migrating ones and those who remain at home; grief and fear for safety and wellbeing of others are results of family separation (Savic *et al.*, 2013). In fact, family relationships mainly depend on the mutual feeling between its members, which affect the different stages of their lives in a way or another. Accordingly, “relationships between parents and children in early childhood can affect a wide range of behaviours later in life” (Gindling and Poggio, 2012, p.1157). Experiences of separation among family members can produce emotional memories that last in members and greatly affect their personal and family lives. In a similar context of separation, a study has been conducted on imprisonment experiences of Scottish teenage children. Life history interviews were conducted with a group of young prisoners convicted of violation to collect the required data for this study to see how prisoners perceive events. Separation and anxiety were one of the main results. Participants, in this study, explained how painful the loss of a person’s beloved ones is and being separated from people they are so attached to. (Holligan, 2013).

In her work with Siri Lankan Tamil refugees immigrated to Australia, Kandasamy (2018) considered family separation in the resettlement and civil war that result in long-standing and emotional memories of determination and fear. The study was done through conducting life story interviews with the 10 participants. The study findings showed that the emotional experiences of people shape the memories of family separation in different areas, and that people understand the call for family in their daily life when they pass through long-range family relationships.

Since most of the universities worldwide are seeking to internationalize their systems of higher education, studying abroad has become a large-scale phenomenon that attracted a huge number of students to study in foreign universities (Teichler, 2017). Students are not always prepared to cope with such transitional situations from the original community they belong to, to the host community they are willing to live and study in. They used to live with their families and relatives and study with their friends and colleagues in their home country. However, that is not the case when they travel abroad and live all alone in a foreign country to study and achieve an academic degree to empower their academic life. In the same regard, it has been said that “the individuals when they move from their hometown to a new environment, it will have a result on internal stress as they will miss their families, friends” (Thomas and Sumathi, 2016, p. 62). Students are expected to be emotionally affected from the separation from their families, and to experience some strong feelings that may have a great impact on

their wellbeing as well as their studies such as grief, loneliness, disruptions...etc. By way of explanation, international students' mental health is highly affected by the separation from their families and their home countries. In this context, attachment theory can be used to explain the close relationships between family members especially between children and their parents or caregivers. Attachment theory was developed by Bowlby in 1969 to interpret the close links and relations between children and their caregivers (Brumbaugh and Fraley, 2010). This separation of international students from their families obviously urge them to have some kind of social support from their families and friends. Thomas and Sumathi (2016) emphasised that the social support provided by the family and friends can decrease the level of stress students studying abroad face and need to manage.

The mobility of international students over the world has greatly increased in the last decades. African students contribute to studying abroad. In this context, Campus France (2016) acknowledged that, in 2013, the UNESCO evaluated 373,303 as the number of African students who graduate with in international diploma. In the same report pointed out that nearly 21% of African students are originated from North Africa mainly: Algeria, Morocco, and Tunisia on top of them (Campus France, 2016). The University World News (2013) stated that African students almost represent the tenth of international students in the world and 6% of the students in Africa, where the greatest numbers of African students that study beyond Africa are originated from: Morocco, Nigeria, Algeria, Zimbabwe, Cameroon and Tunisia.

To gather information to support the rationale for this study, a Freedom of Information request has been made on the 7th of August 2019 with a set of universities mainly in Scotland, which are Edinburgh University, University of Glasgow, University of Stirling, Edinburgh Napier University, University of Aberdeen, and Glasgow Caledonian University. These universities have been chosen because they are the prominent universities in Scotland that receive considerable numbers of international students on annual basis in the last years. The Freedom of Information request was designed to ask for data about the mental health of postgraduate students, UK nationals and internationals. The pre-mentioned universities were asked to: give information about the number of students declaring to the university a mental health issue, e.g., depression, break these statistics down by gender and ethnicity, mention the systems of support available for students to use within the university and the types of mental health issues reported by its frequency, and its name/category (see appendix A).

The purpose behind doing an FOI with some of universities, from one hand, is to get a background of international students' state in UK universities. From the other hand, the FOI data gives an idea about how the coming of international students from different ethnic backgrounds contributes to the total migration movement in the UK. Some of the universities provided me with detailed information about international students within their university. These universities are mainly: Glasgow Caledonian University, University of Aberdeen, and Edinburgh Napier University. The FOI universities responses are provided in this thesis (see appendices B, C, D).

Based on what mentioned earlier and the FOI responses, international students, despite their gender and ethnicity, often encounter and experience some issues during their studies abroad, mainly academic, psychological, and emotional, which affect their mental health. These mental health issues such as depression, anxiety, and panic attacks in most cases, require support to be overcome. Universities, on the other hand, usually provide students with systems of support to help them get over these issues. Moreover, and based on the data generated from the FOI, African students possess a portion in the wide range of international students in the UK. In this context, it has been highlighted that “as the number of African students attending British universities continues to grow, there is a need to study their adjustment” (Maundeni, 2001, p. 253).

This study focuses on Algerian students as one minority group of the wider community of international students in the UK. In the last few years, considerable numbers of government-sponsored students came from Algeria to take doctoral degree in the UK (Guerriche, 2020). As they study abroad away from their home country, Algerian students come across great difficulties and struggle to adapt when they find themselves in a foreign country inside a western culture (Ghodbane, 2020). Looking at the experience of these Algerian students from the angle of their families who remain in Algeria also represents a worth-researching subject. This is because, from one hand, most of research that addressed international students focused on the academic, social, and cultural experiences of the students for instance, Zhang and Brunton's (2007); Sawir *et al.* (2008); Kosheleva *et al.* (2015); Wu, Garza and Guzman (2015) and Nada and Araújo, (2018), and not about their families back home; from the other hand, the few studies that dealt with Algerian students in the UK such as: Ghodbane (2020); Guerriche (2020) and Sadoudi (2021) have mostly focused on the voice of Algerian students themselves and not their families. Therefore, my argument in doing this research is that separation from family would have a great impact on Algerian students in the UK and their families who are

still in Algeria as members belonging to a collectivist society. Also, to understand such transitional situations in the lives of Algerian students and their families, it is of a great importance to understand the social stresses students and their left-behind families pass through and get impacted with in this transitional situation from the perspectives of both parts involved in the experience to get a full understanding and a clear vision of such study abroad experience.

1.3. Research questions:

Considering what discussed earlier, the central research question for this study sought to explore the social stresses that impact Algerian students, and their left-behind families, during the period of conducting doctoral research in the UK as follows:

- What are the social stresses affecting the families of Algerian students and students themselves during the period of their PhD studies in the UK?

The main research question that led this study aimed to understand the major points that Algerian students face during their study abroad journey while they are pursuing their postgraduate studies in the UK and get stressed with, and how they cope with separation. Hence, the main research question was divided into two sub- research questions as follows:

1. How do Algerian PhD students manage the social stresses they experience in the UK and cope with family separation?
2. How do families of Algerian PhD students manage the social stresses they experience back home and cope with family separation?

1.4. Research aim and objectives:

This research aimed to gain an understanding of the social experiences in relation to stress of Algerian students in the UK in a study abroad context and their families back home in Algeria, and to know about family relationships and family separation in the context of these experiences. Accordingly, the following objectives were formulated to achieve the study's main purpose in full:

1. To understand how Algerian PhD students and their families back home perceive social stress and how they co-construct its definition.
2. To understand what has been experienced throughout the family separation of Algerian families and their children in the UK that could lead to social stress.

3. To find out how Algerian students and their families back home perceive and conceptualize family separation.
4. To learn about the coping strategies that Algerian students and their families back home tend to use to cope with family separation, manage stress and maintain their relationships.

1.5. Structure of the thesis:

This thesis consists of ten chapters structured as follows:

Chapter one presents a general introduction that provides a background of the topic to state the main problem of the study. It also addresses the research question, aims and objectives. It highlights the researcher's argument behind undertaking this research. The chapter also tackles my personal experience and how it contributed to shaping this study.

Chapter two presents the context of the study. It gives an overview on the historical, geographical, and socio-cultural context of the Algerian society. It also discusses the system of education in Algeria and highlights the nature of families in Algeria.

Chapter three presents social stress theory, the theory that frames the study. It reviews literature about the central element of the study "stress" and explains it in relation to the theory and the study. It also explains how this theory was applied to this study to expand the understanding of the experiences of PhD students in the UK and their left-behind families.

Chapter four reviews the literature to generate a link between what has been stated in knowledge about the field of the study and the topic of this research. It presented pertinent research regarding the notions of migration, transition, student's mobility, and internationalization of higher education. It also reviews literature about the challenges in study abroad context and the role of social media in such context. It also introduces the concept of family, its definition, types, and its impact on individuals' mental health.

Chapter five deals with the research methodology of this study. It discusses the research design and method of the study. It introduces the philosophical stances of the study and how interpretivism and social constructivism shaped this research. Then, it justifies why qualitative approach and case study design were suitable to conduct this research, followed by a thorough description of the data collection tool used (semi-structured interviews). Finally, I give an overview of the steps followed in the data analysis. Ethical considerations of the research were eventually discussed.

The next four chapters (6-7-8-9) present and discuss the findings of the study respectively as follows: participants' perceptions of social stress, the social stressors affecting students in the UK and their families in Algeria during separation, participants' perceptions of family separation, and the coping strategies Algerian students and their families use to cope with family separation and social stress.

The last chapter presents a general conclusion of the thesis through offering a summary of the study. It highlights the contribution of this research to knowledge and addresses the implications and limitations of the research. Finally, it provides recommendations for future research.

Chapter two: Context of the study

2.1. Introduction:

After finishing their higher education (Bachelor and Master studies), many Algerian students are pursuing their doctoral studies in the UK as they got a scholarship from the Algerian government to carry out a PhD study (Ghodbane, 2020; Guerriche, 2020). This research aimed to study the social stresses impacting the Algerian students and their families back home during the period of conducting a PhD study in the UK. Accordingly, it dealt with Algerian international students who are taking PhD course in the UK along with their left-behind families as a population for the study. Thus, it is important to note that these students have received all their education in Algeria before starting their PhD in the UK. Their age is between 25 and 30 approximately, as being 25 years old or under was a condition to pass the scholarship contest to get a fully funded PhD course in the UK (Guerriche,2020). This chapter discusses the educational background of these Algerian students prior to being PhD students in the UK along with discussing the social context of families in the Algerian society.

2.2. Algeria: general overview:

Algeria is the largest African country that is situated in North Africa with a size over 2 million Km² and a population around 41,5 million (Abbou, 2022; Djoudi, 2018). Religiously, Algeria follows the Malachite branch of Sunni Islam (European Commission, 2017). Linguistically, Algeria has declared itself as “Arabic and Muslim: the successive constitutions since 1963 have remained unchanged with regard to this matter” (Chaker, 2006, p. 136).

Algeria is a linguistically and culturally diverse country mainly consist of two outstanding groups of people in the Algerian society, the Berbers, and the Arabs, depending on which language they speak: Arabic or Berber (Rabehi, 2021). Berbers consist of four different ethnic groups: Chaoui, Kabyles, Mozabites and Tuareg. Both Arabic and Berber languages contain different varieties where Arabic has less varieties than Berber language (Belmihoub, 2018). Additionally, it has also been stated that “Algeria is a culturally diverse and a linguistically heterogeneous country. Four languages are distinctive in the country: Standard Arabic (SA), Algerian Arabic (AA), Tamazight, and French” (Gherzouli, 2019, p.27). Most of Algerians, today, speak Algerian Arabic with around one fifth of the Algerian population still speaking different Tamazight dialects in Kabilya, Aures (Shawiya), Ghardaya (Mouzabit) and Ahhagar (Touareg) (Selougui, 2019; Achoui, 2006; Benrabah, 2005). Adouane and Dobnik

(2017) viewed Algerian Arabic as a mixture of different Arabic dialects in North Africa and language spoken by people in Algeria. As for Tamazight, it has been declared in February 2016 as an official language for the country along with Arabic language by a constitutional amendment while French is used as a lingua franca (European Commission, 2017).

2.3. The educational system in Algeria:

Since Algeria's independence, the educational system was given a fundamental importance, and the Algerian Ministry of Education was established in 1963 as the sole authority owning the right to design and supervise the educational system in Algeria. The educational system in Algeria is governed by the principles stated in the Algerian constitution. The education system in Algeria is made up of two phases: the basic education phase and the higher education phase. Education is compulsory and free for all children no matter what their sex is. Starting from the age of six, Algerian children are obliged to get an education until the age of 16 (Ouadah-Bedidi, 2018). The higher education is made up of three cycles: Bachelor, Master, and Doctorate (Gherzouli, 2019).

2.3.1. Basic education phase:

The basic education phase consists of 9 years of schooling throughout three successive levels (Ouadah-Bedidi, 2018). Since the independence of Algeria until 2003, these levels were designed as 6 years in primary school, 3 years in middle school and 3 years in secondary school (Selougui, 2019). After 2003, the (5-4-3) model was implemented and the levels were designed to 5 years of primary school, 4 years of middle school and 3 years of secondary school.

The mandatory years of schooling usually starts from the age of six years old in primary education (Ouadah-Bedidi, 2018). Students are assessed according to their results of course work. The promotion to the intermediate education depends on the students' performances in the fifth grade's national final exam. On the other hand, the intermediate education level currently consists of four years to be studied in middle schools and ending with a national exam; the certificate of Brevet d'Enseignement Moyen (BEM) is awarded to students who succeeded in this exam which gives students the right to study for the secondary education level (Selougui, 2019). The study in the secondary education level is composed of three years and offers students to study one of three main streams based on their requirements: Letters and Philosophy, Foreign Languages, and Science; the latter is divided into three subdivisions, Mathematics, Technical Mathematics, and Management and Economics (Selougui, 2019). This phase of education is concluded by the Baccalaureate exam; a national official exam that offers

students the opportunity to proceed to the university (Selougui, 2019; Ouadah-Bedidi, 2018). At this stage, after getting the Baccalaureate exam, students would start their journey of higher education.

2.3.2. Higher education phase:

Higher education plays a crucial role in the development of countries. “Higher education should play an important role in society as it produces knowledge, transfers it to learners, and fosters creativity, improvement, innovation and wellbeing” (Benouar, 2013, p.361). Only qualified students in the Baccalaureate exam or those who hold an equivalent certificate can get a free higher education (Ghodbane, 2020). The system of higher education in Algeria covers a total of 91 institutions spread all over the country: 74 universities, 10 university centres, 19 Higher Education National schools, 5 teachers training colleges, 10 preparatory schools and 2 integrated preparatory classes (Benouar, 2013). The last twenty years have seen rapid growth and development in Algeria’s higher education; the latter was predominated by the French system of education since Algeria’s independence in 1962 (Ghodbane, 2020). In 2004, the LMD system (Licence, Master, and Doctorate) was implemented in Higher education by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research under the Bologna process (Mami, 2013).

2.4. The educational reforms in Algeria:

During the French colonial period, the systems of education in Algeria were dominated by the French colonization (Fekih, 2020). French was mandated as the national language for Algerians to be learnt; Arabic and its dialects in Algeria, however, presented a form sign of identity at that time with only 10% of Algerians who could join schools for education (Rezig, 2011). After gaining independence in 1962, the Algerian government created the Ministry of Education in 1963 and implemented a set of educational reforms for the basic (see appendix E) and higher education (Fekih, 2020).

2.4.1. Higher education reforms:

Since Algeria’s independence in 1962, the French system of higher education has highly impacted higher education in Algeria (Ghodbane, 2020). The Algerian higher education system was first following the traditional French model which based on the principle that universities are free to design their teaching curricular (Rezig, 2011). In 1971, there has been a significant reform in higher education to modernize the Algerian university. To better meet

the demands of the country, this reform attempted to change the university management, assessment procedures, instructional contents, and teaching and learning methodologies (Gherzouli, 2019). Another major reform was in the 1980's which worked on arabizing the first year in Social and Political Sciences, Law and Economics (Rezig, 2011). In 2004, the LMD (License/Master/Doctorate) reform took place under the Bologna process, which aimed at fostering students' mobility and to meet international standards of higher education (Gherzouli, 2019; Benouar, 2013).

2.4.2. The Bologna Process and Algeria:

The Bologna process is an educational reform that has been set in higher education system by some European countries in 1999 for the sake of enhancing the quality of higher education. Accordingly, it is stated that “

The expression ‘Bologna Process’ (BP) refers to multi-national reforms and changes currently undertaken by European states, with varying scope and pace, in order to implement the goal of creating a barrier-free European Higher Education Area (EHEA) characterized by ‘compatibility and comparability’ between the higher education systems of the signatory states (Papatsiba., 2006, p.95).

The Bologna process first started its impact in Algeria in 2004 when the Algerian universities started adopting the LMD system. Accordingly, it is asserted that “As matter of fact, a decision was made to implement the European educational system known as LMD – Licence - Master - Doctorate in 2004” (Sarnou, Koç, Houcine and Bouhadiba, 2012, p. 180).

Recently, Algeria developed an ambitious initiative to join international partnership with the Anglophone world (Chellia, 2018). The British Embassy and the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education aimed at strengthening their partnership by offering scholarships to Algerian students to pursue a doctoral degree in the United Kingdom and Northern Ireland to improve the quality of higher education (Guerriche, 2020). In 2014, the ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research of Algeria made an agreement with the UK government to send 500 Algerian PhD students in English, who will be fully funded by the Algerian government, to UK universities in the next five years (Guerriche, 2020; British Council, 2014). The Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research selects candidates from different Algerian universities for each academic year, based on certain criteria (age, academic discipline, and records) and organizes a national contest to take 100 successful students for this scholarship (Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, 2014). Students in this study came to the UK under this programme.

2.5. The status of English in Algeria:

English is the language of international communication in the world due to the huge number of its speakers. It dominates political, economic, cultural, scientific, and industrial fields whereby most of the technological and scientific innovations were in English as the “language of scientific knowledge” (Benrabah, 2007, p. 194). The Ministry of Education in Algeria made English the second foreign language, after French, in the Algerian educational system to make the latter in line with international education standards (Selougui, 2019). English is introduced to students at the age of 11 in intermediate education and taught to as a mandatory course for seven years throughout the intermediate and the secondary education (Benrabah, 2007). In higher education, however, students, who choose to study English language in bachelor’s degree, have three divisions: English language, English literature, or English culture in their masters.

English is taught for educational reasons and has few opportunities to be practiced outside the school for daily life communications. In the last decade, English language has known a dramatic spread in Algeria as a second foreign language (Gherzouli, 2019; Belmihoub, 2018), whereby different conventions were made to improve the status of English such as: a free English language classes program has been launched by the US embassy in Algeria and Berlitz centre in 2013 to Algerians to learn English regardless of their age and proficiency level, the Algerian ministry of education cooperated with the oil company Anadarko who sponsored a program led by the British council to provide 69 teachers with a training in the language (Gherzouli, 2019; Belmihoub, 2018).

Although students in this research were students of English language in Algeria, English can be a challenge for them when they come to study abroad as they use English in all aspects of their lives in the UK not only in their academic life. Thereof, “language discrimination hinders many international students from adapting to a new social environment” (Lacina, 2002, p. 22). Thus, English language can generate stress for Algerian students during their studies abroad.

2.6. Family in Algeria:

As this study deals with family separation in the context of Algerian students taking doctoral research in the UK and their left-behind families, it is important to give a background about the nature of families in Algeria.

As the official religion of Algeria, Islam governs almost all aspects of Algerians life. (Tiliouine and Achoui, 2018). Families in Algeria are highly impacted by Islam and social customs. This is because, as one of the MENA (Middle East and North Africa) countries, Algeria depends on the Quran to set the rules of the society life (McIntosh and Islam, 2010). In 1984, the Algerian family code was enacted to clarify the laws organizing family and family relations in Algeria, which was established based on the Islamic law (Smail Salhi, 2008).

During the French colonization, families in Algeria were structured as extended families, especially in the countryside, that used to include grandparents, their married and unmarried sons along with the families of the married ones, widowed and/ or divorced daughters and their children (Achoui, 2006). Families are patriarchal and patrilineal in which the father leads the family, takes responsibility of all the family members, and decides about all their matters (Berrezoug, 2021; Tiliouine and Achoui, 2018). Family members share a common house with separate rooms for each married couple. Males have the authority over females (Ghiat, 2019); women are under the authority of their fathers before getting married and of their husbands after marriage where being a housewife is their sole job. All family members help in raising up the children (U.S. Library of Congress, 1994).

Families in Algeria are structured as large families that include small families. Two different words are used to refer to family in Arabic language *Aylah* and *Osrah* (Achoui, 2006). As for *Aylah*, it refers to small and nuclear families that usually consist of parents and their children; *Osrah*, on the other hand, used to refer to extended families that include members from at least three generations: grandparents, parents, and children and sometimes grandchildren, and usually denote the traditional principles of family members more than *Aylah* (Tiliouine and Achoui, 2018). Thus, Algerian society can be described as collectivist in essence, where families are guided by the concepts of cooperation, solidarity, and dependency which are inherently rooted in the Algerian society because of the Islamic religion values and social heritage (Tiliouine and Achoui, 2018). Members of the same family support each other and seek to defend the dignity and honour of the family, where wives are supposed to obey their husbands; on the other hand, husbands are responsible to fulfil demands, take care of family members and safeguard the family honour. Additionally, elderly people should be respected along with the mother who is the most loved and looked after person in the family according to the Islamic principles (Achoui, 2006).

2.7. Chapter summary:

This research aims at understanding the social stresses experienced by Algerian students taking postgraduate research in the UK and their left behind families in the context of family separation. This chapter, therefore, highlighted the context of this study by presenting an overview on Algeria, its history, and its socio-cultural context with reference to the ethnic diversity of the Algerian society. The chapter also discussed the system of education and introduced the place of English as a foreign language in Algeria. Finally, this chapter shed light on the family dynamics that frames the Algerian society. The following chapter discusses the main theory used to guide this research.

Chapter three: Theoretical Framework:

3.1. Introduction:

The previous chapter that dealt with the literature review of this research study which covered the notions of migration, students mobility, family separation, and their associated ideas about emotions, social and emotional support along with the research question that sheds the light on the context of Algerian students who take their PhD studies in the UK and their families back home in Algeria proposed a call for researching and understanding the social stresses impacting both the families of Algerian students and students themselves during the period of their PhD studies in the UK. That is to say, the research study aims to know about the social stresses that affect the students' daily lives and mental health in the UK along with their families back home in Algeria in the context of family separation resulting from study abroad contexts. In other words, family separation can affect the mental health and wellbeing of the members being researched. In line with this, it has been stated that "one consequence of separation was a constant worry about the wellbeing and safety of significant others back home and around the globe" (Savic, Chur-Hansen, Mahmood and Moore, 2013, p.385). This is due to, as it has already been stated in the literature review chapter, the extended nature of families in Algeria where grandparents, parents, and children all live together and share their lives in the same family house, which makes people more attached and closer to each other (Achoui, 2006). That is, Algerian students can get affected when it comes to pursuing their studies in countries other than their own and stay all alone away from their families. In this context, separation has been explained as the loss of the parents' bond where children lose protection and love from their parents, which may lead them to face some kind of emotional and social stress (Gindling and Poggio, 2012, p. 1157). This suggests a need to have a theory to frame, guide and support in understanding the research study. This is because a theory "serves as the foundation upon which research is constructed" (Adom, Kamil, Agyem, 2018, p. 438). Additionally, "having a firm theoretical base strengthens research, as it identifies assumptions and enables the researcher to evaluate and critique them" (Cohen, Manion and Morisson, 2018, p.71). That is, grounding the research with a theory helps the researcher to explain and articulate the heart of the problem being researched and studied. A dictionary of sociology (2014, p.101) explains theory as "an account of the world which goes beyond what we can see and measure. It embraces a set of interrelated definitions and relationships that organizes our concepts of and understanding of the empirical world in a systematic way".

Thus, based on the essence that the overarching research question aims to study, social stress theory is the most appropriate theory that guides and frames the research study. This is because the main research question for the current research study aims to understand the social stresses impacting the families of Algerian students and students themselves during the period of their PhD studies in the UK. In other words, the current chapter is devoted to study “social stress theory” as the theory that has been identified as a theoretical framework to guide the research. This is because, this theory provides an explanation to look at the main stressors in relation to family separation in the context of students who are separated from their families to study abroad. In this regard, it has been claimed that several frameworks or models have been used to study the relationship between health and stress (Dressler, Oths and Gravlee, 2005).

With such a globalized world, the number of students who opt for studies across borders has immensely increased (Faleel, Tam, Lee, Har and Foo, 2012). Going to university can be of some degree of stress for students as they encounter a new educational and social setting. However, the level of stress can even be greater for international students who leave their home countries to pursue their studies away from their families especially in cultures where students used to live together with their families and have not experienced living alone as single adults before. Algeria would be an example of that as most families in the Algerian society are built as extended families and started recently to be separate families that constitute from parents and children. That is to say, in addition to the normal requirements that local students may face and need to fulfil when they transit to university level, international students come across more difficulties because of the new culture, new environment and separation from their families. In this regard, it has been stated that “difficulties with the following linguistic, academic, interpersonal, financial, and intrapersonal problems constitute unique sources of stress for international students” (Mori, 2000, p. 137).

Despite the fact that study abroad can be of a great benefit for students as they pass through new experiences in their lives, the doubt and uncertainty in the new surroundings can be a source of frustration and discontent for them which might be resulted from the absence of social support, language barriers and cultural diversities. Additionally, it has been indicated in previous research that cross-cultural differences, language barriers and lack of social support have a significant impact on international students’ psychological wellbeing (Yeh and Inose, 2003). In this context, several research studies have been carried out to study stress among international students (Poyrazli and Lopez, 2007). This is due to the fact that different stressors and sources of stress affect international students’ mental health especially the lack of social

support and the separation from their families as it has been found in previous research studies. Moreover, it has even been documented in research that separation from family is considered to be an outstanding source of stress that has negative effects on the mental health of individuals (Savic, Chur-Hansen, Mahmood and Moore, 2013). In line with this, Chen (1999) asserts that international students when they come to study in foreign countries face changes that are full of uncertainty and unknown as this transition may include language obstacles, difficulties associated to the new countries' lifestyle and culture adaptation, which could be experienced as a threat and a challenge for them. Thus, he views that "stress in one way or another becomes an unavoidable psychological factor for international college students" (Chen, 1999).

The current chapter, therefore, aims to deal with stress and stress related theory that has been selected to frame the research. The chapter starts with a presentation on defining stress as a concept. Then, a section is allocated to review stress in relation to sociology. Thereafter, the most prominent theories of stress are discussed. Most importantly, the chapter deals with social stress theory, along with its application on this research, as a main theory to frame the research study.

3.2. Stress as a concept:

From its general and broadest meaning, the term stress denotes the worry and pressure that occurs to individuals and results from the problems and difficulties they face in their lives. The concept of stress has been used and defined in many ways by different scholars in social science, psychology, biology and even anthropology after it has gained a place of interest in academic research. "By the end of the 1950's, stress as a legitimate subject of academic study had arrived" (Newton, Handy and Fineman, 1996, p. 31). In other words, it has been almost 60 years bygone since stress has been studied and researched for the first time. This is because the term "stress" has been first used by Hans Selye, who is considered to be the founder of stress research, and defined it as "nonspecific response of the body to any demand" in his work *The Stress of Life* in 1965 (Tan and Yip, 2018). Selye's definition of stress is still regarded as the plainest definition that explains what physiologically happens to individuals' bodies when they get out of their equilibrium and balance. Selye's concept of stress influenced different fields such as sociology, psychology, medicine and biology (Tan and Yip, 2018).

"Stress is any situation that evokes negative thoughts and feelings in a person" (Menaga and Chandrasekaran, 2014, p. 1973). However, these situations can differently be perceived by people. That is to say, a given situation that is experienced and perceived as stressful for a

person may not trigger and stress another person to the same extent. Thus, nearly all people know how the feeling of stress looks like and perceive it as being uncomfortable (Crum, Salovey and Achor, 2013). This is because stress cannot be avoided in nowadays' life due to the fast-moving society (Papen, Niemand, Siems, and Kraus, 2017). In addition to Selye's definition of stress, another plain definition was given to stress in the 1980's and still be used by researchers today because of its clarity. The concept of stress denotes "a state of imbalance within a person, elicited by an actual or perceived disparity between environmental demands and the person's capacity to cope with these demands" (Maes, Vingerhoets and Van Heck, 1987, p. 567). In other words, the concept of stress is used to indicate individuals' instability because of the social challenges and the external forces they come across. In this context, it has simply been explained that "stress can also be defined as, any change in the body's equilibrium" (Ghatol, 2017, p. 38).

As stress causes a state of imbalance in people, it obviously affects their lives, families, relationships, and health. In line with this, it has even been claimed that "stress free creates pleasant environment such as mental peace, better and healthy thoughts and good relations" (Reddy, Kannekanti, and Hamza, 2015, p.18). Stress generally arises from the situations people come across in their lives. These stressful situations urge individuals to cope with this stress as it threatens their balance as individuals and may lead to negative consequences. Stressors is the concept used by most researchers to refer to the social aspects that cause and make people feel stressed. As a plain explanation, it was stated that "stressors, of course, refer to the experiential circumstances that give rise to stress" (Pearlin, 1989, p.244). In this regard, "stress is simply defined as emotional disturbances or changes caused by stressors" (Ghatol, 2017, p. 38).

3.3. Sociology and stress:

A dictionary of sociology (2014) regards stress as a general and nonspecific concept that is common in our everyday life to denote feelings of pressure and anxiety. The same dictionary explains stress as "it may refer to external situational pressures (stressors) or to the responses to them (stress reactions)—responses usually assumed to have physical and psychological components, such as raised pulse-rate and adrenalin levels, and feelings of anxiety and discomfort" (Scott, 2014, p.98).

Considering the social factors and organization in the social environment is regarded as a must when it comes to understanding the human behaviours. This is because sociology deals with the social life of human beings at most. In this context, it has been asserted that

“sociologists have an intellectual stake in the study of stress. It presents an excellent opportunity to observe how deeply well-being is affected by the structured arrangements of people's lives and by the repeated experiences that stem from these arrangements” (Pearlin, 1989, p.241). That is, sociology is mainly based on the idea that social forces, which are originated from the environment, frame human behaviours.

In his book entitled *Suicide* in 1897, Emile Durkheim, the French sociologist, put emphasis on individuality among human behaviours and discussed the impact of social forces on individual behaviours. This book contributed to grow interest in that social forces from the social environment originate individual human behaviours. In his work, Durkheim wondered about whether suicide is a completely individual behaviour and a personal choice based on the individual's free will, why averages of suicide differ from one group of society to another, from men and women, married and unmarried. He admitted that suicide could happen because of many different reasons. The latter differs from one individual to another among social groups.

In his work on suicide, Durkheim discussed the notion of social integration and its impact on family and aspects of the individual's life like religion and politics. He deduced that rates of suicide depend on how much the individual is socially integrated with the group he/she belongs to (Wray, Colen, and Pescosolido, 2011). According to Park and Lester (2006), Durkheim's theory of suicide mainly stands for two main points, which are social integration and social regulation. They explained social integration as “the extent to which the people in a society are bound together in social networks” (Park and Lester, 2006, p.48). As for social regulation, it has been explained as “the extent to which the desires and behaviours of the members in a society are controlled by social values and norms” (Park and Lester, 2006, p.48). That is, Durkheim's theory of suicide suggested that there is an inverse relationship between suicide and social integration. When the individual is highly integrated in the social group he/she belongs too, it is unlikely for him/her to commit suicide. However, suicide is more likely to happen when individuals have low levels of integration in their societies.

Based on what has already been stated before, Durkheim's work on suicide is considered as an outstanding example of how individuals get affected by the social forces and organizations in their societies. In this vein, Aneshensel (1992, p.33) claimed that “the occurrence of social stress, therefore, can be seen as an inevitable consequence of social organization”. That is, social experiences can affect individuals and cause them to face certain level of stress. In line with this, it has even been argued that “social statuses create or reflect

structured conditions characterized by differential exposure to social stress” (Turner and Turner, 2005, p.211). They have explained the exposure by giving employment status as an example which result in job-related and financial issues as stressors but can also affect the physical environment and cause problems in life (Turner and Turner, 2005). The next section is devoted to discussing the most prominent theories of stress including social stress theory.

3.4. Theories of stress:

Several research studies had been conducted to study the concept of stress. As a result, different theories have been formulated on stress in psychology, biology, and sociology (Søren Ventegodt and Wiedemann, 2014). Starting from the fifties, the concept of stress had a widespread use in different domains. At the beginning, the term was used in physics to indicate external powers and forces that are applied on a given structure and result in a malformation of that structure. In other words, engineers use the term stress to denote to the external force and strain that result in a deformation. (Krohne, 2002). However, the term stress has been differently used to mean different things in domains like psychology and biology that deal with humans’ behaviour and health. It is used to denote the individual’s body reaction that resulted from circumstances and demands. Those external forces and circumstances that urge the human’s body to react are referred to as stressors. In this regard, it has been clarified that “stressors, of course, refer to the experiential circumstances that give rise to stress” (Pearlin, 1989, p.243). These stressors are considered as challenges to individuals and urge them to seek for resources to cope with them, which is to say, stressors represent those conditions and situations that threaten and challenge humans and may affect them in a negative way if they cannot cope with them. That is, “the combination of greater exposure to stressors and fewer resources to cope with stressors may result in a deterioration of mental and physical health statuses” (Elliott, 2000, p. 288).

Theories of stress are mainly concerned with the relationship between the external stressors and the human’s body reaction to this stress. Physiologists and psychobiologists developed systemic stress theory. Psychological stress has been researched by researchers in the domain of cognitive psychology.

3.4.1. Psychological stress and coping theory:

Psychological stress and coping theory (also called Lazarus and Folkman’s Transactional Theory) is a theory that has been developed on psychological stress by Lazarus and Folkman in 1987 to provide some visions and understandings on how individuals are

influenced by stressful events in their environment and cope with them. The theory suggests that individuals evaluate and appraise the demand or the stressor and then initiate some strategies to cope with these environmental stressors. It is mainly based on how individuals assess the events rather than how difficult and stressful the event is. In this context, it has been claimed that Lazarus and Folkman's theory of stress and coping "takes into account individual appraisal of stressful events rather than the occurrence or severity of the event itself" (Kelso, French and Fernandez, 2005, pp.3-4).

According to Krohne (2002), the theory basically depends on two key concepts: appraisal and coping. Appraisal refers to the phase when individuals assess the event and decide about its relevance to their wellbeing regarding its harm and beneficiality. As for coping, it refers to the individual's attempts and efforts to manage and cope with the faced stressful events. According to Lazarus and Folkman (1984), a stressor appraisal comprises a primary and a secondary appraisal that takes place within the same time and interplay to decide about the importance of the happened event and its relation to the individual's wellbeing. Individuals, in primary appraisal, attempt to determine the significance of an event or a situation to their own beliefs, values, and goals. This allows individuals to assess the stressor, interpret it and evaluate its impact on their wellbeing. Then, individuals decide whether it is irrelevant and requires no modulation for their well-being, positive after deciding that the stress or the demand is not threatening their wellbeing and that there is a possibility to boost it, or stressful when the stressor is perceived as threatening and negative for their wellbeing. As for the secondary appraisal, individuals try to assess what can be done as a response or a strategy to avoid the maximum of harm or benefit from the gains of the demand through coping strategies.

As it has previously been mentioned, individuals may perceive situations differently. That is, a certain situation can be experienced as stressful by a person and unstressful by another, which makes people differ in the evaluation of events. In line with this, "a key feature of the model is that individuals differ in their appraisals of similar events and circumstances" (Kelso, French and Fernandez, 2005, pp.3-4). After the foundation of this theory by Lazarus in 1966 as a comprehension theory, it knew different revisions: Lazarus and Launier 1978, Lazarus and Folkman 1984, and Lazarus 1991. The latter revision views stress as the relationship that links between persons and their environment rather than considering it as behavioural or psychological reaction because of a certain stimulation (Krohne, 2002).

3.4.2. Selye's theory of systemic stress:

After the work of Hans Selye in 1976, the concept of stress has been accepted as a term in many languages, gained its popularity in science, and started to be a subject of research studies. “Selye claimed to have coined the term stress, which was consequently accepted into the lexicon of various other languages” (Stojanovich,2010, p.A272). In a set of his studies on animals, Selye noticed that different events of stimulation for example applying the stimulus of heat and cold produces certain responses and reactions. Each stimulus results in a certain response or produces its own effect (Krohne, 2002). Hans Selye’s systemic theory of stress is also known as the response-based model of stress as it mainly puts emphasis on the psychological consequences that results from facing stressful situations.

3.4.3. Social stress theory:

There have been some studies that were conducted using the social stress process model to explain the relationship between social differences and health disparities (Osborne and McLanahan ,2007; Meyer, Schwartz and Frost, 2008; Meyer and Schwartz, 2010; Osborne, Berger and Magnuson, 2012). Social stress theory was generated from that model (Mossakowski, 2014). It is well known that Pearlin and partners (1981) are the leading authors who theorized about the social stress process, that is social stress theory. The process of social stress covers coping mechanisms, exposure to stressors, and its impact on mental health (Mossakowski, 2014). Social stress theory is the theory that is used to clarify stress related aspects and issues in the social life. Stojanovich (2010) listed some examples that can be considered as contributing factors to stress as follows: jail period, changing place of residence, changes in social acts and sleeping styles and deterioration of political situations. The theory is comparatively a new theory as it is yet developing through research. In this vein, it is clearly explained that “interest has recently surged in the use of social stress models” (Chaouloff, 2013, p. 179). This is because attention has recently drawn to the effects of social stressors on individuals’ psychologies and mental health. In another context, it has been even explained that “social stress theory is about the sociological category of disadvantage and not about particular disadvantaged groups” (Schwartz and Meyer, 2010, p.1113). In the same context, Schwartz and Meyer (2010, p.1113) explained that the expression “disadvantaged groups” is used to refer to individuals of lower social position and status who pass through difficult situations and conditions that result in them experiencing more stress which makes them struggle with these stressful conditions. They have also explained the expression of “disadvantaged groups” by

that group of people who are subjected to prejudice, discrimination and stigma and can face health problems because of them (Schwartz and Meyer, 2010). They have argued that social stress theory has not met sufficient attention from researchers on its possibility to support research studies about mental health (Schwartz and Meyer, 2010).

“Stress is not an inherent attribute of external conditions but emanates from discrepancies between those conditions and characteristics of the individual-his or her needs, values, perceptions, resources, and skills” (Aneshensel, 1992, p.16). Social stress theory suggests that stress can result from bad and even good social experiences that individuals pass through. It also proposes that not all the stressful events can stress all individuals. In this regard, it is stated that “exposure to stress also differs across the life course. Younger adults appear to experience more stressful life conditions than middle-aged and older adults” (Turner and Turner, 2005, p.211). However, a stressful event or experience that can lead a person to a certain level of stress may not stress another person. In line with this, it has been asserted that “socio-environmental conditions differ in the capacity to evoke stress, however; some conditions threaten virtually everyone, whereas others are uniformly navigated with ease” (Aneshensel, 1992, p.16). In order to study the social stresses that affect the families of Algerian students and students themselves during the period of their PhD studies in the UK, it must be realized that these students along with their families pass through different experiences of transition. That is, not all these students and families experience the same difficulties and social stresses, which denotes that a range of coping strategies will be used. Changes to an individual’s life are stressful even if the general scope of the transition is good. In this context, it has been claimed that “stress research continues to emphasize one particular type of stressor, life-event change” (Aneshensel, 1992, p.17). This feature of social stress theory makes it the suitable theory to frame the current research to study the social stresses affecting the families of Algerian students and students themselves during the period of their PhD studies in the UK. Thus, the current research focuses on applying the theory of social stress on the context of family separation in relation to study abroad contexts from the perspectives of Algerian students taking doctoral research in the UK and their left-behind families.

As it has already been mentioned, social stress theory was regarded as the most suitable theory to be used in research studying the relationship between mental health and social differences. Despite the wide range of research studies that have been done on stress, social stress theory has not been used a lot in research. Few research studies have used social stress theory and applied it on their research on health disparities and social status: Osborne and

McLanahan ,2007; Meyer, Schwartz and Frost, 2008; Meyer and Schwartz, 2010; Osborne, Berger and Magnuson, 2012. On this basis, using such theory to frame the current research study gives the researcher a point to be original in conducting the research. Thus, the next section is devoted to discussing the reasons and premises why social stress theory has been seen as the appropriate theory for this study.

3.5. Social stress theory and the current study:

Social stress theory presents a valid theoretical framework to study research about health disparities and differences (Dressler, Oths and Gravlee, 2005). “Social stress theory has been used as an explanation of the persistent relationship between social inequality and mental health disparities” (Mossakowski, 2014, p.1). Social stress offers extensive illumination to the empirical dimension of the study. The central elements of the theory “stress” and “social” are reflected in the main research question that guides the research study, that is, to understand the social stresses affecting the families of Algerian students and students of the families themselves during the period of their PhD studies in the UK. This makes social stress theory a useful and valid theory for the current research study due to its possible applicability to the research and its contribution in extending the understanding of the research. This is because of the claim that “a useful theory is one that tells an enlightening story about some phenomenon. It is a story that gives new insights and broadens your understanding of the phenomenon” (Anfara Jr and Mertz, 2006, p. xvii). Stress, at a distance, is an unusual concept as many experience stress within more physically proximate places. On this subject, it has been asserted that different forms of stress, depending on the reasons behind, are really of a great importance as being exposed to socially stressful settings can last for weeks, months or even years (Lederbogen, Haddad and Meyer-Lindenberg, 2013).

This theory is seen as a valid and overarching framework theory to study Algerian students as an ethnic and national minority group from the Arab students at micro level and international students at macro level who are conducting their postgraduate studies in the UK. As a social theory, it connects with psychological issues which the extract denotes in the claim that “sociological interest in stressful life circumstances originated to explain associations between markers of social placement such as class, gender, and minority group status and rates of mental and emotional disorder” (Aneshensel, Rutter and Lachenbruch, 1991, p.166). This theoretical model has been a little misleadingly perhaps referred to as the “sociological paradigm”. The latter sees social circumstances as a prime reason that evoke mental stress for

people of disadvantaged or discriminated groups (Aneshensel, Rutter, and Lachenbruch, 1991). The reason behind choosing this theory to frame the research study is that social stress theory stands for the idea that “people with disadvantaged social status are more likely to be exposed to stressors and to be more vulnerable to stress because they have limited psychosocial coping resources, which, in turn, lead to a higher risk of becoming mentally ill” (Mossakowski, 2014, p.1). Algerian students are arguably disadvantaged through marginality in a foreign culture where they are a minority without social and economic capital that ties them into the host’s forms of capital. It is in this way they are “outsiders” to the UK and its academia.

Social stress theory suggests that positive life events can result in loads of stress just like the negative events can do to individuals. Osborne and McLanahan (2007, p.1067) asserted that “according to social stress theory, even “positive” events, such as getting married, forming a new partnership, or ending a bad relationship, may ironically lead to increases in stress”. In order to study students, mainly females and some males in the third decade of their age, who have experienced family separation in the context of study abroad; it is of a great importance to mention that these students have also experienced a number of transitions at the level of their psychology, emotions, and mental health. These effects of family separation can also be applied to the students’ family members who have been left back home. In line with this, psychologists have noted that “family separation has a negative impact on the mental health of family members - mothers, in particular, often experienced depression and/or physical illness” (Gindling and Poggio, 2012, p.1158). Transitions are commonly stressful as they cause a change in a certain routine in an individual’s life even if this change is made to be good and positive. For that reason, social stress theory is viewed as the appropriate and most suitable theory to frame the study as it matches the context of Algerian PhD students studying in the UK in which students might have reasons to support and reasons to oppose their study abroad experiences despite being separated from their families back home. That is to say, despite the fact that having the chance to pursue a PhD course as internationals is good for Algerian students, their experiences of transitions in terms of changes in culture, system of life, and system of education can fractionally be stressful and challenging. Thus, it is seen that social stress theory is appropriate to be used to frame the current research study as it mainly stands for the idea that life events can be stressful to people no matter whether these events are positive or negative.

Additionally, social stress theory tends to deal with disadvantaged groups of a certain social position who encounter stressful situations and experiences (Schwartz and Meyer, 2010).

Algerian students as well as their families, in the current research study, are regarded as disadvantaged groups who come across stressful situations because of family separation. However, they, Algerian students and their families, represent disadvantaged groups with different conditions and face different stresses. This is because students' families in Algeria still have each other despite missing one member of the family whereas students studying in the UK miss all members of their families. This illustrates another feature of social stress theory that makes it more appropriate to be used in the research. The feature is that theory of social stress is centred on studying the notion of being socially disadvantaged and not about certain disadvantaged groups (Schwartz and Meyer, 2010).

Another reason why social stress theory has been chosen as a theoretical framework for this research would be that Algerian students along with their families back home are going through different stressful experiences depending on their situations and life conditions despite the fact that they are all going through the "student-family" separation experience that might have negative impact on their mental health, and all students are studying abroad to get a PhD degree. This is owing to the centrality of social stress theory on social change-health relationships. In line with this, it has been claimed that "social stress theory describes a mediator in the relationship of social structure and illness" (Meyer, Schwartz and Frost, 2008, p.368). Additionally, Osborne, Berger and Magnuson (2012), based on social stress theory, suggested that transition type is crucial to define whether life events will result in long-term effects.

The current section was allocated to explain the reasons behind selecting social stress theory and use it as a theoretical framework for the research study. The theory was seen useful for the research as it extended the understanding of the main research question that seeks to understand the social stresses affecting the families of Algerian students and students of these families during the period of their PhD studies in the UK and gave new insights about the research ideas. It helped in explaining the situation of Algerian PhD students and their families back home in the context of family separation as disadvantaged groups who are exposed to high levels of stress and mental health problems.

3.6. Chapter summary:

Stress is amongst the most common problems international students' worldwide face during their study abroad experiences because of the lack of social support (Yeh and Inose, 2003). The lack of research on Algerian students' experiences of studying abroad in British

universities as well as their families back home was the motive behind conducting this research. Moreover, I am, the researcher herself, addressing this research problem from within, as I am one of those Algerian students, who take their PhD study in the UK, and left her family back home in Algeria. I have experienced and still experiencing different social stressful situations throughout my PhD journey in the UK as being separated from my family.

Like international students worldwide, Algerian students come across different difficulties and challenges that affect their mental health and psychology and shape a source of stress for them. Therefore, the current study focuses on understanding the social stresses affecting the families of Algerian students and students of these families during the period of their PhD studies in the UK. The fundamental focus of the research, that is “social stresses”, hints that a stress related theory could be appropriate to frame the research and broaden its understandings. Social stress theory has been selected as a valid and suitable theory to be applied on the research study. This is due to its appropriate features that can be applied to the research context. For that reason, the current chapter built the discussion on social stress theory in relation to the current research study where the main features and principles of the theory were applied to the context of the research.

Chapter four: Literature review

4.1. Introduction:

The review of literature in this chapter aims to clearly build a link between what is currently stated in knowledge about the field of the study and the topic of the research. It goes over the notions of migration and students' mobility and their associated concepts in study abroad contexts. The literature review aims at building the researcher's argument by describing the bigger picture of what has been done in previous research to identify the gap in research (Ridley, 2012). In this chapter, the literature was done through searching in a set of online academic databases such as Education source and Web of science, online journal websites like: Science direct, SAGE journals, Springer link, Taylor and Francis journals, and Wiley online library and website such as Google scholar. The literature searching process also involved searching in scientific social networking such as Academia and Research gate. Key words and citation-based search were the main search strategies used during the literature searching process. The key words were related to the main concepts covered in this chapter and combining them in different ways for instance: migration, mobility, globalization, internationalization, higher education, study abroad, international students. Several articles and journal articles along with books were selected to be read, examine, and obtain literature from them.

4.2. Studying abroad:

Studying abroad, which has recently known a dramatic increase with globalization, is being regarded as a crucial aspect and an overwhelming phenomenon of higher education especially in well-developed countries (Li, Chen and Duanmu, 2010). The major common destinations for international students are the United Kingdom, France, Australia and the United States of America. Certainly, international students' experiences abroad are completely different from their experiences back home. This is because international students leave their families and relatives back home and travel overseas to another country to pursue their education, which leads them to come across new experiences all alone in isolation from their families. In this context, Sawir *et al.* (2008) conducted a study on loneliness and international students in Australia and interviewed 200 international students. The study revealed that almost two-thirds of the interviewed students faced issues of isolation and loneliness particularly in the early periods of their journeys abroad. According to them, international students experience three types of loneliness: personal loneliness due to the lack of contact with families, social

loneliness due to the lack of social networks, and cultural loneliness, which arises from the favourite cultural environment's absence. This serious loneliness makes international students in desperate need of social media to stay connected with their families and friends back home. "Social media plays an important role for international students" (Chang and Gomes, 2017). Social media plays a crucial role in the experiences of international students abroad in keeping them in touch and offering them the opportunity to have direct communication with their families in their home countries (Gomes, Berry, Alzougool and Chang, 2014, p.345). This is due to the new advances in communication through social media, which connects international students with their original cultures and home countries such as Skype, Facebook, Viber, Instagram, and Twitter. Saw, Abbott, Donaghey, and McDonald (2013) found that the most used kind of social media by international students is Facebook, and they identified the most common reasons that lead international students to use social media as chatting with friends, keeping up with friends' activities and staying in touch with family.

Several studies have been conducted to study the experiences of international students when living abroad as international students are facing completely new environments in the host country and come across many issues, which are mainly related to the relations between the international students and the new environment. Similarly, "The US, the UK, and Australian literature on international students—and English-speaking countries more generally—have plentiful studies that focus on students' adjustment to the host country and the needs of international students in higher education" (Oplatka and Hemsley-Brown., 2010, p.115). Studies on the experiences of international students are mainly conducted in these countries as they host the almost largest numbers of international students in the world.

As international students are separated from their families to study abroad, they face many challenges and difficulties within their educational and social life for instance loneliness and isolation, homesickness, loss because of the new social norms and culture. In this respect it is illustrated that "the literature pertaining to international students demonstrates that mental health is connected with many aspects of international student lives, not only because they are often at an age when mental health issues may arise, but also because of their new social environment" (Forbes-Mewett., 2019, p.3). Mental health becomes one of the most researched topics about international students. Moving to a completely new foreign setting can generate many different health issues notably mental health and psychological stress (Norton and Brett, 2011). The challenging situations international students come across in the host country led them to face certain levels of stress. The latter makes them in need of some kind of support so

that they can overcome their emotional, educational, and social challenges. Immigrants experience a kind of loss referred to as “ambiguous loss” to denote the inability to recover after losing a loved one who is emotionally present and physically absent (Gindling and Poggio., 2012; Boss, 2010).

International students present different types of life history in terms of the diverse cultural and linguistic backgrounds they come from and belong to in their home countries for instance social norms and behaviours, which might have an impact on the socio-cultural learning environment they come across in the host country. This diversity may cause feelings of confusion and disorientation for students that make them in need of support especially at the emotional level. “International students are constantly trying to adapt to new living conditions that encompass a change in the built environment, and a lack of social support” (Bhochhibhoya, Dong and Branscum, 2017, p.672).

4.3. Transitions and migration

Moving to a new academic and social environment at a foreign university can be a new and stressful experience for international students. This transition of students from their home education to a different university in the host country can support and help them develop their academic engagement and self-confidence. Research about students’ transition from their home countries to a new university in the host country has mainly focused on international students’ difficulties of adjustment to a completely new and different cultural, social and academic environment. Additionally, literature on educational transition is seen as a challenge for researchers due to the different meanings and definitions the word “transition” is given especially when coming to research the transition to postgraduate studies which has not been sufficiently explored. In this context, it is admitted that “in contrast to other types of educational transition, the transition to postgraduate study has not benefited from a wide and diverse literature” (Tobbell, O’Donnell and Zammit, 2010, p.261). Additionally, in the same work, Tobbell, O’Donnell and Zammit approach the notion of educational transition and admit that “educational transition can be understood, in simple terms, as the shift from one educational environment (primary school to secondary school, school to university, the shifting of study between universities) to a different one” (Tobbell, O’Donnell and Zammit, 2010, p.265). From this definition of educational transition, it can be deduced that shifting between universities across borders is also classified under the umbrella of educational transition

4.3.1. Transition:

The word “transition” means the change from one state to another (Reger, 2016). Correspondingly, it is also stated that “the notion of transition generally indicates the progression from the familiar to the unknown and involves the adoption of new cultural, social, and cognitive challenges” (Prescott and Hellstén, 2005, p. 76).

Transition is a subject of interest for many researchers in different fields of research such as sociology, education, psychology, and other fields, which contribute to the existent literature on transition in research. Hereof, “the literature on transition generally is necessarily broader than the literature on educational transition specifically; and the educational transition literature in general encompasses more than just higher education transition in particular” (O’Donnell, Kean and Stevens, 2016, p.5). About educational transition, “transition to postgraduate study is largely overlooked in the educational transition literature” (O’Donnell *et al.*, 2009, p.29). There are lots of researchers who have studied and are interested to study transitions in education.

Crafter and Maunder (2012), in their work “Understanding transitions using a sociocultural framework” approach transitions from an educational point of view. They claim that “transitions encompass more than the move from one physical location (e.g. moving from one school to another) or a forward trajectory in age (e.g. developmental periods). Transitions are complex and multi-faceted and invariably involve changes to self-identity born out of uncertainty in the social and cultural worlds of the individual” (Crafter and Maunder, 2012, p. 3). According to them, transition cannot be understood only by focusing on the individual or the context but rather the focus shifts on the social and cultural explanations of the individual and the context, which admit the behaviours, and thoughts of the individual. It appears that the word “transition” refers to the process of physical change from one location to another, the movement, or the evolution from one stage to another that affects the individual’s identity. Accordingly, Crafter and Maunder define transition as the change that is caused by or has been affected by social and external situations and lead individuals to shift their understandings of themselves (Crafter and Maunder, 2012).

In another work *Navigating change: a typology of student transition in higher education*, Gale and Parker (2014) argued that the concept of “transition” is under-theorised in research especially in the field of higher education. Research that has already dealt with transition and attempted to define it, found it difficult to understand it in relation to its reasons.

Accordingly, it is admitted that “it is impossible to arrive at a single definition of transition that might gain consensus” (Colley, 2007, p.428).

In the same work, Gale and Parker (2014) pointed out three conceptions through which student transition can be conceptualised. These conceptions are transition as induction, as development and as becoming. Transition as induction covers “sequentially defined periods of adjustment from ‘one institutional and/or disciplinary context to another ... navigating institutional norms and procedures” (Gale and Parker, 2014, p.738). That is, the emphasis is put on the periods of time during transition. It considers transition as successive determined periods of adaptation from one context or institution to another through which individuals come across new norms, curriculum, institutional practices and pass through new experiences that lead to culture shock. The latter signifies the level of stress people face when they come across new and unfamiliar situations and find it difficult to adapt to these new situations which may increase their stress. The stronger is the level of stress, the more likely is turned to strong feelings of anxiety, loss and confusion. In this context, culture shock is defined as “the anxiety and feelings of disorientation and uncertainty that a person feels when he/she has to function within a different and unknown culture” (Chen, Lin and Sawangpattanakul, 2011, p.249).

The second conceptualisation, however, focuses on the stages of development during the transitional period rather than focusing on the periods of time. Transition as development encompasses the different phases of the individuals’ maturation and the impact of their experiences during the transitional period on their identity and identity formation after experiencing some critical and sensitive situations and incidents. Gale and Parker view transition as development as “qualitatively distinct stages of maturation from one student and/or career identity to another... navigating sociocultural norms and expectations” (Gale and Parker, 2014, p.738). Gale and Parker view these first two conceptualisations of transition as linear processes while the third conceptualisation as a spiral move. They consider transition as becoming to be characterised by “perpetual series of fragmented movements, lived reality or subjective experience, from birth to death, navigating multiple narratives and subjectivities, rhizomatic, zigzag, spiral movement, and crisis as neither period/stage specific nor necessarily problematic” (Gale and Parker, 2014, p.738).

Gale and Parker’s third conceptualisation considers transition as an aspect that characterises the human’s life during their lifespan rather than viewing it as a period or a stage of adjustment that can be categorised in the human’s life. This can be explained by the fact that

transition to higher education might be of some degree of stress and anxiety, but this is not the case for all students as their experiences of transition might be different which decides upon the positivity or the negativity of this change. This view of transition is also highly matched with Crafter and Maunder's conception of transition that focuses on the experience of change instead of focusing on the process of change.

As mentioned earlier, transition has been differently conceptualised by researchers, which led them to categorise these conceptions in different ways. Moreover, when attempting to give definitions to the concept of transition, researchers may refer to different things and describe them differently as denoting transition. In this context, Colley (2007) sums up the notion of transition as "it is predominantly constructed as a process of change over time-whether the change is conceptualised as being in contexts for learning or in learners' identities (or both), whether it takes place over a short or long-time span and whatever the causes and consequences of that change may be" (Colley, 2007, p.428).

4.3.2. Migration:

The phenomenon of migration has associated with different domains of human life such as work, education, healthcare ...etc. Hence, migration has been turned into one of the most studied subjects by researchers for years. Several definitions were given to the word migration. Essentially, migration has been defined as people's movement and leave, either individually or in groups, from their original place to another place with the intention to settle temporarily or permanently due to different reasons political, economic, religious ...etc. Similarly, "migration is the relocation of individuals to some distant place, i.e., at least beyond one's own city or town" (Bartram, Poros, and Monforte, 2014, p.4). In sociology, migration is defined as "the permanent movement of individuals or groups across symbolic or political boundaries into new residential areas and communities." (Gordon, 2009, p. 415). Gordon (2009) also emphasizes that a distinction should be made between push and pull factors in the studies of migration; where pushing factors are those motives that encourage people to migrate while pulling factors are those reasons that attract them to go to a specific host country for instance the economic expansion. Additionally, migration can be within one country or between countries. That is, "a distinction is also made between external migration – between countries- and internal migration – between regions" (Gordon, 2009, p. 415).

Migration is often confused with *immigration* and *emigration*. Although they are closely related, they have different meanings. Migration denotes general movements of people

from one place to another. Immigration denotes the state of entering a new country of residence. On the other hand, the act of leaving one's own country to a new host country is referred to as emigration. Keeping track of migrant people who leave their countries is more difficult than measuring people who enter a new country. This is because migrants usually interact much more with the authorities of the country, they are migrating to than with the authorities of the country they are leaving (Eurostat Statistics Explained, 2019).

According to the United Nations' international migration report (2017), international migration has dramatically grown over the last seventeen years to reach 258 million international migrants in 2017 up from 173 million in 2000. The same report acknowledged that more than half of the international migrants live in Asia and Europe, then Northern America, Africa, Latin America and the Caribbean followed by Oceania. The Office for National Statistics (2019) acknowledged that the UK population is increasing in the last years by the migration of people who intend to stay for 12 months or more. It also admitted that non-EU migration of people ranks the highest since 2004 and knew a gradual increase in the last five years mainly to study and work. This goes in line with the coming of Algerian government-sponsored doctoral students to the UK (Chellia, 2018), which represent the population of this research.

4.4. International Students' Experiences of Study Abroad:

Research on students seeking to study abroad at university is greatly increasing through encouraging thorough understandings of lived experiences of international students. Studies on international students' experiences abroad primarily focuses on understanding how these students perceive, adapt, and cope with the new environments they encounter in the host country (e.g. Zhang and Brunton's (2007); Sawir et al. (2008); Kosheleva et al. (2015); Wu, Garza and Guzman (2015) and Nada and Araújo, (2018); Ghodbane (2020); Guerriche (2020). This section, therefore, offers an overview on the challenges experienced by students travelling abroad to study at university and the benefits of study abroad experiences.

4.4.1. International students' challenges in study abroad context:

Since their first day abroad, international students start to come across many transitional situations and find themselves struggle with many difficulties. Studies conducted about international students revealed that international students have several difficulties when they are studying overseas that mainly revolve around adjustment issues and culture shock (Cullingford, 2017). These difficulties can be related to the language of the host country, the

foreign culture and social norms, the new educational system, and most importantly feelings of ‘strangeness’ (Nada and Araújo, 2018), which greatly affect foreign students in their experiences abroad. Toyokawa and Toyokawa (2002, p.364) summarized the difficulties that are most confronted by international students as “culture shock, language difficulties, adjustment to unfamiliar social norms, eating habits, customs and values, differences in education systems, isolation and loneliness, homesickness, and a loss of established social networks”.

One main challenge for international students that was indicated in research is that international students are often influenced by the feelings they experience and confront in the host country like loneliness and homesickness (e.g. Montgomery, 2010; Sawir et al., 2008) due to the lack of contact with nationals from the host country (e.g. Brown, 2009; Montgomery, 2010), or because of discrimination and feelings of exclusion (e.g. Karuppan and Barari, 2010). Accordingly, it is stated that “an often-found problem among international students is their feelings of social isolation, loneliness, and disappointment with the lack of friendship ties, especially with local students” (Sakurai, McCall-Wolf and Kashima, 2010, p.176).

Focusing on how international students seek to adapt to the new culture and society of the host country, social support was found as a challenging factor that impacts the experiences of students travelling to study abroad (Rui and Wang, 2015; Sullivan and Kashubeck-West, 2015). Social support helps foreign students to cope with the social, educational, and emotional issues they come across in the host country. International students usually seek to have social support from their families, friends, and relatives. At the same level as this, when facing emotional and social problems, students tend to seek help from their parents, friends, or other students. When facing educational problems, foreign students tend usually to seek help from educational advisors, parents, or friends (Sawir et al., 2008). The lack of social support and loneliness that resulted from family separation urge the migrated individuals to have contact with their family members in their home countries. It has even been stated that “despite the associated difficulties, the need to maintain contact with family members was considered important in bridging the distance that separation created and as a way of maintaining old social worlds” (Savic, Chur-Hansen, Mahmood and Moore, 2013, p. 385). This is because, it is found that missing family was one of the main challenges encountered by international students with collectivist backgrounds like Algerian students, and that the most challenging thing is to get used to that feeling of loneliness (Ghodbane, 2020; Sadoudi, 2021).

Research on the experiences of international students have examined the academic challenges that encounter students during their study abroad journey at university. These academic challenges included differences in the academic cultures of the host university and the originating institution (Wu, Garza, and Guzman, 2015). The lack of understanding of the academic culture can hinder their ability to adapt academically and culturally to their new universities (Handa and Fallon, 2006). Academic challenges for international students also included students-supervisor relationships (Winchester-seeto et al. 2013) and thesis writing difficulties (Wang and Lee, 2011).

Several studies have also demonstrated language barrier and the lack of English language proficiency in the experiences of students studying abroad in English speaking countries (e.g. McMahon, 2016; Mak, Bodycott, and Ramburuth, 2015; Savignon, 2017) as one of the major academic challenges for international students. McMahon (2015), who researched international postgraduate students in a British university, noted that students' limited proficiency in the English language makes it difficult for them to communicate. Also, he reported that students had a sense of alienation from British society and found it challenging to integrate into the host community.

Language plays a crucial role in helping international students adapt with life in the host country. In this regard, it is stated that “one of the fundamental aspects of successful training in the recipient country is knowledge of the language of studying” (Kosheleva, Samofalova, Holtman and Kopotilova, 2015, p. 40). Alternatively, lack of mastering the target language being used in study might have a negative effect on foreign students' learning and achievements in their studies, which will consequently affect their feelings. According to Zhang and Brunton's (2007) research findings, language difficulty leads to international students' failure in achieving their academic goals. According to Masgoret (2006), there is a mutual relationship between language proficiency and social interaction. High proficiency in the target language leads to high interaction in the host country, which inevitably leads to high proficiency in the target language. Similarly, Wu, Garza and Guzman (2015, p.1) acknowledge that “many international students are high ranked in their home countries; however, they have to also meet requirements in academic and language aspects”. Therefore, interactions of foreign students with locals in the host country can be hindered by low levels of their language proficiency. However, if the language of the host country is well-spoken by international students, they will represent their own cultures very well. Similarly, it is claimed that “international students constitute an increasingly relevant and important source of diversity on

college campuses. They enrich the cultural diversity of campuses with their home culture and ethnic experiences” (Wu, Garza and Guzman., 2015, p. 1). As such, the target language of the host country does not only affect international students’ academic achievements and social experiences but also might have a profound impact on their identity and personality through using it to express themselves and their cultures.

Literature also showed that international students experience other challenges during their journey abroad such as financial problems and support (e.g. Leong, 2015; Elliot et al., 2016; Lee, 2017). The pre-mentioned studies and others have plainly demonstrated that the experiences of students who seek to study abroad are challenged by several factors. The degree to which international students find it difficult or easy to adapt to the host culture varies from one individual to another and is influenced by factors like their level of English language and their openness to the new culture, both of which can contribute to their cultural and academic success (Meng, Zhu, and Cao, 2017).

4.4.2. International students' benefits of study abroad:

Several studies have shown that international students speak highly of their study abroad experience, despite the emotional, cultural and academic challenges and difficulties described above (Gould, 2018; Nada, Montgomery, and Araújo, 2018; Ploner, 2018). International students perceive their lived experiences as a valuable, significant and memorable learning experience that offer them various chances to learn (Nada, Montgomery, and Araújo, 2018; Saubert, 2014). Several recent research about the benefits and results of the study abroad experience on international students included shifts in perspective of students, independence, and personal development in addition to improved academic performance (Saubert, 2014, Lefdahl-Davis and Perrone-McGovern, 2015, Maharaja, 2018; Nada, Montgomery, and Araújo, 2018; Ghodbane, 2020).

International students' interactions with members of the host culture may be advantageous for their academic, psychological, and social development. Several studies have shown that increased interaction with the host society is linked to improved communication, adaptation, and less social and academic difficulties (Coleman, 2015; Costello, 2015; Beaven and Spencer-Oatey, 2016). For students studying abroad, friendships with students from the host culture may have more advantages, such as improved psychological adjustment, reduced stress, and a more positive experience overall (Hirai, Frazier, and Syed, 2015; Crowne and Engle, 2016; King and Sondhi, 2016). International students typically spend more time

interacting with their co-nationals, whom they view as their closest friends (Taha and Cox, 2016). Engaging with others from the same cultural background is linked to possessing a strong sense of national identity (Liu and Turner, 2018). Overall, homesickness and other psychological issues related to living abroad can be lessened by social support from co-nationals and host nationals (Rui and Wang, 2015).

Ghodbane (2020) researched the experiences of Algerian doctorate students studying in the UK and reported that, in spite of the difficulties associated with the academic, social, and cultural contexts of study abroad, the Algerian PhD students were able to adapt by participating in challenging but constructive social interactions. Results also imply that having enjoyable interactions with others across many situations might help to increase self- and other awareness. Participants in his study described how the time they spent living abroad helped them discover more about their identities. According to Ghodbane, a lot of doctoral students talked about the various abilities they developed while studying abroad that enabled them to function in their new environment. These abilities included social skills, academic and language proficiency, resilience, cultural awareness, independence, and responsibility.

4.5. International students and social support:

When studying abroad, students experience different stressful situations that can affect their mental health. This makes them in need of getting support from people they count for like family and friends. Thomas and Sumathi (2016) conducted a study on international students studying in India and Indian students studying abroad to understand the role of social support in decreasing acculturative stress that faces international students. The data for this study was collected through using online questionnaires. The study findings revealed that the social support international students have from their families and friends helps them reducing the acculturative stress to a greater extent in the new environment. Also, they admit that “the social support from the families is having a strong relation with the acculturative stress, the support given by the families could reduce the acculturative stress that the students face” (Thomas and Sumathi, 2016, p. 69). Therefore, family and friends are considered a strong source of stress relief and social and emotional support for international students and PhD students in particular (Jazvac-Martek, Chen and McAlpine, 2011).

Social networks present effective support systems that provide psychological support for international students in the new environment, as they exist in their personal lives. International students coming from different ethnic and cultural background confront the need

of adjusting to the new environment, which urge them to develop new modes of living and new social networks that help and assist them to navigate their life and cope with the new situations they come across in the new environment. In this context, it is claimed that friends from the home country can be a significant source from which international students who are pursuing a doctoral education in a place that is away from their home receive social support (Hopwood, *et al.*,2011).

4.6. Globalization and internationalization:

As the world is becoming more and more globalized, globalization has dominated several fields of human life such as economic, cultural, political ...etc. different countries are interacting and integrating together to expand international activities at the economic, cultural and political levels. In sociology, globalization is defined as “a process in which social life within societies is increasingly affected by international influences based on everything from political and trade ties to shared music, clothing styles, and mass media” (Johnson, 2000, p.122). The term globalization is used to refer to the economic and cultural interdependence of the world countries resulted from trade and investment in goods, information, technology, and people across borders through building economic collaborations between countries. Therefore, “perhaps the most powerful form of globalization is economic, in which planning, and control expand from a relatively narrow focus- such as a single firm doing business in a regional or national basis- to a broad global focus in which the entire world serves as a source of labour, raw materials, and markets” (Johnson, 2000, p.122).

Despite the fact that globalization and internationalization are related and adopt the same principles and aim to expand international activities, but they differ and are not the same thing. Albatch and Knight clarify the difference between them, as “Globalization is the context of economic and academic trends that are part of the reality of the 21st century. Internationalization includes the policies and practices undertaken by academic systems and institutions—and even individuals—to cope with the global academic environment” (Albatch and Knight, 2007, p. 290). Internationalization is much more concerned with putting the idea of globalization into practice. Therefore, even the sector of education has been affected by internationalization. Several countries in the world start to rely on improving and investing their education as a strategy to develop the country’s economy. Thereof, “international student mobility nowadays is one of the most promising research areas, not only for the development of an innovative university, but also for the economy and the foreign policy of the whole

country” (Kosheleva, Samofalova, Holtman, and Kopotilova, 2015, p. 38). That is, international education became a universal trade that has grown rapidly especially in the Western world (Sakurai, McCall-Wolf and Kashima, 2010; Zhang and Brunton, 2007).

4.7. Students’ mobility:

The internationalisation of higher education resulted in the mobility of students from their home universities to different universities worldwide. Walker (2014) claimed that “the internationalization of tertiary education has given rise to student mobility of industrial proportions and affects and is affected by national economies” (p. 325). Similarly, Wu, Garza and Guzman (2015, p.1) admitted that “given the recent demand for internationalization and globalization of our world, a cross-border student mobility around the world has ensued”. This section discusses students’ mobility.

Mobility is, in its broadest sense, the state of *being mobile*. The latter describes the quality of something that moves from place to place. Sociologically speaking, mobility refers to the movement of people from within or between social groups, places, classes, or occupations. Mobility of individuals within or between social groups and social classes is often referred to as social mobility. Social mobility was defined as the shifting between various positions within a society's social stratification system, mostly by individuals but occasionally by groups (Gordon, 2009).

Mobility in higher education refers to the situation when students and teachers move to another institution within or out of their home country to pursue their studies or teach and work abroad. “Historically, mobility has always been an important characteristic of academia...Today, a high degree of mobility continues to characterize academia” (Bauder, 2012, p. 3). This is often referred to as academic mobility. International student mobility is one of the most promising research areas, not only for the development of an innovative university, but also for the economy and the foreign policy of the whole country. That is, international student mobility is influenced by educational as well as economic reasons. Correspondingly, it is stated that “although student’s migration decisions probably also involve economic incentives, the institutional context of their decision, and thus inflows of foreign students, may also depend on higher education policies in place” (Kahanec and Králiková, 2011, p.21).

This study addresses Algerian students taking doctoral research in the UK. The mobility of these students to the UK was upon an agreement between the Algerian government and the

UK that aimed provide scholarships to Algerian students (Guerriche, 2020; British Council, 2014). Based on the statistics presented by the Office for National Statistics (2018), there was an increase by 7% in the number of visas for study issued by the UK Home Office. The number has been increased to reach 10% including Tier 4 (Sponsored Study) visas for 12 months or more by the end of September 2018. The visas issued were mainly for Chinese students and Indian nationals. The ONS (2018), in the same report also conducted statistics on National Insurance number allocations to adult overseas nationals to September 2018 in which there was an increase in the number of Algerian registrations for National Insurance by 26% from September 2017 to September 2018. These registrations were to issue visas for both short and long-term migrants including students. Furthermore, the ONS (2019) admitted that since 2011 the number of people coming to the UK to study has been increased with the immigration of the non-EU students topping in the first rank.

For the sake of enhancing and promoting students' mobility in Algeria, the latter has adopted several mobility programmes and activities. This section mainly aims to shed light on the mobility of doctoral students in Algeria, which gives a share in internationalizing the higher education. As a matter of fact, the French colonialism in Algeria resulted in many connections between France and Algeria at the economic level which led to their cooperation in many other domains and was mainly under the Bologna process.

The Bologna process is a higher education reform set by some European countries in 1999 to promote the quality of higher education in Europe. In this regard it is stated that "The expression 'Bologna Process' (BP) refers to multi-national reforms and changes currently undertaken by European states, with varying scope and pace, to implement the goal of creating a barrier-free European Higher Education Area (EHEA) characterized by 'compatibility and comparability' between the higher education systems of the signatory states" (Papatsiba., 2006, p.95). In another context, it is simply defined as "a process of cooperation and reform in the field of higher education bringing together 48 countries. It established and seeks sought to consolidate the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) with comparable and compatible systems of higher education to facilitate mobility, increase employability, allow equitable student access and progression and strengthen Europe's attractiveness and competitiveness competitiveness worldwide" (European Commission.,2015).

After adopting the Bologna process model, the French government has set some educational programmes to help Algerian students to study abroad by providing them with

financial support. One example to illustrate this point is the programme of the Franco- Algerian scholarship, which was set up in 2009 to give Algerian students an opportunity to pursue their studies in France. The programme spells that the fees are shared between the Algerian and the French government with 60% covered by France and 40% by the Algerian government. Under this programme, over 300 Algerian PhD student PhD students have joined French universities in 2009. In this respect, is claimed that “significant numbers of Algerian students study abroad, virtually all of them in France” (Rose, 2015, p.6). Algerian students studying in France are mainly enrolled under scientific subjects such as: mathematics, information technology, pharmacy science, and medicine. Furthermore, to improve the sector of Higher Education and Scientific Research in Algeria both of the Algerian and French presidents; Abdelaziz Bouteflika (Algerian politician who served as president from April 1999 to April 2019) and Francois Hollande (French politician who served as president from 2012 to 2017) respectively, in 2009 have signed a convention to promote mobility of Algerian university and PhD students to France.

As English language has spread in Algeria, the Algerian government have introduced some mobility programmes for graduate students. Yet, it started recently since 2014 to take English programmes designed for Algerian doctoral students to carry on their PhD studies in the UK after the adoption of the Bologna process. One way of illustration would be the international programmes introduced by the US embassy in Algeria. “The U.S. Embassy in Algeria offers a wide range of academic exchange programs for Algerian citizens” (Belmihoub, 2012, p.40). Fulbright and Youth Leadership are among these international programmes, which are designed only for graduate studies offering them the opportunity to carry on a MA degree in a US university. Even though these mobility programmes were limited only to graduate students, but they can be considered the basis upon which more programmes will be designed for PhD students in the future.

To enter and participate in the global partnership and international cooperation with the Anglophone countries, the Algerian government did not made make agreements only with the US but also with other countries. The Algerian Ministry of Higher Education along with the UK government has recently signed an agreement to grant up to 500 offers for Algerian students, who are sponsored by the Algerian government and receive a fully funded scholarship, to conduct their PhD studies in the UK over a period of five years (British Council, 2014). These programmes of academic exchange aim to internationalize the Algerian system

of higher education and set up cultural bridges between different countries (British Council, 2014).

4.7.1. Purposes of students' mobility:

The mobility of postsecondary students aims in the first place at enhancing and promoting the internationalization of higher education. Thus, to keep up to date with this globalized world, it is important for universities to attract international students and promote international students' mobility. Different universities in several countries all over the world are globally competing to attract international students.

In line with the global competitiveness of countries to invest on higher education, universities aim to achieve a better rank and word class, internationalize their campuses, increase their revenue and income, boost the exchange at the educational and cultural levels, and contribute in building the knowledge economy. In this respect, Kim (2009) agrees with the global competition of countries and states, "In the contemporary era, interpreted as an age of 'the knowledge economy', HE has become an indicator of economic competitiveness, and the internationalization of HE is often regarded as an innovative response to external marketing opportunities. The internationalization of HE has been taken as a strategy in the mire of increasing global economic competition in many countries, with the emphasis on trade in HE and the world university rankings, and the international recruitment of the best and brightest students and scholars" (Kim, 2009, p. 396). Correspondingly, as for the UK Ozga (2006, p.1) acknowledges that "Knowledge transfer (KT) has entered the higher education arena in the UK as the 'third sector' of higher education activity—along with research and teaching".

Mobility can also help students in improving their professional life and achieving their academic objectives. Chellia acknowledges that "at the professional level, mobility relates to career objectives in the sense of developing professional and research skills" (Chellia, 2018, p.65). From a linguistic point of view, mobility of international students is a good method for countries to maintain and keep their languages. Many universities in many countries are motivated to use the international languages mainly English which helps English speaking countries to maintain their language (Altbach, 2015). An example to demonstrate this point would be the case of United States, United Kingdom and Australia, which are among the Anglophone countries and represent the leading countries in enhancing the mobility and exchange of students in the globe. Accordingly, Coleman points out that "the adoption of

English as the medium of instruction in Higher Education is raising increasing concern” (Coleman, 2006, p. 1).

The British higher education highly seeks to internationalize its system and education through putting emphasis on enhancing the mobility of students and staff coming to the UK. Furthermore, the existence of foreign academics and students in British universities cannot be denied. Correspondingly,

“The UK Government’s internationalization of HE policy has been focusing on international students. Furthermore, a lot of research on the internationalization of HE in the UK has been concerned about international students’ experiences and the issues around ‘internationalization at home’ strategies, which involve relations and interactions between international students and local British staff and student” (Kim., 2009, p.398).

A great proportion of British research focuses on the experiences of international students. To increase the number of international students in the UK, the British government opt for offering user-friendly visa services to allow international students who complete a study degree in the UK to apply and have an up to two years visa to look for work in the UK (Home Office: UK Border Agency 2007).

4.8. Family:

4.8.1. Definition of family:

Family is the smallest unit that constitutes society. It is a social group of people that is usually made up of parents and children. “The family remains a complex and dynamic concept, variably defined and experienced” (Mckie and Cunningham- Burley, 2005, p.3). In this regard, it is stressed that ““Family” is a hotly contested term among family scholars in general, including family communication scholars” (Baxter et al., 2009, p.170). Different definitions have been given to the concept of “family” by different scholars.

From a sociological perspective, family is defined as “an intimate domestic group made up of people related to one another by bonds of blood, sexual mating, or legal ties. It has been a very resilient social unit that has survived and adapted through time” (Gordon, 2009, p. 222). Additionally, it is also stated that “Aristotle argued that families were the fundamental social unit of society (I.1252b) because they have a transformative effect on individuals and on the larger body politic” (Goodsell and Whiting, 2016, p. 484). Goodsell and Whiting (2016) explained that as family is the first school where people learn about responsibility that help in

building up a good society. Accordingly, it is stated that “family has its own specific structure and is called the “Basic Building Block” of human society. It plays a pivotal role in providing the most congenial atmosphere to an individual to form his style of life and basic patterns of behaviour” (Ahangar and Khan, 2016, p. 236). Ahangar and Khan (2016) also added that individual’s values and ambitions are affected by their families. Based on Aristotle’s dogmatism that family is seen as an ethical school or academy that teaches its members responsibility and what is appropriate and what is not, a definition has been given to family as it “is a multigenerational institution of mutual responsibility, defined in part through narratives that are developed and passed down by its members, and oriented around developing virtue in the lives of its members and collective and individual movement toward a conception of the good” (Goodsell and Whiting, 2016, p. 485).

The United States Census Bureau claims that before the 1930s, the concept of “family” was differently defined from its recent definition today, and that family used to be defined the way the concept “household” is defined today. Family, before the 1930s, is defined as “a group of persons, whether related by blood or not, who live together as one household, usually sharing the same table. One person living alone is counted as a family, and, on the other hand, the occupants or inmates of a hotel or institution, however numerous, are treated as a single family”. However, a new definition has given by the United States Census Bureau in 2010 that “a family consists of a householder and one or more other people living in the same household who are related to the householder by birth, marriage or adoption”. This definition is quite similar to the family’s definition after the 1930’s that a family signifies the group of people that are related by blood, marriage or adoption to the head of the family.

4.8.2. Types of family:

Despite the fact that family is known to be a universal school, it differs from one society to another and from one cultural context to another. Different kinds of families have been mentioned by sociologists based on the different cultural backgrounds of human beings. The way families differ depends on how they are organized, where it resides, who owns the main authority of the family, and the form of marriage that sets up the family.

This section discusses family structure based on organization. Families are classified in two broad categories depending on the way they are organized and structured. These main broad categories are the nuclear family and joint (also called extended) family. In this context,

Ahangar and Khan assert that “the main types of family are nuclear and joint which play their role in the development of an individual” (Ahangar and Khan, 2016, p. 236).

4.8.2.1. Nuclear family:

“The nuclear type of family is the one, in which the group consists of a male, his wife and their children. In nuclear families the concept is ‘me, my wife and my children’ with no place for others which is alarming” (Yadav and Shukla, 2017, p. 119). Nuclear families are made up of the husband and wife and their unmarried children. Correspondingly, “the word ‘nuclear’ was picked upon, that represents a married couple as forming the ‘nucleus’ of a family” (Sharma, 2013, p.306). Nuclear families are those small families that are usually consisting of a mother, a father, and their kids. This kind of family is the most prevalent type of families in the modern society, and it is built up based on companionship between its members. Nuclear family’s size is dependent on the number of the kids.

4.8.2.2. Joint family:

As mentioned in the previous section, joint/ extended family is expanding from the married parents and their children to include grandparents, grandchildren, aunts, and uncles. So, as the term “joint” suggests, joint family denotes joining the family of a married individual with the family of his parents, his married sisters, and his married brothers. To differentiate between nuclear and joint families, Ahangar and Khan states that “nuclear families consist of parents and their unmarried children while as joint families refer to the families consisting of parents, grandparents, uncles, aunts etc. and their children” (Ahangar and Khan, 2016, p. 236). Simply put, joint family is joining two or more nuclear families. Unlike the nuclear family, the size of the joint family depends on the number of grandparents, aunts, uncles, and cousins.

As this study deals with the Algerian students studying their PhDs in the UK and their families back home in Algeria, it is of importance to mention how families are structured in the Algerian societies. Algerian families are described as extended families that encompass individuals from three generations: grandparents, parents and children and sometimes grandchildren (Achoui, 2006). Families in Algeria are structured as large families that include small families.

4.8.3. Family relationships:

As previously mentioned, family is a group of individuals live together and share a common house with the head of family and have duties and rights over one another. In addition

to the house, family members also share the same culture, experiences, values and feelings towards one another. Family members usually interact with each other depending on the roles they perform socially in the family for instance the wife and husband as father and mother, and the children as daughters and sons. These social roles along with the rights and duties they own to one another establish relationships among the family members which play a focal role framing people well-being. In this regard, it has been stressed that “family relationships are enduring and consequential for well-being across the life course” (Thomas, Liu, and Umberson, 2017, p. 1).

Family has been defined in different way by scholars. Traditionally, family denotes a set of members who have certain kind of ties by blood, love and commitments towards each other. Family members, moreover, share reciprocal feelings and emotions of love, care, mercy and compassion. These mutual feelings, in addition to sharing certain behaviours and thoughts, make the lives of family members shared together by intimate ties which result in some kind of social and emotional support between family members. Thus, it is claimed that “family can be kin and non-kin and is often about care and trust in the context of enduring relationships” (Murray and Barnes, 2010, p.533).

Family relationships have a significant role in the lives of family members. This is because family relationships frame people’s well-being across their lives. In this context it is even stated that “social relations are known to affect well-being in a variety of ways” (Antonucci, Lansford and Akiyama, 2001, p.68). Moreover, it is also admitted that “the quality of family relationships, including social support (e.g., providing love, advice, and care) and strain (e.g., arguments, being critical, making too many demands), can influence well-being through psychosocial, behavioural, and physiological pathways” (Thomas, Liu, and Umberson, 2017, p. 1). Additionally, the earlier individuals experience good family relationships in their life course, the more they get support from their families and experience well-being in early stages of their lives. “Relationships within the family are important for the development of children's well-being, as well as for their evaluations of their family and their overall life satisfaction” (Dinisman, Andresen, Montserrat, Strózik, and Strózik, 2017, p.1). Thus, family relationships are the basis that provides family members and gives the family a sense of solidarity which results in family well-being. Accordingly, it is even claimed that “Family relationships provide resources that can help an individual cope with stress, engage in healthier behaviors, and enhance self-esteem, leading to higher well-being” (Thomas, Liu, and Umberson, 2017, p. 7).

Thomas, Liu, and Umberson (2017) discussed the different types of relationships inside the family that have a significant impact on individuals' well-being, which they link to good physical and mental health, happiness, satisfaction about life, as marital, intergenerational, and sibling relationships. As for the marital relationships, they explain that happy marriage is much related to good physical and mental health (Thomas, Liu, and Umberson, 2017). Correspondingly, "marital relationships are more importantly related to well-being" (Antonucci, Lansford and Akiyama, 2001, p.74). Thomas, Liu, and Umberson (2017) asserted that intergenerational relationships among family members by the relationships that relate adult children, their parents, and their grandparents who care about each other in different stages of their life which results in social support and social control that affects the health and well-being. They have explained this as: firstly, parenthood produces stress and decrease well-being when the children are young but it increases social incorporation and leads to emotional support that results in increasing well-being, secondly, child- grandparent relationships have positive impact on their well-being especially when both of them live in the same household; however, grandparents experience a level of stress when they lack parents' support and take care of the children by themselves, lastly, sibling relationships have a significant role in supporting individuals' well-being as "sibling relationships can be characterized by both positive and negative aspects that may affect elements of the stress process, providing both resources and stressors that influence well-being" (Thomas, Liu, and Umberson, 2017, p. 6).

4.8.4. Impact of family separation on mental health:

It has been claimed that "the family is indisputably the central element and most important aspect of peoples' lives" (Wilmsen, 2011, p.44). It is important to note that family relationships provide the family members with a sense of life as a "family life" that is mainly based on emotional links. However, despite these emotional connections and relationships, family members can sometimes be separated from each other because of several reasons. These reasons can be social, political, economic or academic. As for the social reasons, the main reason that can lead to family separation is divorce which makes the parents separate from each other along with children being kept with one of them. Politically, some families are separated because of wars and political conflicts by which some members of the family tend to seek asylum to other countries as refugees. In this context, it is claimed that "an increase of 12.4 million individuals during the 12 months of 2015, which equates to almost 34,000 people per day forced to leave their homes due to conflict or persecution" (Miller, Hess, Bybee, and Goodkind, 2018, pp.26-27). Economically speaking, some family members tend to leave their

families and migrate beyond borders to search for good job opportunities and improve their income level. Another reason why some people are separated from their families is mainly related to educational purposes where students over the world leave their home countries to pursue their studies abroad. Accordingly, it has been stated that separation from family is the hardest part of migration (Suárez-Orozco, Bang and Kim, 2010).

Savic, Chur-Hansen, Mahmood and Moore (2013) conducted a qualitative study to explore the effect of family separation on well-being mental health and of Sudanese refugees in Australia and what strategies they used to cope with separation. In this study, data were collected through conducting in-depth interviews with Sudanese community representatives, workers in health, practitioners of mental health care, policy makers and managers of health service. The study results reveal that the Sudanese refugees have negative perceptions regarding the effect of their family separation on their mental health and expressed their concerns and worry about their relatives back home and the opposite way. They were prioritizing sending money to their families back home. To cope with this separation, Sudanese refugees used the information communication technologies to keep in touch with their families such as the internet that was of great importance and mobile phones. A conclusion has been drawn from this study that family separation is an outstanding source that affect the individuals' mental health and cause them sadness and stress. Accordingly, "given the difficult life experiences that many refugees have had to overcome, it is unsurprising that high rates of mental illness have been documented among refugee populations" (Miller, Hess, Bybee, and Goodkind, 2018, pp.2).

González, Kula, González, and Paik (2017) in their article "Context of Latino Students' Family Separation During and After Immigration: Perspectives, Challenges, and Opportunities for Collaborative Efforts", discussed the consequences and challenges of family separation and reunification of Latino students immigrating to the US. They also addressed the effect of the separation duration and what impact the separation had on family and students' academic success. As for the length and duration of separation from family, González, Kula, González, and Paik (2017) found that many families have been separated for many years and sometimes permanently in addition to the huge numbers of short-term separation of families. Furthermore, it was found that "the separation of immigrant children from their fathers has been found to last longer than separation from mothers" (González, Kula, González, and Paik, 2017, p. 216). The study findings also demonstrate that parents tend to support their migrated children and to maintain contact with them even if they are physically absent and to decrease the level of stress

children face because of their parents' absence. With regards to the academic achievements and success, it was found that family separation affects children in negative ways. In this context, it has also been claimed that children who are separated from their families experience difficulties and struggles in their studies (Gindling and Poggio, 2012).

4.9. Social media:

4.9.1. Definition of social media:

Social media plays a crucial role and touches almost all the domains of people's lives. People use it for different purposes such as education, marketing, and trade. In this context, it has been stated that "Now a day's social media has been the important part of one's life from shopping to electronic mails, education and business tool. Social media plays a vital role in transforming people's lifestyle" (Siddiqui and Singh, 2016, p.71). The concept of social media has not been allocated a constant definition. "There is no single recognized definition for social Media" (Jacka and Scott, 2011, p.5). correspondingly, it has also been asserted that "there seems to be confusion among managers and academic researchers alike as to what exactly should be included under this term" (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010, p.60). Additionally, it has been mentioned that "providing a single definition that encompasses all of the technologies and activities associated with social media is extremely difficult, in part because social media is not defined by any specific scope, format, topic, audience, or source" (Treem, Dailey, Pierce and Biffel, 2016, p.3). Therefore, social media denotes the set of applications and websites that people usually use to share information, pictures, and messages, express their thoughts and opinions, and to connect with each other by means of online platforms on the basis of people's shared interests.

4.9.2. Types of social media:

The main idea that the previous definitions share is that social media allows people to communicate with each other via internet. In this content, "Social networking sites have become the most popular online destinations in recent years" (Sultana, 2017, p.46). Social media is also referred to as social networking sites. The expressions "Social networking sites" "Social network sites" are used in an interchangeable way to denote the same idea and the same meaning. It has also been stated that "While we use the term "social network site" to describe this phenomenon, the term "social networking sites" also appears in public discourse, and the two terms are often used interchangeably" (Boyd and Ellison, 2010, p.211). Social media

involves the different social networking sites that people usually use in their daily life such as Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp...etc.

Even though Facebook is the mostly used social media platform by people on a daily basis to share pictures, videos and thoughts about their lives with friends and comments and like others' content, it represents only one example of the 13 different kinds of social media including collaborative projects, social gaming, social bookmarking...etc (Aichner and Jacob, 2015). In this regard, Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) attempt to group the different kinds of social media into six distinguished categories as the following:

4.9.2.1. Collaborative projects:

Collaborative projects are those specific forms of applications within social media that allows end-users to mutually create knowledge content at the same time. Unlike blogs, collaborative projects are seen as democratic social media as all the users are given the right to make posts, and modify or add content (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010). Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) made the difference between Wikis and Social Bookmarking Applications in collaborative projects. As for Wikis, they have explained them by the “websites which allow users to add, remove, and change text-based content” (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010). While they have defined social bookmarking applications as those websites that “enable the group-based collection and rating of Internetlinks or media content” (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010). Social bookmarking has also been explained as it “describes the concept of saving and organising internet bookmarks at a centralised platform in order to share them with friends and other users” (Aichner and Jacob, 2015, p.260). That is, wikis allow readers to generate and alter articles such as the encyclopedia Wikipedia that exist in many different languages whereas social bookmarking applications allow users to share websites such as Delicious and Reddit. Aichner and Jacob also claim that “Collaborative projects bring together internet users with a common interest and/or certain knowledge in order to plan, develop, improve, analyse and/ or test technological, academic, scientific or fun-oriented projects. The results (e.g. programs, codes, findings, results, games) are usually distributed as open source and made available to the public for no charge” (Aichner and Jacob, 2015, p.260).

4.9.2.2. Blogs:

Boing Boing and Tumblr would represent examples of blogs. A blog is, also called weblog, a website that people create in which they express their ideas and opinions just like they do in diaries. People who use blogs are bloggers. Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) states that

blogs are those personal webpages that include personal information about the author and other information about specific areas. In this regard, a blog has also been defined as “(from ‘web’ and ‘log’) is a chronological list of postings, which can be read and commented upon by visitors. Blogs are run by both individuals and companies, which post news or other informational material, such as product tests” (Aichner and Jacob, 2015, p.259). Blogs include “writings that discusses a wide range of topics, including food, fandoms, hobbies, lifestyle, gaming and beauty” (Edwards, 2018, p.33). Furthermore, “blogging is a brilliant way for building young writers, journalists, and photographers to build on their skills and foster their creativity” (Edwards, 2018, p.34). That is, blogging motivate its users to interact with others and build up their academic skills.

4.9.2.3. Content communities:

Contents communities aim for “the sharing of media content between users” (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010). Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) also added that several types of social media are existing in the form of content communities and the most common examples of content communities are: YouTube for posting videos, SlideShare to make PowerPoint presentations, Flickr for photos and Bookcrossing for sharing books across countries. Kietzmann, Hermkens, McCarthy and Silvestre claim that (2011) YouTube was originally set up to give users the opportunity to share their experiences with others in the world. Moreover, YouTube is the most incredibly popular video sharing tool being used by children, adolescents and young people (Edwards, 2018).

4.9.2.4. Social networking sites:

Aichner and Jacob have stated that social networking sites “connect people that know one another, share common interests or would like to engage in similar activities. Users have an individual profile; they can be found by other users using their full name, and they upload pictures and videos” (Aichner and Jacob, 2015, p.260). Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) pointed out that this kind of social media allows individuals to create profiles, based on their personal information, and adding friends send messages to see those profiles of each other. Additionally, it has been claimed that “there is a huge array of social networking apps, websites and platforms that allow users to set up their own public or private profile, on which they can share photos, information, and updates about their day-to-day lives” (Edwards, 2018, p.24). Edwards (2018) lists out the most popular types of social media used by children and young people as: Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Snapchat, WhatsApp.

4.9.2.5. Virtual game worlds:

Kaplan and Haenlein define virtual worlds as “platforms that replicate a three-dimensional environment in which users can appear in the form of personalized avatars and interact with each other as they would in real life” (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010, p.64). Virtual worlds refer to digital worlds. According to them, since virtual worlds provide an extremely good level of social presence and all applications media richness, they represent the ultimate occurrence of social media. Virtual worlds allow users to approach others and engage in activities. There exist two forms of virtual worlds: game worlds and social worlds. Accordingly, “online gaming allows players to connect through the internet and converse with each other through headphones while playing” (Edwards, 2018, p.24). The difference between computer games and virtual game worlds has been explained as, “in contrast to computer games, time continues even when the user is not logged in. Virtual worlds often use virtual currencies, which have an actual value, and allow companies to sell virtual or real products” (Aichner and Jacob, 2015, p.260).

4.10. Chapter summary:

The current chapter reviewed the literature related to the key concepts, notions and ideas that are associated with the current research. It dealt with what is currently stated in knowledge about the field of the study and the topic of the research, covered the notions of transition, migration, mobility, and associated them with students’ mobility and international students challenges abroad, and the social support they need while studying abroad. The sections in this chapter attempted to make a background in knowledge for the research.

Chapter Five: Research methodology

5.1. Introduction:

This chapter explains how the research is philosophically underpinned and how the study was conducted. It explains the ontological and epistemological perspectives of the study and how they relate to the methodology of the research. The chapter aims to determine the beliefs that frame the views of the researcher towards the research problem, how the problem was investigated and what methods were used to answer the research question. It also outlines the methodology of the research and explains how the research sample was selected. The chapter seeks to link the research question of the study with the selected methods that have been chosen for the research. It also deals with how data was collected and analysed for this study. The chapter ends with discussing how trustworthiness was ensured, and how ethical challenges were overcome in this study. That is, this chapter deals with the research methodology that has been followed to answer the central research question of this study as follows:

- What are the social stresses impacting the families of Algerian students and students themselves during the period of their PhD studies in the UK?

This research sought to understand the social stresses that affect the families of Algerian students and students of these families during the period of their PhD studies in the UK in the context of family separation. It aimed to understand the main points that stress the families and their children during the study abroad journey of the Algerian PhD students in the UK and how they cope with separation.

5.2. Research Approach:

To conduct research, Creswell (2014) proposed a framework to explain the process of research when researchers come to select a research approach: qualitative, quantitative, or mixed methods research approaches. He explained that a research approach is the proposal, or the plan suggested to conduct the research. He also pointed out that since the latter half of the 20th century, interest in doing research through qualitative approaches increased in social sciences.

According to Creswell's (2014) research framework, a research approach encompasses three components along with it: research paradigms, research methods and research designs. That is, the approach to research includes the philosophical assumptions that underpin the

research and the different methods and procedures used to conduct the research. Creswell (2014, p.17) also added that “the worldviews, the designs and the methods all contribute to a research approach that tends to be quantitative, qualitative or mixed”. Based on the nature of this study, the researcher chose a qualitative research approach to address the problem, as the notion of family separation has not been addressed much before in literature about international students, besides that the research topic has not been dealt with before in an Algerian context. Accordingly, Creswell (2014, p.20) asserted that “if a concept or phenomenon needs to be explored and understood because little research has been done on it, then it merits a qualitative approach”. This legitimizes qualitative approach for this study. The next sections explain the research paradigm, method, and design of the qualitative approach in this study.

5.3. Research paradigm:

In any research, researchers need to be familiar with the underlying philosophy of the research and choosing the research paradigm for the study. Creswell (2014) referred to research paradigms as philosophical worldviews, and he explained them as the general philosophical assumptions or orientations about the world and the nature of the research that researchers aim to study. It is the philosophical perspective adopted by the researcher to approach the research development, design, data collection, data analysis and interpretation. It is defined as “a contextual framework which provides the overarching theoretical basis for undertaking research” (O'Reilly and Kiyimba, 2015, p. 3).

Regarding beliefs about research, there are different research paradigms that are commonly used by researchers whereby different scholars have differentiated several paradigms. Shah and Al-Bargi (2013) explained three major research paradigms identified as Positivist, Interpretive and Critical research paradigms and argued that are mainly used in educational research. Conversely, Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) distinguished different types of paradigms mainly: positivistic, post-positivistic, naturalistic, interpretive, and normative paradigm; the normative paradigm advocates the idea that human behaviour is rule-governed and must be studied using natural science methods, while interpretive paradigm is centred on studying the individual and its context. Creswell (2014) and Mackenzie and Knipe (2006) considered four most common paradigms that are referred to in research which are interpretivist (constructivist), positivist, transformative, and pragmatic.

5.3.1. Interpretivist / Constructivist paradigm:

Interpretivist paradigm believes that there is no single truth or reality, which necessitates the need for interpreting the different realities different people have. Constructivists claim that “groups construct knowledge for each other and thus a culture of shared meaning is created” (O'Reilly and Kiyimba, 2015, p. 18). In social science, social reality is viewed and constructed differently depending on the way it is interpreted. Interpretive paradigm, also referred to as humanistic, naturalistic and constructivist, is seen as an anti-positivist paradigm that rejects the viewpoints of positivism in terms of understanding social reality. It is mainly subjective as it deals with how individuals understand and interpret things and social phenomena. Interpretive research studies are concerned with how the objective features of society are subjectively interpreted by individuals. In this regard, it is stated that “since social research is guided by the researcher’s desire to understand social reality, all is interpretive” (Shah and Al-Bargi, 2013, p.257). Also, “the central endeavour in the context of the interpretive paradigm is to understand the subjective world of human experience” (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p.19).

The interpretive paradigm aims to make people aware of the social factors that influence their perceptions and understandings of the social world. “Interpretivists are concerned with understanding the social world people have produced and which they reproduce through their continuing activities. This everyday reality consists of the meanings and interpretations given by the social actors to their actions, other people’s actions, social situations” (Blaikie, 2009, p.115). Interpretivism, which is often combined with constructivism or social constructivism, is viewed as a perspective and an approach to study qualitative research. Social constructivism holds the same views as interpretivism of how people subjectively perceive and interpret things in the social world (Creswell, 2014).

This study chose the social constructivist/interpretivist paradigm. This is because the research essentially intends to study the social experiences in relation to stress of Algerian PhD students who are conducting their PhD studies in the UK in a study abroad context and their families back home in Algeria and to know about family relationships and family separation in the context of these experiences. The research’s aim, therefore, urges the researcher to go for social constructivism as the research aimed at understanding how the individuals involved in the current study understand, and perceive their social lives (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Thus, social constructionism/ constructivism was the most appropriate philosophical

stance for this study. This is because the study is twofold social research that seeks to understand the social stresses that affect the families who are left behind in Algeria of the Algerian students taking PhD course in the UK from on one hand, and the students themselves during the period of their PhD studies in the UK in the context of family separation from the other hand. Accordingly, the study is located under the interpretive paradigm, as it intends to understand social reality is interpretive (Shah and Al-Bargi, 2013). The nature of the study, as social research, prompted the researcher to adopt qualitative approach (Flick, 2007).

5.3.1.1. Ontology:

Ontology refers to the study of the nature of being and reality. It is defined as “a branch of philosophy that is concerned with the nature of what exists” (Blaikie, 2007, p.13). That is, ontology deals with what there is to know about the world and the nature of reality. Ontological inquiries deal with the potentiality of the existence of an independent social reality from human interpretations. Ontological questions revolve around whether there is a shared social reality or just a variety of context-specific ones, and whether there is a social reality that exists apart from human interpretations, and whether there is a shared social reality (Ritchie *et al.*, 2014).

The ontological assumptions, which are concerned with what can be said about being and the existence of social reality, resulted in two main opposing philosophical positions: objectivism and constructionism. Objectivists believe that there is an external reality that is out there and independently exists without any impact from humans. Constructionists, on the other hand, view reality as the result of social interactions, where humans have an active and crucial role in its construction. Social constructionist view that “individuals seek to make meanings of their social lives and that the researcher has to examine the situation in question through the multiple lenses of the individuals involved to obtain their definition of the situation” (Cohen, Manion and Morisson, 2018, p.23). This study, therefore, adopted constructionism as an ontological position; meanings in this research are constructed through participants’ experiences.

5.3.1.2. Epistemology:

Epistemology is a philosophical discipline that is concerned with what can be counted as knowledge, how knowledge is produced and how people know what they know (Bryman, 2012). It stresses the relationship between what is known and the knower. It deals with the way knowledge is created, its acquisition by people and how they communicate with it (Cohen, Manion and Morisson, 2018). It deals with the meaning that the verb “to know” conveys.

Epistemologists hold opposing views when coming to conduct social research in which a debate has been arose concerning the possibility of studying the social world using the same principles of the natural sciences. Epistemologists are divided into two main opposing positions: positivism and interpretivism. Positivist view consider knowledge as being presented through the senses in which humans are regarded as natural objects and researched using the methods of natural sciences (Bryman, 2012).

Within research, the choice of the ontological perspective dictates the choice of the epistemological position of the research. This research, therefore, followed interpretivist view as an epistemological position. This is because the researcher in this study aimed at getting as close as possible to the participants to obtain data from their experiences and their individual views regarding the topic being investigated.

The philosophical underpinnings of the research pave the way for researchers to choose the research methodology through which they gather knowledge. The way researchers choose to proceed with their research depends mainly on their ontological beliefs about the social world and their epistemological beliefs regarding knowledge and the way it is acquired (Ritchie *et al.*, 2014). Based on the chosen ontological and epistemological positions for the research, this study opted for qualitative research approach. According to qualitative research, individuals are anticipatory, meaning-making individuals who actively create their own interpretations of things, make sense of their environment, and behave accordingly (Cohen, Manion and Morisson, 2018).

5.4. Research method:

As mentioned earlier, a research approach is made up of research paradigm, research method and research design (Creswell, 2014). This section looks at the research method of this study.

Research methods have been explained by Creswell (2014) as the specific methods researchers plan to use in terms of collecting, analysing and interpreting data; these methods also refer to whether a study is being conducted qualitatively or quantitatively. Researchers sometimes confuse research methods with research paradigms. Accordingly, Mackenzie and Knipe (2006) acknowledged that although quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods are sometimes used in literature by novice researchers to refer to research paradigm, the terms are more likely to be used in research to mean the methods used to collect, analyse, and interpret data. Following Creswell (2014), this study uses the notions of *qualitative*, *quantitative*, and

mixed methods to refer to the methods used for data collection, analysis, and interpretation in addition to using them to refer to the approach of research. Hence, the researcher selected a qualitative research approach to conduct this research (see section 5.2.).

Bryman (2016) argues that although qualitative and quantitative research differ in that quantitative researchers use measurement and qualitative researchers do not, different researchers claim that the difference is much deeper quantification as it lies even in the philosophical considerations that underpin them. Qualitative research follows an inductive orientation where a theory is to be generated, adopt interpretivism and constructionism as epistemological and ontological orientations. Quantitative research, however, is deductive where the researcher aims to test a theory, selects a positivist paradigm, and adopts objectivism as ontology (Bryman, 2016).

Cohen, Manion and Morisson (2018) distinguished between quantitative and qualitative research in that the former aims to explain something while the latter aims to understand a phenomenon. Thus, deciding about qualitative or quantitative research depends on the nature of the research question of the study and the paradigm (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006). The choice of the research method is also dependent on whether the aim is to define the kind of data that will be gathered prior to the study or to let it emerge from the participants (Creswell, 2014).

5.4.1. Qualitative research method:

Qualitative research is “broadly inductivist, constructionist and interpretivist” (Bryman, 2012, p.380). Qualitative research relies on constructionist and interpretivist positions as ontology and epistemology respectively. Thus, the study selected the qualitative research method to approach the research based on the nature of the research question. Accordingly, Flick (2014, p.11) states that “qualitative research is of specific relevance to the study of social relations”. Qualitative studies are usually concerned with describing people’s experiences as they express them. It aims to study phenomena as they occur in their natural setting (Kılıçoğlu, 2018). Moreover, qualitative research is an interpretative approach that deals with the meanings that people give to social phenomena in the social world as they experience them (Cohen, Manion and Morisson 2018; Bryman, 2012; Malterud, 2001).

This study chose qualitative method due to the nature of the research question for the study. This study looked at understanding the social stresses that affect both, the Algerian students studying in the UK and their families back home, how they experienced these stresses in the context of separation and how they coped with them. Thus, qualitative research has been

used in this study as it is characterised by its relevance to the studies of social relations and the different perspectives of the study participants (Flick, 2014; Malterud, 2001). Most importantly, in the field of educational research, qualitative methods are the most appropriate when attempting to understand the experiences of teachers or students (Thanh and Thanh, 2015). Therefore, conducting this research using qualitative approach allowed the researcher to get detailed answers to the research question of the study and research family separation as experienced by the people involved in the phenomenon.

5.5. Research design:

“Qualitative research is a systematic scientific inquiry which seeks to build a holistic, largely narrative, description to inform the researcher’s understanding of a social or cultural phenomenon” (Astalin, 2013, p.118). Qualitative research approach involves different research methods and designs. According to Creswell’s (2014) research framework, research design is the third component of a research approach, which he explained as the forms of inquiry that offer specific instructions for procedures in a research design. Moreover, Yin (2014, p.26) also explained it as “the logic that links the data to be collected and the conclusions to be drawn to the initial questions of study”. Creswell (2014) and Astalin (2013) listed some of the main types of research designs in qualitative research as ethnography, phenomenology, narrative research, grounded theory, and case study design. This section, therefore, seeks to discuss the research design for this study.

5.5.1. Case study design:

Case study is a qualitative research design that seeks to deeply research a certain social phenomenon using different sources of data, and that it could be descriptive, exploratory or explanatory research (Shah and Al-Bargi, 2013). Similarly, Yin (2014) stated that believing case study is used only in exploratory research is just a misconception that many social scientists still hold as it is also appropriate in explanatory and descriptive research. Additionally, the typology of case study research design was broadened to include several distinctive types (Cohen, Manion and Morisson, 2018; Baxter and Jack, 2008). Following Yin’s (2003) types of case study design, Baxter and Jack (2008) distinguished seven types of case study design as follows:

Type of case study	Definition
--------------------	------------

Explanatory	Explain causal relationships of situations that cannot be understood using experimental designs (Yin, 2003).
Exploratory	Explore phenomena that have no clear outcomes (Yin, 2003).
Descriptive	Describe a phenomenon in its real-life context (Yin, 2003).
Multi-case studies	Explore differences between different cases (Yin, 2003).
Intrinsic	Researchers are interested in the case.
Instrumental	Seeks to achieve something rather than understanding a specific phenomenon.
Collective	Like multiple-case study design in nature (Yin, 2003).

Table: 5.1. Different Types of Case Studies [Source: Baxter and Jack, 2008].

Creswell (2007) asserted that case study research is sometimes being confused with narrative research when researchers select a single individual case to research, demystifying the difference between case study and narrative research in that case study is mainly focusing on a specific issue within the chosen case while the focus of narrative research is on the individuals themselves and the stories, they narrate about their life events. In this study, the focus was drawn essentially on the social stresses experienced by Algerian students and their families.

The term “case” is used to indicate an individual, a social group, a social phenomenon (Creswell, 2014). Case study design does not focus on studying people as individuals only, but it also researches other phenomena in the social world (Thomas, 2011). Yin (2014, p.16) defined case study design as “an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon in-depth within its real-world context, especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context may not be clearly evident”. That is, researchers opting for case study seek to understand a certain real-life case situation in relation to its context. Defining the research question of the research is the first step researchers must do as it guides the research in terms of design and doing the research (Braun and Clarke, 2013). Yin (2014) identified a set of criteria that lead researchers to prioritize the use of case study design over other designs in research, stating that case study would be the appropriate research design to be used where: the research questions being asked in the research are “how” and “why” research questions, researchers have little or no control over the event and where the event being studied is a contemporary event (Yin, 2014).

This study selected case study design to conduct this research as it met the suggested criteria by Yin (2014). This is because, firstly, the research is mainly centred on understanding the social stresses affecting the families of Algerian students and students during the period of their PhD studies in the UK and how they both cope with these stresses in the context of separation. Secondly, the researcher has no control over the phenomenon being studied and the participants' behaviours. Finally, the research is concerned with studying a contemporary situation of family separation during the period of taking doctoral research. Most importantly, case study design allowed this research to study real people in real situations to understand the phenomenon (Cohen, Manion and Morisson, 2018).

According to Merriam (2009), case study is a detailed explanation and investigation of a bounded system, which refers to the case as the object of study. Besides, he pointed out that case study design is featured by special characteristics that help in defining it which are: particularism in which case study research is centred on a specific phenomenon, heuristic in which it enlightens the reader's perception of the phenomenon being studied, and descriptiveness as case study research ends with a thick description of the phenomenon (Merriam, 2009). The study focused on understanding the social stresses experienced by Algerian students taking doctoral research in the UK and their left-behind families in the context of family separation. The research, therefore, aimed at studying the phenomenon of *social stress* that occurs in the context of family separation and, thus, the bounded systems or cases of the research would be Algerian students in the UK, and their families in Algeria. Consequently, the research was also congruent with the exploratory and descriptive nature of case study research that strive to understand people's perceptions about the situation.

Yin (2014) has distinguished four types of case study design based on how many units of analysis (cases) the research requires, as follows:

- a. Single-case design with a single holistic unit of analysis,
- b. Single- case design with multiple embedded units of analysis,
- c. Multiple-case design with a single unit of analysis,
- d. Multiple-case design with multiple embedded units of analysis (Yin, 2014).

According to Yin (2014), single-case study research designs look at one case. Multiple-case study research designs, however, seeks to investigate two or more cases. On the other hand, single unit of analysis case study designs look at the global phenomenon while multiple

units of analysis case study designs seek to have a deep investigation and examine the embedded units of the phenomenon.

When conducting case study research, researchers first identify the case they wish to look at and determine its type, then, deciding about having a single case or multiple cases to get a greater level of understanding of the phenomenon (Yin, 2003). According to Baxter and Jack (2008), questioning the difference between a holistic case study with embedded units of analysis and a multiple case study design is most likely to be faced by researchers, where having different context for each case is the answer for that question. The researcher, in multiple case study design, investigates the phenomenon within each context and between contexts to compare between the cases. In single case study design with embedded units, however, the researcher investigates a sole unique case.

Descriptive multiple-case study design was used in this study as it aimed to address the same phenomenon of *social stresses* within two different contexts, the Algerian families back home and students in the UK. The study also aimed to address how these Algerian students and their families cope with separation, and thus look at the similarities and differences across both cases, which legitimize the use of multiple case study in the research. Also, the case study type allowed for getting narrative accounts of the individuals and describing the phenomenon as it occurs in real-life settings in this study (Yin, 2003; Cohen, Manion and Morisson, 2018).

5.6. Data collection:

5.6.1. Pilot study:

After having the questions of the semi-structured interview initially done, a pilot study was conducted with a small sample to test the questions. Thereof, a pilot study was defined as “a version of the main study that is run in miniature to test whether the components of the main study can all work together” (Arain, Campbell, Cooper and Lancaster, 2010). Teijlingen and Hundley (2002) claimed that conducting a pilot study prior to the main study gives the researcher insights about where the research could fail or whether the designed methods and tools are appropriate or not. Moreover, Doody and Doody (2015) declared that pilot study is conducted with a small group of participants like the larger scale participants of the main study to assess the effectiveness of the data collection techniques. Even though doing a pilot study does not ensure the success of the main study, its value could give promises for a successful data collection step as it helps to ensure the success of the data collection tool and highlight weaknesses of the interview questions.

To investigate the methodology of the study, a pilot study was developed to test the research instrument and find out what could be adjusted (Kim, 2010). As the study sought to study two case studies, Algerian PhD students in the UK and their left-behind families, the participants of the pilot study were four participants, two PhD students and two family members of theirs. Both Algerian PhD students have been taking their PhD course in the UK for more than two years. The study relied on in-depth semi structured interviews (Braun and Clarke, 2013; Merriam, 2009) as a data collection tool, namely, one designed in English language for PhD students and another one designed in Arabic language, which was conducted in Algerian Arabic, for the family members. Interview questions were piloted to test the questions and to check their feasibility whether they are appropriate to obtain the expected results and findings about the problem being investigated (Yin, 2014)., and to develop the researcher confidence of the selected approach for research.

Piloting the semi-structured interviews with a small sample consisting of two PhD students and two family members provided the researcher with scientific insights that helped to develop the type and quality of questions. Some amendments were made based on the interviewing experience the researcher has gain and the participants' answers. The researcher became more mindful and developed strategies of interviewing. She learned how to ask questions related to the participant's scope of concern without intervening her own concerns. Accordingly, it has been deduced from the pilot study that the focus should be put on the participants' experiences regarding the issues being tackled in the interview so that it reflects the participants' experiences of social stress in the context of family separation.

Based on the piloted interviews, the amendments were as follows:

The first section in the interview schedule is about a short introduction about the participants in which a set of introductory questions was set to know the participant, their hometown in Algeria, the ethnic group they belong to and their families, and then moving to ask about for how long they have been in the UK doing their PhDs. After piloting, this question should introduce stress as it has been explained by participants as an integral part of PhD life.

In the section about social stresses, the second question was changed from: "What is the best part of being an international student?" to "what do you like the most about being an international student?" so that participants do not perceive the question as a leading question and assume as if there is a worst part of being international student.

The question: “is family separation a source of stress for you?” This question was omitted, as it is similar to the question: “is being separated from your family stressful to you?”. The latter was also amended to become “how does family separation affect you?” Very few questions were also deleted as participants have given them the same answers and the researcher noticed that it is a kind of repetition in the questions.

Some words in the Arabic version of the family interview schedule were changed so that family members can better understand them. Since the interview is a semi-structured interview, new questions resulted out of the discussion, which helped in strengthening the questions to get more data for the study. Moreover, there were some probing questions to ask for further details and to fill up inconsistency (Cohen, Manion and Morisson, 2018), if it was found in their answers. It has also been noticed that participants sometimes give answers to some of the questions within discussions prior to asking them.

As stated earlier, the reason behind conducting the pilot study was to check the interview questions whether they are operative enough for the interview to address the research topic and to check to what extent Algerian families get involved in the study. The answers of the participants were helpful and assisted in editing the questions before starting to collect data for the study.

5.6.2. Semi-structured interviews:

The term “interview” commonly refers to a conversation between two people where the interviewer asks questions, and the interviewee gives answers. Interviews are mainly used in qualitative research to collect data. Accordingly, Merriam (2009, p.87) affirmed that “in all forms of qualitative research, some and occasionally all of the data are collected through interviews” and added “the most common form of interview is the person-to-person encounter in which one person elicits information from another”. In other words, interviews’ premium purpose in research is to explore the respondents’ perceptions about the phenomenon under investigation (Silverman, 2017).

Cohen, Manion and Morisson (2018) highlighted that interviews range from; formal interviews where questions are first set and then asked to the participant in which the answers are recorded on a standardized interview schedule, less formal ones where the questions can be altered, reordered, and explained by the interviewer, to the informal interviews where the interviewer runs the interview as an informal conversation raising the key concerns of the interview rather than pre-designing questions. Correspondingly, Merriam (2009) has

categorized three main types of interviews: standardized or highly structured interviews where the order and wording of the questions is predetermined in a written survey from which the interviewer conducts the oral interview, semi-structured interviews where the questions do not require predetermined wording and order, used flexibly and guided by the issues the researcher seeks to explore in the research, and unstructured interviews which are more like a conversation as researchers intend to learn from the interviewee about the phenomenon through asking flexible open-ended questions.

This study aimed at understanding the social stresses affecting the families of Algerian students and students themselves during the period of their doctoral research in the UK in the context of family separation. The focus is on students and their families as the primary sources of data. Accordingly, semi-structured interviews were used as a research technique for collecting data. This is because, semi-structured interviews provide participants with the opportunity to raise issues that has not been expected by the researcher, which enrich the researcher's understanding of the problem (Braun and Clarke, 2013). Thus, semi-structured interview presented a useful data collection technique for this research. Two interview schedules were used in the study after piloting them; one interview in English was designed for students (appendix G) and another two interview schedules in Arabic and English for family members (appendices H, I). The interview questions were quite similar as the aim was to understand social stress in the context of family separation within two different settings.

5.6.3. Online interviewing:

Due to the COVID 19 pandemic, the interviews could be conducted face-to -face with most participants. This is because the study dealt with Algerian students in the UK and their left-behind families. Borders closure hindered the researcher from having face-to-face interviews with Algerian students' family members back home. Face-to-face interviews could not also be conducted with some of the Algerian students in the UK due to the lockdown regulations. This is because, "many of the immediate effects of the pandemic resulted from the need to control it by restricting mobility and migration – from movement across international borders down to movement within spaces of everyday life" (Settersten Jr et al., 2020, p.7). This urged the researcher to opt for online interviews to collect data for the study.

Online interviewing refers to the conduct of interviews with computer and internet. Cohen, Manion and Morisson (2018) explained online interviewing as conducting interviews in the virtual world which can take distinct forms: text-based only (email, blogs, chat rooms),

audio only (WhatsApp, conferencing), a mixing up of text and visuals (social networking sites, instant messaging) and audio and visual interviews (net meetings, conferences and skype). Internet, hence, has offered researchers several forms to conduct online research. Accordingly, James and Busher (2009, p.6) acknowledged that internet has significantly impacted how qualitative research is conducted in social sciences as it has changed the kind of environment in which knowledge is created and research is conducted; the latter can be virtually conducted with one person or a group of people. In this study, participants were given the right to choose the online form of interview that suits them. Thereof, several forms were used like, Skype, Zoom and Facebook messenger. Only two interviews were conducted face-to-face with two students.

Shapka, Domene, Khan and Yang (2016) have conducted semi-structured interviews with adolescents through instant messaging or in-person to study the quantity and quality of data generated from online and face-to-face interviews. The findings showed that even though online interviews took more time to be completed and resulted in fewer words than face-to-face interviews, there was no difference in the resulted themes in terms of number, kind, and depth of discussion. Moreover, the quality of data in online interviews is as good as in face-to-face interviews. Thus, the form of data collection has no effect on data quality.

5.6.4. Sampling strategies:

The quality of any piece of research depends mainly on choosing the appropriate methodology and making early decisions about the sample for the research (Cohen, Manion and Morisson, 2018). A sample is defined as a portion of a population; the latter denotes the total number of people or things to be researched.

Sampling strategies through which researchers select their samples differ from qualitative to quantitative research. Based on randomization, there exist two different strategies of sampling: probability and non-probability sampling (Cohen, Manion and Morisson, 2018; Bryman, 2012). As for probability (random) samples are used in quantitative research which opts for the random selection of participants (Ritchie *et al.*, 2014). This type of sample gives more chances to different members of the population to be selected, as the selection is made randomly without any criteria. Conversely, non-probability samples are used in qualitative research where members of the population do not have equal chances of inclusion and exclusion, as the selection is made according to a set of criteria that are pre-determined by the researcher according to the needs of the research. Therefore, the researcher aims to study a

particular group that only represents itself and cannot be generalized to represent a bigger population. There are different types of non-probability samples like, purposive sampling, snowball sampling, quota sampling and convenience sampling, theoretical sampling, and others (Cohen, Manion and Morisson, 2018).

The sample size is a crucial for researchers when coming to select a sample. Qualitative researchers tend to use small samples. Samples in qualitative research are neither too small nor too large; very small samples can lead researchers to miss key constituencies and diversities within the population (Ritchie *et al.*, 2014). Qualitative researchers do not have a fixed number of participants at the beginning of their research; however, the sample size depends on the process of data collection (Flick, 2009); researchers collect data until they feel it is sufficient and reach “the saturation point” where researchers are no more getting new information from collecting data, (Kumar, 2014).

The choice of the sampling technique depends mainly on the nature, purpose and the type of the research being undertaken. That is, the research objectives and the characteristics of the population determine which people or subjects are going to be selected for the sample. When researchers have limited access to the wider population and select only the participants who are available and easily accessible until reaching the required sample size; they used convenience/ opportunity sampling (Cohen, Manion and Morisson, 2018; Etikan, Abubakar Musa and Sunusi Alkassim, 2016; Ritchie *et al.*, 2014; Bryman, 2012).

The population this research addressed is Algerian PhD students taking doctoral research in the UK as government-sponsored students (Guerriche, 2020). The study dealt with family members of these students who remain at home. This study focused on understanding the social stresses affecting the families of Algerian students and students themselves in the context of family separation. So, the study dealt with two groups of people: Algerian students in the UK and their left-behind family members. In addition to being a government-sponsored doctoral student, spending almost two years in the UK or more was another inclusion criteria upon which students were selected for the study. This study, therefore, opted for a convenience sampling to select the research sample.

Students were asked to participate in the research first. Students who accepted to take part in the study were then asked to identify the closest family members to them whom they nominate to participate in this study. Recruiting family members was challenging and time consuming due to families’ unfamiliarity with the nature of academic research. This resulted

in having fewer family members than students. At this stage of recruitment, some students withdrew their participation because of their family members' unwillingness to take part in the study.

5.6.5. Sample dimensions:

As the study aimed at understanding the social stresses affecting Algerian PhD students in the UK and their families in Algeria during the period of conducting a PhD in the context of separation, the two cases of study were determined from the beginning of the research. Convenience sampling was used to gather participants based on their availability with their families.

The research participants identified themselves as being religiously Muslim (Tiliouine and Achoui, 2018), and culturally Arabs or Berbers. Arabs with reference to the culture, language and system of values introduced by the Islam, and Chaoui and Kabyle as community groups of Berbers as the first ethnic inhabitants of Algeria (Benrabah, 2005). A total of 18 PhD students (2 males and 16 females) and 11 family members, who were ranged from sisters, brothers, mothers, fathers, and cousins, took part in the study. All research participants are born from Algerian parents and brought up in the Algerian society. The tables below present information regarding gender, age, ethnicity, previous travel experiences, and family structure of research participants.

Student's name	Gender	Age (at the time of the interview)	Ethnic group	Religion	Algerian Region	Doctoral stage
Nancy	Female	27	Chaoui	Muslim	Northeast	2nd year
Clover		28			Northeast	3rd year
Jane		27			Northeast	2nd year
Carol		28			Northeast	3rd year
Lucy		28			Northeast	3rd year
Anne		27			Arab	Northeast

Rose		29			Northeast	2nd year
Katy		27			Northeast	2nd year
Steven	Male	28			Northwest	3rd year
Jack		28			Northwest	3rd year
Emma	Female	28			Northwest	2nd year
Gill		27			Northeast	2nd year
Lisa		27			Northeast	2nd year
Emma		28			Northwest	2nd year
Spencer		28			Southwest	3rd year
Emily		27			Northwest	2nd year
Josie		27			Northeast	2nd year
Ashley		27			Northeast	2nd year
Catherine		28	Kabyle		North centre	3rd year

Table: 5.2. Algerian PhD students' background.

Family member	Gender	Age	Ethnic group	Religion	Algerian region	Profession	Family structure
Emma's sister	Female	27	Arab	Muslim	Northwest	University graduate	parents, Emma is the eldest, 3 sisters
Clover's mother	Female	late 50's			Northeast	Housewife (Primary school teacher before getting married)	deceased husband: 5 married daughters, 2 sons

Spencer's sister	Female	Late 30's			Southwest	PhD student in Algeria	deceased mother, stepmother, father, 2 brothers, 3 sisters, Spencer is the youngest sister
Emily's father	Male	60's			Northwest	Retired	wife, 4 daughters, 2 sons
Josie's mother	Female	50's			Northeast	Housewife	husband, 4 daughters.
Ashley's brother	Male	19			Northeast	Man of arms	parents, 1 sister, 1 brother. Ashely is the eldest and the only sister
Lisa's cousin	Female	31			Northeast	Did not mention	Maternal cousin of Lisa - Lisa's family: parents, 1 brother, 1 sister
Jane's twin sister	Female	27	Chaoui		Northeast	University graduate	parents, six sisters,

						Nephews, nieces
Carol's sister	Female	30			Northeast	University graduate parents, 1 sister, 1 brother.
Nancy's brother	Male	19			Northeast	University student deceased mother, father, stepmother 2 sisters, 2 brothers
Catherine's sister	Female	24	Kabyle		North centre	University graduate parents, 1 brother, 4 sisters.

Table: 5.3. Family members backgrounds.

5.7. Data analysis:

In any research, the analysis of the collected data is required for finishing the fieldwork and collecting the needed data to answer the research questions of the research. Accordingly, Merriam (2009, p.171) claimed that “data analysis is one of the few facets, perhaps the only facet, of doing qualitative research in which there is a preferred way”. Furthermore, it is an ongoing process that arises throughout the research process and finishes at the end of the research (Cohen, Manion and Morisson, 2018). Thus, data analysis is often regarded as the most difficult step in the research process as it might go on for ever (Merriam and Tisdell’s, 2016). Novice researchers frequently worry that they might not be able to find answers to the research questions or that data is not enough, because data analysis might be a very time-consuming and exhausting task that needs patience. Data analysis is the process of making sense of the collected data, understanding, and interpreting what participants have explained and said about the phenomenon under research and what the researcher has understood (Cohen, Manion and Morisson, 2018; Merriam, 2009). Flick (2014) added, the main goal of qualitative data analysis is to interpret the verbal or visual data to form statements that address the research questions. Following the six stages of Braun and Clarke (2006), I used thematic analysis to

analyse data in this qualitative study. This section explains the steps I followed to analyse data in this study.

5.7.1. Thematic analysis:

Thematic analysis is a method that is used to analyse data in qualitative research. As the term “thematic” suggests, thematic analysis focuses on the main themes that resulted from the research data. Correspondingly, Guest, MacQueen and Namey (2012, p.10) mentioned that “thematic analyses move beyond counting explicit words or phrases and focus on identifying and describing both implicit and explicit ideas within the data, that is, themes”. It urges the researcher to look for the common themes across the whole data collected from the set of interviews with all the study participants rather than focusing on a single data unit from one participant. This is a significant feature that enhanced the analysis of data in this research, as the latter aimed at explaining the phenomenon of *social stress* in the context of family separation from the perspectives of Algerian students taking PhD study in the UK and their left-behind families.

Thematic analysis aims to identify and analyse themes in the research data. Braun and Clarke (2006, p.82) have defined the key term in thematic analysis “theme” as “something important about the data in relation to the research question and represents some level of patterned response or meaning within the data set”. They have identified six steps to analyse qualitative data thematically as follows: reading and re-reading the data, setting primary codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, identifying final themes, and writing the final report of analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

The analysis at the level of single data units, that is by participant, allowed the researcher to elicit the similarities across the participants’ narratives from which the themes were identified. Data analysis in this study was an iterative process; I kept going back and forth to the interview transcripts to check my interpretations throughout the whole process of producing the findings chapters.

5.7.2. Transcription:

At the very initial stages of data analysis, I started to learn about my data when listening to the interview recordings prior to the transcription process. Transcription, however, despite taking time especially for verbatim aims, gives researchers the opportunity to be more familiar with their data; that is, transcription of an hour-long interview could take up to five hours

(Cohen, Manion and Morisson, 2018). I conducted a total of 29 semi-structured interviews (18 with students and 11 with members of families), each was between 60 and 180 minutes long. At the beginning, it took me up to 5 hours to transcribe 30 minutes as I aimed for a verbatim transcription where I kept record of all verbal and non-verbal parts of the interviews. That is, I tried to transcribe all participants' words including the wordlessly vocal sounds like “mmm” and “ugh” that expressed the participants' feelings like surprise, hesitation and thinking. Progressively, I initiated to take out the unnecessary parts of interviews such as: pauses, greetings and jokes that made the transcription process take more time. However, I made sure not to eliminate details like crying, laughter, and long pauses that might contribute to understanding the research question and aims of the study.

As for transcribing Algerian Arabic interviews, I had to choose between transcribing in Arabic or Latin letters of alphabets as most of family members were using French with their Algerian Arabic. I initially went for writing the interview transcripts in Arabic letters with French words and expressions in Latin alphabets (see figure 5.1), when possible, as this was not the case with all interviews. Sometimes, I used Arabic letters of alphabets to transcribe the whole interview (see figure 5.2).

المشاركة: اهيه تسمى انايا مع الاول ماكنتش نهدر معاها ياسر ياسر في التليفون ولا فهمتيني ماكنتش
 نهدر معاها ياسر **APRÈS** كي راحت لتما وليت نعيطلها نسقسي عليها **SOUVENT** كي وليت
 نعيطلها نسقسي عليها ولينا ندره مع بعضانا ياسرانا وياها
 الباحثة: اممم

المشاركة: فهمتيني **LA RELATION** نتاعنا **C'EST PAS PROFONDÉ** فهمتيني ولات
PLUS ودرك ولينا انا وياها ما ماكانش **IMPOSSIBLE** نهار يفوت بلا مانهدره فيه مع بعضانا و
 بلا ما فهمتي نعهده نحكيو مع بعضانا انا وياها حتان نرقده **LA CAME** محلولة
 الباحثة: هيه

المشاركة: فهمتي **ON EST TRÈS TRS PROCHE**
 الباحثة: اهيه

Figure: 5.1. Transcription with Arabic and Latin letters of Alphabets.

عليهم ولا!..

الآخ : كايين كايين ايه كايين مخاوف في بالنا هك ماعلاباليش انا قادر نفقدو شخص من العائلة نتاعنا وهي ماتحضرش
..... ا سيرتو فالظروف هانو نتاع كورونا ما مستحيل ااا كايين ااااا الناس بزاف لي حرقتم الغربية وكيفا يقولك
تسمى الغربية بعد ابي بخلاصة القول راهي شمعة تسمى اذا شعلتلك ..هاي شعلتلك و اذا طفالتك قادرا طفالك اذا ااا
قادرة تنوبك ولا اذا ماذبتش قادرة تحرقك كيما حرقت اا بزاف ناس هذي الغربية سمي فيها مخاوف فيها قدها من حاجة
ااا بالنسبة لينا حن مخاوف انا قتلك ممكن مخاوف بالنسبة لينا حنا قادر نخصرو حنا فرد من هنا من العائلة ماعلاباليش انا جد
اوو ااا ااااا مثلا نانا مثلا الاب تاغي مثلا اا فهمتي يسمي واحد يتوقع شوية .. هكا

الباحثة : اهيبه اوكي

Figure: 5.2. Transcription with Arabic letters of Alphabets.

5.7.3. Translation:

Translation in this study was related to the interviews conducted with members of families. This is because most of the interviews with family members were conducted in the Algerian dialect, only two interviews were in English. All family members who spoke in the Algerian dialect of Arabic, sometimes used words or phrases in Standard Arabic or French. The reverse case also worked with two members of families and some students who used mainly English to express their thoughts, while switching to French and Algerian Arabic in some points. The reason is that Algeria, as previously mentioned in the context and background of the study, is linguistically diverse (Gherzouli, 2019; Belmihoub, 2018). Accordingly, making a decision on translation was not simple and easy for the researcher. It was exhausting and challenging to catch as much meanings family members conveyed as possible. I have opted for a few different approaches. I started to translate one interview while transcribing it. However, several words and phrases used by the participants had no accurate equivalents in English. Therefore, I chose to retain them in the original language of interviewing. I decided to work on the transcription of all the interviews in the original language of interviewing, Algerian Arabic. The transcribed interviews then were analysed, where themes and codes were all set up in English. I only went for the translation of data pieces that were needed to be used to support the analysis and discussion chapters.

I adopted strategy of “back translation” suggested by Merriam and Tisdell’s (2016) to improve the accuracy and reliability of my translations. I essentially asked some of my colleagues, who are said to be multilinguals and taking postgraduate study in the UK, to translate my translated segments of data back to the original language of interviewing to help verify that my translations are reliable and accurate. The process of back translation with my

colleagues revealed no important modifications between the initial and the final translation (see figure). My translations were well received by my colleagues. I only shared the data excerpts with them that I needed to use in the presenting and discussing my findings to maintain the confidentiality of participants interviews.

Original language of interviewing

كيعاد طفلة ميش طفل تخافي عليها اكثر، راح تخافي اكثر اتقولي كيفاه الطفلة راح تعيش وحدها

Translation to target language

Because she is a female not a male, you should fear more. You would be frightened more for a female and how she can manage to live alone.

Back translation to original language

كي راهي طفلة ميش طفل راح تخافي اكثر عليها، تخافي اكثر على الطفلة و كيفاه راح تعيش وحدها

Figure: 5.3. Back translation sample.

5.7.4. Coding process:

According to Merriam and Tisdell's (2016), the analysis of qualitative data is often inductive; the researcher inductively derives the findings from the data by searching for themes and patterns. Contrarily, deductive analysis is theory-driven and uses pre-existing theories to analyse data (Cohen, Manion and Morisson, 2018; Merriam and Tisdell's, 2016). As the transcription process was time-consuming, I started the process of analysis after conducting almost half of the interviews. Following the steps of thematic analysis (Clarke and Braun, 2013), I generated codes and formed themes from the data. The flexibility of thematic analysis allows the researcher for the inductive and/or deductive identification of patterns inside and across data sets (Braun and Clarke, 2006). In this study, I adopted inductive approach to analyse the collected data and construct the findings. The analysis process in this study is explained below.

5.7.4.1. Codes generation:

After having the transcription of interviews done, which is the first step of the analysis process (Merriam and Tisdell's, 2016; Clarke and Braun, 2013), the researcher read the transcripts several times to become familiar and immerse herself more in the data. After organizing the transcripts, I started the coding process. I first tried with one printed transcript underlining and highlighting interesting pieces of data and then giving them names, which I

wrote on the margins, as codes. However, I changed my method and used the electronic copies of transcripts where I started the process of coding through assigning codes to important parts of data that are related to my study aims and writing them as comments on the Microsoft word document. Coding, therefore, is the process of breaking down data pieces into units of analysis (words, phrases and even paragraphs), labelling them and organizing them into different categories (Cohen, Manion and Morisson, 2018; Merriam and Tisdell's, 2016). Accordingly, codes can be derived from a variety of sources; they may be inspired by the theory, research questions, participants' statements, or the researcher's interpretations (Cohen, Manion and Morisson, 2018; Merriam and Tisdell's, 2016). A code, consequently, is a term or a short phrase that expresses the main idea of why the researcher believes that a certain piece of data might be helpful to answer the research question (Clarke and Braun, 2013).

Figure: 5.4. Coding process using Microsoft Word Document.

At this stage, interview transcripts were approached inductively, data-driven, in which I opted for “complete coding”, which involved identifying "anything and everything of interest or relevance" across all data (Clarke and Braun, 2013, p. 206). This is especially helpful in cases of broad research questions and there are no specific patterns to concentrate on (Clarke and Braun, 2013). In doing so, the researcher must take into account every element of data contained in the transcripts. This helped the researcher in using the segments that she coded at first and then considered them later as irrelevant to the central subject of study, yet they were useful in supporting her argument in the research and highlighting the significance of this study findings. For instance, when I generated codes in relation to taking a PhD study in Algeria and started to make connections across them, I could find out under which theme I should put them, and I could consequently recognize their importance in explaining participants' perceptions of stress in relation to study.

5.7.4.2. Themes formation:

The second stage of the analysis process revolved around searching for and naming themes. This was mainly done through opting for axial coding. The latter refers to the step in which the researcher classifies and groups codes into categories that share similar characteristics to form themes and sub-themes (Cohen, Manion and Morisson, 2018; Saldaña, 2016). Several codes are combined to create themes, a theme is wider than a code. A theme, should, subsequently, has a “central organising concept” (Braun and Clarke, 2013, p. 224), that is, a key aspect of the data to address the research questions.

After an extensive list of codes was generated, at this stage, I started looking for potential themes through using “visual representations” (Braun and Clarke, 2006, p. 89) to make relationships between different codes to form themes. To better understand the themes and sub-themes and the relationships between them, I created initial thematic maps (Braun and Clarke, 2013), I was then able to recognize the connection between the themes and sub-themes that serve to fulfil the same research objective of the study and answer the research question. This allowed me to look through the themes, review and name them. At this step, I ended up having four main themes each with different sub-themes.

5.8. Trustworthiness of the research:

Although there are no fixed quality criteria to evaluate qualitative research, it is possible to distinguish between good and poor quality of research (Braun and Clarke, 2013). Like quantitative researchers, qualitative researchers need to assess the quality of their research using a set of criteria (Bryman, 2016). Since this study is qualitative, the interpretivist concept of “trustworthiness” was used to replace the positivist notions of validity and reliability in quantitative research (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). The qualitative criteria: credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability were suggested to respectively substitute the quantitative criteria: internal validity, external validity, reliability, and objectivity (Merriam and Tisdell’s, 2016; Lincoln and Guba, 1985). Accordingly, several scholars suggested several strategies to assess the quality of qualitative research and ensure trustworthiness (Merriam and Tisdell’s, 2016; Creswell and Miller, 2000; Lincoln and Guba, 1985). The following discusses how I attempted to meet trustworthiness criteria and the strategies I used in this study.

5.8.1. Credibility:

Credibility aims to answer the question “How congruent are the findings with reality?” (Stahl, and King 2020). It deals with how findings of the research match with reality and whether they really capture the participants’ views? (Merriam and Tisdell’s, 2016). In this study, I attempted to ensure the credibility of the findings using different strategies:

- **Member checking** is “the most critical technique for establishing credibility” (Lincoln and Guba, 1985, p.314). It involves seeking feedback from some participants on initial emerging findings of the research (Merriam and Tisdell’s, 2016). Accordingly, some interview transcripts were sent to the available participants to check for their answers’ accuracy. These participants did not show any disagreement to the transcripts, yet few of them showed their willingness to answer any further questions. Initial findings were then discussed with four student participants who offered few comments.
- **Prolonged engagement in data collection** involves spending enough time in the fieldwork to build trust through getting closer to participants’ understandings of the phenomenon (Merriam and Tisdell’s, 2016; Creswell and Miller, 2000). I spent almost five months in data collection. Recruiting participants took time especially with family members who needed more time to know about the research and to think about their willingness to participate. This allowed me to build trust with my participants, listen to the interview recordings and reflect on them during gaps of fieldworks and to member-check with participants.
- **Peer review/debriefing** involves having someone who is knowledgeable about the research and the phenomenon under study, playing the “devil’s advocate” through challenging the researcher’s methodology and interpretations of findings (Merriam and Tisdell’s, 2016; Creswell and Miller, 2000; Lincoln and Guba, 1985). In this study, my interpretations were discussed with three critical friends of mine who were also conducting doctoral research, yet in different disciplines. Their comments allowed me to view my interpretations from different angles.

5.8.2. Dependability:

Dependability it is concerned with whether the findings would be consistent when repeating the study under the same conditions (Amankwaa, 2016; Anney, 2014). Lincoln and Guba (1985) referred to the interrelation between credibility and dependability and that ensuring the former can, to some extent, ensure the latter, noting to the use of audit trail to check dependability, further to credibility strategies.

- **Audit trail** allows the researcher to keep record of the data collection and analysis procedures and ask an external auditor to check them (Creswell and Miller, 2000). This strategy was maintained in this study through providing my supervisors with details regarding the steps and decisions I undertook before and during data collection, and consulting with them in data analysis and interpretations. Another way to ensure dependability was having feedback from different academics in workshops.

5.8.3. Transferability:

Transferability deals with to what extent the findings are applicable to other contexts (Amankwaa, 2016). It aims to check whether the research findings can be generalised or transferred to different research setting and participants through providing enough descriptive data about the research context (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). This is maintained through thick description (Merriam and Tisdell's, 2016; Creswell and Miller, 2000; Lincoln and Guba, 1985).

- **Thick description:** Merriam and Tisdell's (2016, p.257) defined it as a rich description of "the setting and participants of the study, as well as a detailed description of the findings". It aims to create a sense of familiarity with the events being reported in a study so that readers feel as if they have/ could experience them (Creswell and Miller, 2000). To enhance transferability of this study, a thick and detailed description of the research context (chapter 2), participants and research process (chapter 5) and findings (chapters 6, 7,8,9) is presented in this thesis.

5.8.4. Confirmability:

Confirmability is concerned with "degree of neutrality or the extent to which the findings of a study are shaped by the respondents and not researcher bias, motivation, or interest" (Amankwaa, 2016, p.121). It can be achieved in research through "providing rich quotes from the participants that depict each emerging theme" (Cope, 2014, p. 89). Audit trail and reflexivity can be used to establish confirmability in research (Amankwaa, 2016). Confirmability was maintained in this research through illustrating my interpretations with participants quotes throughout the findings' chapters (6,7,8,9). Reflexivity and acknowledgment of my positionality as researcher in this study is explained in the next section.

5.9. Reflexivity and researcher positionality:

In qualitative research, researchers serve as the instrument for gathering data; the researcher's beliefs and background are significant factors that could influence the research

process (Bourke, 2014). Qualitative novice researchers, however, might find it challenging to locate their position and beliefs when undertaking postgraduate research (Holmes, 2020); as positionality in qualitative research represents an intersection point between being objective and/or subjective when researching social phenomena (Bourke, 2014). Positionality “reflects the position that the researcher has chosen to adopt within a given research study” (Savin-Baden and Major, 2013, p. 71). Therefore, it is important to recognise my positionality in this study.

Since being an Algerian doctoral student in the UK, just like participant students in this research, made me question my position in the study and my relationship with the participant, I made sure to be aware of my position as a researcher at different stages of the study. For instance, when recruiting participants, I had to assure that my position as an Algerian PhD student would not be seen by participants as putting any pressure on them to take part in the research or to ask their families to do so. Thus, I made sure to make participants aware of their voluntary participation and their right to withdraw at any time through giving them enough time to read the information sheet and make their decisions.

So, my position, as the researcher of this study, is a Muslim, female, Chaoui, Algerian, friend/ colleague to some participants, international student, and a PhD student in the UK who experience family separation in the context of taking doctoral research in the UK. This led me to assume that my positionality would in some way affect my study and how I collect and interpret data as I had some assumptions about the participants because I believed that I would always be able to relate to the participants’ stories because we are going through the same experience of family separation. However, I was mistaken because, although I am also an Algerian PhD student in the UK like my student participants, but we came from different parts of Algeria, have different personal experiences, perceive things differently and study in different universities in the UK. I share the experience of taking a PhD study in the UK and leaving family behind in Algeria at macro level, but we still differ at micro level as each of us pass through different circumstances, experience different stresses, and opt for different coping mechanisms. This would make me an insider and an outsider to the research.

As an insider, I was, at the beginning of my research journey, relating the experiences of Algerian students to my own experiences in some way because I had some preconceptions that since we are all Algerian students, came from the same cultural background, received the same education, and we were exposed to the same collectivist society in Algeria, then we would

probably perceive family separation in the context of study abroad and cope with it in the same way, we might encounter similar academic challenges based on the same education we received and we might fight similar social struggles. Through conversations with Algerian students in my university and different universities in the UK, I started to realise that the way I perceive things in relation to this study abroad experience in the UK is different from their way of perceiving things. So, although we are all Algerian students, but we do experience different stressors, and when these stressors are alike, we perceive and cope with them differently. This made me feel an outsider to the research.

When conducting interviews, I was an insider at times, and an outsider at others (Braun and Clarke, 2013), which might have helped or impeded data collection. As an outsider, since Algerian PhD students in the UK and I were enrolled in different universities, we had different academic challenges, obligations and limitations based on our supervisors and our university requirements. I also felt an outsider when interviewing family members when I realised that they communicated their perceptions from the opposite angle of the experience of taking doctoral research in the UK. This made me feel an outsider to family's perspective regarding separation in the context of this study. Moving to being an insider, family members considered me as an insider when they referred to some cultural events in Algeria without giving many details as they assumed that I already know everything from the Algerian social context I share with them. This made it easier for me to build rapport and trust with my participants and made it possible to collect rich and in-depth data.

In addition to being reflexive and acknowledging my role as a researcher throughout different phases of the study, I opted for some techniques to manage my dual role as an insider/outsider in the research. I made sure to be aware of my assumptions and preconceived ideas and I acknowledged them through writing them down in a research journal of mine. I set some primary guidelines to guide myself throughout my study such as thinking critically, counting on the participants and the data I gathered from them as the primary source of data for the study and not making interpretations on my assumptions. By doing this, I was able to better represent the participants' voices through improving my understandings of their perceptions.

Because the researcher is the one who generates data in qualitative research, their personal beliefs and background, will unavoidably have an impact on the research and the positionality of the researcher (Bourke, 2014). Since I am one of those Algerian PhD students

in the UK whose family remain at home, I can relate to the group of the participants as being part of it. This made me feel an insider to this research. This was extremely apparent when some participant students spoke about other PhD students who are mutual friends for both of us, when they used Algerian Arabic to express themselves sometimes and even when they referred to the Algerian culture. It was also clear when some family members asked me to reflect on my experience as a student in the UK and on my family in Algeria who experience the same feelings as them so that I can truly get their voices.

Sometimes, I was reflecting on my own experiences when asking some questions, for instance, whether celebrating special occasions like Ramadan and religious feasts online with their families would make them feel less separated from their families or makes it much difficult for them. Although, I was somehow thinking of myself as an Algerian student who experiences separation from her family, I was conscious of their uniqueness and distinctiveness and thus I attempted to approach questions objectively and beyond the limits of my own experience. So, I aimed at learning about their experiences and accounts through their voices instead of my own reflections. This made me feel an outsider at some points.

5.10. Ethical considerations:

In qualitative research, researchers must emphasize ethical challenges for two main reasons; first, dealing with individuals' beliefs through having close contact with them entails ensuring their consent, and anonymity, second, the use of qualitative research to study sensitive topics that might provoke painful memories requires the researcher to gain their trust (Silverman, 2017). Conducting research in an ethical manner allows researchers to avoid causing any harm to the participants through taking their interests into account. To conduct this study, an ethical approval was granted from the ethics committee in the University of the West of Scotland on March 2021 prior to starting the fieldwork (see appendix J). To get the ethical approval, an online application was filled in and submitted online via the university website. The application was supported by required documents regarding the description of the study and data collection procedure.

The ethical guidelines suggested by the British Educational Research Association (2018) were followed by the researcher in this study. The BERA offered a set of responsibilities that researchers need to adhere to. Bellow, I explain how I took these responsibilities into account in this study:

- **Responsibilities to participants:** participants were emailed a consent form to sign prior to conducting interviews and collecting data for the study. The form indicated an assertion that participants have the choice to withdraw their participation from the research at any time. They were given sufficient time to decide upon their voluntary participation in the research. They were also sent an information sheet that explained the nature, purpose and benefit of the study, information about the way the interview would progress, and the way results would be presented in the research. The consent form, information sheet, and interview schedules. Exemplars of the consent form, information sheet, and interview schedules are found in the appendices respectively (K, L, M, N, O, G, H, I). Furthermore, participants were informed of the anonymity of their personal information regarding names and identities, through using pseudonyms, to maintain their privacy (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018; Silverman, 2017). Confidentiality was also guaranteed to participants via the consent form and information sheet; as participants might tend to talk about sensitive and personal matters while being interviewed (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018; Silverman, 2017). Therefore, the researcher saved the interview recordings on her personal laptop in an encrypted folder.
- **Responsibilities to sponsors, clients, and stakeholders in research:** as mentioned in section 5.9, the researcher is one of these Algerian doctoral students who are sponsored by the Algerian government in the UK. This, however, did not impact this study as the Algerian government did not make any decisions regarding choices of the research topic and methods, yet all choices in this research were made by the researcher.
- **Responsibilities to the community of educational researchers:** this was maintained at different stages of the study through using several strategies to ensure the trustworthiness of the study (see section 5.8).
- **Responsibilities for publication and dissemination:** the researcher drafted a research paper on one part of the research findings in this study, which she is planning to publish soon. As for dissemination, the researcher participated in an online conference event in which she shared insights from her initial findings of the study. She also considers future publications and participation in academic events. Furthermore, the study findings were shared with the supervisory team and three critical friends (see section 5.8).

- **Responsibilities for researchers' wellbeing and development:** since the researcher in this study came from the same cultural background of the participants, she felt emotional towards some painful experiences of the participants (Silverman, 2017), especially because she experiences family separation like her participants, yet she maintained careful attention to the participants during the interview process. The researcher, therefore, relied on her support system including family and friends to look after her wellbeing.

5.11. Chapter summary:

This chapter dealt with the methodology of research for this study. It introduced the philosophical assumptions that underpinned this study and justified the choice of the research paradigm and approach. The steps followed for collecting and analysing data are then elaborated. At the end, the chapter provided an explanation of how trustworthiness was maintained in this study in relation to reflexivity and researcher's positionality. The chapter was concluded with the different guidelines used to overcome the ethical challenges of the study. The next chapter presents and discusses findings in relation to participants' perceptions of social stress to assist answering the central research question of this study.

Chapter Six: Perceptions of social stress

6.1. Introduction:

The study aimed to understand the social stresses affecting Algerian postgraduate students during the period of their doctoral research in the UK and their families who remain in Algeria in the context of family separation. In this chapter, I present and discuss findings in relation to the perceptions of Algerian students and their left-behind families of social stress in the context of this study, which addresses the first aim of this study. To explain how they perceive social stress, students and family members centred their views on two main points: separation and study. Social stress, in this research, is generated from separation from each other, and from the difficulty of studying for doctoral degree.

6.2. Participants' conceptualizations of social stress:

Social stress is the central concept around which this research is centred. Accordingly, figuring out how participants perceive and view social stress was critical, as it is more likely to help in finding out the social stresses impacting the families of Algerian students and students themselves during the period of their PhD studies in the UK. However, all participants when I asked them to define social stress and explain how they perceive it, found it challenging mostly because of the complicated nature of the term as being a huge and general concept, as described by some students, and, for family members, due to the Algerian society unawareness of academic research and research fairness from society. Initially, Algerian PhD students struggled and hardly managed to explain their ideas at the beginning with regards to what social stress is for them. Primarily, students, who were mainly females and only two males, mentioned that stress can be defined depending on situations. This is in line with Fink's (2016) assertion that stress has different meanings for different people and conditions. For instance:

“You cannot like give a general understanding of stress; it must be referred to a situation” (Steven).

Students tended to give a general definition of stress as the state of being perplexed and not knowing what to do next. They also pointed out that stress makes individuals negative towards everything, which leads to depression.

Family members, however, who varied between mothers, fathers, sisters, and brothers struggled to give a precise definition to the concept of stress, but their responses were like Menaga and Chandrasekaran's (2014) definition of stress as situations that trigger negative

feelings in people, and Akhtar, Herwig, and Faize's (2019) conception of anxiety as subjective experiences of worry and tension.

Because research in Algeria is not very much well integrated in the social life of the Algerian society, it was challenging to get family members involved in the interview process at the beginning. Hence, it was very interesting when a family member was hesitating in her answer and asked me whether I am looking for the general definition of social stress or her definition of social stress:

“What stress means you mean, or how I perceive stress in this experience?” (Josie’s mother).

Another family member was thinking out loud:

“Social stress for me as Clover’s mother, how can I define social stress?” (Clover’s mother).

In few cases, some family members, after providing their definition, asked me how I would define social stress as if they wanted to check their answers: *“Am I right this way?” (Clover’s mother)*, *“What about you, what is social stress for you?” (Ashley’s brother, Emily’s father)*, *“You tell me now; how would you define it?” (Emily’s father)*. These participants seemed to believe that there is a fixed correct definition of the term.

Furthermore, it was very motivating to engage with the interview when one family member mentioned that the experience of family having a member studying abroad is very stressful in all sides for the family and for the member who left abroad (Josie’s mother). Similarly, another family member confirmed that in the context of this study, the family member studying in the UK and the left-behind family are both affected by stress of separation:

“Stress of separation affects the member and the family as well” (Nancy’s brother).

For these participants and others, the experiences of separation by families are highly stressful. This finding is very similar to studies that dealt with family separation in the context of migration and refugees and found that stress is one of the main impacts of family separation (McMichael, 2002; Wilmsen, 2013; Hiitola and Vähä-Savo, 2021).

Thereafter, students and family members started to gradually explain what social stress means to them and described their feelings and attitudes when they feel stressed in the context

of separation. In many cases, their answers were related to notions of alienation, loneliness, homesickness, being independent, taking responsibility and doing a PhD. These match with Msengi's (2007) findings in his research about the sources of stress international students experience and its impact on their health behaviours and academic performance in which he found out that among the common sources of stress international students face loneliness and homesickness.

For instance, one student explained:

“It is a great experience but at the same time, it is stressful because ... before we are PhD students, we are human beings... so living abroad is the hardest. It is so hard to be fully independent” (Emma).

Looking at perceptions of social stress from the lenses of Algerian doctoral students in the UK and their families back home, participants from both cases explained how they perceive social stress in relation to separation and study. Accordingly, I classified their definitions of social stress into two main categories: **separation-related stress** and **study-related stress**.

6.2.1. Separation-related stress:

Separation seems to be a core aspect that triggers the social stress Algerian students in the UK and their families who are still in Algeria encounter throughout the experience of students' doctoral journey in the UK. Participants' perceptions of separation entail their understandings of the transition from “living together” as a family to “living apart” after students' departure to the UK, which was stressful for both students and their families. To illustrate, one family member made an analogy to explain how stressful this separation of family is to both: families and students:

“Stress of family separation is like a candle that melts and burns its holder when it is flaming and so is the case of family separation, which is stressful and hard for both family members back home and the alienated family member abroad” (Nancy's brother).

The example shared by the participant above clearly depicts how stressful separation is for the left-behind families and their adult children in the UK. Nancy's brother here likened separation to a candle, where the candle's flame represents the impact of separation on students and their families who both represent the candle's holder. With this, the participant explained that study abroad context is not only difficult for students, but also for their families back home.

This is highly connected with the researcher's argument behind doing this research, which revolves around understanding the social stresses students and their families experience in the context of family separation. Most participants explained their beliefs of separation stress through two major points: alienation and responsibility.

6.2.1.1 El Ghorba – feeling alienated:

Most of the family members, at different points of the interview process, agreed that social stress in this experience is mainly about separation and alienation stress and its difficulties, which they, mainly family members, expressed in Algerian Arabic as “El Ghorba”. Participants initially tended to explain what alienation means for them and how they perceive it as follows:

“Social stress is alienation stress; how can I explain it? Alienation -El Ghorba- is when a family member leaves the family either still in Algeria or abroad – it has same stresses and fears” (Spencer’s sister).

And:

“It is El ghorba alienation when you are in a place all alone. For me, alienation is for example, I can go and live in a place 80 km away from my home and I am all alone. I would consider myself to be living in alienation because I am all alone. I don't even have one member of my family with me, neither my brother, nor my sister or a parent or my cousin, my uncle, my aunt, no one” (Lisa’s cousin).

Some family members, however, used this single word “El Ghorba” to refer to their perceptions of social stress. For instance, Emily’s father noted:

“All I can say about stress in this context of Emily studying in the UK is simply El ghorba- (alienation)” (Emily’s father).

And:

“Stress in this context of separation is just El ghorba” (Carol’s sister).

And:

“It is Alienation -El Ghorba- being alone away from family (Nancy’s brother).

The participants above, and others, used the word “El Ghorba” in Algerian Arabic to describe the situation, and its challenges, when a family member leaves the family to live alone whether living in another state or county in the same country or abroad. The depiction of stress in this study abroad experience as El Ghorba was mainly shared by members of families in this study. This is because it is the most common used word in the Algerian society to indicate to migratory contexts. This word was introduced into literature through the works of Abdelmalek Sayad “*El ghorba: From original sin to collective lie*” (2000) and “*The Suffering of the Immigrant*” (2004), which he used from his from his interviewees’ voice. El ghorba, which is Arabic for "exile," has two distinct meanings: one that is idealised and associated with the decision to be independence, or "travelling west," and another that is customary and linked to things like sunset, leaving, isolation, and being lost (Sayad, 2000;2004). This explanation of the term “El Ghorba” confirms its use by the participants to talk about the context of doctoral students leaving Algeria to a Western country, the UK, to pursue their postgraduate research, and the difficulties they encounter in the host society.

That being so, many family members stated that, for them, separation-related stress is mainly revolving around thinking about how alienation can affect students in the UK as this family member explained:

“El Ghorba (alienation), as we say, is a double-edged sword. It either educates you and you succeed and teaches you to take responsibility to be all alone in this world. No one stands by you and tells you what to exactly do in alienation. Either it overcomes you or you overcome it”
(Spencer’s sister).

Looking at alienation in study abroad contexts, the participant here hinted that living abroad away from family in a completely new society is a learning experience that could be of a two-sided impact on students. As for the first, the better adaptation students perform in the host environment, the more benefits they get from the experience, which can be on the academic and personal level. Examples of better adaptations to the host society can be found in taking responsibility, being more independent and developing self-confidence. This is confirmed by Dunkley (2009) who found out that self-confidence was a significant benefit of study abroad programmes students developed, in her qualitative postgraduate research project exploring the educational and cultural experiences of students studying abroad and focusing on

undergraduate students at an Australian university recently returned from studying on exchange at overseas universities.

Several participants affirmed that the longer the stay in the UK is, the more alienation feelings and homesickness are overcome, and the more separation stress is decreased, which is achieved with gradual adaptation through time. For instance, these family members, amongst other, described how their stress decreased about their associated alienated members studying in the UK:

“Now, I’m, like, less 30% worried right now. I used to be at 90% worried but now I am like less stressed. She is... she coped... she put herself in a comfortable zone that she is... surviving” (Emma’s sister).

And:

“We got used now to her being away. It was very stressful and difficult in the first year, but it gradually got less [...] We still miss her, but we gradually coped with that” (Clover’s mother).

The participants here reflected that families’ stress towards their students living away from them gradually diminished with time. This is conditional to students’ adaptation to the host culture, which Emma’s sister referred to as a “comfortable zone” to mean students’ ability to manage and adapt to the new culture, and progressively set up a new system of life on their own. This finding is in line with Lee, EunYoung and vWachholtz’s (2016) claim that new international students find it very difficult to adapt to the host community and university at the beginning of their study abroad journey, struggling with homesickness and fitting in with the society and the university. This also mirrors the findings of Rathakrishnan et al. (2021) who found out the worst performances for socio-cultural adaptation and a high risk of homesickness have been shown by international students in their first year, which is why they have greater levels of stress in comparison with students from other years. This explains families’ claim of gradual of stress decrease with students’ adaptation through time.

Students stress of separation and homesickness was reflected on their families in Algeria. That is, the less homesickness alienated students in the UK feel, the more reassurance their families have back home. Thus, it is worth to mention that although family members are still in Algeria, they always tried to explain alienation stress as a reflection to students’ stress on them. For instance, this student’s twin sister articulated:

“At first it was very stressful for her. She had a really hard six months. She didn't accept the fact that she's away from us. She did maybe get along with a new culture [...] but with time she gets used to it, but she still misses us [...] The first month was stressful for me [...] I was so depressed also” (Jane's sister).

In agreement with others, Jane's twin sister noted the difficulty of separation at the beginning of the experience. Jane's stress of the new environment, culture and system of life was mirrored in her twin sister. This participant might be the most impacted member of the family after Jane's departure due to the nature of twins' relationship.

This family members' view above was also confirmed by students, amongst them the following:

“You just get used to the absence of that person or your family and just get... the situation becomes... well your current state becomes familiar to you. That is the thing” (Steven).

And:

“It starts like healing over the time, but do not disappear. It still exists, but not as worse as it was in the beginning” (Spencer).

And:

“I struggled the very first days. Yeah, I will not like lie, but like, I am finding myself that I am gradually adapting with the situation, like, you stop, I started like, taking responsibility of myself. Like I do everything, my... all my stuff, whether it is personal life, or when it comes to education. Yeah. Yeah, it is a good experience, that, like teach you how to rely on yourself” (Anne).

Students, family members above and others agreed that the gradual adaptation to the host society over time and getting used to separation context are associated with less levels of separation stress, where the latter becomes more accepted by students and their families. This is confirmed by (Rathakrishnan et al., 2021) who found that international students' homesickness positively contributes to their stress, while their socio-cultural adaptation

negatively impacts the stress with specific reference to the role of better adaptation in decreasing stress.

6.2.1.2. Being perfectly responsible:

A remarkable point to mention that most of the participants agreed on, and implicitly hinted to in the previous section when elucidating their views of students' alienation, is that they linked their understandings of social stress in separation contexts to be fully responsible for all aspects of one's life. To illustrate, one female student voiced:

“What is stressful about being away from your family is, I can summarize it in only one word, which is responsibility. You become like a responsible adult, human, because you become in a state, wherever you are, you are obliged to do everything by yourself, which is not the case in your home, for example, paying the rent, paying for the energy, paying attention for your health, going to doctor by yourself, so everything that used to do by one of your family members, when you move overseas, you become obliged to do all these things by yourself” (Emily).

Emily's comment here shows that the stress of being away from family revolves principally around being responsible. That is, besides their role as students, studying abroad and living away from family urged students to change their social role from a dependent member who used to be cared for by other members of the family, chiefly parents in Algeria, to an independent individual who is supposed to take over several roles in the UK, as exemplified by the participant above. Most of students and family members also shared this view. For instance,

“Thinking about paying the bills; you are thinking about shopping, you are thinking about cleaning, cooking, scheduling your meetings, maybe planning for a trip or going to a place just to chill” (Lucy).

And:

“Here, the only responsible is you, you are the responsible for everything. You have to know how to manage your finances, you have to know how to be very responsible” (Catherine).

And:

“From living with the family to living alone, make shopping for herself, cooking for herself and doing everything for herself by herself” (Ashley’s brother).

These participants and others demonstrated taking responsibility of the social life aspects besides studying for the PhD is very challenging and stressful for students. This is because students find it difficult to balance between their academic life to achieve the aim for which they moved to the UK, and their social life to meet their daily life needs, accommodate with the host culture and enjoy their experience. This is similar to what Ghodbane (2020) found that making balance between academic and social life represented a significant challenge for Algerian students in his qualitative research that investigated the impact of studying abroad on the identities of Algerian PhD sojourners in the UK. Participants’ belief that responsibility is one of the major aspects that shapes students’ experiences of study abroad and stresses them is consistent with Tran and Vu (2017) who argued that international student’s responsibility and capacity to exert responsibility is becoming more crucial in the context of student mobility as these students must live and study outside of their sociocultural comfort zone.

The transition to the UK to take doctoral research presents a challenge and a great source of stress for both students and their families in Algeria. This is because of the new role attributed to students in the UK as independent individuals from their families. On this matter, a family member explained:

“It is also about responsibility. For example, you are taking the role of male and female. Sometimes, as girl, she needs to get out at night. So, sometimes you have to do things that other family members used to do in the house” (Spencer’s sister).

The participant here argued that students’ responsibility was expanded to include the roles assigned for males and females. That is, the different activities described by students above are mainly performed based on gender differences in Algeria. This is confirmed by Bouguesri and Nait-Brahim (2021) who acknowledged that in the Algerian collectivist society, social roles within the family are distributed on males and females, mainly parents where financial issues are controlled by the male (as outlined by students above paying for bills and shopping), and care activities are assigned for females such as cooking and cleaning as listed by students. This nature of families in Algeria, where family members were dependent on each

other make it hard for students to live on their own in the UK. In this regard, Lisa elaborated on this matter as follows:

“In Algeria, either the girl or the boy... they do not leave their parents’ house until they get married. Of course, they allow them to study, to work but still they live with them until they get married... yeah, it is like they are responsible for themselves but like a partial responsibility. I mean, like, for example... the simplest example would be like the father of the family who brings like food. He goes for shopping and stuff like that... and the mother is like the one who is responsible for cooking and taking care of the house” (Lisa).

This piece of data presented by Lisa explains the reason why most participants perceived stress in relation to separation as a responsibility challenge for students. To explain her view, Lisa used marriage as an example illustrating to what extent adult children are dependent to their families. This reflects Achoui’s who acknowledged that in Algeria, even married newlywed male and female adult children, although they are allowed to live separately, typically reside with or quite close to their parents especially with the housing problem in metropolitan cities (Achoui, 2006). The cultural environment where Algerian students and their families were raised and the fact that they were exposed to the same family system contributed to forming almost similar understandings of stress in the context of students in the UK, which revolved around taking responsibility.

More interestingly, it was thought-provoking how one female student commented on how dependent she was on her family in Algeria. She said:

“The first time I arrived, it was hard for me even to look for busses, because I didn't use to use transportation in the public transportation back home, and my father, you take me every day to the university and bring me up back again in the evening. So that was very challenging” (Nancy).

The personal account of Nancy here projects the conservative nature of Algerian families towards females which seemingly stood against them to act independently and be responsible when they travelled to the UK. Being raised in such a cultural context, a female would feel uneasy and overwhelmingly anxious to depend on herself in a foreign community, especially in the first experience. That is, females’ performance is significantly hampered by

these community restrictions (see section 8.6.). This is mainly due to the restrictions Islamic conservative societies like Algeria put with regards to gender roles and female's mobility (McIntosh and Islam, 2010; Ghodbane, 2020). For that reason, such community traits are critical factors in students' adaptation to the new environment and play an important role in shaping the participants' understandings of stress in study abroad contexts.

It is worth mentioning here that when explaining social stress as a responsibility issue, both students and family members targeted students in their views as the latter represented the ones in charge of taking new social roles and responsibility after their departure to the UK.

6.2.2. Study-related stress:

Another angle from which students and family members perceived social stress is study. Participants expressed a strong relationship between the social stress they feel during separation and the fact that students are living and taking PhD in the UK. Although study - related stress was most popular for students as the factor of study is directly related to them in the context of this study, several family members implicitly mentioned that taking a PhD in the UK does not stress Algerian students only, but it also stresses them back home in Algeria. However, only some family members clearly emphasised this point. In this respect a sister said:

“If she was just living there, I would be more comfortable. She is just living. She is not having something to think about. Now, she is doing a PhD. So, she has... she has many things to think about... many things to do... it is different” (Emma’s sister).

As shown in the extract, Emma's sister referred to taking a PhD as a stressing factor that increases families' stress about their adult children as alienated members. That is, taking doctoral research in the UK plays a crucial role in the stressful challenging nature of living in a completely new cultural environment. The participant then went on to elaborate on her view:

“If she was just living, it will be like normal, she is living her life. I will cope with that, but she is doing her PhD, I am always worried about her not finishing some work or not finding the time to read, I do not know, some books or to answer some questions. It is much more stressful for her with study” (Emma’s sister).

With a strong emphasis on her attitude, the participant here justified her view through listing some study-related aspects that her sister, Emma, might encounter in her PhD journey,

which according to her, are features that stresses the family as well. These study features are said to be stressors for students in the UK (see section 7.3.).

“I believe stress in this context is gradually shaped. First, Nancy left Algeria and departed to the UK. This is stressful, as she went to a foreign country where she is completely new to the environment. Then we have studying for the PhD, which adds more stress to her” (Nancy’s brother).

This claim presented by Emma’s sister and Nancy’s brother justifies why students’ families in Algeria perceived stress as a study-related although they are still in Algeria and are not involved in a study abroad atmosphere, which hence intensified their separation stress.

Similarly, many family members agreed that study-related stress increases alienation stress for students and this would increase family separation-related stress for families back home in Algeria as this family member reflected:

“Study is not that easy. Sometimes when my daughter tells me that she is struggling in her studies or in doing a certain task, I feel very stressed about her, and I start thinking of possible solutions and give her some suggestions maybe to ask her colleagues or her tutors. So, all our reflection goes to her about her life there, her study just because she is away and separated from us” (Josie’s mother).

Apart from being stressed with students’ studies, family members tended to give advice to students and support them willing to emotionally decrease their stress. Thus, family members pointed out that their concerns are always “out there” centred around their adult children in the UK.

Looking at study as one crucial facet of social stress in the context of this study, students argued that stress is an integral part of the study abroad journey. To illustrate, Lucy said:

“PhD is a journey... and all of us are like experiencing the same hardships, the same amount of work, the same thinking, the same stress, the same everything. So, it is something common to all PhD students. All of us are doing research” (Lucy).

Lucy's statement above gave a synopsis, from students' perspective, why this section was created. That is, taking doctoral research in general is a stressful task that confronts students with academic stress throughout the whole journey. According to Lucy, this type of stress is shared among all postgraduate students as it is much more related with their studies, rather than the context of separation. This is in agreement with Dixit (2020) who confirmed that academic stress is simply education related stress. This also quite matches with the scope of this section entitled study-related stress.

In the same regard, Clover expressed:

“If I'm going to talk about the academic side, I'm not going to stop talking from now till forever. I will not finish because I've been stressful. Yeah, I suffered with academic stress” (Clover).

And:

“My PhD has always caused me stress, to be honest” (Katy).

Several students, amongst them the participants above, reported academic stress as a major issue that encountered them throughout their doctoral journeys in the UK. The point students attempted to explain here denotes that academic stress is an integral part of conducting doctoral research. That is, it has not necessarily to be related with separation context. In this sense, it was confirmed that academic stress is a common feeling that experienced by domestic and international students (Alharbi and Smith, 2018).

Some students have directly expressed their understandings of study-related stress through listing some of the factors that consequently led them to feel stressed. Rose mentioned:

“It's the stress of not finishing this PhD, for years, and it's not finished. It's the stress of writing one section again, and again, and again. It's also the stress that I experienced whenever I send a chapter to my supervisors, and being anxious and nervous, just 10 minutes before meeting them” (Rose).

Similarly, Jane stated:

“Stress is obviously not being able to keep up with your studies, to feel overwhelmed, also to feel like you don't receive enough support from

your tutors or from the university, also the stress and the fear of failing in your studies” (Jane).

Two main points were highlighted in the students’ statements above. One is concerned with the feelings that students experience because of their studies such as, anxiety, nervousness, and fear, which explains the feeling of stress (Scott, 2014). The second is the reasons behind them feeling stressed like PhD completion, supervisory meetings. These point to the stressors students came across in their studies (see chapter 7). This is in consistency to what Alharbi and Smith (2018) found that great academic stress is experienced by international students because of factors like deadlines, work overload and failure in achieving goals.

A strong belief was common among participants, which helped in shaping their perceptions of study-related stress, was the difference between studying in Algeria and studying in the UK for doctoral research. For instance:

“Sometimes, I say studying in a British university is not like studying in a university in Algeria, and then I say, my daughter is diligent and hardworking student, and she can do it, and then I say no, despite this, taking a PhD in the UK is not that easy and I find myself so stressed about her (Clover’s mother).

The participant above referred to the notion of “study abroad” as a crucial element in forming her perception of stress and implicitly hinted to the difference between studying abroad and studying in one’s own home country to support her view, in which she stressed out how challenging taking a research degree abroad is for students and stressful for their families. This finding is somehow compatible with Adeoye-Agboola and Evans, (2015), noting that international students in the UK face several serious challenges, which lead to anxiety, amongst them: educational system, language, culture, weather, discrimination and environment; and failure to overcome these difficulties results in increasing international students’ level of stress and anxiety.

Considering the idea that studying in a completely new different context that differs from students’ home country, all Algerian students and family members agreed that taking doctoral research in Algeria would make a difference in their perceptions of study-related stress. The next section presents participants’ views regarding this issue.

6.2.2.1. Taking PhD in Algeria:

The interviews analysis revealed the participants' awareness of the difference between taking doctoral research in Algeria and in the UK, and how this contributed to forming their understandings of stress and stressors in the context of this study. Even participants showed similar views at first; for example, they all shared a belief that taking a postgraduate study in Algeria would mean less, if no, stress due to family separation. For many of them, students, when taking doctoral research in Algeria, would be concerned only with study-related stress as they do not necessarily need to move out of their family house to pursue their studies. Hence, shedding light on the difference between studying in one's country and abroad helped participants to in depth express their views of stress in relation to the context of this study, and this is why this section was created. To comment on this subject, several participants emphasised the absence of separation stress, if students were to take their PhD study in Algeria, for both students and their families; for instance, Lucy said:

“I was saying to my friend the other day. I was telling her... people are thinking that we are better than they are because we are here in the UK... but they are wrong... because they are better than we are... because they are with their family, and that is the point, if I were with my family, I would be more positive about what I am doing. I will be more... brave to... take risks doing different things... like... I will be more confident. I will be more energetic... in the sense that my family is in... like is on my back” (Lucy).

Lucy's comment displays that being within the family atmosphere provides students with supportive and positive vibes which would be reflected on their mental health to keep up with the PhD hurdles, yet this is not the case in the UK where the absence of family stresses students. That is, pursuing doctoral research in Algeria could be less challenging for students on the familial social level as it might not necessitate adaptability skills to cope with stress due to separation. This might explain why some students reported their need for their family physical support in the context of them studying in the UK (see section 8.5.).

Another participant reported:

“It would be less stressful, because I will study in the comfort of my own home. I will be surrounded by my family. So obviously, my mental health will improve, which gives me more energy and motivation to do

the PhD and... also, it's going to be less expensive because I won't be like completely financially independent, my family will take care of me. Both for your mental health and for the expenses as well” (Jane).

Jane above provided another interesting example of how students could be supported by their families if they were to study in Algeria. In addition to the emotional support students would get in Algeria, Jane reported financial support as one of the advantages students would enjoy in Algeria. This is because students would not be required to pay for their accommodation and living expenses in Algeria, and they would rather be living within their family house where the father or husband serves as the head of the household and is the primary responsible to provide for the family (Dwairy and Achoui, 2010).

Lisa had a similar viewpoint to Jane, yet she illustrated it in a slightly different way. She said:

“I would only like be doing my PhD. I am not away from my family. I am not responsible for myself. So, I won't, I wouldn't be like doing my grocery shopping alone, like cooking. So, this really takes time... takes a great time from your day. So, you are just there like to study” (Lisa).

Lisa above implicitly agreed that taking her doctoral research in Algeria would be less challenging and stressful. She justified her viewpoint by giving an example of some house activities that she is obliged to do in the UK, yet she would not do them if she were in Algeria. This is because, in Algeria, the father and the mother are the primary ones in charge of taking care of the house and the family members' needs. In Lisa's example, the father would buy groceries and the mother would cook for her. This example illustrated the roles of men and women in the family according to the typical Algerian culture (Ghodbane, 2020). Then, Lisa added:

“You are near to your family. You are inside the house... I would not be worrying about them because I am with them” (Lisa).

Lisa hinted here to a very important aspect that most participants used to distinguish between studying abroad and studying in one's home country. She emphasised that taking postgraduate research in Algeria would allow students to be physically present with their families, and hence would prevent their separation stress. This could be the reason why some

participants perceived separation as a physical absence in the context of this study (see section 8.2.).

Discussing how participants referred to taking PhD in Algeria to explain their perceptions of stress, Emily viewed:

“Overall, pursuing PhD or any degree of study is hard but these details which are being with family or away from family evaluate the degree of the hardship you may face during this experience of the PhD. So, in both cases, the PhD is hard but being away from your family, of course, this is an extra hardship” (Emily).

Emily believes that not only taking postgraduate research abroad is stressful but also claims that pursuing a research degree is challenging aside from where to take it. That is, students would find it very challenging to study for the PhD whether in Algeria or in the UK. However, being separated from one's family is the feature that would make the difference between the two and makes the cuff swings to one side. Emily implicitly expressed that taking a PhD as an international student is much more difficult than it would be if she was in Algeria. Other students also said:

“If I'm doing it in Algeria, I would have been going through different situations of stress... let's say a doctorate degree is related also to social life, for example, if I am with my family doing PhD in Algeria, and one of my family members is sick, or I will feel also the same thing. But what makes it different is that I am not with them, that's it. But when it comes to PhD, I'm pretty sure that there is stress, but the situations differ” (Rose).

And:

“So, if I'm doing my PhD in Algeria, I would be living with my family. So, I wouldn't be that much stressful when it comes to my family's well-being... but I don't think that the level of stress would be any different when it comes to studies... because doing a PhD is a challenge, whether it's here in Algeria or in the UK, which I think, it would be like more stressful if I'm doing it in Algeria... because there are no resources and no place where like... libraries, like we have here in the UK” (Steven).

The participants' reflections above are consistent with those of others who believe that pursuing doctoral research in Algeria would be less socially stressful due to the fact of students being together with their families. That is, the main concern for students in Algeria would be their research and academic context, where the stress they face would be only study-related stress. The fact that taking doctoral research in Algeria does not involve separation-related stress, unlike taking PhD abroad, which affects students' mental health goes in line with the premise of social stress theory that deals with social inequality and mental health disparities (Mossakowski, 2014). Additionally, like in Steven's assumption; by conducting postgraduate research in Algeria, he could encounter more challenges due to the limited academic context and lack of resources that could help students in pursuing their PhD study. However, as indicated by Rose, the stress about family would not disappear when students are in Algeria, yet it would decrease.

Another important feature reported in data in relation to studying in Algeria for a doctoral research degree is when students take the degree in a different state than their hometown. For instance, Emma said that:

“I will be close to my family like I know if anything happened I can drive to my home and I can see them whenever I want and I know I will be there for them because it is easy to reach them or to see them in an instant whereas here is like the distance is so far like from your own family ... you cannot help them and they cannot help you” (Emma).

Taking a PhD in Algeria would make it easy for students to reach out to their family house. Emma explained that it is possible for students to drive home whenever needed without having to plan a long journey like that from the UK to Algeria. Not only that, she also implicitly emphasised the opposite where her family can join, help, and support her in Algeria through indicating their inability while she is in the UK.

Commenting on the possibility of family visits to students if they were to take their doctoral research in Algeria, Jane's sister and Emma's sister talked about how they would feel in such a case. In that regard, Jane's sister said:

“It would be really better here because she would be closer, and it would be easier to go to... We will be less worried but, you know, she is closer, when we are too much worried about her, we just visit her.

So, I think it is going to be much easier [...] We will I think we will visit her I will visit her constantly” (Jane’s sister).

Emma’s sister added:

“I will be less stressful because she is here. I may not be able to help her while she is there ... but here at least I can type for her sometimes or help her reading... reading some stuff. I would be less worried about her if she was doing her PhD in here” (Emma’s sister).

The participants above used the pronoun “here” to refer to studying in Algeria while they used the pronoun “there” to refer to studying in the UK or studying abroad in general. The difference between the two cases that participants implied above would be the physical and emotional closeness of families to students which could decrease the level of separation they both would feel towards each other and could retain students’ sense of belonging to their home country. This is consistent with Yahirun and Arenas (2018) who examined how parents are emotionally and psychologically affected by their offspring migration to the United States and within Mexico and found out that the outcomes for parents of children who immigrated to the US are poorer than those for parents of children who moved from their family but stay at home country.

Studying abroad could be seen as a challenging experience for students and would impact their families who remain at home. This is because, students’ inability to cope with life in the host country could adversely affect them, which could be reflected on their families. However, most participants indicated that this would not be the case when students get to study at home. For instance, Nancy’s brother and Ashley’s brother were family members, among others, who expressed how better they would feel if their sisters were still studying in Algeria:

“If Nancy was taking her PhD in a different wilaya (state) in Algeria, everything would be different. You can visit her whenever you want. There would be no challenges that hinder us from visiting her. [...] Also, she is still in her country. One would not be concerned about adaptation and adjustment like in study abroad contexts. She would not be that stressful because of being away from her family because she can join us whenever she wants” (Nancy’s brother).

And:

“We would be more reassured if she was taking her PhD in Algeria, in another state in Algeria” (Ashley’s brother).

The statements above support other participants’ view in the predisposition of family visits to students in Algeria. The reassurance that the brothers spoke about is as a matter of course in the context of studying for a PhD in a different state in Algeria. What they brought up here is that adjustment is neither a basic need nor a challenge for students in such an Algerian context of study. As students would stay within their country, this should not require them to learn about the host community forms of capital and all that is required to properly function in the society such as system of education, culture, language and way of life and transportation.

Under this section I attempted to show a common attitude that the participants appeared to have and used to explain their beliefs regarding what stress in relation to studying for PhD is for them in the context of this study. It appears that taking a postgraduate study in Algeria allows students to enjoy several features that cannot be enjoyed by students in a challenging environment abroad such as the UK in this study.

6.3. Chapter summary:

This chapter discussed findings in relation to the perceptions of social stress in the context of Algerian PhD students in the UK whose families remain at home. The findings showed how participants explained social stress with special reference to the experience of being separated from family for the sake of studying for doctoral research in the UK. In doing so, participants shed light on the difference between taking PhD in Algeria and in the UK. Participants’ attitudes of social stress in relation to separation were mostly affected by their socio-cultural background as members of the collectivist Algerian society.

Chapter Seven: Social stressors impacting students in the UK and their families in Algeria during separation.

7.1. Introduction:

As previously mentioned, the main overarching research question of this study sought to understand the social stresses that affect Algerian students and their left-behind families during the period of conducting PhD study in the UK. In this chapter, I aim to present and discuss findings that revolve around social stressors affecting students and families during separation, which addresses the second aim of the study.

When asking participants how they perceive social stress (see chapter 6), they often tended to refer to what they have experienced in this context of separation, which they considered as stressors, mainly separation itself and studying for the PhD. Thereof, it has been asserted that separation is a stressor that threatens attachment bond between individuals that stimulate individuals' behaviours to maintain this attachment bond (Pietromonaco, Uchino and Dunkel Schetter, 2013). Participants described their fears and confusions that made them live in tension. In many instances, their stressors were centred around health issues, safety, missing family events, failing in studies and COVID pandemic. Thus, participants' responses were principally related to three main issues, which I classified them as three major categories: separation-related stressors, study-related stressors and COVID pandemic.

7.2. Separation-related stressors:

As noted earlier, Algerian PhD students in the UK and their families in Algeria, pointed out to the idea that separation represents a great portion of the social stress they both experience in the context of separation. Participants cited several reasons why they felt stress because of separation. These reasons are referred to as stressors that triggered their feelings of separation. I examined what participants listed as stressors in relation to the separation of students and families and classified them as separation-related stressors, which I present and discuss in this section. Almost all participants, students, and family members, referred to the same stressors in relation to separation.

7.2.1. Losing a family member:

Most participants from both cases, Algerian PhD students and their families in Algeria, interviewed in this study, acknowledged that the most stressful and frightening thing affecting them is their fear of losing a family member of theirs while students are taking their PhD in the

UK. That is, losing a family member was most prevalent and popular amongst participants' answers as one of the most impactful separation-related stressors. A clear example would be that of Jack when he commented:

“The thing that I am scared about most is waking up to a call saying that someone has passed away from my family members [...] especially during the lockdown because you're hearing, or we were seeing different posts on Facebook saying that people have been passing away due to COVID. So, I was always expecting that I would, one day, I would wake up to a post like that” (Jack).

As displayed in the extract above, Jack referred to his great fear of losing a family member of him and chiefly during the COVID pandemic, which decreased his fear for his family and transformed this fear to a stressful expectation that he was considering.

In addition to Jack, Nancy, who spent more than two years of separation from her family in the UK because of the COVID pandemic, when asked about what she fears and stresses her the most, she voiced:

“What a person could fear more than death or illness, or you know, something that is quite serious” (Nancy).

Here, Nancy emphasised that the most fear and stressor in relation to separation that stresses Algerian PhD students is the fear of losing a person from their families and experiencing a death case while being away from them. She also pointed out to illness as an impactful stressor for her about her family.

On the other hand, several students talked about experiences of death cases with their families and people they know back home while they are in the UK. For instance, a male participant, Steven, reflected:

“I think about my family, and I get stressed, especially when they went for instance not long ago, my friend told me about this... A neighbour, which we have back at home, died. This person was so nice to me, and I wish to see him like once more but honestly, I did not have the chance to see him. Also, like a couple of months ago, my cousin also died because of medical error. So, seeing all the death, like roaming around my family is very stressful” (Steven).

This data excerpt shows Steven's fear of death of family members in Algeria while he is in the UK. This frightening idea gradually continued to stress Steven especially after the death of his cousin and his neighbour and he could not see them.

Clover talked about losing her father as the most stressful experience she passed through during her PhD journey in the UK as follows:

“But when it comes like to the family side... when I talk to my family, like sometimes my father is okay, sometimes he is not. But you know, it depends on his physical health situation. But recently, one week before he says he really could not I mean, it was like the end, his health situation was getting worse day after day. That week, it was so difficult for me. All I do is just like speak to my sister. How is he? I'm just like, crying. That's what I've been doing. I booked my flight that week to go to Algeria, but I could not get there because he passed away before my flight day” (Clover).

Here, in this data extract Clover communicated that the death of her father was the most stressful and difficult experience she passed through while she is in the UK. The fact that Clover kept constantly contacting her family to check on her father and booked her flight back home denotes how keen she was to see her father before his death and how frightened and fearful for him. Crying also denotes that this greatly affected her mental health and her psychology.

At another point of the interview, Clover added:

“My fear always goes to my father. What if something happened? because he was sick. So yeah, what stresses me before when my father was alive, it was my father basically. Now, Now, it is my mother yeah, my mother. So those are the dearest closest people ever to my heart. One of them passed away. My mother is still alive” (Clover).

Here, Clover distinctly shows that the thing she fears for the most is her parents and their health. This indicates that Clover's stress and fear for her mother makes her sensitive to this issue and does not want to risk her mother while she is in the UK and not with her family especially after the experience of her father's death.

Similar to Clover's experience, in what follows, Emily stated about the experience of her uncle's death while she is in the UK:

“Last January, I lost my uncle. So, at that moment, I felt like I really need their support... (Emily is crying) ... It is just like a sensitive question for me. It is fine. I just like giving you a concrete example when... I think this is one of the impacts of being an international student because you become like more sensitive than before. So, this random example when I felt like I really need them” (Emily).

And then she articulated what stresses her about her family the most as follows:

“Of course, losing them or if something happened to them? So, this is what stressed me a lot” (Emily).

In this data extract, Emily noted that being an international student is very challenging and makes students sensitive to difficult situations and lacking their families' support. She illustrated this with a personal experience of hers, her uncle's death, that stressed and affected her emotionally. The fact that Emily cried beyond her control during the interview when she was talking about her uncle interprets how impactful this kind of experiences is on her. It was a very emotional moment in the process of my data collection that I took the following fieldnotes:

When talking about her deceased uncle, she cried until she could not talk. I asked her whether she preferred to stop and reschedule the interview. She said she is fine and that we can carry on with the interview. It was a very sad and emotional moment. (Emily's interview, fieldnotes).

Conversely, Gill demonstrated a different experience regarding losing a family member of hers while she is in the UK, and she articulated:

“Because last year, during the COVID-19 before I went back to Algeria. My youngest uncle has died. I mean, who passed away at very, I mean, he was very young, he was 29 years old, and we didn't know the cause. So, I mean, my family did not tell me, and I just did not know. Yeah, I was in the UK, and I saw a post on Facebook saying Yacine has died and everything and I'm like, who is your Yacine, who has died? I called my mom and she ... and I can see from her face and she's like,

*we don't want you to feel... how to say hmmm scared and frightened
(used Arabic word makhlou3a) We don't want to frighten you” (Gill).*

These data lines show that Gill has not been informed of her uncle’s death by her family. She came across a post on social media where she read the news. She was astonished and did not believe what she read at first. After checking the news with her family, her mother illustrated hiding the news by their fear she gets affected when she knows about her uncle’s death. This indicates family’s fear for Gill’s mental health from bad news that frighten and stress her while she is alone, and they cannot support her during such a bad situation.

On the other hand, Gill was not understanding towards her family’s perception in this experience as she stated:

“I felt I'm not one of them. I'm not a family member. If I do not deserve to know what happened. I mean, it is my uncle is the closest uncle to me and he died and with no reason and it was a very, it was all very mysterious up there and messy and you don't tell me... I felt very upset. I did not talk to them for two days, something I have never done. But then... even during those days, I was feeling left. I mean, let down by my own family. But at the same time, I was... I was hoping that one of them calls me and say we apologize in that and make me feel the sense of belonging again” (Gill).

Gill expressed her feelings of anger from her family by stopping her contact with them. The effect of this experience on Gill’s mental health made her feel excluded by her family and prevented her from understanding and perceiving her family’s view of doing this. This implies to how impactful these situations are on Algerian students. Although not every international student would necessarily get affected by separation and such situations of losing family members, Algerian students are likely liable to get affected by both. This finding is consistent with what Sadoudi (2021) found that missing family and losing members of family while being abroad are of great impact on Algerian students in Britain.

Although some family members implicitly mentioned their fear of losing a member of their family while students are in the UK, only few family members emphasised this in their responses. For instance:

“Of course, there are many fears and stresses that stresses us about Nancy for example, we can lose a member of our family, and she is not here with us” (Nancy’s brother).

Here, Nancy’s brother clearly reflected that being separated from his sister because of her taking a PhD in the UK is a stressful experience and involves many fears, amongst losing a family member of theirs during Nancy’s absence.

Similarly, according to Spencer’s sister:

“The thing we fear the most is something bad happens in the family or losing someone in the family and Spencer is away” (Spencer’s sister).

Spencer’s sister here put emphasis on fearing bad events and losing a family member as the most stressor affecting families in the context of being separated from their students taking PhD in the UK.

Likewise, when asked about the thing that frightens them and stresses them the most while Jane is in the UK, Jane’s sister answered:

“I think being sick, or you know, Losing the people that we love members of the family” (Jane’s sister).

In addition to losing a member from the family, Jane’s sister, here, also demonstrated sickness as a stressor in the context of family separation.

7.2.2. Health issues:

Second to presenting the fear of losing a family member as a separation-related stressor, the fear of health issues was also cited as a stressor by participants. Different Algerian PhD students and members of their families pointed out to their stress about each other of being sick and experiencing health problems as a primary concern in this context of separation. From a student perspective, when asked what stresses her about her family, Spencer replied:

“Let’s say about their state in general, but within like, as I told you within like the current situation, you will always be wondering or concerned more about their health or they are affected by the COVID if anything goes wrong, you know” (Spencer).

And added:

“I feel many insecurities about being away from home and from my family. Like, if you ever feel sick and you are away from them or if any member of the family feels sick or unhealthy. This makes you feel like... you have plenty of worries, plenty of concerns. Of course, this will affect your stability, you are going to be uncomfortable” (Spencer).

Here, the participant initiated her talk by admitting that family separation involves many stresses that she describes as insecurities.

In the data extracts above, the participant acknowledged her stress and concern about her family’s situation in Algeria while she is away from them. She also indicated that whether health problems are experienced by herself or by her family members, this would still stress, worry and affect her. She also pointed out to the COVID pandemic as a stressful factor that increased her stress about her family.

Likewise, Lisa reported:

“Three months ago, my father was sick. Yeah, he almost got the hospital... but he refused to go to the hospital though. Although he was like, sick. So, this stressed me very much. It had a bad effect. I think... I was kind of sad, depressed, all the time, anxious... I get the feeling that if something happens and I am not there. I will not like be able to see him. It makes me anxious and stressed” (Lisa).

These lines of data clearly explain how stressful family health issues were on Lisa which led her to depression, anxiety and the fear of losing her father. This denotes the relationship between health issues and losing a family member as impactful stressors for students.

Some participants mentioned how stressful it is when their families hide their health issues for them. For example:

“The thing is, my mom is very sick and I, let's say, when I wake up in the morning, I wake up with... with a notch in my heart, that say... okay, you have to talk to your mom. You have to make sure she is fine” (Gill).

And added:

“In terms of her health, she doesn't tell me anything. Even if she is sick, she tries to hide it, which adds to my stress” (Gill).

Here, Gill shed light on the point that family's health issues cause a psychological pain which urges students to check on their families. Also, the fact that families hide their health problems and sickness from students stresses them even more.

Jane mentioned the same point in the following:

“My father got sick this year. So, I felt very stressed, and you know, very sad that I couldn't be with him when he was sick and I didn't even know that he was sick, because they were afraid that I'm going to be sad and stressed. So, they had hidden bad facts from me, which made me more upset, because if I was there in Algeria, I would have been there for him... and last year, my mother got sick as well... and it was the same thing, I couldn't be there with her. So, it always causes me to worry about them, not being able to be there for them or see them when they are not well, or a problem happens with them” (Jane).

Here, Jane expressed the stress she felt when her parents were sick, and she has not been informed of that by her sister. However, she also realized that the reason behind not informing her is just because they fear for her which explains the perspective of families in this context of separation.

Another type of health issues experiences that reported by students is when students experience health problems in the UK away from their families. Two female participants talked about their experiences of having a surgery in the UK with no family support. For instance, Katy spoke about her mother's stress when she had a surgery, and she said:

“One of their stressors is if I fall ill or sick or something like that... and they can't be there with me because my mother really hated it that she wasn't able to come and be with me when I was in the hospital, and I had my surgery and everything. So, how I know that it is very much a stressor of hers is that the other day she sent me a parcel and even though she told me like what she sent me in it, one of the things that I found extra in the parcel was medication, because I told her that I was having some leg pains” (Katy).

Here, Katy indicated the stress of her family especially her mother because of not being with her and supporting her when she had a leg surgery. In spite of this, Katy's mother emotionally supported her and did her best from home and sent her daughter some medications to use.

Carol also reported a similar experience of having a surgery in the UK away from her family. Carol first started to express her stress for her family back home as follows:

“I think about the health of my parents, and I think about, you know, how we always hear bad news about car accidents in Algeria happening all the time. So that can be a source of worry and stress” (Carol).

Here, Carol gave an example of how news of traffic accidents in Algeria increases her stress for her family's health.

After acknowledging her fear for her parents and family's health, Carol expressed that this was the reason behind not telling her family about her surgery and health problems at the beginning. She stated:

“I went through surgery, an appendicitis operation. It wasn't good. It wasn't happy” (Carol).

And added:

“By the way, I didn't tell my family that I was in the hospital, and I did not tell them that I was having surgery, because I have been told you might have surgery and I had nothing confirmed, and I did not want to worry my mom and my family, I only texted my Algerian friend and told her. Then, it has been confirmed and I was asked to sign the consent form. I did not even have time to read it carefully. Everything went so fast. Just before entering the surgery room, I called my mom, and I told her. My mom and dad were so stressed and frightened about me. They kept asking me why and why. I told them my story of having severe pain for a long period and I spend days going back and forth to the GP. It was so scary. It was the first time I had surgery, and my biggest fear was that I will not wake up that is why I told my mom in the last moment. My family deserves to know that I am passing through this. We cannot

know what will happen. My parents spent the whole afternoon just waiting for me “(Carol).

And:

“Yeah, it is the most stressful and challenging situation I have come across here” (Carol).

Carol narrated above how stressful her surgery experience was for her and her family, and she denoted that it was the most stressful experience she passed through in the UK. Despite of her need to her family support, Carol preferred not to tell her family because of her fear for them at the beginning. However, the stressful thought and fear that took over Carol urged her to inform her family eventually. This refers to the emotional support she was seeking to have from her family in this hardship.

This finding of providing emotional support to students is in agreement with what has been claimed that “these mobile and transient groups of students have significant issues to contend with, especially in relation to the emotional support that is required, to live and study in another country successfully, especially when they have left their families at home” (Harvey, Robinson, and Welch, 2018, p.749).

Among the family members interviewed, some members talked about their stress of health issues when their students experience health problems in the UK or when family members pass through some sickness situations. For instance, one brother said:

“When someone from the family gets sick or my grandmother or any member of the family, Ashley gets very stressed and keep checking on them” (Ashley’s brother).

Here, Ashley’s brother clearly demonstrated that health issues that Ashley’s family came across while Ashley is in the UK does not only stress and affect them, but it also stresses Ashley.

In contrast, Nancy's brother mentioned how Nancy is affected by the illnesses of her family members and how her illness impacts them:

“There are a lot of stressors that we fear for Nancy. We do not know what can happen to her there while she is all alone. For example, she

can get sick, and no one is there to support and stand by her” (Nancy’s brother).

And added:

“And, if one of the family members here is sick. For instance, my father is sick. I cannot call her and tell her that, because that would stress her and affect her, and she starts to think scary thoughts out of her stress and fear for us” (Nancy’s brother).

Nancy’s brother, in these extracts, explained that the stress of health issues is mutual between the student and their family members. In this regard, it has been confirmed that both international students and their families worry about developing health problems when students are abroad (Qadeer *et al.*, 2021). The participant also indicated to Nancy’s need of social and emotional support when passing through such situations of health problems. Moreover, Nancy’s brother mentioned a very important point that students’ stress of their families’ sickness makes them exaggerate in their fear for them.

On the other hand, Clover’s mother narrated a slightly small experience regarding Clover’s experience of getting sick:

“Clover called me the other day and she said she feels so dizzy, and she has a pain. I felt so confused. I wished I could fly to help her (laughing). I told her to make some herbal teas then I checked on the internet for some tips. I asked her to try to sleep but I kept calling her every 5 mints checking on her. Separation is so hard especially with sickness and health problems. I wanted to help her, to be there to take care of her but I felt helpless and incapable just talking with her and supporting her behind the phone screen” (Clover’s mother).

Here, Clover’s mother showed how helpless and stressed she felt when she saw her daughter sick on the phone. She demonstrated that she was only able to emotionally support Clover and gave her advice at time when Clover needed her mother and family to be with her. The mother also emphasised that health problems and experiencing sickness while abroad makes separation even harder.

Relatively, Spencer’s sister mentioned a similar point:

“Who consoles her if she gets sick, there is no one with her. So, just the fear for her to get sick is a stressor” (Spenser’s sister).

This segment of data agrees with Clover’s mother and Nancy’s brother claim that students in the UK are in need of social and family support when they experience sickness.

Conversely, one family member talked about a case where her daughter hid her sickness from her as follows:

“For example, it happened once, and she hid her sickness from me. She knows I get stressed of these things. So, she told her sisters that she had severe pain that led her to vomit, and she went to the hospital. I did not know that. If she was here, I would take care of her. I would not be that scared but because she is there. She is away from me I cannot endure. It so stressful” (Josie’s mother).

This data extract shows that health issues students pass through in the UK stresses their family members in Algeria. As previous family members expressed, Josie’s mother also agrees that students in the UK need emotional and social support from their family in situations of health problems.

This finding that health issues affect Algerian students and stresses them is pretty similar to Akram, Kamran and Ahmad’s (2020) study that aimed at examining the challenges Pakistani international students encounter in China, and the data generated from in-depth interviews revealed that psychological problems like loneliness and anxiety and physical health problems and sickness were reported by students among the main challenges they came across.

7.2.3. Racism and discrimination:

Findings also show that discrimination and racism represent one of the social stressors that affect Algerian students in the UK and their families in Algeria. Some respondents from the case of family members expressed their fear for their students to get discriminated and encountered with racist incidents in the UK. On the other hand, some students in the UK reported some racist experiences that came across in the UK, which had an impact on them.

Two female participants (Lisa and Katy) reported the same case of discrimination, which they experienced together when they first came to the UK and were studying for the pre-session course (Guerriche, 2020). Lisa first started her talk about discrimination as follows:

“Since I am like, veiled, so I thought there might be like a degree of racism... because, you know, we have this notion of Islamophobia all over the Western culture... like, whenever they see Muslim people, some people would react badly with the stares, like talking bad words to them like, go back to your country. What are you doing here?” (Lisa).

Here, Lisa clearly introduced that religion is one of the reasons why Algerian students are get discriminated, especially veiled female students as their physical appearance reflects their religion as being Muslims. That is, veiled females who wear the hijab are more likely to recognized as Muslims and thus more susceptible to be discriminated.

Then, Lisa narrated the incident:

“We went, with my friends to London, and one from the bus... We were talking and laughing and then there was a woman, she kept staring at us, in a very weird and scary way and after a moment, she came to us, she was like, what are you doing here? You go back to country... and I remember a girl was filming for taking pictures of the street from the bus and she was like, are you taking pictures of me? Stop doing that? And she even talked to the driver telling him that they are scaring me. And can you call the police? It was scary. Because it was our first time in there and we were really scared. I was sitting in my chair, trying to avoid the lady and, and she almost, she almost like hit my friend. She was like, my friend like was, she was ignoring and laughing and kept... she kept talking and she came to her... and she told her and I'm quoting her, Shut up. Shut up. Stop talking. Stop laughing. We were really like in a bad situation” (Lisa).

Katy, reported the same experience and added:

“I am not veiled but I was with a group of girls who were veiled... and I remember one of the things that stuck with me from what she said was like, how damn Muslims are. [...] That is one of the reasons why I do not like London. Yeah, it is because I experienced it” (Katy).

The incident that Lisa and Katy went through made them feel stressed, anxious and confirmed their perception of Islamophobic discrimination against Muslims. Although Katy is

not veiled, the fact that her friends, Lisa, and others, were wearing the hijab was a reason for getting discriminated by people of the host culture and prejudices. Encountering racist incidents from people in the host country had a profound psychological impact on Katy and formed a negative perception about London in her.

Other female students also expressed that they passed through incidents where they got discriminated based on their religion and hijab (headscarf). For example, Jane stated:

“I also expected that I am going to deal with a lot of racism, which happened a couple of times” (Jane).

And:

“So, because I was wearing the scarf, I had some incidents of racism. I also was very self-conscious about what I wore. So, that was one of the hardest things to deal with as well. The one that I can remember of racism towards Muslims. There is one time when a woman shouted at me. She is like, no, no, she thought that I was a terrorist or... So, the thing is, I went to shopping and it was one of my first days in Glasgow, so I did not know where to go and I used to live very far from the city centre. So, I remember I was going to ask them to buy something. I approached her to ask her in very friendly way. I asked her about the road where to go. I was asking for a specific road where I live so I can go home because I was lost. She was so terrified, and I understood from what she was saying, You're like, no... She like felt threatened because I was wearing the scarf. She thought that I'm a terrorist or something like that. So, that terrified me and embarrassed me at the same time... and I remember I was sad about it for a week” (Jane).

In these lines, Jane noted that encountering racist behaviours from people of the host country was one of the expectations she had before coming to the UK and starting her PhD journey. Jane talked about the discriminatory incident she experienced when she asked for help during the first days of her experience in Glasgow. Jane felt she was treated in a discriminatory way because of her religious identity as a veiled Muslim girl and the primary reason for her to be discriminated was her veil. Jane voiced that this racist act from people of the host culture had a deep effect on her psychology.

Having views alike regarding the hijab as stimulus for Algerian female students to be discriminated, Spencer talked about her personal experience with a racist incident as follows:

“I just worried if I have ever been in a situation of racism, maybe it's the only idea I have, if I go to a foreign country, non-Arabic non-Muslim country, this is, like, the concern I have. To be in a situation of racism or been facing some people will turn races. I didn't have like, other questions at that time” (Spencer).

Like other students, Spencer also expressed that racism was one of her expectations before departing to the UK, and then she added:

“I was not involved. But I faced some, some situation where I felt that is kind of discrimination and racism, sometimes if you are in any, for example, administration, bank, let's say, supermarkets in public transportation, you can feel like the way they deal with you, there is a kind of discrimination, they would never do it to a native, like in their way of speaking in the tone of speaking. And, like, you will feel it. Okay. Racism. So, the first day is, when I was in London, when I first came here for the induction. I used to do like full veil. Like, the looks, the way people around you look is very uncomfortable. And if ever lost, or you're not sure how to transport, you want someone to ask, they don't. I am not generalizing, but there are some people who do not welcome a question from a veiled woman” (Spencer).

The experience Spencer went through of having weird gazes from people of the host country made her feel unwelcomed in the host society. She also expressed that discrimination can be sensed in the way British nationals deal with Muslim veiled women. Likewise, Spencer mentioned that some people of the host community do not accept to give help for veiled women. This slightly resembles Jane's experience of getting discriminated when asking for help because of wearing the hijab.

Lucy also expressed her experience of discrimination because of her hijab. Lucy, when talking about the social anxieties and stresses that she was expecting before her departure to the UK, mentioned:

“The first thing, which is about being veiled and being Muslim. I have been in situations where I was treated depending on my religious belonging” (Lucy).

And she started to narrate the incident as follows:

“I was in this in the supermarket. I was doing groceries... and when I was done, I just left the supermarket... and I came across with a family of, if I can remember three ladies and two teenager, female teenagers and they were shouting at me, and it was 7pm and I was very scared because I was alone and I was living in an area which is kind of isolated from the city centre... and they were shouting, and saying, Oh, poor, look at her... look at how she looks like slaves of the shop... slaves of the shop... and she was shouting this sentence to me... and I was like, very terrible to hear such a sentence (...) but just at that moment, I can't like to react. I could not do anything, and I just hurried back home... and I was very upset but once I arrived, I started crying and I told this to my flatmates. So, it was very painful” (Lucy).

The incident Lucy passed through led her to feel stressed and anxious. Lucy also felt marginalized and rejected in the host society when she has been described as a slave. Lucy was convinced that she should not have been described this way, and believed she was treated harshly. Despite Lucy's self-esteem to herself, this kind of verbal abuse and racist act deeply affected her mental health and made her feel in danger which led her to run home crying. She also confirmed her preconceived idea regarding discrimination against Islam and the hijab.

For Lucy, Muslim veiled female students are vulnerable to such discriminatory acts more than Muslim male students as she stated, referring to the case if it was her brother who is taking his PhD in the UK:

“Maybe it is going to be a little bit different because he is a guy. And he can be able to protect himself better than a daughter... because, like talking about the previous point of being veiled and Muslim, he can't like... as a man... he can't be identified as being a Muslim man or guy because the way he looks like says nothing about his belonging and ethnicity, and that is why he is going to be less exposed to maybe discriminatory comments, racism, or whatever” (Lucy).

Here, Lucy gave her personal belief that the Islamic religious identity of Muslim male students would not provoke discrimination against them as it is not featured on their physical appearance. This is quite similar to Mir and Sarroub's (2019) claim that "hijab-wearing women and other visibly Muslim students are at particular risk of being targets of bigotry, prejudice, and racialized sexism" (p.10).

Conversely, Steven emphasized:

"I would hate to encounter racial incidents where you are being alienated or you are being called off, because of where you come from, or because of the colour of your skin. That is not nice. imagine the situation when, or where someone, like a British person or guy comes to me and say, hey, go back to your country... it is always on the tip of my tongue. I say like, hey, UK is good, but it is not... It is not great, is not like paradise, and I am going to my home country anyways. So, no need to tell me that. So, yeah, racial abuse is not the best thing that could happen to anyone" (Steven).

Steven explained that racial abuse against migrant groups has a bad impact on migrants and can be for several reasons amongst them the skin colour. He also pointed out that he had been through a discriminatory incident where he was asked to leave the UK by a British national. Steven also stated that he is planning to go back home to Algeria after finishing his PhD. This part of data resembles the findings reported in Brown's (2009) ethnographic study which examined the adjustment experiences of a group of postgraduate international students at a university in the South of England, where Muslim students declared some racist acts that they have been through and different people from the host society asked a Jordanian student to go home, assaulted a Turkish student, refused to serve a student from Bangladesh, and the Islamic prayer room at the university was disfigured; students then came to a conclusion that the tension between Islam and the West was the reason why they were harassed.

Unlike others, it was also very interesting how Emily talked about discrimination from an academic point of view. She first stated:

"Sometimes the term internationalization is used for, like, discriminative purposes. Well, sometimes your institution says that, for example, when hearing international students, Chinese international

students. So, it is kind of discrimination. I think categorizing them maybe, yes” (Emily).

And explained:

“Sometimes it's that way, but sometimes you feel like it is discriminative somehow. Let me explain this for you. For example, sometimes when we want to enrol or... we found these terms like, European and non-European, have you noticed it before? It remains my opinion, but I think it is a kind of discrimination because I think that all international students share the same experience, which is studying abroad or studying overseas. There are many common things between us, either Algerian or Chinese or European, which is, for example, we are studying in the country where the language is different. The culture is different. The social norms are different. So, I think it is common among all international students. Do you get me?” (Emily).

Emily indicated that the categorization of international students based on the geographical area they come from is a discrimination that undervalues a group of students coming from a given country over other minority groups of students that constitute the wide community of international students in the UK. She illustrated her opinion with the classification of students in the enrolment process. This is consistent with what Saeed (2019) who asserted that Muslim international students can also experience discrimination from administrators and administrations. This is also compatible with the premise of social stress theory that explains the status of Algerian students in the UK as disadvantaged/ discriminated social group that lacks the host country's forms of capital (Aneshensel, Rutter and Lachenbruch, 1991).

Emily also talked about a racist behaviour she witnessed from a teacher as follows:

“When I was in the pre-sessional course, one of the teachers, without mentioning names, one of the teachers said to us that you are African PhD student. Do not assume that you know everything. I can remember this expression. He said it that way. You are just African PhD students. As if he said to us, do not assume that you know everything or you know more than we do. So, that is why I consider the term internationalization as a discriminative word. It is not an ethnic discrimination. It is intellectual discrimination” (Emily).

Emily reflected a discriminatory case in which she was involved that centred on getting offended by a teacher, along with her Algerian colleagues, when she was studying for the pre-session course prior to starting her PhD course. The racist behaviour in this case arose from underestimating and undervaluing the group of Algerian students and making them inferior to the British. Although the group of Algerian students taking PhD in the UK is regarded as the elite students in Algeria when they got the Algerian scholarship (Guerriche, 2020), the British teacher made them inferior to the British academics and described them as Africans. Although it is in a different setting, this finding of getting discriminated by an academic slightly matches with what has been reported that one out of five Muslim students experience discriminatory behaviour by members of school staff in California (Mir and Sarroub, 2019, p.10).

Carol expressed that she feels uncomfortable in the host society when she struggles to prove herself:

“I would say that I fight a lot, because I try to prove many points to many people. And the reason why I try to prove many points to many people, because I feel that some people around here are very judgmental, racist, and not as friendly as others would say. So, I find myself having to fight for every single thing that I want” (Carol).

Contrary to others, two student participants indicated that they have never come across a racist behaviour or act during their PhD journey in the UK. In this context, Jack said:

“Well, one of the things that actually I was expecting to go through but personally I have never experienced this is racism. Especially when I was telling people that I will be going to Scotland that they were like, are... people there are racist towards Muslim people or Muslim community but when I came here, I knew that there was a negative stereotype that was not true” (Jack).

Even though discrimination was amongst Jack’s expectation before coming to the UK, he plainly demonstrated that he never been through a racist act throughout his PhD journey despite the prejudice that the Scottish community is discriminatory against Muslims. This is somehow consistent with what Bonino (2019) claimed the existence of discrimination against Muslims in Scotland, although it is distinct in both extent and nature. This also goes in accordance with Lucy’s claim that Muslim males are less exposed to get discriminated as their religious background cannot be figured out from their physical appearance.

Similarly, Rose stated:

“Here, you can see that there are people from different backgrounds. So, luckily, we are in Britain, or let's say in UK, I mean, at least me I have never experienced racism or even if it is shown in the way I dress that I am a Muslim, I have never experienced racism, in contrast, I have always been thanked. Or let's say, I have heard different compliments on the way I dress. And so... this is just an example that makes me feel that UK or where I live is a very welcoming society or environment in a way that you don't feel that you are foreigner, you are someone that is not accepted into the society. So, to put it in other words, if, for example, I have experienced people looking at me, or pointing at me, and people saying something to me, for sure, I'm going to feel that I'm not that, I don't belong to this environment, or I'm not white from this environment. What I experienced was totally different. That's why I don't feel as a foreigner in here” (Rose).

Rose argued that the UK is a non-racist country that hosts several ethnic minorities from different backgrounds. However, she demonstrated that facing racist and discriminatory behaviours increases the feelings of alienation and foreignness in students. She also mentioned that she has never been through discriminatory act although her religious background is noticeable from her physical appearance. That is, being Muslim veiled girl and wearing hijab does not necessarily imply getting discriminated, but it can give rise to discrimination against veiled women as reflected by other female students. This is because hijab presents a distinctive indicator of Muslimness that may put women under stigmatised group because of Islamophobia (Bonino, 2019).

The collected data distinctly demonstrated different perspectives of students and their families regarding discrimination of students in the UK. As for family members, few participants tackled the point regarding the possibility of students getting discriminated and encountering racist behaviours. For example:

“Because she is there. I am worried about some racist people... about her being Muslim in non-Muslim country. At least if she is in a Muslim country, I would... I would be comfortable that if... even if they are not Arab, but at least they are Muslim, they share some kind of... they share

something. However, to be in non-Muslim non-Arab country is much difficult. I am worried all the time about her having incidents, some racist people or some people who hate Muslims or something like that” (Emma’s sister).

Here, Emma’s sister clearly noted racism as an impactful stressor that stresses her about her sister. She elucidated that taking a PhD in a Muslim country that shares the same religious background (Islam) as theirs would have made her less stressed about her sister. That is, taking a PhD in a Muslim country would decrease families’ fear and stress for their students’ safety as students will, at least, have something shared with people of the host country, which will help them to adapt to the host environment. This reflects an awareness from the part of families of the difficulty of adapting to new environment of the host society.

Similarly, Clover’s mother stated:

“I am always stressed about her, and I am always frightened she faces some racist people and experience discriminatory acts. This is what I fear the most” (Clover’s mother).

Clover’s mother here affirmed that the fear for her daughter from encountering racist people and discriminators is one of the most impactful stressors that affect her. In the same way, Josie’s mother asserted:

“Honestly, I am always stressed and frightened about her. I follow the news and updates on internet, whenever I read about an attack against Muslims, I get more stressed especially with the notion of Islamophobia” (Josie’s mother).

Josie’s mother explained that the fear for her daughter’s safety from getting discriminated is an ongoing stress. The latter urged her to follow the news and updates of the UK and Europe regarding the state of Islam and Muslims. She pointed that Islamophobia presented a severe stressor for her as it represents a contemporary form of discrimination that is the most significant issue that Muslims face abroad (Allen, 2019).

Two family members expressed an opposite perspective and mentioned that they did not expect their sisters as Muslim veiled girls studying in the UK to face discriminatory acts from British people. What appeared as reassuring to Nancy’s brother and Ashley’s brother was

the influx of international students from different cultural backgrounds to the UK. Ashley's brother expressed:

“There are many Muslim people and veiled women in the UK. It has been two years and 6 months since Ashley got the scholarship and went to the UK. She has never told us about a racist act she has been through. She keeps to our religion Islam and respects theirs, and they respect our religion” (Ashley's brother).

Ashley's brother, here, implicitly indicated that Islam and the hijab (the headscarf veiled women wear to cover their heads and hair) is accepted in the British society where all religions are respected. In like manner, Nancy's brother voiced:

“UK is a developed country with a lot of foreigners. I think people there respect the existence of different religions. That is, you can practise whatever religion you want” (Nancy's brother).

And:

“UK is a law-abiding country. Everyone minds his own business. You can live the way you want and practise the religion you want” (Nancy's brother).

Nancy's brother did not feel that being a Muslim would be a real reason for discrimination and getting rejected by the society in a law-abiding country like the UK, which became a multicultural and multifait society with internationalization where all religions are accepted and respected.

As far as the females' perspective of the sister and the two mothers prementioned above regarding discrimination against Algerian students in the UK is considered, from a male perspective of family members, Nancy's brother and Ashley's brother felt that the UK is a good study destination for Muslim students in general and veiled female students in particular as they can practise their religious beliefs freely without the fear of getting discrimination.

7.3. Study-related stressors:

As mentioned earlier (chapter 6), participants indicated that taking a PhD in the UK plays a crucial role in the social stress students in the UK and their families in Algeria, experience in the context of separation. Accordingly, when speaking about stress in relation to

study, participants tended to refer to some points that they consider as study-related stressors. The latter is discussed in this section from the perspectives of both: students and their families.

7.3.1. Students' perspective:

7.3.1.1. Meeting deadlines:

Meeting deadlines was most common in participants' talk about study-related stressors as PhD students consider it one of the highly stressful aspects of studying for a PhD. Several students indicated their stress because of struggling with deadlines in their PhD studies. Anne, a PhD student who was preparing for her upgrade (transfer event) mentioned her stress of deadlines at different points of the interview as follows:

“We have deadlines and stuff, and sometimes you do not, like, meet the deadlines, and then you feel stressed, and time is passing [...] You become more stressed with when the deadline is approaching. You have deadlines, missing deadlines... and deadlines are broken. So, you are always stressed. [...] I did not expect that we will work according to deadlines and stuff like this because it really disturbs you when you have, like, deadlines and you need to meet them” (Anne).

This extract of data distinctly shows how working through deadlines and having to meet them affected Anne and stressed her. The fact that Anne kept repeatedly mentioning meeting deadlines demonstrates how stressful deadlines are in the academic life of PhD students.

Rose, who was about to submit her final thesis, demonstrated the stressfulness of deadlines in PhD students' academic life as follows:

“Let's suppose that you've got a deadline, or your supervisor tells you that you need to submit something in 10 days, this is very stressful” (Rose).

Two PhD students linked deadline as a study-related stressor with the skill of time management. The latter is also considered as a study-related stressor by students. For instance, when asked about the most challenging and stressful aspect of study Lucy, a student who was at the beginning of her fourth year of PhD when she was interviewed stated:

“Time. Yeah, it is time management, because I... like I tried and I'm still trying very hard to master the skill of managing my time and

meeting the deadlines... and doing the work that I have within the given amount of time... but I... almost every time I fail to do this. So, time management is the first thing that I found challenging and stressful, because I can't control this” (Lucy).

Lucy clearly noted that struggling to manage time in her studies and to meet her deadlines imposes a great stress on her throughout her PhD journey.

Likewise, Emma is another student who highlighted time management as a study-related stressor affecting her mental health:

“It is maybe to have like a balance between like your PhD and just calling your family to check up on them is like how you're going to balance... but only that your stress about your studies and to finish and... like to meet deadlines and to submit... like to succeed in our studies, which is like that the main thing, that ...the main reason that you're here, but as well as like you need to be... like in contact with your family, just to check up on them and to reduce like that homesickness... which is like that was the hardest like doubled stress” (Emma).

Emma confirmed that the main stressor for her as well is to manage her time and make balance between the time she devotes to her studies and the time she gives to her family. She plainly communicated her commitments to meet deadlines, submissions and to succeed in her studies as her priority in her study abroad journey emphasising that taking her PhD is the core reason from her journey. Emma also acknowledged her need to contact her family and spend time with them to make her mental health in a better state and to reduce her feelings of homesickness. This also proves homesickness as a separation-related stressor (discussed in the previous section). This is finding in agreement with the claim that “at the doctoral level, many students attempt to balance social and familial responsibilities with their academic work, thus requiring difficult decision-making regarding priorities and resource allocation” (Sverdlik, Hall, McAlpine, and Hubbard, 2018, p.371). That is, making balance between the academic life and the social life is one of the challenges that encounter PhD students.

Also, it was very interesting how Steven described his situation with deadlines especially for a male who is living alone:

“At some point when I am not... when I am not being chased by deadlines. I enjoy cooking but whenever there is, but when there is no time for cooking, I just do not do it. I just either eat outside or make something quick like sandwiches” (Steven).

Steven demonstrated how he devoted his time in pursuance of meeting his submissions deadlines to the point that he excluded cooking for himself from his list of priorities. This indicates how important role deadlines play in the academic life of a PhD student and how committed students should be towards their deadlines.

On the other hand, Gill made a connection between the stress of having to meet deadlines and having to make decisions alone about her PhD research when she said:

“Stress is always there... and when you say PhD, you would stress because you have deadlines. You have presentations to deliver. You have got decisions again to make because when you talk to your supervisor, he says it is your own PhD. you have to take that decision, and I say would you advise me to do... do it qualitative research or quantitative research, and he says, it is your PhD, please decide ...” (Gill).

Gill explained study-related stress as a crucial and inevitable part of doing a PhD and she referred to having to meet deadlines or preparing for a presentation as stressors. Gill also demonstrated that making decision about her PhD by herself acts as a stressor for her as she expected to have more guidance from her supervisor. This is mainly due to her past education in Algeria where the system was mainly dependent on teacher-centred learning process (Berrezoug, 2021). With this, Gill also introduced a very important aspect of taking a PhD in the UK which is the different system of education between the UK and Algeria.

7.3.1.2. PhD completion and securing a job:

Second to meeting deadlines, most of the students implicitly expressed their stress and fear of not completing their PhD theses on the agreed time with the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education, which is four years. However, only few respondents distinctly acknowledged that. For instance, Rose highlighted:

“After all those four years, like, maybe you didn't manage to cope with that stress, maybe all I think the most... stress is not finishing my PhD,

is not submitting a thesis. So, when I submitted, I will... I feel very, very good about it” (Rose).

Correspondingly, Spencer explicitly described stress in the context of Algerian students taking a PhD in the UK as follows:

“It is the stress of two sides like, two-sided stress, from study like worrying and stressing about your study about your progress about your degree about time because we are sponsored students, and we are very limited by time constraint, like self-funded, one wouldn't care about the time when she can finish her PhD within six, seven years, or he can opt even for part time PhD. but, So, as international sponsored students, I found it like, facing three major stresses. One being away from your family. One about your academic progress, your knowledge, your thesis, your progress, and another measure stress about time that I need to do and cope with all these within specific time limits” (Spencer).

As seen in the participant's statement above, Spencer, here, summed up the fundamental stressors Algerian PhD students encounter throughout their journey, which are family separation and studying a PhD. She also shed light on time limitations for the PhD completion as a very important stressor for Algerian students as being sponsored for a given period by the Algerian government. That is, the possibility of having administrative issues in the future with their sponsor, the Algerian government, due to not completing their PhD theses on time represents a critical study-related stressor for students.

In the same way, Lucy referred to her stress regarding the scholarship and PhD time limitation for completion as follows:

“Every time I think about the time and the things that I have to do, I feel so shaking and I start sometimes trembling and... and I feel very stressful, because I feel that if I don't finish on time, I'll be... my offer will be declined... maybe I'll be blamed... maybe the government will end up my contract. So, all these thoughts come to my mind every time when thinking about time” (Lucy).

Lucy implied here that if she was not able to finish her PhD study within the agreed timeframe with the Algerian government, the latter would rescind her contract and she would not have a job position as defined by the scholarship contract. As enacted in the scholarship contract with Algerian government, students will be granted job positions as university lecturer once they get their PhD diploma and go back to Algeria (Bursary Sponsorship Contract, 2015).

Similarly, Steven also mentioned the point of securing a job after finishing the PhD and stated:

“You just do this Research, then you finish, then you come back in full time, university teacher position” (Steven).

This finding regarding the fear of losing the granted job position by the Algerian government quite matches with Bazrafkan, Shokrpour, Yousefi and Yamani’s (2016) finding that the fear of unemployment after graduation was amongst the socioeconomic problems that cause stress and anxiety to PhD students. Their qualitative study used semi-structured interviews and field observations to examine the causes for stress and anxiety during thesis writing and the different coping strategies PhD students of Medical Sciences use to manage stress and anxiety at Iranian Universities (Bazrafkan, Shokrpour, Yousefi and Yamani, 2016).

7.3.1.3. Lack of Data:

One participant, Jack, shed light on a very important stressor in relation to doing PhD research which is the lack of data. When talking about study-related stress, Jack kept mentioning the lack of data as one of the most stressful aspects of taking a PhD he came across throughout his journey. Jack said:

“I started doing my PhD. I faced a lot of obstacles, like most of PhD students, so but one of the most like, most difficult things that I went through is lack of data and lack of recent statistics when it comes to the status of mental health system in Algeria” (Jack).

Jack indicated that doing a PhD is stressful for all students. However, he asserted that the most stressful and difficult study-related stressor he came across, according to his experience in taking a PhD in the UK, is lack of data and academic research in the field of study he is researching, which is mental health in Algeria. This is due to the nature of his PhD research, mental health, which is not well-researched in Algeria due to the lack of academic research in Algeria.

Like others, Jack also demonstrated the fact that taking a PhD in the UK embraces the stress of being away from one's family and environment in addition to PhD stress:

“Doing a PhD in general is stressful. So, if we add to that being away from your family, from your friends, yeah, that will add more pressure but personally speaking, the stress is not about being away from my family but because of the lack of data in my research” (Jack).

And:

“In relation to my experience, I would say lack of data is the first reason why I get frustrated. The second, the second thing that frustrates me most is, is that my work revolves around the ID, which stands for dissociative identity disorder and this mental illness, in particular, is debatable in the Western society” (Jack).

In Jack's case, the thing that stresses him the most is lacking data in his research due to the difficulties in accessing it in Algeria as he mentioned earlier. His study-related stress also originates from the difficult and debatable nature of his research topic.

7.3.1.4. Supervision-related issues:

The analysis of the conducted interviews showed that participants are aware of the significance of good supervision and supervisors in taking PhD research. In this respect, it has been stated that “a key factor of the success of a research project is the relationship between the supervisor and researcher during the training stage” (Orellana, Darder, Pérez, and Salinas, 2016, p.88). Participants reported supervision-related issues as another stressor in relation to study that affected them. Participants' talk about supervision mainly revolved around establishing a good relationship between PhD students and their supervisors and getting support from them. Emma stated:

“When I met, like the director of PGR studies, I didn't know how to speak with him, how to handle his questions... because like, the status of lecturers is so different in Algeria, and here. So, that was so stressful to meet my supervisors. And I don't know, like how our relationship... like, I will deal with the supervisors for four years or five years, I didn't know how to manage or how to establish my relationship with them. So that was very stressful” (Emma).

Emma talked about the period when she first joined the university in the UK and started her PhD course. She referred to her stress in meeting the university staff and her supervisor for the first time. She was concerned about how her relationship with her supervisor should be and how she can maintain it throughout the period of her PhD. She also pointed out to the difference between the student-lecturer relationship in Algeria and the UK. This is because, in Algeria, this kind of academic relationships often tends to be very formal. This finding of Emma's confusion regarding the student-supervisor relationship at the beginning of her PhD agrees with what Elliot and Kobayashi (2019, p.911) said that "pursuing a PhD in a 'foreign' context inevitably brings forth distinct opportunities and challenges for students and their supervisors".

Gill, on the other hand, talked about her situation with her supervisor at different points of the interview as follows:

"Let me tell you that my supervisor is British and by telling you, he is British, I would say that he is... how to say, he's very strategic, he doesn't talk much. When he says something, he means it. But me, coming from a North African background and coming from an Algerian university, I always need reassurance. I always need to talk a lot... and at the very beginning, I struggled a lot with him... but then... when I understood the way he is, and that when he says something, he means it, I got over my... let's say confusions, and just followed what he said, and we are good now" (Gill).

Here, Gill mentioned that she found difficulties to deal with her supervisor at the beginning of her PhD journey due to the different educational background and environment. This goes hand in hand with what has been claimed that "several international students noted a sense of being caught between two worlds once they began studying at the UK university" (Robinson-Pant, 2009, p.420).

Gill also expressed:

"At first when I came here, it was too hard for me to accept that I am away from my family and I tried to go back many times to Algeria, but my supervisor was not cooperative and he was like if you're doing PhD here, you have to stay here and work here. So, I struggled with that. I had a lot of problems with him" (Gill).

Gill reflected that she got affected by family separation and stressed by the feeling of homesickness at the beginning of her PhD journey in the UK. However, she did not find the support from her supervisor to go back and visit her family in Algeria. Gill described her supervisor as uncooperative and mentioned that she struggled with him. This finding denotes that Gill sought support, empathy and cooperation from her supervisor when she experienced homesickness. This is referred to as personal help in Haksever and Manisali's (2000) proposed framework for supervision requirements evaluation from the perspective of PhD students. The framework suggests that supervision is divided into three components: personal help which involves providing support, motivation, help in accommodation issues and other issues that require help and are not related to research; indirect research-related help which covers providing contacts and initial help in references; and direct research-related help involves the critical analysis of the work and providing help in terms of methodology, direction and management of the project (Haksever and Manisali,2000).

Gill:

“I saw that my... some of my friends from other cohorts went out and had coffee with their supervisors but my supervisor doesn't do that”
(Gill).

What Gill brought up here is that supervision can also involve informal meetings between supervisors and their supervisees, PhD students, over coffee outside of the PhD world and research atmosphere which can help in establishing a good and friendly supervisor-student relationship. She also pointed out that she had never had such an informal meeting with her supervisor, but it appears from her voice tone that she would love to, if she had a chance. This finding goes hand in hand with Hemer's (2012, p.832) finding that “supervision over coffee provided a different sense of time and space from the more formal and sometimes intimidating space of offices”, when she researched postgraduate supervision over coffee using semi-structured interviews with supervisors and students.

Another participant, Jane, voiced:

“You might not find the support that you're looking for from the university or your supervisors” (Jane).

And added:

“They count, like 90% on the students to do their research on their own. They give very little support. Also, the supervisors... what I expected... I expected them to provide resources to give more guidance. They also do not do that” (Jane).

Jane expressed that she did not receive support from her supervisor as she expected. She expected to have more guidance and support in her research from her supervisor. That is, taking the full responsibility of conducting the PhD research represented a stressor for Jane. This is due to her educational background in Algeria, where learning processes were based on teacher-centred rather than student-centred education (this also emphasizes Gill’s perception in the previous section).

On the contrary, Carol talked about her stressful experience with her supervisors. She stated:

“I had academic stress in the first few months, especially when my supervisor, the first one in October, and she said by last October that she was leaving in February. So, it was a shock for me. Because I felt like I was lied to, I was betrayed, I was deceived... So, there was a stress, and then having to find a new supervisor. So that was October to February that I had a new supervisor in February, and then someone else joined” (Carol).

Here, Carol explained that she started to have supervision related issues ever since the beginning of her PhD course when she was surprised and shocked by her supervisor leave. However, when talking about her new supervisor, Carol stated:

“My supervisor is a good person, so not the first person. My new supervisor... she's trying to do her best now by supporting me” (Carol).

And added:

“She was very supportive when I got a surgery, I got a “get well soon message” from her. So that was nice” (Carol).

Carol demonstrated the support of her supervisor when she needed it, which she appreciated. At another point, Carol mentioned:

“I know stories of people whose supervisor is a bullying them. They bully them” (Carol).

Here, Carol showed that there are other students who do not receive support from their supervisors and struggle in dealing with them. This denotes that student-supervisor relationship is different from one student to another and from one supervisor to another. That is, their relationship mainly depends on their characters as individuals. This finding matches with Haksever and Manisali’s (2000, p.27) claim that “as problems between students and supervisors are generally highly individualized. The student/supervisor relationship depends significantly on the personalities involved”.

7.3.1.5. The weather:

When respondents from the case of PhD students were asked about the main stressors affecting them, few of them mentioned weather as a stressful aspect of their journey in taking a PhD in the UK and in Scotland in particular. These students demonstrated that weather played a role in their stress and had an impact on their mental health, which affected their studies. For example, Jack, who is taking his PhD in a Scottish university said:

“When I started my PhD in the UWS first, like I was safe to say that I was really depressed during the first six months, especially because of the weather in Glasgow” (Jack).

And added:

“When it comes to my mental health, yeah, PhD has affected my mental health on different levels. First of all, doing a PhD in Scotland in the UK in general, comes with pros and cons. One of the cons is... the weather is not really helpful for us especially as Algerians... who are really used to the sun and during my first and even my second year, I was diagnosed with vitamin D deficiency which was also one of the reasons why I was depressed most of the time” (Jack).

Jack listed the weather as a stressor that had an impact on his journey in Scotland especially at the beginning of his PhD course. He also noted that it affected him mentally and physically. As for his physical health, it caused him a deficiency in vitamin D. The latter led him to depression as Vitamin D deficiency is, biologically speaking, considered to one of the causal symptoms for depression, which affected his mental health, and it obviously affected

his studies. In addition, Jack communicated that Algerian students are used to a warmer and more convenient weather back home than that of the UK.

Another participant, Lisa mentioned the Scottish weather as a stressful aspect of her PhD journey along these lines:

“When I came to Scotland last year, it was like when we started our actual PhD journey. So, in Scotland here I could not really adapt at the beginning especially because of the weather, because we came in the wintertime and the weather was always like gloomy and we had like, a pre-sessional program to study. It was like intensive, and it was really stressful and then it lasted like for three months... and after like it ended I couldn't really stand to stay here anymore minutes... because I really missed my home. I don't know what happened to me? I was not like able to sleep well. I was not able to eat well. I was kind of depressed. I do not know. So, I had to go back home as soon as I could. Yeah... and when I went back home, it is like the first minute I put my foot on the grounds of Algeria when the plane like arrived. I was like, happy. It was like all those feelings that I had... all vanished” (Lisa).

Lisa shared her experience and explained her stress during the first months when she first joined her university in Scotland and started her PhD course. According to Lisa, the Scottish weather and the intensive program of study were stressful for her and triggered her feelings of homesickness and depression. These stresses affected Lisa's mental health and her inability to adapt to the new environment urged her to go back home to her family. In these few lines, Lisa referred to different and interrelated stressors in which one leads to the other and that affect students in the UK, which are homesickness, depression, weather and study.

Likewise, Katy mentioned weather several times as follows:

“Yeah, I do not like the weather very much” (Katy).

And:

“Yeah, it definitely affects your psyche, especially if you are the type of person that does not like cold weather and that does not like gloomy shades of grey and stuff like that. Even though I do love that, like fall is my favourite season and I do love this type of weather where it's like a

bit rainy but to have it all year long is kind of like hammers down on your psyche” (Katy).

Katy highlighted that the Scottish weather is seen as a stressor for Algerian students that they struggled to cope with especially at the beginning of their journey. Even though Katy loves autumn and rainy days and partially got used to the Scottish weather, but she found having this weather in Scotland almost all year-round depressing. She also confirmed the impact of it on her mental health.

Alternatively, Emily insisted that gloomy weather had a great negative impact on her study and productivity as she stated:

“Because the mood and the atmosphere in the house is not first study. So, it's a big problem” (Emily).

And:

“No, it's not supportive for study. Especially when it's raining, and the weather is gloomy, and the dreadful. I feel like I only want to sleep” (Emily).

This finding is in line with Adisa, Baderin, Gbadamosi, and Mordi's (2019) study finding that the British weather posed a great challenge to international students and sometimes caused them sickness and hindered them from attending classes. Their study mainly aimed to investigate the issues and challenges that confront international students in the UK. The data generated from conducting semi-structured interviews revealed that international students process of adjustment is impacted by language and communication difficulties, difficulties in adjusting to the British educational system, culture, food and weather (Adisa, Baderin, Gbadamosi, and Mordi, 2019).

7.3.2. Families' perspective:

From families' responses, it was clear that families experienced stress because of their students' study struggles and challenges. That is, Algerian PhD students' stress of study reflected on their families' stress when students share their study stress with them. For example, one family member stated:

“Study is not that easy, it is difficult. Sometimes she says: “mum, I am struggling with my submission. I have a deadline to meet”. I spent that

night on my nerves thinking of her, wishing someone could help her”
(Clover’s mother).

And added:

“As for study, we are not stressful about her that much, but when she complains about her study and feels so stressful, we get stressful as well. We keep thinking of her... and her father used to give her advice so that she asks other colleagues and lecturers of hers of any possible help” *(Clover’s mother).*

Clover’s mother, along with her husband -Clover’s deceased father- expresses their concern and how they get stressed about Clover while she is stressed with submissions and struggling to meet her deadlines. This denotes that Clover seeks to get emotional support from her family through sharing her stresses with them to relieve her stress. This also denotes that despite of their unawareness of the nature of academic research and doing a PhD, Clover’s family checks on her. Clover’s mother, also, pointed out that they wish they could help her to decrease her stress but regrettably they could not. The only thing they could do on their level is giving her advice. The latter is regarded as a family emotional and social support for Clover.

At a different point of the interview, Clover’s mother added:

“Well, when she gives assignments to her supervisors or when they tell her to repeat her work again and she fails. We fear that she studies hard, but she fails and could not get to the level their supervisors need”
(Clover’s mother).

Clover’s mother brought up that the fear of submissions and getting negative feedback from supervisors does not stress Clover only, but it also stresses her family back home. She also expressed their fear of Clover’s failure in upgrades when she does not meet her supervisors’ expectations despite her hard work and diligence.

Correspondingly, Jane’s sister shared a similar concern regarding deadlines and supervisor’s feedback. She first stated:

“Well, she's, I think sometimes she doesn't say she needs help PhD. And she her ideas don't get along with the ideas of her supervisor. I think yes, I think I think we both didn't expect that her supervisor will maybe

stress her out on the work, on the research. I think she's a little bit stressed on that. And I get stressed. And I didn't expect that” (Jane’s sister).

Here, Jane’s sister shed light on the point that Jane struggled to meet her supervisor’s expectation which stressed her. This stress reflected on her family and stressed them. Jane’s sister also mentioned that both. Jane and her family did not expect that Jane will experience supervision issues.

Like what Clover’s mother expressed earlier, Jane’s sister also stressed-out deadlines as a study-related stressor that affected students and reflected on their families as follows:

“When she gives her, when she gave her deadlines, you know, not enough time to complete that homework. You know, this is something that we both didn't expect. And we are stressed about” (Jane’s sister).

In this data excerpt, the participant showed that submission deadlines of the PhD research do stress the student Jane and her family as well.

Another family member expressed the following:

“Like one of the things that I was thinking and that stressed me was losing her documents, her passport, or her study documents and her work. Because Nancy is a bit hasty especially when she is stressed. She gets hasty and acts in a great haste” (Nancy’s brother).

And added:

“When she gets stressed, she starts to rash things and lose her focus” (Nancy’s brother).

Nancy’s brother voiced his stress and fear towards the possibility of her sister losing her travel documents and study-related documents and assignments. He illustrated his stress by his sister’s, Nancy, habit of haste when she feels stressed as he mentioned that Nancy loses her focus and concentration while stressed and might act unconsciously without paying attention to what she is doing, and this could result in her regretting herself later.

On the other hand, Spencer’s sister stated:

“There are a lot of issues that stress me about Spencer, amongst them her dereliction in her studies, her work would not be enough for her success” (Spencer’s sister).

Spencer’s sister here expressed her feelings of fear and stress about her sister not being able to work in her PhD as required to meet her supervisor and university requirements. She mentioned that Spencer’s dereliction is what stresses her about Spencer’s study. Spencer’s sister also pointed out to the fact that several stressors are affecting her about her sister. For instance, she noted:

“When she was doing her pre-session course. She did not have time. She had to study to secure a PhD placement which stressed her a lot, and it stressed us as well” (Spencer’s sister).

The participant showed that study-related stress that affected Spencer reflected also on her family and stressed them. She emphasised that securing a PhD placement was a crucial stressor that affected Algerian students and their families at the beginning of their study abroad journey. This is because securing a PhD placement would grant student the offer to take the PhD in the UK after finishing the pre-session course.

7.4. The COVID-19 pandemic:

The COVID pandemic has greatly and adversely affected people worldwide and international students were included (Nguyen and Balakrishnan, 2020). On December 2019, the first case diagnosed with COVID-19 was detected in the Chinese city Wuhan (Kumar, Doshi, Khan, and Rathore, 2020). It presented a crucial health disaster to the world in a short period after it has first been discovered. This is because the COVID-19 virus was fast spreading, threatening lives and augmenting death toll in many countries over the world. The COVID-19 major symptoms include coughing and having fever and fatigue; its spread mechanisms, however, can take three main ways: direct close contact with infected people through droplets when coughing, sneezing or talking, touching face especially mouth, nose or eyes after touching surfaces on which droplets might be, and inhaling aerosol from the air mixed with infected people’s droplets (Sun, Wang, Li, Li, Zhang, Zhang, Jin, and Feng, 2020).

To stop the virus’ spread, governments worldwide, including the UK, urgently executed a set of confinement procedures. That is, the lockdown was imposed sooner or later by nearly all countries. This imposed shutdown included closing the national and international borders

(Kumar, Doshi, Khan, and Rathore, 2020). Like many countries, “to combat the spread of COVID-19, the UK Government implemented a range of “lockdown” measures” (Sharman *et al.*, 2021, p.1). The lockdown measures in the UK were released by the end of March 2020 until the end of June (Higham, Ramírez, Green, and Morse, 2020).

International student’ mental health has been highly affected by the COVID-19 outbreak (Chen, Li, Wu, and Tong, 2020). Nearly all research respondents in both case studies came to an agreement that COVID pandemic was one of the main stressors during the experience of family separation for both students in the UK and their families in Algeria. When speaking about COVID-19 pandemic, most of respondents leaned towards the facts associated with this pandemic: borders closure, anxiety and fear for each other from getting COVID and the fact that students got stuck in the UK with the stoppage of international flights and lockdown. Algerian PhD students expressed that COVID-19 pandemic was one of the major stressors for them. For instance, when talking about what affected his mental health Jack said:

“The weather, lack of data, COVID, lockdown...” (Jack).

Similarly, Spencer indicated:

“I can see like the COVID had like a great impact...” (Spencer).

Furthermore, students’ family members, agreed that COVID-19 pandemic was an unexpected situation that made the separation experience even harder. For instance, Josie’s mother stated:

“As I have mentioned before, with COVID pandemic, things have changed. For example, if there was no COVID, my daughter Josie would have come back every 6 months or once per year... or we would have visited her maybe” (Josie’s mother).

Likewise, Nancy’s brother mentioned how unexpected and impactful the COVID pandemic was in the context of separation:

“One thing that affected me and I have never expected was the COVID pandemic, because we have never expected there will be a pandemic one day, the borders will close, and if... I do not know... a family member among us gets COVID and dies -Allah forbid- and there is no...

So, we have not had this fear and way of thinking, but we found ourselves in this situation and thinking this way” (Nancy’s brother).

At this point, Nancy’s brother expressed the fear and stress of family for their daughter Nancy during the COVID period if something bad happens to them and she is not there with the family, how she would endure this while she is in the UK. This illustrates how the Algerian family is interconnected and related to each other and how they got affected by this separation due to Nancy’s study abroad experience. The extract also represents COVID pandemic as a stressor that affected families back home and made the separation experience more difficult for them.

One family member has explained how difficult the COVID period was on both students in the UK and their families in Algeria:

“COVID period, it was really, it was, I suffered from anxiety like worrying about... especially because the UK had really severe... It has really severe cases. And the new COVID, the new COVID was in the UK. So, we were really worried about her, but she was much worrying about my parents. She keeps calling me telling me don't get out. If you get out, do not kiss my parents stay out of them. Do not let people come to you. And you're like given her advice how to not get out but she's... she's really cautious” (Emma’s sister).

Emma’s sister clarified the mutual fears and stress of Emma and her family members on each other, caring about each other’s health, giving advice and precautions to each other on how to protect themselves from getting COVID- 19.

Lucy, has clearly and deeply explained how the COVID pandemic represents a critical stressor that affected her while she is studying for her PhD in the UK away from her family in Algeria as follows:

“The other thing is being detached from your family, and especially during COVID. So, I wasn't able to find a flight ticket back home. So, I was very stressed because I was thinking about my family... about the health of my parents... about me, like maybe they might be affected, maybe something bad will happen to them due to this virus. So... and I was very... I was very scared that something bad happens to them and

I'm far away from them. Yeah. So, I started like... I abandoned my studies, like for two or three months, I did nothing. I did not... and I could not focus, and I even could not do the... the upgrade. So, I felt that it's better to delay it, or to reschedule it because I couldn't write anything and all... all I was thinking is about being able to join... to join my family... to join the place I used to live in and just... and that's all for me. So, the first source of stress was that being socially detached, being socially... it's like, sometimes you feel, especially when the borders are closed, you feel that you were exiled... but in... like, socially exiled because you have the right to go but you can't go, you know what I mean” (Lucy).

Lucy talked about family detachment and how she got affected by being separated from her family especially during the COVID period when she got stuck in the UK as she described and had to stay in the UK despite of her attempt to go back home due to the travel disruption and borders closure. Lucy's stress and anxiety about her family's health and her panic of bad things to happen with her family affected her psychologically and made her ruminating. Lucy's rumination about COVID-19 and her constant thinking and fear about her family hindered her from progressing in her studies. In this respect, rumination has been defined as a “type of perseverative cognition which involves repeated and unproductive dwelling on a particular theme – for example, replaying a past event or thinking over and over about one's emotions” (Moulds, Bisby, Wild, and Bryant, 2020). Ruminating about the COVID-19 pandemic proves it as a main stressor for Algerian students in the UK and demonstrates how impactful and anxious this situation of uncertainty was on their mental health and academic life which made the separation experience much more difficult. This finding is pretty much similar to Kee's (2021) outcome, whose qualitative study explored the emotions and challenges graduate students experienced over six weeks in the Spring of 2020 in response to the COVID-19 disruption. Anxiety and fear were identified among the study results especially for international students who reflected that the COVID-19 represented a major problem for them with the borders closure thinking about their families and needing their support. Participants also highlighted that their family's health and well-being added to their fear and anxiety.

Only two students demonstrated that they have not experienced the stress of family separation during the beginning of the COVID pandemic as they were in Algeria as follows:

“During COVID I was with them. I was in Algeria. I was eating and sleeping with them and everything” (Steven).

Here, Steven expressed that he was not stressed because of family separation at the beginning of the COVID period as he was staying back home with his family, and he did not have to worry or think about them as he would be if he was in the UK. However, this does not deny Steven’s and his family’s stress because of the COVID pandemic in Algeria.

And Lisa:

“Because of the Coronavirus situation, the borders were closed. So, I had to stay home for almost seven months. Seven months and I came back again in October... but this year, it was different. It was different I... although like I spent here, almost like one year here without going back home but I'm stressed” (Lisa).

And added:

“Because of the COVID pandemic, the borders were closed. So, it made it harder to go back home” (Lisa).

Lisa here highlighted that she spent the first period of the COVID pandemic (seven months) with her family back home and she could not go back to the UK because of the borders closure. In the first part of the extract, Lisa did not mention a family separation-related stress as she was not experiencing a separation at that time. However, she mentioned that she got stressed when she went back again to the UK and stayed for nearly a year away from her family. This demonstrates that both, the COVID pandemic and family separation are major stressors for Algerian PhD students in the UK. Correspondingly, Lisa added:

“Well... definitely, the Coronavirus had like a bad effect on our PhD journey. We were like in period of like great stress. We were like in lockdown. So, it affected us. It affected my progress personally. I could not... I could not like do any progress in my PhD... and this is maybe like so stressed. Since we are like... this is my first time like in the real world of research and as, like, a novice researcher, it made me like... the situation made me stressed really stressed” (Lisa).

Lisa here described how stressful the COVID pandemic is on her PhD journey and what negative impact the lockdown had on her mental health and academic progress especially for a novice researcher as she described herself. This finding is in line with Alaklabi, Alaklabi, and Almuhlaifi (2021) who stated that COVID-19 had a great negative effect on the emotional well-being of international students.

Emma described her feelings of stress and depression during the lockdown period because she felt lonely with no family and no friends to socialize which triggered her depression, homesickness and loneliness:

“But after covid, I think it was the hardest because now I am between like four walls, inside, I do not enjoy as much as I did before which made me like a little bit kind of depressed especially at the beginning because not only, I do not have my family, but I do not have like friends to hang out with or ... I just can call them, but I like face to face interaction. Well, I think that was the hardest” (Emma).

The COVID-19 pandemic has affected international students especially in the context of them being away from their families. This finding agrees with what has been declared that “today, stressful situations and loneliness due to the pandemic are even more intense. In particular, in international universities where student families are often thousands of miles away in combination with compulsory lockdown due to the pandemic, they create an explosive mix of emotions that often leads to increased stress or even depression” (Misirlis, Zwaan, Sotiriou, and Weber, 2020, p.21).

Still with the COVID-19 pandemic, Emily, a participant who spent two years of the pandemic in the UK away from her family described how COVID pandemic psychologically affected her and added to her stress about her family as follows:

“For sure, it affected me because I was worried about them. I was like, confused, whether I can go to see them or not. For example, if you remember the last year, when the pandemic started, we were all confused and stressed whether you go to Algeria, and take the virus with us to our family, if you remember. So, it was like a very stressful period. And even until now I have like this, this fear... you still have the fear of not going yeah, in terms of taking the virus” (Emily).

And she added:

“Yes, yes. I really missed them. But when I think about this pandemic, and the consequences of going home or this circumstances, I feel afraid of taking the virus” (Emily).

Emily above talked about her feelings of worry, stress and fear about her family back home and she described her confusion on whether to go back home or not, when she had the choice in a government repatriation flight, as she was afraid of taking the virus to her family. This indicates that Emily prioritizing her family’s health over her desire to join them during this difficult period of the COVID pandemic despite the effect of this stress on her mental health in this context of family separation.

This finding confirms that of Maleku et al. (2021) who conducted a mixed method research and consider it to be the first study to investigate the effects of COVID-19 on international students’ mental health in the US with reference to the roles of loneliness and anxiety in relation to discrimination and depression. Among the study findings, it has been concluded that international students’ concerns were loneliness, anxiety, scare and frustration. Students also pointed out to their need of mental health support from their families and reported that they were concerned about their health and their families’ health back home. They have also mentioned that being away from family because of the lockdown and borders closure had a negative effect on their mental health (Maleku et al., 2021).

Participants’ voices in this section illustrate the main standpoints through which students and their families based their talk to describe how impactful the COVID-19 pandemic was on them in the context of family separation. This presents the COVID-19 pandemic as one of the main stressors that they came across during this separation. This section that presented a part of the study findings also helps in contributing to research worldwide about the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on international students. This is because, there is a lack of academic research that focuses on the impact of COVID-19 on international students as a vulnerable group rather than focusing on families and communities in general (Firang, 2020).

7.5. Chapter summary:

This chapter addressed the second aim of the study and to answer the research question that leads this study which aimed to understand the social stresses impacting Algerian students who take doctoral research in the UK and their families in Algeria. As they explained their

perceptions of social stress through two major aspects of this experience: study and separation, participants also talked about their fears and sources of stress in relation to these aspects. Participants also reported how the COVID-19 pandemic affected their experiences.

Chapter Eight: Perceptions of family separation

8.1. Introduction:

In the previous chapter, I analysed and discussed the social stressors affecting Algerian students taking doctoral research in the UK and their families in Algeria in the context of family separation. In this chapter, I present and discuss findings in relation to the notion of family separation, which addresses the third aim of the research.

Although participants showed conflicting opinions with regards to naming the experience of students taking doctoral research in the UK who left their families back home by family separation, they, in many instances, demonstrated that it had a profound impact on their mental health. Participants' answers also revealed that it had an impact on relationships amongst family members, the social support they mutually used to provide to each other. The findings also indicated that gender plays a significant difference in the experience of separation of families. Accordingly, this chapter deals with participants' beliefs regarding family separation and its related aspects.

8.2. Participants' conceptualizations of family separation:

Family separation is a key element in this study. Hence, learning about how participants perceive it was critical to understand the experience of taking PhD in the UK from the perspectives of Algerian students in the UK and their left-behind families and its impact on them as members of the collectivist Algerian society (Berrezoug, 2021). Nevertheless, participants, when asked how they perceive family separation, found the question challenging due to the nature of the expression itself. This is because, describing this experience as a separation of family was controversial among participants. That is, some participants accepted to call the experience of students taking their PhD research in the UK and leaving their families in Algeria as family separation, while others refused to use this concept.

Some of the participants have explicitly voiced their perceptions that the fact of students being in the UK while families are still at home is a family separation. For instance, Lisa described the experience as a separation and mentioned:

“With the literal meaning of the word when you are no longer part of your family. Yeah, it is like the word separation denotes that you are no longer with your family. You are separated from them, you are like,

separated physically from them, and probably a degree of like, mental and spiritual separation too” (Lisa).

Family separation here was perceived in relation to being physically absent from the family and not sharing the family house with other family members, which entails psychological impacts on individuals. The case of Algerian students in the UK who left their families behind in Algeria was perceived as a kind of family separation by Lisa. Lisa’s perception here is similar to what Boado and Ferrer (2022) has claimed that the two most common causes of family separation are migration where students have ever been apart from at least one of their parents for more than three months, and parental divorce or separation. This also reinforces other students’ perceptions who chose to call their study abroad experience as a family separation.

Steven also shared a similar idea regarding family separation and its psychological implications:

“Well, there is family and there is separation... it is self-explanatory concept... but it has more psychological implications. It is a feeling of being away, being distant, like emotionally distant from your family. It is the feeling of a gap inside. It is the feeling of alienation when you do not feel like you are as close to your family as it used to be, because when you're with your family, you've got these inside jokes with your with... your sister or with your father and you get along like smoothly ... but family separation to me is that when you... even you are with them, like literally with them, but you are not getting along, and you are like operating on different levels. So, it's not necessarily to be far from your family to be a family separation” (Steven).

Here, family separation was explained by alienation which denotes experiencing physical and emotional distance from family. For Steven, family separation is more about being emotionally and psychologically separated and distant from other members of the family. That is, family separation is the loss of the emotional bond and attachment that ties family members with each other although they are still physically together. This outcome matches with what Boss (2010) has explained as the second type of ambiguous loss, which essentially describes the situation when a loved one is physically present and psychologically absent such as cases of autism, chronic mental illness, and depression.

Then Steven emphasized:

“It is said that “out of sight, out of mind”, of course, if you are not accessible to me, then it is going to make it harder because there is separation, there is like physical separation but what matters the most is the emotional separation [...] It is a separation, but it is not as much important as psychological separation. If I am to choose which one is more impactful, then it is the emotional separation” (Steven).

Steven highlighted above that family separation can also be felt when individuals are not physically present with their families. Although physical separation is stressful, he voiced that emotional separation is much impactful on family members. The participant view here implies that students in the UK and their families in Algeria are not completely separated, yet they are, to some extent, separated in this situation. This is because, although they do not share the same country, family house and atmosphere, they still have emotional bond and attachment of family with each other.

Correspondingly, Jane explained that family separation stands for both physical and emotional separation:

“Completely being distant from your family like both physically and emotionally, you are not there anymore, as you see that I cannot attend events with them, I cannot be there with them. So, it causes a lot of space and distance [...] It includes both the physical obviously it is there because you are in a completely different place than that, and emotionally, not being able to know what's going on in their lives, they don't know what's going on in your life as well. You cannot share everything with them, and you cannot be there with them when they need you and vice versa” (Jane).

Jane here noted that the inability to share moments and family life with other family members is a separation that involves physical absence and emotional distance. Jane's account is based on the belief that the emotional bond that ties family members with each other arises mainly from sharing the family house and life.

Perceiving family separation as a physical absence and emotional presence was most common among participants. This belief is in accordance with the first type of ambiguous loss

used by Boss (2010) to refer to cases when a loved person is physically absent and psychologically present due to the possibility of coming back and joining family, like in kidnapping, divorce and migration.

Still with the physical separation of family members in the context of Algerian students studying in the UK, in Lucy's words:

“It is a separation but not for always. Yeah, it's temporary because I'm not staying here for years and years but just once I'm done with my studies I will be back home. So, I will join the family again, but it's considered as a separation because we are not living with them. You are not sharing their life with them... yeah, so it is a separation to me”
(Lucy).

In agreement with Jane, Lucy showed that family separation is not physically sharing the family life with other members. Given the context of the study, Lucy draw attention on a very important aspect that students separation from their families is temporary and bounded with the duration of the PhD course. This goes in line with how Chinese and Taiwanese international students in the U.S. perceived their study abroad experience as entailing a temporary physical separation from most of their attachment relationships (Wang and Mallinckrodt, 2006).

Likewise, Catherine said:

“I think family separation is being away from your family for a short period of time. It is being away from your family, not completely separated, because if you say family separation for me, as a person, I think about leaving them, but for me, it is getting away from family for a period of time. Because if you just think that you are separated from your family? Oh, my God, it's already a big word. Yeah, but family separation is being away from your family, which makes you very sad and affect you as a person, and the way you are living here and affects your studies. Also. It's a separation for a period of time, and it depends on the period of time you are away from your family” (Catherine).

Catherine demonstrated that her separation from her family is temporary; however, separation of family, in her opinion, is complete detachment from other family members. That

is, the fact of her being away from her family is primarily for pursuing her doctoral research, which, owing to her PhD programme, urged her to be physically away yet still in contact with her family. Physical absence, according to Catherine, generate negative impact on students in the UK. This conforming to what has been found that physical separation of parents and their children, regardless of the migration status, implies negative effect on their children's wellbeing, in a study that looked at the mental wellbeing costs that migrants' children experience because of long periods of physical separation from their parents after reunification (Boado and Ferrer, 2022).

So far, physical absence and presence seemed to be an important factor through which students conceptualise family separation. This quite matches with the researcher's argument behind doing this research, that Algerian students in the UK and their families in Algeria, who belong to a collectivist society, would be greatly impacted by separation.

Alternatively, after acknowledging to their experiences in the UK as a kind of family separation, some students expressed their views through describing the feelings they experienced while being apart from their families. For instance,

“It is bitter. It is sad. It is depressing. It is very stressful, and most importantly, it taught me a lot. I mean, if I do it again, I would do it again but just for the short term, I would love to go back to them and live with them permanently” (Gill).

And:

“It is really bad, negative experience... I don't know sometimes, I think it's good and bad, it's bad because they cannot support you, as they did, and you cannot support them as well. Good is like now you will start to develop maybe emotional independence, you won't be that much attached to your family... but overall, I describe it like 24 hours stress, 24 hours anxiety... like are they okay? Are they doing fine?” (Emma).

And:

“Being separated from your family is not an easy task anymore. It causes a lot of stress. It does hugely affect your mental health and your well-being in general” (Ashley).

The students' comments above reflected on the emotional impact separation had on their mental health. Stress, anxiety, and depression were among the negative effects of being away from family. This has been referred to as international students living with emotional turmoil in a study that examined the lived experiences of international students whose family remains at home (Harvey, Robinson and Welch, 2018). Gill and Emma demonstrated that family separation is a double-edged sword. Despite challenges, it is a learning experience that gave them the chance to learn several qualities and develop emotionally. This agrees with what has been found in a study that researched the lived experience of female Arab-Muslim students who live and study nursing in the United States, where Omani students declared emotional growth as an outcome of being psychologically separated from family for the first time (McDermott-Levy, 2011).

Not all participants shared the same conception, although most of them did, that the experience of Algerian students taking postgraduate studies in the UK leaving their family in Algeria is a separation. This can be illustrated by Nancy's view:

“I have kind of a negative connotation to this term separation as though they are completely separated. Let's call it something else. I don't know a... family arrangement, because I know that I'm going back. So, it's just temporary, you know, in a way we're not completely separated. I'm still in contact with them, they're still in contact with me. So, I will say this as a family arrangement or reorganisation somehow, for a temporary period of time, maybe it's just me not feeling okay with the term” (Nancy).

In agreement with Catherine who preferred to use “getting away from family” instead of the concept “family separation”, Nancy showed explicit disagreement with using the concept to talk about the experiences of students who study in countries different than their own. Similar to Lucy, Catherine and many other students, Nancy placed emphasis on the temporary feature of students' stay in the UK as they limited by the course duration and are bounded by the contract, they signed with the Algerian ministry to get the scholarship (Bursary Sponsorship Contract, 2015).

Nancy, then, added:

“So, family separation in the context of study abroad is something important to be taken in interest because not all societies are

collectivist, a lot of liberal societies are individualistic, and they rarely give attention to these family ties and everything. So, I think it's a very important factor behind mental well-being and academic outcomes. I feel family separation, as you would call it, could be the reason behind, I wouldn't say the failure, but the delays that a lot of students are experiencing in terms of progress in their PhD [...] So, I think family separation is a big subject that needs exploration, a lot of research and attention. Even though in Western societies, it doesn't look like that big problem" (Nancy).

Nancy brought attention to a very important point that family separation is a primary source of stress for Algerian students, which reflects on their studies. This is conforming to what has been found in this research to answer the main research question that guides this study (see chapter 6) that stressors in relation to separation hugely affect Algerian students who take their doctoral study in the UK and left their families in Algeria. Looking at Algerian students as a minority group among international students in the UK, Nancy asserted that belonging to a collectivist society would make living abroad away from family a major challenge for students. Collectivist societies, like most of countries in Asia, are those in which individuals are raised as members of strong, cohesive in-groups and place a strong emphasis on maintaining harmony within a family or society (Kimura, and Nakajima, 2011). Hofstede (1986) distinguished between individualist (loosely integrated) and collectivist cultures (closely integrated) as individualist societies emphasize the person's self-interest and the interests of their immediate family (husband, wife, and children); collectivist cultures, however, believe that people are born and live in-groups and are unable to separate themselves from the group which defends its members' interests. This is also compatible with the argument behind researching Algerian students and their families in the context of family separation.

Although families of these Algerian students are still together in their home country, they are an essential component in comprehending the notion of family separation and its meaning in this research. This is because, families of migrants who stay in their home countries do not have to deal with the difficulties of adjusting to a new culture but being apart from their migrant family members can still stress them (Silver, 2011). In different circumstances and from a different angle to look at the experience of Algerian students taking postgraduate study in the UK, family members of these students, in Algeria, also showed conflicting views regarding whether the notion of family separation can be used in the context of Algerian

students studying for postgraduate research in the UK and left their families behind in Algeria. Like their students in the UK, family members also tended to explain their perceptions of family separation in relation to two main points; the reasons that lead members of the same family to live away from each other and the fact of being physically present or absent in the family. To illustrate, Ashley's brother outlined:

“Family separation can take two meanings. For instance, one might not accept that this situation of study abroad is a separation of family just because his sister is living in the UK. He would perceive it as if his sister is dead or something, if you tell him that your sister is separated from his family. While for others, it is a separation of family even if their sister is just in another state of the country other than their home state” (Ashley's brother).

Ashley's brother here commented that the notion of family separation is open to discussion as different connotations can be given by individuals. The participant's belief here is somehow compatible with what has been argued that family separation can take several forms such as divorce, death of a parent or separation, and migration (Wen and Lin, 2012). He based his explanation of the term separation in relation to family chiefly on physical presence of family members and sharing the same family house. The participant then explained his own perception and stated:

“For me, it is not a separation. We are in daily, even hourly, contact with Ashley. I call her when I am outside in the neighbourhood. She sees our neighbours. She talks with our relatives. She shares family events with us. She celebrates religious feasts with us via calls” (Ashley's brother).

Ashley's brother here argued that being physically away and absent from the family house does not represent separation as members of the family still maintain their relationship together via online platforms of social media. That is, physical absence does not necessarily mean emotional separation. Hence, the dualism of presence/absence in the family represents a crucial factor through which participants build their perceptions.

Nancy's brother expressed:

“For me, you can call it a family separation, but it does not seem like a separation of family, actually. It is not a family separation. You can just call it a study abroad maybe. If you say a family separation, some may get it as a family conflict or dispute where a girl or a boy had conflict with their father or family, and they left the family house and do not live and talk with them anymore [...] But when there still be a contact between the family members, even if it is virtual contact, then it is not a separation. It is just a study abroad, alienation or you can call it a temporary absence of a family member from the family” (Nancy’s brother).

The participant above explained that separation of family stands for negative reasons that divide and split members of the family and cuts off the contact between them like family conflicts. This is referred to as family estrangement which signifies a severance of communication between family members and may develop into a temporary or permanent condition (Conti, 2015). However, when members of the family move out of the family house due to good and positive reasons where family relations are still maintained and members get along with each other, just like the case of students and families in this research, then the concept of family separation would not be the best notion to use for description.

Still with how families in Algeria perceived the context of students studying in the UK and leaving their families back home, Emma’s sister voiced:

“Family separation is like one person is away. One person is dead. You are going to cope, like, you can say this person is no more around really the person is just leaving and... putting you in a place when you cannot have them, you cannot talk to them, just like he's there, but he's not there. It's really difficult. It's like the person is there, you are talking to him, but he is not around like you cannot talk to him face to face, you cannot feel him. For me, this is the most difficult thing” (Emma’s sister).

Emma’s sister was another participant, among others, who perceived family separation in relation to physical absence and presence. She clearly noted that separation of family is about distance.

“It is absent physically and present, like, virtually, which it's not enough. I would say that it is like an ongoing pain, ongoing missing, you are talking to her, but you are still not satisfied enough? She's not there. But you still miss her even while talking to her, you still miss her” (Emma's sister).

The participant here explained family separation in relation to the emotions individuals feel when they pass through experiences of separation. In contradiction with Ashley's brother and Nancy's brother, Emma's sister above asserted that virtual presence of students and being involved in the family's life through social media does not replace being physically present in the family, which she described as a separation of family.

This finding reinforces previous study in somewhat, but not completely similar setting conducted by Reyes (2008) on Filipino left-behind children after their mothers' departure abroad to work, where it has been stated that technology and social media is used to replace the parents' absence and make up for their stay away, yet this virtual parenting cannot substitute the emotional bond children would develop from the physical presence of their parents.

From a parent perspective, Josie's mother expressed her maternal instinct and feelings as follows:

“Before her departure to the UK, I was not expecting myself to get highly affected by being away from her. I was thinking that it would be manageable, but now, after I experienced separation from my daughter, I just count the days, months and even years waiting to see her back with us” (Josie's mother).

Josie's mother above commented on how challenging and stressful her separation from her daughter, which was not as she expected before starting this journey.

Jane's twin sister, on the other hand, referred to consequential change of separation and the need of getting used to it. For instance, she expressed her perception:

“When it is someone, you really love, and you used to share your life details with gets distant from you. So, you will have to be used to live your life in a new way, from a new perspective, you will have to be used to a new style, you know, a style where you will not share those moments, those beautiful moments with that person” (Jane's sister).

The participant here highlighted sharing details and moments of each other's life as an important aspect of family life and togetherness, which is missed when they got separated after students' departure to study in the UK.

8.3. Impacts of family separation on mental health:

This section aims at presenting and discussing the impacts of family separation on mental health. The interviews' analysis revealed that all participants are aware of how family separation has affected their psychology. In a different context, refugees also, when interviewed, described how their mental health was impacted by family separation in a study conducted by Wilmsen (2013) that examined the impacts of family separation on refugee settlement in Australia. Participants' awareness of the family separation impacts on their mental health helped them form their perceptions of family separation (presented in the previous section), and to develop strategies to cope with this separation (see chapter 8).

Family separation seem to have a profound impact on participants' mental health. The data has revealed that female students were more impacted by being separated from their families more than males did. Participants almost described similar features which indicated that how separation of family has affected them. The most common mental health consequences of family separation for students in the UK and their left-behind families in Algeria included: overthinking, worry, depression, crying, doubting oneself, and sleeping disorders. The most illustrative extracts from the participants' data are used to support this section.

The conversation about mental health was introduced by the researcher asking participants whether family separation has affected their mental health. Participants then went on to express themselves in relation to this issue.

Jack thought the following:

“Not really, because I get to talk to them whenever I want. We can video chat. So, I don't see a problem with being away from them” (Jack).

As a male student, Jack, who mentioned earlier that separation-related stress does not affect him as study-related stress does to him (see chapter 6, section 6.3.), acknowledged here that staying in touch with family through social media reduced the passive impact that family separation could have on his mental health.

A similar opinion was shared by the male student in this study. Steven reported:

“I found that my mental health... it does not affect me, honestly speaking. I got used to live it on my own. I did not use to live on my own. Actually, I am afraid if I go back, and I don't fit with... with my family... because here in the UK, I'm just doing everything on my own the way I want but once back, I would be living with my father, with my mum, my sister, I would have those obligations that I once had... and I would, you know, what I mean, right... Yeah, just like getting my old life back. and it's not nice, because I feel like I made progress, depending on myself and doing everything on my own, then going back home, and that would bring me like, five years ago, and that's not progress. That's, you know, regression not progressing” (Steven).

In this case, Steven elaborated in more details why family separation did not affect his mental health as a male student like Jack. He highlighted that the experience of studying and living abroad away from his family had a positive impact on him at the personal level as he developed a new independent identity as a postgraduate student to strongly stand against the family social norms of the family unit in the Algerian society where male and female children live with their families and bounded by the family rules usually set by the father, which he referred to as “obligations”. This is because families in Algeria are governed by the father or the husband as the leading person or the breadwinner of the family who is responsible for the family decisions (Bouguesri and Nait-Brahim, 2021).

Gender differences play an important role in the context of family separation of Algerian students in the UK who left their families behind in Algeria. This is because, unlike Jack and Steven, Algerian female students in the UK recounted different opinions than males with regards to the impact of family separation on mental health.

A common negative effect of family separation on mental health was mentioned by female participants is that of depression, which engendered from feelings of loneliness and missing the family atmosphere and family members. As an example, Emily asserted:

“Actually, I passed through depression because of this issue because I used to be like next to my nephew, my niece. I used to check my parents every day; I used to kiss my mom, every morning. So, I become... in general, I miss all this stuff” (Emily).

With this, Emily highlighted the significance of family circle in the lives of Algerians in their country. This denotes how the family atmosphere Algerian students lived in and grew up influenced their experiences in the UK and led them to develop signs of depression. This is because feelings of loss, separation and missing are the primary reasons that lead international students to feel lonely, homesick, and depressed (Saravanan, Mohamad, and Alias, 2019).

Jane did the same by emphasising how being away from her family led her to severe depression. She recounted:

“It severely affected me because it made me fall into full depression. There were times when I considered giving up completely about continuing my PhD here, leave everything and go home. Last time, I thought about leaving the PhD and go home. This is how much it affected me because I could not keep up with my studies and separated from my family. There was so much pressure on my mental health” (Jane).

Then she added:

“It is very hard. Obviously, it affects your mental health severely. You cannot focus on your study when you have that kind of mental stress. So, in general, it just makes it harder to keep up. You cannot live your life peacefully. You are in a constant feeling of homesickness, of missing your family members, or in my case missing my twin sister most of the time” (Jane).

In Jane’s case, the depression resulted from her inability to cope with being away from her twin sister and family led her to think of quitting her doctoral study in the UK. Although depression in study abroad contexts is common for all international students over the world, its impact on students’ mental health in the context of Algerian students in the UK lies mainly on its associated feelings of loneliness and homesickness that engendered from missing the family atmosphere and leaving family with whom students grew up and lived with for almost three decades, since birth until departing to the UK, and share the family house with other family members. This revolves around the nature of family as the basic unit upon which society in Algeria stands for (Khammar and Dekoumi, 2022).

Carol was another participant who brought up a different angle through which she explained how separation of family has affected her mental health. She stated:

“If something stressful is happening with them, I will be very affected. If I miss them a lot, and I started going about it, then I will give this as well, for example, my first year I had this thought, I was looking at people and then I said to myself, why can't one of them be my family? Like why it is so hard to see my family face to face. So, it is so hard” (Carol).

In this case, Carol’s self-reflection implies that having a family, or at least one family member, with her in the UK would make her experience much easier and boost her ability of adaptation to the new environment and move on with the new experience. Then she went on to say:

“In my second year, the first few months, I wanted to have a plan to go back. So, if I have a plan, then I will of course have something to think about, to be happy about in the future. I wanted to meet my partner. I wanted to move on with him. I mean in our plans and things like that. So, I really wanted to go back, and I planned a trip in January, and I think it is only when I planned it, I started to be way happier. I went for shopping. I knew that even if I was really lonely in here, or even if I saw people who are not my family, I know that my family is waiting for me, I have people whom I know, and love are waiting for me. So, I don't have to care about people having their families while I don't” (Carol).

The participant here brought up a very important point of how the experience of separation made it difficult for her to move on and plan for her future due to the absence of her family. However, having the hope and optimism for reunification with family acted as a booster that encouraged her to plan for her future. This outcome quite matches with what Wilmsen (2013) has found that moving forward and making plans for the future required having the entire family together in the context of refugees in Australia.

Carol then added:

“Sometimes when I miss my family like these days, for example, I always, every single night, have dreams about them, and I'm really

happy in those dreams because in I'm sitting with them as if I was there already. So, I have it every single night these days, and that's how I know that I miss them a lot” (Carol).

Another aspect that Carol mentioned and is associated with how family separation has affected students' mental health is having dreams about her family. The student's need to see her family has impacted her subconscious mind, which formed dreams in which she was reunited with her family. This implies how keen students are to join their families back home. This finding is similar to what Miller, Hess, Bybee, and Goodkind (2018) have found out that refugees expressed how they had dreams about their separated family members and hopes and plans for reunification.

Another negative impact of separation on students' mental health was that of having panic attacks. Several students gave examples of experiencing panic attacks when not being able to reach out to their families in Algeria. For instance, a female student recounted:

“When I am not in contact with them, and I don't know how they are doing sometimes I have panic attacks. For instance, there was this one time where I called my mother several times, and she did not pick up. I was like, where are they? So, I reached out to one of my friends who is still back in Algeria, and I was like, here is my mother's number, call her and ask her where she is, and my friend did call her, they are outside, and they do not have data on their phones right now. That is why you cannot reach them when they go back home, they will call you” (Katy).

The participant here explained how being informed about family situation back home seems to be a crucial aspect of students' experiences in the UK as it gives them reassurance and lowers their stress and fear for their families. Therefore, losing that reassurance triggers students' mental health and gets them in intense anxiety. A similar result was found in a slightly different context in a qualitative study that examined the impacts of separation from family on Sudanese refugees in Australia where refugees indicated that separation caused them “a constant worry about the wellbeing and safety of significant others back home and around the globe” (Savic, Chur-Hansen, Mahmood, and Moore, 2013, p.385).

Katy then elaborated on this point:

“So, being separated from them does not exactly affect my mental health, but there are moments when being separated from them, not being in contact with them causes me to spiral into a panic attack. I do not think that the PhD has ever caused me to spiral into a panic attack. Like it causes me loads of stress and anxiety but not like an actual panic attack where I'm crying or anything like that... but my mother not picking up the phone after I called her for like five times. I am literally shaking” (Katy).

Katy's account here is based on her personal experience. She brought attention to panic attacks as one of the major impacts of separation on her mental health. Physical symptoms of panic attacks like shaking and crying were brought up to illustrate the student's reaction to her fear and stress for family.

Still with the impact of family separation on mental health, families in Algeria, on the other hand, also got impacted by the absence of students after they departed to study in the UK. Findings from families' data suggest that family members developed signs of bad mental health because of getting affected by separation from their adult children. In this regard, it has been stated that family members that are separated from one another experience serious mental health problems (Okhovat et al., 2017). Like their adult children in the UK, families in Algeria demonstrated features of mental health issues as a result of separation such as depression, overthinking, anorexia (appetite loss), sleeping disorders and insomnia. To illustrate the families' standpoint in Algeria, Clover's mother, for example, considered the profound impact of separation on her and mentioned:

“In her first year abroad, I was really stressed and concerned about her, it affected me a lot” (Clover's mother).

In like manner, Emma's sister elaborated in more details the difficulty of being separated from students when they first departed to the UK. She articulated:

“The first days of her not being here. I did not sleep. I stayed up into... the day that she departed from the airport, I did not sleep at all until I saw the message that she arrived well, and then I slept. The days that I know that she has some difficulties in her PhD. I just kept thinking about it. I just took her subject of study, and I keep looking for some books thinking that I might help her or something” (Emma's sister).

Here, Emma's sister hints to the difficulty of having a family member travelling away while the rest of family remains at home for the first time and the stressful impacts engendered from this separation, where she is one of the family members left behind in the home country. She brought up anorexia and insomnia as one of the impacts of separation stress on family's mental health. Students' safe arrival was crucial for family's reassurance.

On the other hand, from a father perspective, Emily's father brought up a very important aspect that affected his mental health as a parent of a student who got a sponsored scholarship. He stated:

“When Emily is stressed because of study or some paperwork with the ministry, at that time I get really stressed about her and whether she managed to deal with those problems. I always think of her and keen to know about her updates” (Emily's father).

As government sponsored students, Algerian PhD students in the UK had to deal with paperwork issues with the ministry of higher education in Algeria which took them time and stressed them out. This was reflected on and had a profound impact on their families' mental health and added to their stress of separation.

To most family members in Algeria, a profound impact of separation on their mental health lies in the ongoing feeling of missing especially in special occasions like religious feasts, wedding partings and so many situations which are celebrated through family gatherings. In that regard, Carol's sister said:

“Sometimes, I could not sleep from thinking about her. Even if in happy occasions, I keep thinking about her ... like not... sometimes in moments where I'm supposed to be happy, I am not because I am thinking about her... if she was here, as if there is always a missing piece” (Carol's sister).

Lisa's cousin reported an analogous viewpoint:

“On every occasion, whether it is big or small, her place always like... we always mention her, even if it was really small, like family dinner or something we mention her. We just keep remembering some stuff she used to do like, or some food she used to like” (Lisa's cousin).

The participant here described in general how students are missed in family gatherings. It seems that, missing some members in family gatherings, the latter which are supposed to be the core element in many social, religious, and cultural occasions in Algeria, had a huge impact on families.

Several family members talked about how celebrating religious occasions in Algeria with the absence of students was hard and had a great impact on them. Ashley's brother gave an example of Ramadan as a religious occasion while missing two members of his family. He uttered:

“In the same days when Ashley first departed to the UK, my eldest brother left the family to join the military service. So, I stayed alone with my parents at home. It was the first Ramadan without Ashley and my eldest brother. It was the hardest Ramadan ever because of missing two members of the family. I was so difficult to adapt to their absence”
(Ashley's brother).

Ashley's brother here noted how difficult the month of Ramadan is when the family is incomplete. The participant's recognition above denotes how religious celebrations in Algerian society depend on the family get-together. In this respect, it has been asserted that Ramadan is a month of community that stands for family and where Muslim communities celebrate family gatherings (Caidi, Ekmekcioglu, Chandra, and Jamali, 2022). Thus, the month of Ramadan was one of the most impactful experiences students in the UK and their families in Algeria pass through in the context of separation due to students and families missing each other. To illustrate, a male student emphasised this point in his talk and stated:

“I really appreciate the need of family in Ramadan. That is why in previous either on although I was doing a PhD in the UK, but I made sure to spend Eid and Ramadan with my family. So, the last three years I spent Eid and Ramadan with my family. It was only this year when it was the COVID thing and everything was closed, the flights were banned and all that I had to spend Ramadan here” (Steven).

Steven here confirms Ashley's brother vision regarding the hardness of Ramadan missing family members. This is due to the glorification of religious practices and celebrations by families in their life in Algeria. Taking the context of studying abroad into consideration, international students find it very difficult to spend the month of Ramadan away from their

families and their loved ones in a non-Muslim country especially for the first time as they miss Ramadan vibes and rituals like having the Iftar (breaking fast) and Suhoor (pre-dawn meal) with the family, missing the call to prayer and the traditional food of Ramadan (Golestani, 2011; Tayyab, no date).

This section discussed how family separation has affected the mental health of Algerian PhD students in the UK and their left-behind families during students' period of study in the UK. With the data extracts presented in this section, I have shown how difficult the feeling of missing someone was for families in Algeria during students' stay in the UK, and how the latter struggled psychologically with their feelings of missing the whole family. Participants effectively demonstrated this by mentioning several signs of poor mental health. Although the impact of separation was apparent in participants voices, male students showed less signals of bad mental health than females as the impact of family separation on the latter hindered them from going on with their studies.

8.4. Family separation and family relations:

In this section, I shed light on how family separation has affected family relations in the context of Algerian students taking doctoral research in the UK and their left-behind families. Through a holistic view of the participants' voices regarding their experiences of separation, I attempt to catch some of the changes at the level of student/family relationship after students' departure to the UK making it an important facet of the separation experience as both students and family members belong to the Algerian collectivist society that value relationships among members of the family (Ghodbane, 2020). In the beginning, when being interviewed, all participants agreed that separation in the context of this study had no impact on the relationship between students and their families; yet most of them, at later stages of the interview process, brought attention to how family separation has positively affected family relationships between students in the UK and their left-behind families.

As it has already mentioned in the previous section, living in a different country away from family was not that impactful for male students' mental health. However, this is not the case when it comes to their relationships with family. For instance, when asked whether his journey in the UK affected his relationship with his family Jack said: *"In my case, No. No, I cannot say that"* (Jack). In Jack's case, there was no negative impact of separation on his family relations.

On the other hand, Steven had an opposing view regarding this matter and noted that the impact of separation on family relationships was positive. He voiced:

“I think it did. Um, of course it did. Yeah. My father trusts me even more now after like, five years or something, four years of living away from him and away from everything else. Yeah, away from my family. I mean, yeah, I think it is not necessarily a negative effect. Of course, there is the factor of missing, but this separation made us both evolving when it comes to our relationships” (Steven).

Steven here implicitly reflected the leading role of the father in the Algerian family where all the responsibility of the family regarding children was taken by the father. However, after his experience of studying in the UK, Steven got the chance to take the full responsibility over his life, which made him develop his personality and became more independent of his family. That is, separation had a positive impact on Steven’s relationship with his family, especially with his father as it became stronger than it was. This is because, Steven mentioned the following at some point of the interview:

“I had incident with my father... Okay, it is not disobedience to parents but my father and I... do not get along in many circles, in many situations. Whenever I am home, a lot of problems happen. So, I am living with the guy, but we are not, you know, as close as we are when I am here in the UK. When I am here in the UK, he misses me and he told me, okay, you need to take care of yourself and stuff. He did not do this stuff when I am living with my family” (Steven).

The fact of being separated from each other made Steven’s father explicitly expresses his feelings to his son out of his fear and stress for him. So, separation made parents become more emotional towards their children through showing love to each other, which had a positive impact on their relationship. Steven also hinted to his disagreement, sometimes, with his father’s decisions regarding family issues. This is consistent to how Khammar and Dekoumi (2022) asserted that the authority and power of families in Algeria belongs to the father.

Similar to Steven, Lucy also talked about how her family’s feelings towards her became more apparent after getting separated from them. She voiced:

“I think you know in a more positive way because I felt that the love that my family used to have towards me became stronger, the care became stronger the... like the way they miss me also became different” (Lucy).

Like many other participants, Lucy was optimistic regarding her relationship with her family and praised how constructive separation was on improving and reinforcing this relationship through projecting their feelings to each other.

Spencer, who was among the participants who refused to describe this experience as a family separation and indicated that the latter refers to conflicts of families, articulated that separation can have positive and negative impact on family relationships. She said:

“It depends on which kind of separation if someone goes to study abroad. I mean, this will not affect his relationship to his family, I mean, stay always as strong as it used to be, or as strong as it should be. Maybe it will go even stronger, because they are missing this member and he is missing his family as well. But if someone just separates from his family because he no longer wishes to be with his family that would definitely affect the relationship between the two in a negative way. So, it depends on the type of separation” (Spencer).

In agreement with Nancy’s brother, the participant above implicitly argues that separation resulted from negative reasons like family conflicts generates weak relationships between the separated members, whereas a positive improvement is seen in relationships in cases of separation like study abroad contexts where the separated members get more support and love from their families back home as reported by participants earlier in this section. This view is in line with Nelly Trevinyo-Rodríguez and Bontis’ (2010) claim that positive and negative family relationships, which are mainly based on emotions, result from the circumstances family members experience.

Among the participants who voiced their belief of how separation strengthened the relationship between students in the UK and their family members in Algeria, few of them justified their beliefs. For example, Rose said:

“This positively impacted our relationship because we ask about ourselves each other more now than when I used to be there because

we took it for granted. There. I am with them. So yeah, I see them, they see me, but when I am away from them, we contact we ask about each other, frequently” (Rose).

Rose here brought up a very important point in familial relationships in general. She hinted that people usually do not pay attention to the worth of taken-for-granted things, and so is the case with family relationships. That is, when students departed to the UK and had to live on their own away from their families and to take full responsibility of their lives, started to figure out the value of family and feel its importance in their lives. Correspondingly, this has boosted the family ties between students in the UK and left-behind family members.

This view was also held by some participants from families in Algeria. In that regard, Nancy’s brother statement has clearly depicted and strongly agreed with this point:

“The fact that Nancy is studying in the UK has affected the relationship between us. It made the relationships stronger. When Nancy was here in Algeria, we were taking each other for granted. However, when she departed to the UK, we get to know the value of family and the value of each family member even more” (Nancy’s brother).

Also, Jane’s sister expressed:

“Even though we lack communication, but we discovered that we really love each other. And we started to share that more often. You know, when you have someone by your side, you don't pay attention to say how much you miss them, or how much you love them or how much you care about them. But when they are aware, we start to share those feelings more. You make sure the other person knows” (Jane’s sister).

The extracts above show that the experience of studying abroad gave families the opportunity to cherish their relations and to appreciate family togetherness. That is, despite the collective nature of families in the Algerian society where several members tend to live together and extend families, members accepted this structure of social group without questioning their ties as an integral pillar upon which the family and the society stand for. However, the situation of studying in the UK triggered participants’ feelings to revalue the worth of family bonds and the roles of different family members which they were taking for granted.

Spencer's sister shared a comparatively similar belief:

“It became stronger I think because when the person is there around you all the time, you will not feel his place. But when he is not there, you will know how important he/she is and how important his/her place is. So, the relationship become much stronger and more emotional” (Spencer's sister).

Like Nancy's brother belief, Spencer's sister showed that being detached and living away from the family was a chance for them to appreciate the value of family and recognize the roles of its members, which has positively been reflected on the relationships amongst the family members. Moreover, as it has been mentioned earlier in this section with Steven and Lucy, it seems that it is not so common in the Algerian society to express emotions and feelings to each other despite attachment and the societal nature of families. It also appears that both students and families needed to externalize their emotions so that they accept, cope, and manage the separation experience.

To further illustrate this view, Katy elaborated on this point and stated from her angle:

“It can even like make them grow fonder or make them a bit shaky or something... I feel very much closer to my mother now than I did when I lived back home, mostly because whenever I am talking with my siblings, or anybody else, I tell them like you people do not know how much mom matters or like how important and significant her existence in your life is. I know how much it is because I do not have her with me 24 seven, you people do so... I think that has strengthened my relationship with my mother” (Katy).

With reference to relationships among family members, Katy was of the same mind with Spencer in that separation can have a negative as well as a positive impact on family ties depending on the reason lying behind separation. In Katy's case, the change was advantageous as a closeness has been developed at the level of the daughter-mother relationship. Separation in this context played the role of a stimulus for revaluing family relationships. In that regard, Katy expressed her gratitude for the role her mother played in her life, but more importantly, this urged her to advise her siblings and make them aware of how important family ties and family presence are in one's life.

The finding of developing close relationships between students and their families presented above by Lucy, Spencer, Katy and others is in some way similar to some findings in Leigh's study (2016) that examined family relationships among skilled immigrants in Calgary, Alberta. Although all the family members immigrated to Canada, one mother participant expressed that her relationship with her children become much closer in comparison with the distant relationship they had when they were in the Philippines (Leigh, 2016). Even if Leigh's study (2016) differs from the context of this study where only one member of the family immigrated to study in the UK, but there still an aspect of similarity in that alienated members need more support from their families which could positively be reflected on the relationship between family members and make them much closer to each other.

A significant remark that has been noticed in data regarding the participants' accounts about family relations was the opposing views for a student and the associated family member. While the sister thinks that Catherine's departure to the UK has strengthened the relationship between them, Catherine believes in the opposite. In this respect, Catherine's sister mentioned:

“No, I don't think it's affected because we still miss her. Her place is still the same. I think we love her more now especially because she is away, and we are also proud of her. So, we know that she is there because she is doing a good stuff. She is making us proud. So no, it is not affected. It is much more developed.” (Catherine's sister).

With this, the participant communicated that having a sister, or any member of the family in general cases, who takes an academic degree abroad is a source of pride for the family. Besides, she stressed that this feeling of pride and achievement poked the internal emotions the family has toward their daughter and made them more apparent to her through giving support and encouragement along with being proud of her. This finding goes in line with what social stress theory suggested that even positive life events, taking doctoral degree abroad, can be stressful to individuals (Osborne and McLanahan, 2017).

So far, separation seems to be of an advantageous effect on family relations based on the personal experiences of the participants' accounts. However, there was a distinctive viewpoint in data regarding family relationships in which few participants, unlike the others, expressed disagreement with the positive effect of separation on family relationships, but related them to whether family members are still living together. For instance, Catherine, unlike her sister, thought the following:

“I will give you an example. When I came back to Algeria, distance created a gap, there is for example, if I touch something, they say, oh, don't put it there, we changed its place, and in fact, we used to put it there. You feel like a stranger in your house. You feel and if you come back here to the UK, you are also a stranger. So, you are in between. There is a gap in your life [...] Yes, this is what I felt. I felt just like a stranger in my life. Even the relationship is not the same as before, even if we are talking on the phone, but sometimes they reveal things that do not seem like before. So, we are close to each other but not as close as we used to be. It is in between” (Catherine).

Although she mentioned the closeness between family members, the participant plainly believes that alienation and being physically absent from the family for a couple of years abroad made her family exclude and eliminate her from certain aspects of their family life. That is, foreignness led Catherine to feel confused about her sense of belonging. Feeling stranger is typically one of the most common feelings that international students have when they first depart to the host country. However, in Catherine's case, this feeling accompanied her even in times when she joined her family back home. The participant might have been unable to cope with her stay in the UK and could not integrate herself in the British community and culture due to her strong attachment to her family, culture, and social group as a female Algerian. This might have resulted in feelings of loss and made her sensible towards her family back home and this is why Catherine seemed to feel negative with regards to her relationships with her family amidst her journey in the UK.

From a different angle, Clover explained how she thought that her relationship with her family has changed along these few lines:

“It affected mine. Yeah. I mean, the idea is that you're no longer talking to your family on day-to-day basis. It means like billions of things happening with you they do not know about them. You don't share with them, why because, basically, for example, when I talk to my mother, it's like after three or four days, I talk to her. I don't share every single detail. I mean, there are things like the major ones that I share with them... because maybe I have changed, or I would call it growing and being maybe emotionally independent. So yeah, so definitely, it

changed. It's not as it used to be, like, so open and they know everything about you, and you know everything about them” (Clover).

Then she added:

“Also with my sister, the one who's now living in Egypt, before she got married, she was living in Algeria. Well, we used to talk a lot with each other and share things but, because she has now settled down with her husband and just has like a new life. So, we don't talk as often as we used to before. And the less you talk to other people, the more the changes you see in your relationship with them” (Clover).

To offer context, Clover’s family has already experienced the alienation of a family member prior to Clover’s departure to the UK. Clover believes that family ties stand mainly for attachment and sharing life details together. As the latter has been reduced through time with the nature of Clover’s life in the UK and her commitment to study, her communication with her family decreased as well, which affected their relationship. It seems that Clover accepted this change in her relationships with family and did not get affected by her emotions of living away from her family, which led her to develop an emotional independence. Unlike Catherine, Clover seemed to have managed to cope with living in a different culture and social group than hers and this refrained her from feeling negative towards her family ties. Also, having someone from the family who experienced life abroad helped Clover to be more positive with her own experience in the UK.

A significant case in data worth mentioning was that of Lisa's cousin. As a member of the extended or large family, Lisa’s cousin talked about her relationship with Lisa after the latter’s departure to the UK. She said:

“Her relationship is still the same with me and our other cousins and relatives. Nothing has changed, I guess. We still call each other and share things as before” (Lisa’s cousin).

The participant here noted that the nature of relationship between relatives, members of several small families, with the alienated member has not been affected by separation or distance. The reason behind this view might be the close relationship Lisa had with her cousins when she was at home. However, this might not be the case with all students in this study. That

is, other students' relationship with their relatives might have been changed with distance and communication between them might have been decreased.

Within this section, participants' views with regards to family relationships in the context of study abroad have been demonstrated. It was revealed that leaving the family to study abroad had, although it was not the case with all students, strengthened ties among students in the UK and their family members who are left behind in Algeria. Since human relationships stand essentially for feelings, Algerian students and their families found themselves express their feelings more openly in words to show support and love for each other in this context. This emotional connection justifies participants' conceptualization of family separation as an emotional presence despite of the physical absence.

8.5. Family separation and family support:

As it has been voiced by most participants in the earlier section, the relationship has positively evolved between students and their families in the context of separation. Family support seem to have performed a significant role in the development of the family ties between families in Algeria and their young children in the UK throughout their journey of separation. This section presents participants' views regarding the family support students and family members provide to each other, although most of the views were centred around the need of students in the UK to receive support from their family as alienated members. This is because, students in this study like other international students need social support to emotionally and socially adjust and cope with the host environment (Lee et al., 2017). Similar to what Bulgan and Çiftçi (2018) has explained, social support, in this research, is used to describe the kind of support provided to international students from their families, friends and people they count for during their period of adaptation abroad.

In Algerian families, members are supposed to stand by each other to provide support whenever it is necessary (Achoui, 2006), and this is what has contributed to building the strong ties between Algerian families and their members. In the context of this study, almost all participants' views as to the impact of separation on the social support they used to give to each other were indistinguishable, yet they were in some way different. For instance, one student said: *"no, never. That would never affect, you know"* (Jack); similarly, one family member expressed: *"we still support her the same way we used to do when she was here with us"* (Emily's father). Other participants shared similar responses which initially indicated that

family separation had no bad effect on the family support, especially for students as alienated members.

One perspective that was held by some students was that their family support became abstract and intangible, which was based on feelings and emotions. Students shared few examples to explain their views. In this respect, Gill reported:

“My mom has always been supportive, but the thing is... it's not enough when you are online. When I don't meet you, you see. Yeah, she gives me the support, but in a way that when I tell her maybe I can't do it, or I tell her all my supervisors told me this and this and this. She is like, I know, and I always told you do not doubt yourself and she gives me that support talk. So, she's supportive, but I feel like she would be more supportive if I was in front of her eyes” (Gill).

Despite of the support Gill's family provided her with after her departure to the UK, Gill implied here that if she was with her family, she would have been received more support as the emotional support, which she described as online, would have been transmitted physically to her. She gave example of how her mother verbally and emotionally stands by her and motivates her when she was struggling with her study. However, Gill felt that these words of support would have more impact on her if they were accompanied by physical acts like hugs and real eye contacts.

Likewise, according to Lisa:

“Because I am not physically there. Even if we talked via social media, basically every day but it's not as if you are there. It is not as strong as you are, like, when you are there. You get support, but you do not really feel it. I mean, you feel it but not in a strong way. For example, you miss those hugs during the speech. So, it is not like when you're face to face with someone” (Lisa).

In Lisa's case, even though her family were supportive and virtually sharing moments with her, the lack of physical support was noticeable for Lisa. It seems that the reason behind this might be that Algerians often used gestures along with supporting words to demonstrate their support and sympathy to each other, which made the support much more meaningful and tangible.

Similarly:

“If I was like in Algeria, I will just talk face to face with hugging, with like physical emotional gestures, but like, here... yeah, I can call her... technology is great, amazing but it lacks, you know, that physical interaction” (Emma).

And added:

“My relationship with my sister evolved, like, greatly since coming here, because now I needed her more. I needed her emotional presence [...] when it comes to, like, emotional communication, I think we, like we are way stronger now, because I made it clear that I need her more here in the UK” (Emma).

In the two extracts above, Emma hinted to the importance of technology in coping with separation through which her family provided her with emotional support, yet the physical support is incomparable. Emma brought up a significant aspect of her own experience regarding students' need of family support when they are abroad, which she asked her sister for. This explains how the social support from family helped in improving family relationships (discussed in the earlier section). That is, the emotional family support that Algerian students received in the UK was an integral part of their coping process to the challenges they face abroad. This is because social support could be a coping mechanism that lessens the negative effects of stressors on wellbeing (Thoits, 2010).

Despite the geographical distance, families in Algeria could provide students in the UK with a virtual supportive family environment. In this respect, some students reported that they received much more support from their families when they left to study abroad. For instance, Emily said:

“I think the family support is stronger than before. In terms of maintaining the contact and the relationship between me and my family. But overall, I think the social support I'm getting now is more than before because as I told you earlier, I used to be with my family. So, there was that kind of support, but I didn't realize it until I came to the UK... but for the moment, I think the social support I'm getting from my family now is stronger than before because they know I'm here alone,

and I'm with strange people, and so they need to ask about me, to care about me” (Emily).

And Spencer reported a similar view:

“Their support is even stronger, because they are aware of you being away, and you have some challenges that you are facing. So, they are making sure to provide you with this kind of support, but it is just the feeling you have because... speaking about myself, again, not sharing with them every single detail or problems, and the challenges I'm facing, so you feel as if something is missing or there is something you are not getting support on specifically, but it is not because their support is affected, but maybe because you are away. but the level of support is always the same” (Spencer).

Just like Spencer, her sister shared a similar belief:

“Our support to her is much more now. We used to support her but now while she's there. We support her much more than we used to because she needs that support” (Spencer's sister).

The viewpoints of participants above that the family support has increased after students' departure to the UK contributed to showing the supportive nature of families in Algeria. The strong relationships between family members stand mainly for the exchanged social support between them (Thomas, Liu and Umberson, 2017), and this is why support, like family relationships, was taken for granted by Algerians. However, although being in different environments, the extensive emotional support that families in Algeria gave to students in the UK such as providing emotional care, advice and showing love (Thomas, Liu and Umberson, 2017), helped in strengthening the relationship between students and their families and made students aware of the value and importance of social support in the family and its connectedness. This finding is in harmony with the claim that social support is crucial for maintaining the social structure of family (Toyoshima and Nakahara, 2021).

On the other hand, other findings showed the opposite where few students believed that they received less support from their families during their journey in the UK. To elaborate on this point, Jane explained:

“I remember when I used to do my master's degree in Algeria, I was always surrounded by them. They were always there to support me. So, I did a lot better in my studies when I was in Algeria but when I came here and I was all alone, I didn't get the same support, because I don't even get to see them and talk to them that much at all. Well, they try to give me much support, but because they do not know what it is like to study here in the UK or doing a PhD, they do not know how to support me. So, they want to provide that kind of support, but they can't” (Jane).

It seems that family support, to Jane, is much more about the physical presence of the family members. The reason behind such belief could be the fact that taking doctoral research in the UK was the first experience for Jane to leave her family. That is, throughout her life course, Jane used to receive emotional and physical support from her family together. So, her emotional stability and wellbeing was associated with her being in her comfort zone. This was also reflected on her academic achievement when she was in Algeria. However, family's unawareness of research context in the UK along with their absence led Jane to feel the loss of her family support despite their attempts to. So, Jane here linked the emotional support of her family with the academic support she might get in her studies, yet both are significant in helping international students to cope with the challenges abroad. In this regard, Schartner (2015) emphasised the significance of academic and emotional support in overcoming the difficulties and the stress in study abroad contexts.

Josie reported almost a similar view yet in a very different way:

“When I talk, for example with my friend, she is also an Algerian PhD student. She gets it without me talking too much because she is going through the same thing. But with my mom, sometimes it is hard for me to explain to her. Like, what I am doing, how I write and then how I do my research and why is it hard for me” (Josie).

The personal account of the participant here distinguished the need to be supported academically in study from the social support of family. In agreement with Jane's attitude, Josie elaborated that effective academic support is derived from colleagues in the same study context which is not the case for students' families in Algeria. This type of support that Algerian students mutually give to each other is based on the common conditions that these students enjoy as Algerian students taking doctoral research in the UK. This is consistent with

what Brown (2009) found, in an ethnographic study she conducted in a British university, that international students rely on their friendships with their co-nationals to reduce their stress and loneliness abroad. In the same way, Schartner (2015) advised international students to collaborate with their co-nationals as a coping mechanism for their challenges abroad.

As for the familiar support, Josie demonstrated:

“In Algeria, when I'm going through rough time, I just stay with my mom and just hug her and stay with there and I feel better immediately. But here, it's not the same thing. I don't think there's anything they can do to make things better. Sometimes I just don't want to talk, but I want people surrounding me. And I think like when I'm going through really hard time, usually I don't want to talk much about it because it just makes me remember I am alone and then it stresses me out. Also, because I have to explain it to people and all of that. Especially like with my mom. So, I don't think it is about the number of calls with them, I just want to be there with them” (Josie).

The supportive nature of parents and family to their adult children especially in Algeria appeared several times throughout the data. One instance of that is what Josie mentioned in the extract above. Like many others, the family support the participants talked about here involved the physical comfort through gestures like hugs, notably with parents, which helps in reducing stress and fosters emotional wellbeing. This quite matches with what Tobin, Slatcher, and Robles (2013) asserted that supportive and encouraging parenting relationships decreases children's stress and results in better health outcomes. However, the absence of such comforting physical support in the UK made Josie believe that she received less support from her family despite the emotional support she virtually got through social media. This goes in line with what Silver (2011) claimed that getting separated from close members of the family, in migration contexts, may result in the breakdown of one's support system for both migrants and their families who are left behind.

There are other few mentions in data where students linked the family support they got in the UK with their needs to be physically involved with their families. The reason could be the impacting features of coming from a collectivist culture on the perceptions of social support by individuals, as they are more impacted by their need to be close to parents and extended family more than individualist ones as they have different assumptions of social ties and social

support. The absence of these supportive social relationships has profound impacts on students originated from collectivist societies (Sawir *et al.*, 2008), which is likely the case of Algerian students in this study.

It is worth noting that family members of these students above had an opposite mind. Family members confirmed the augmentation of their support to students in the context of their experience abroad. In this sense, Jane's sister pointed out:

“We stand by her and support her stronger now. Maybe when she was here around, we didn't give her that much and big social support. But now once she has gone, I assume we support her more” (Jane's sister).

Although she did not give many details, Jane's sister hinted to, in contrast to Jane, family's attempts to be a source for emotional support. In like manner, Josie's mother contrasted with her daughter:

“Our support to Josie has increased, for example, we support her in her studies. When the COVID pandemic hit, we were following the news about the number of infected cases and the death toll in the UK. We were supporting her. We gave her advice to decrease her fears and stress” (Josie's mother).

The excerpt above could come to be an instance for family support from families' angle in Algeria in mentioning how families tried to stand by their adult children during the COVID pandemic through giving advice. The type of support the participant is referring to here is emotional. Unlike her daughter, Josie's mother did not mention the physical support.

The fact that Josie's mother and Jane's sister were positive towards their support to Josie and Jane, who felt negative as receiving less support from their families, illustrates how different people can have different experiences from different angles of one thing. That is, what one person deem as negative can be positive for others. In the context of this study, some participants perceived family support as augmenting with separation, while others thought it decreased.

Another example of families supported their students with the UK was shared by Catherine's sister:

“We always support each other in the family. When Catherine was here, we were supporting her. But when she departed to the UK, we support her more. We have to support her much more than before. I would give you a simple example, for instance, sometimes she just calls me to do some paperwork for her, maybe scan some documents and send them to her. So, helping her this way is supporting her in a way. This is just a simple example” (Catherine’s sister).

Although it seems a simple act, Catherine’s sister deemed sending documents to her sister whenever needed to assist and support her. The reason behind this example could be that families in Algeria unable to help students in different issues because of geographical separation, which made them value this kind of basic help.

Another sister talked about another type of assistance that families could help and support students in:

“For example, my sister always when she wants to do new stuff, she talks to us. For example, when she wanted to move to a new apartment. She called us and she tells us here is the good stuff about the new house and the bad stuff, and we try to help her to get a decision” (Carol’s sister).

With this, Carol’s sister showed how families assisted their students in decision-making, which is considered by them as a kind of family support. The fact that Carol consulted her family about her life events and decisions in the UK could also be related to the collectivist background of society she belongs to. This is because, it is common for collectivist communities to place a strong emphasis on “We” rather than “I” to deal with different matters (de Mooij and Hofstede, 2010), which is the case here for Carol in this example. Moreover, in spite of her living in the UK by her own, the reason why Carol still functions with her Algerian principles could be the fact of her coming from a conservative community where most of families are patriarchal as most of the family decisions are taken by the father in Algeria (Berrezoug, 2021; Bouguesri and Nait-Brahim, 2021).

This section presented and discussed family social support from the perspectives of both students in the UK and their left-behind families in Algeria in the context of separation. Although most of participants agreed on the augmentation of emotional family support for students during their journey in the UK, few opposing views were revealed by students. Since

family support is closely related to family relationships, participants linked support with being physically and/or emotionally present and absent in the family. This essentially goes back to their conceptualizations of family separation.

8.6. Family separation and gender:

Although most of participants hinted to gender differences in the context of separation from family only few participants stressed this out with more emphasis. They linked the issue of gender in study abroad contexts with the socio-cultural norms of the Algerian society. The general populace in Algeria seemed to have an attitude that living away from the family would be much harder for females. Such a belief probably intensified families' stress towards their female adult children especially for parents.

When he was talking about the social support he gets from his family, Steven linked associated his view with the fact of him being a male student. He said:

“When I was in Algeria, I wasn't that much demanding of support. I mostly counted on myself and everything. I gave the support but when it comes to getting the support, I just do things on my own. Yeah. that was maybe because I am a guy, maybe, this situation would have been different for a girl because she would be sharing everything with her mum or sisters” (Steven).

The judgmental viewpoint explained by the participant above was also shared by other participants. The underlying reason for such a perspective could be the community's conception that females are more dependent to their families, and thus, need more support after departing abroad. Males, however, are perceived as independent and responsible which make their families less stressful about them.

Still with the male perspective with regards to gender issue, Jack supported this viewpoint by supposing his sister studying in the UK. He assumed:

“My mom wouldn't survive being away from her daughter for two years. I can assure you that. As I said before, it is because I had a medical condition when I was young that I used to the idea of being separated from my mom and my dad and they got used to the idea as well. But when it comes to my sister, she has lived with them for as long as I can remember. So, I think that if she was in the UK and she stayed

in the UK for two years without being able to travel back home I think that way my mom wouldn't have survived that” (Jack).

Accordingly, Jack here explained how the sociocultural conception regarding females would affect families and present a challenge for them in the context of separation. This supports why female students in this study got more impacted by being away from family (see section 7.3). Jack also drew attention to his experience of separation from family before his PhD journey, which according to him, reassured his parents and helped in minimizing their stress about him when he left to the UK. That is, it is not only difficult for families to be away only from their female offspring, but it is also the case with for males. However, by giving this example, Jack also emphasised the prevailing society’s perception that shaped a difference in favour of males over females (Berrezoug, 2021; Bouguesri and Nait-Brahim, 2021) resulted in emotional dependence of females to the collectivist family more than males. The latter is confirmed in data through the voice of Nancy’s brother. He explained his viewpoint by giving an example:

“Living away from family is very difficult for females. Alienation is very difficult for females. In my opinion, alienation is so hard for girls, whether they left their families for study, work or whatever the reason is. It is very hard for females to leave their families. [...] If I were in Nancy's place, I would have the same feelings of being away from my family. However, it would be slightly different, because she is a female, and I am a male. I can manage to forget that stress and alienation and keep myself busy to forget about those feelings. I might even think of staying abroad. Whereas, if you ask Nancy whether she will come back to Algeria or stay in the UK, she will definitely choose to come back” (Nancy’s brother).

Still with gender inequalities in the Algerian society, Nancy’s brother supported the populace attitude that alienation is much harder for females due to their excessive emotional attachment to family, which makes their adjustment process much more difficult. He justified his opinion by the decision he would make if he ever got the chance to study abroad. This view is quite common among the Algerian social groups and confirmed by Belhoucine (2022) who found out that adults in Algeria, to escape the country's problems with cohesion and integration,

tend to support leaving abroad and have positive attitudes towards Algerians, including students, who already did.

From a parent point of view, Clover's mother perception in relation to gender in study abroad setting confirms Jack's example in a way. she commented on this subject:

"Because she is a female not a male, you should fear more. You would be frightened more for a female and how she can manage to live alone"
(Clover's mother).

And the father's opinion:

"I assume all parents get stressed and concerned about females more than they do about males. For males, they would just say it is a male and he can manage to be by his own in a way" (Emily's father).

Based on the perspectives of the two parents mentioned above, it appears that the sociocultural beliefs in Algeria regarding gender disparities make men to be viewed as superior to women. This is confirmed by Ghiat (2019) who asserted that gender separation is frequently observed in the Algerian society where females are greatly impacted by this cultural norm. Participants here implied that male students can cope with studying in the UK away from their families more than what female students can perform. This resulted in the belief that living alone is much harder for females, and this is why families expressed their stress for them more than they do for male students.

An illustrative instance of gender conception in Algeria is in Jane's story when she first got the scholarship to study in the UK:

"I am very close to my mother. She is very open-minded. The issue was a little bit with my dad, although he was very good with me, but he was kind of doubtful about sending me to study alone here because a woman usually in my community or in my family does not leave home or stay far. That is one of the aspects of being conservative. So, it was hard for him to accept me going independently and studying in completely different country. Also, because I am a girl... single and wearing the scarf and going into a completely foreign, non-Muslim country.... that was also hard for him, because he felt that I might get affected by the community here and understand the freedom in the wrong way" (Jane).

The personal account of Jane here continues to elaborate on females in the Algerian society. The reason behind Jane's father hesitation to permit her to study in the UK was mainly a matter of culture, religion, and society norms. This is due to the fact that women, in conservative Islamic communities are restricted in terms of mobility and social interactions with people outside (McIntosh and Islam, 2010). So, it could be that the father feared his daughter would abandon her morals in the UK. On the other hand, it was impossible for Jane to depart to the UK without her father's permission (as she described above the issue). This is because, in addition to the patriarchal nature of families in Algeria, the parent-child relationship is regarded as one of the most important relationships on religious and cultural basis, which stands for not only respect and obedience to parents, but children also cannot make decisions about their personal lives without their parents' approval especially the father (Berrezoug, 2021). Jane's story here could serve as an example that might give a hint of some families' reaction to the scholarship before students' departure to the UK, yet it was not the case for all students. On this matter, Emma's sister mentioned:

“It was her own choice. She won the scholarship. She did not take permission. Permission was already granted for her... like you do what you want to do. She just shared the idea that she wants to study abroad. So, the family, like, accepted it and supported her decision” (Emma's sister).

The participant here implied the family's support to Emma in her decision to study in the UK without any objection or hesitation. Such a positive attitude towards females' studies abroad was mainly resulted from changes in the family structure in Algeria where families accepted the education of females and their participation in the workplace, became more open to modern ways of life and gave the right to family members to decide upon their lives (Bouguesri and Nait-Brahim, 2021). Emma's sister then added:

“Unlike some families here where women do not work but just marry and be a housewife” (Emma's sister).

Gender inequality is still apparent in the Algerian society despite the change in family structure and the progress in females' education. The reason behind such an objection to working women is mainly due to the socio-Islamic culture that restricts women interactions with stranger men (Ghiat 2019; McIntosh and Islam, 2010).

Another case that clearly brought up the subject of gender is that of Josie's mother. She articulated:

“Honestly, whether for a female or a male, allowing your child to go and live away from you is not easy at all. You can only understand how hard it is when you pass through it” (Josie's mother).

It seems that separation of family members of both genders is still so impactful for Algerian families. Although it was a female student who left the family to the UK in the case of the participant above, but Josie's mother gave an inclusive attitude towards the experience in general. She might have expressed herself according to her maternal instinct.

She then went on to say:

“Since 2000, what we notice in our society males are not successful in their studies like females. It became infrequent to see males pursuing their postgraduate studies like a PhD degree. This is in real life. Females do succeed more in study” (Josie's mother).

The phenomenon observed by the participant here in the Algerian social community is confirmed by Bouguesri and Nait-Brahim (2021) and Khammar and Dekoumi (2022) who admitted a relative increase of females' access to higher education and getting job opportunities. Ouadah-Bedidi (2018) claimed that female students' success in higher education is because of their higher academic achievement, which led to their desire to further their education, and as a result, they are less likely to be deterred by arguments that would prevent them from doing so. This justifies the dominance of female Algerian PhD students in this study as most of the students who got the scholarship were female.

This section highlighted the participants' beliefs about gender inequalities in relation to the experiences of Algerian students taking doctoral research in the UK. Interestingly, the community's perspective that was shared by all participants who brought up this subject, but one, was in favour of females, claiming that left-behind families fear for females as alienated members more than males. This is due to socio-cultural conceptions of the Algerian society.

8.7. Missing a family member VS missing a family:

Earlier in this chapter, I presented how participants perceived family separation. Although participants were from different angles of the experience, families in Algeria that

missed only one member and alienated students in the UK who missed the whole family, they had almost similar understandings of separation, yet in very different ways (see section 7.2). That is, participants' perceptions of separation were given from two different contexts; families in Algeria that missed only one member and alienated students in the UK who missed the whole family. This section, therefore, discusses how participants addressed this issue and how they emphasised their views regarding the difference between the two cases: missing a whole family and missing just one member of the family.

One participant emphasised why this section is important in this study. She said:

“Well, the idea of angles is very important in this context, I guess. You know, to get a clear understanding of any topic, you need to see it from different angles so that you get the full vision and the full picture... Previously, when I see parents do not allow their children to study abroad, I think they are wrong, and I see it from students' angle who wanted to achieve their ambition and study abroad. However, when I experienced separation from my daughter after she departed to the UK, I started to understand other parents' views of not allowing their children to go abroad. I felt their feelings and I understood their visions” (Josie's mother).

This view strongly supports the argument behind this study about the experiences of students in the UK and the left-behind families in Algeria in the separation context. Josie's mother here revealed a sense of awareness when she started to understand the experience of separation in depth from within after her daughter's departure, as she was not knowledgeable of the experience particulars before getting through it. Through hinting to the parents' right to permit their children to study abroad, the participant stressed out how difficult this separation is for parents among the left-behind family members.

After agreeing that separation is very much stressful for families who are still in Algeria as well as for students who departed to the UK, several participants, notably, shared similar attitudes in favour of students as being the most impacted part of the experience dealt with in this study. Most of the participants who supported this claim based their understandings on the fact that family members in Algeria still have each other in contrast with students who have no family member with them. To illustrate, some participants articulated the following:

“It is not easy at all. I know she has friends there, but it is not like having someone of your own flesh and blood. You got me... There is no family sense” (Spencer’s sister).

And:

“It is much harder for the absent member of the family. The absent member misses the family more and misses the country. He misses everything. Yeah, I guess students there in the UK miss their families and Algeria more” (Clover’s mother).

And:

“When we compare between the individuals who stayed in the family house here in Algeria and Nancy alone. Of course, we are affected by this, but she is in El Ghorba (alienation).it is alienation. she is affected more than we do. She is alone but we are still together here, only one member who is missed... It is much harder for the member who leaves the family, and it is so hard for him/her to adapt to the situation.” (Nancy’s brother).

Like most of the participants, the family members above have directly expressed their beliefs that missing the whole family, which is the case of students, is much harder than missing just one member of the family. Although these participants reported that students in the UK are completely alone and have no one, which Nancy’s brother described here “El Ghorba”, the Algerian word to refer to alienation (See chapter 5), two points were successively used by Spencer’s sister and Clover’s mother to summarize and justify this belief. The first is concerned with missing the family sense at the micro level. That is, the family atmosphere at micro level that family members enjoy together in events and celebrations cannot be found by students in the UK despite of having friends to share with. The second, however, is concerned with the features of the Algerian society, at the macro level, that students grew up in.

In contrast with male students, most of females appeared to give priority to themselves as alienated members who miss the whole family to represent the most difficult part of this experience. In this sense, Anne, amongst others, stated:

“Because the family when they miss you, for instance, they are together like they find each other, it is not like when you are missing them. You are alone, like, it is more painful” (Anne).

And Jane:

“It is specifically severe and difficult for parents, and in my case, my twin sister. But of course, it is actually... much more stressful for me” (Jane).

This belief was held by many female students. They appeared to give praise to the family connectedness which made them emphasise their need to this family togetherness and which they lack to in the UK in comparison with their families who remain at home. This might be because of the negative impacts the socio-cultural background these females were brought up in and the kind of socialisation they received back home had on them, which resulted in a great level of females' dependence to family (Ghiat 2019). It is for that reason why Algerian females could not develop a full sense of autonomy and appeared to have been impacted by separation from their families and reflected that missing the whole family as much harder than missing only one specific member of the family.

Data also contained one notable viewpoint in which one participant equated between the two cases:

“For me, both cases of separation are very stressful and so hard to deal with. It is very difficult for the family here with the absence of Ashley, also it is very difficult and stressful for Ashley to stay alone away from the family. They are equal. I cannot say that one is easier or harder than the other” (Ashley’s brother).

Ashley’s brother, who is still with his family in Algeria, believes in the stressfulness and difficulty of separation in all cases. That is, what matters for the participant here is the togetherness of family members, rather than the number of absent and missed members. This is because, the common feature between the family who missed only Ashley and Ashley who missed the whole family is togetherness and attachment. Such a belief might be based on the fact of having one and only sister (see section 5.6.5.).

There was a distinctive view where three participants, chiefly Gill, Jack and Steven in contrast with others, believed that their families might get impacted by separation more than these students themselves based on their experiences. Gill for instance expressed:

“It is really both ways, because when... during Eid or during any traditional or religious celebration, I can see it especially in Ramadan, you know. We are a small family, and my mom does not fast because she's sick. So, it's just my father and my sister fasting and sitting in the table. It's very sad for them and it's very sad for me as well like I'm sick maybe I'm not alone because during Ramadan, I asked my Saudi and Moroccan friends to do it like a gathering, it started together. So, I'm not alone but they are alone so it's hard for both of us” (Gill).

Through the example she gave, Gill illustrated how getting involved in the Muslim Arab community, perhaps as a second family, hearten her sense of belonging and slightly compensated for her feelings of detachment. This finding matches with Sinanan and Gomes' (2020) outcome that friends almost played the role of immediate family for international students, in their qualitative study that explored how international students invest in making relationships with other international students based on common experiences in the places where they live and study in Australia and Singapore. She, however, noticed the opposite with her family. Gill's vision here was formed on the basis of one of the main stressors that both her family and she came across in this experience. Another reason why the participant used Ramadan to clarify her view is the familiar nature of celebrating Ramadan in the Algerian society, which represented a stressing factor from both angles; students alone in the UK and families in Algeria, and thus allowed Gill to value the significance of family members' existence together and claim it to be stressful for students as it would be for their families.

“So, for example, during the Eid or during religious celebrations, I can see like while having a video chat with them, I can see that there is something missing with them, they are not really happy because I'm not there. But on the other hand, I'm really excited about being in the UK. So, I feel guilty that I am the reason why they are not really happy” (Jack).

Jack and Steven had similar opinions which they explained differently:

“I would say a family misses a member is the hardest. Although, being with a family is kind of... they support one another. It is not like when I am here on my own. Yeah... but I was living in that house, and everything in that house reminds them of me. So, for that factor, I would say, it's bad because in every corner of the house, my mom would say... okay, that is... Steven used to sit there. We used to do this. We used to do that. Whenever they are sitting together, they said... Okay, well, Steven used to eat this, and I wish he was here and my mother... she was telling me this in multiple occasions” (Steven).

Jack portrayed the case of Algerian families who remain at home as a full picture with a missing piece, for which he felt sorry when seeing the impact of his absence on his family. A better representation of the missing piece in the family picture was given by Steven who tended to list aspects of daily life that might seem normal but left a mark in his family and can give a better representation of the missing piece in the family picture. In Steven's case, the reason might be because he is the sole boy in the family (see section 5.6.5). The reason why these male students thought their family got more impacted by their absence than themselves would be their ability to cope with the host society and to integrate with the British culture as males (see section 7.6). That is, male students seemed to have done many efforts of socialisation in the host community which reduced their feelings of loneliness and missing family, and thus, they tipped the scale towards a family missing a member to be more difficult in this context of study. This goes back to the socio-cultural background they grew up in and received more independence than females which Ghia (2019) referred to as a males' society.

The notion of family separation in this study was addressed based on the experiences of Algerian students in the UK and their left-behind families in Algeria. This section discussed participants' views regarding the two angles through which family separation was viewed in this study. The aim behind this section was to shed light on the difference between family as connected unity that misses only one member, and how the latter misses the whole family. Although participants revealed conflicting views regarding which case is more difficult, the importance of family togetherness was emphasised by all participants. This is because, connectedness between families and their children represents one of the basics in collectivist societies like Algeria (Dwairy and Achoui, 2010).

8.8. Chapter summary:

Addressing the third aim of the study, this chapter presented and discussed findings in relation to the perceptions of family separation in the context of Algerian doctoral students in the UK whose families remain at home and its impact on them. The findings demonstrated the extent to which the nature of families in Algeria influenced the study in the UK experience. The results revealed conflicting views of both students and family members on several points such as depicting this experience as a separation of family, and whether the latter has positively and/ or negatively affected family relations and support. Participants highlighted how separation affected their mental health. They also shed light on the role of gender in this experience. Participants mentioned how difficult it is to miss the whole family and to miss just one member of the family and differentiated between them. Participants' attitudes of these family-related aspects were mostly affected by their socio-cultural background of the Algerian society.

Chapter Nine: Coping strategies Algerian students and their families use to cope with family separation and social stress

9.1. Introduction:

Social stress and *family separation* are crucial elements in this research, as both are experienced by the research participants of the study. This chapter presents and discusses findings in relation to the strategies Algerian PhD students in the UK and their families back home used to cope with separation and stress. This addresses the fourth aim of the research. Both Algerian students and family members mentioned that the need to cope with stress in the context of separation was crucial to adapt to this experience. This is because “coping is typically viewed as a response to existing stressors or negative events” (Allen, and Leary, 2010, p.114). Participants presented different strategies that they used and still use to cope with the stress of separation from the perspective of family members, and from separation and study for students. Participants pointed out to their use of social media and reliance on religion and emotions, to cope with separation and stress. This chapter explores the coping strategies participants used to cope with stress and separation as follows: religious coping, emotional coping, avoidance coping, positive thinking and using social media.

9.2. Religious coping:

This type of coping essentially stands up on individuals' religious beliefs, practices, and relationships (Abu-Raiya, and Pargament, 2015). Interviews analysis revealed that all participants (whether a student or a family member) are conscious of the importance of religion, chiefly Islam for Algerians, to cope with stress. Even their strategies seemed to be similar and dependent on the principles of the Islamic religion. This agrees with what has been stated in the literature that “when confronted with a stressor, Muslims will consider religion a resource in managing their distress” (Adam, and Ward, 2016, p.6). They all share a conviction of how the Islamic religion greatly helps individuals to overcome stress and its effect on the individual's mental health, mainly through having faith in Allah, praying, reading Quran and patience. Allah is the Islamic Arabic word that Islam and Muslims use to refer to the one and only god to whom they pray on daily basis (Pieper, van Uden, and van der Valk, 2018). Most of the research participants tackled these points in their talk about how Islamic religion functions as a coping strategy for them to deal with stress. Thus, this section is supported by data extracts that are most representative of the findings from all the participants in this research

with regards to religious coping. Findings from the students' interview data and family members' interview data will be presented and discussed respectively in this section.

Gill introduced her religiosity as follows:

“I have faith, and I have a very strong religious belief that... what I mean is God knows everything and knows what the best for us and that is it” (Gill).

Gill asserted above that having faith in Allah gives the feeling of reassurance and satisfaction to the individual that trigger him to rely on Allah and trust the choices of Allah.

Lisa presented her vision of faith and destiny as follows:

“To be honest, since I'm like a Muslim girl, we as Muslims, we believe that everything that happens is with the will of God, and we have no control over anything. So, everything is like in the hands of God. I mean because he knows what is best for us. So, I do not really tend to worry much because I am a believer that everything has like every, for every problem, there is a solution eventually” (Lisa).

Lisa emphasized her reliance on religion as a primary strategy to cope with stress and expressed her belief in destiny in everything. This mode of religious coping “the belief in fate and destiny” brought up by Lisa prompts the feeling of reassurance in students that everything will go according to Allah's will, which help them to cope with their feelings of stress.

Lisa also brought up praying as an effective religious practice to cope with stress and minimize its effects on her mental health. She stated:

“Mainly prayers. Yeah, prayers and like, your connection with your God. So, because when you pray you relieve yourself from all the burdens of life, you forget everything” (Lisa).

Lisa emphasized praying as a main religious practice to maintain one's relationship with God and to seek one's comfort. This is because, with reference to Muslims, “fulfilling their religious duty of prayer gives them inner calm and satisfaction” (Pieper, van Uden, and van der Valk, 2018, p.148).

Carol emphasized praying to deal with severe stress and stated:

“When it's too bad, I pray” (Carol).

Lucy also shared the same view:

“I pray, and I just feel that I need to get closer to God and just because only God can help me become the person I used to be or better than I used to be. So, renewing my faith, or let's say I look for kind of spiritual renewal” (Lucy).

Lucy above explained that she counts on praying to seek help from Allah to become disciplined to her commitments as she used to be. This is because Lucy mentioned in another point of the interview that she used to be a very committed person when she was in Algeria. Lucy also indicated that strengthening faith and empowering the relationship with Allah through praying lead to refine individuals.

Another way through which religion (Islam) is significant to the Algerian students is represented along the following lines represented by Nancy, among others, as she spoke about her experience of using religion to cope with stress:

“I think the most important thing I didn't mention, for me as a Muslim, the thing that's a source of comfort is praying and reading Quran, the Holy Scripture. So that's what I think, I think I should have special meaning I mentioned this fact, early on from the beginning, because I think this the main reason why I'm still fighting, why I'm still trying, why I didn't give up, why I didn't say it's over. Because spiritual care, you know, care is self-care is very, very important for me, for us as Muslims and for me, particularly because I try to try to seek refuge I would say in my prayers, and in the reading of Quran, in learning about the religion and in engaging myself in different religious activities. That is something that I would say, it is the first factor that helps me to deal with my stress. Stress is there, but that kind of increased spirituality really outweighed that stress to a certain extent, to the point that I feel at peace, I'm stressed by feel at peace, like, I know, stress is there, it didn't go, but I feel at peace, because of the time I spent practising my worship and practising religion” (Nancy).

Nancy mentioned her own way of religious coping and talked about the religious behaviours she opted for to cope with her stress while she is in the UK. At first, the participant emphasized religion as a primary and crucial source to seek comfort and satisfaction for her as an Algerian Muslim girl who is taking a PhD in the UK away from her family, and for her other colleagues and Muslims in general. Nancy listed some religious practices and behaviours that she uses to cope with her stress and through which Muslims maintain a good relationship with Allah, such as praying, reading Quran, and learning about the Islam. She also highlighted that these religious behaviours greatly assisted her to reduce her stress, to reach satisfaction and comfort, and prevented her from giving up to her challenges in the UK. Religious behaviours (prayers and reading Quran) are considered as an effective means to deal and cope with stress. This finding is propped up with previous literature in research which claimed that adhering to religious behaviours increases the individuals' feelings of satisfaction with their lives (Adam and Ward, 2016).

Emma also pointed out to her use of the Quran to deal with her spirit-mindedness seeking for inner peace:

“When I want to deal with my spirituality, I would listen to the Quran” (Emma).

Students' families in Algeria also emphasized religion as a strategy to cope with stress and separation. Family members revealed their awareness of the importance of religious practices to seek peace for themselves as well as for their students in the UK. For instance, one mother said:

“Having trust in Allah reassures me. I depend on my religion and patience to cope with this separation. I always pray for her [...] I always ask my children to keep faith in Allah and keep to their prayers on time. Prayer connects us to Allah and give us reassurance to overcome stress and fear feelings” (Josie's mother).

Josie's mother above draw attention to the importance of having faith and maintaining the relationship with Allah. She expressed that she relies on religious practices like praying and patience to cope with her stress and fear for her daughter in the UK. The participant also indicated her advice to her daughter and other children to maintain their faith and prayers. This implies to the importance of prayers in religion, which is considered as one of the five pillars of Islam, for Muslims to maintain a good relationship with Allah. This is because “worshipping God in the salah prayer constitutes the second pillar of Islam. In this prayer, the believer

surrenders to God” (Pieper, van Uden, and van der Valk, 2018, p.147). The word *salah*, here denotes the Islamic Arabic word for prayer.

Similarly, Clover’s mother, shared her advice to her daughter when she was about to start the PhD journey abroad:

“When she was first departing to the UK, I gave her the Quran and her praying mat, and I asked her to keep to her prayers and read the Quran” (Clover’s mother).

The fact of giving the praying mat and the holy book of the Quran to Clover showed the mother’s emphasis on religious practices of praying and reading the Quran and their significance in the daily life of Algerians.

Then, Clover’s mother went on with her advice:

“I always ask her to read Quran when I see her stressed, you know, reading Quran is very reassuring and stress-relieving” (Clover’s mother).

Like Josie’s mother and other students, Clover’s mother shed light on the significance of reading the Quran in seeking comfort and reassurance and decreasing stress. She also referred to her advice to Clover to do so to cope with her stress. Participants, emphasis on praying and reading Quran matches with the claim that prayers and Quran recitation are religious practices that Muslims consider as strong means to use in coping with difficulties and challenges (Adam and Ward, 2016).

Then, she added:

“I always pray for her actually” (Clover’s mother).

Here, Clover’s mother introduced “Dua”, which signifies praying for someone, as a strategy that family members use to cope with the separation of students. She voiced her constant praying for her daughter. This results in a reassuring feeling that help families to cope with separation.

Emma’s sister also shared:

“I always pray for her. Like, all the time when I pray, when I am sitting down, when I just see her picture, I pray for her. My mom ... the same...

my mom, like every time when she prays like she is the centre of her prayers, especially when she's not around” (Emma’s sister).

These few lines of data demonstrate how Emma is always recalled in her sister and mother’s daily prayers while she is in the UK. As Muslims, Algerians are required to pray five times a day on daily basis, and this is what Emma’s sister explained by “*when I pray*” (Emma’s sister). “Five times a day, many Muslims worldwide pray this obligatory ritual prayer on five fixed daily points in time” (Pieper, van Uden, and van der Valk, 2018, p.147). However, by the expression “*I always pray for*” (Emma’s sister), which denotes praying for someone, Emma’s sister referred to reciting Dua for Emma to have good health, to be safe and to succeed. Emma’s sister also pointed out to the fact that coming across Emma’s pictures in the house brings her up to her memory and made her recite Dua for her. The fact that participants highly depend on prayers and Dua to cope with separation indicates their religiosity and trust in Allah’s will and how they seek help from Allah.

Emma’s sister also added:

“I always when I talk to her... like my mom always keeps asking her, did you pray today? She is sometimes scared of her, like, indulging in life while she forgets her religious side. So, always like when we are talking... Did you pray today? Sometimes when I talk to her, like, I like to read stories about prophets. So, every time when I talk to her, I just keep telling her a story, new story I read today like about this prophet. I know that she will never forget her religious side, but I just always like to remind her of that side” (Emma’s sister).

The participant explained how the family, mainly Emma’s sister and her mother, advise Emma to maintain her religiosity and to keep faith in Islam through emphasising on prayer and reminding her of it. Emma’s sister brought up a new strategy by which she could implicitly advise her sister, Emma, to maintain a good relationship with religion the Islam. This is learning from the prophets’ stories to learn about religious values that assist individuals to deal with struggles and challenges, like patience and trusting Allah’s will which help them to cope with separation. This is congruent with Aflakseir and Coleman (2011) who noted that Islamic teachings motivate Muslims to rely on religious practices like praying, fasting, and reading Quran to deal with stressful events.

This section presented how religious coping is a strategy to overcome first, the stress resulted from family separation of Algerian students in the UK and their families in Algeria, and second the stress of taking a PhD in the UK for Algerian students. The data excerpts presented have revealed the common beliefs of participants about the undeniable importance of religion in coping with stressful life events like family separation. This was essentially displayed by participants through listing some religious practices like praying to seek Allah's help, reciting Dua, reading Quran to seek comfort and trusting Allah's choices by showing patience. This is in accordance with what Aflakseir and Coleman (2011, p.46) elaborated that "there is an emphasis within Islamic literature on religious beliefs and practices being used as resources for dealing with life difficulties. Islamic teachings encourage people to be patient, to perform prayer, and trusting and turning to God in times of need and for guidance".

9.3. Emotional coping:

This pattern of coping revolves around focusing on emotions as a method of coping. Emotions play an important role in participants' perceptions of family separation (see chapter 7). The data generated from the participants showed their awareness of the impact of separation on their emotions and mental health. This urged them to develop strategies to control their feelings of separation. This is consistent with emotion-focused coping introduced by Folkman and Lazarus (1980) referring to the strategies individuals use to regulate the stressful emotions resulted from the stressful situations they encounter that need to be accepted rather than changed.

Participants were aware of how separation emotions affected them and tried to respond to them appropriately to minimize the negative impact of separation stress on their health. Their strategies were mainly centred around remotely sharing moments together via social media and providing support to each other. This section discusses emotional coping in the context of the stress resulted from the separation of Algerian students and their families.

Clover mentioned that she managed to cope with family separation after 3 years of PhD journey in the UK. Then, she explained:

"It was not also as bad as I had expected. Okay, like I could manage. I could live alone. I realized that I'm not very much emotionally attached to my family. I love it. But I'm not that very much... because I've seen people like they are extremely attached to their families that they hated the fact they were in the UK. And you know, one girl, it was in

Canterbury, she was... I mean, the UK is nice come on. So, because she is attached to her family, and it is the first time for her to travel abroad by the way. Despite like being the UK in Canterbury. Like I was wowed by the beauty of the city centre, like how it is small home, no cars are there and everything. And she was like, Oh, it's horrible. I want to go back home. Like, she kept in that in that bad, bad mood. Like for four months. And every single month she posts on Facebook, one month is gone. Still Three, two months are gone, still two. So, you know, no, I'm not judging her. I'm not saying what is that? But just like comparing myself with her? No, I can live alone. Like away from my family. Yeah, I mean, something it was doable for me” (Clover).

Clover reflected that she managed to cope with separation from her family. At the beginning of her journey abroad, she was amused by discovering the new place and environment. Her enthusiasm of the new experience helped her decreasing the feeling of separation. To illustrate how well she has coped with being separated with her family, Clover made a comparison between herself and a friend of hers. While Clover expressed her enjoyment with the new experience of being in the UK for the first time, her friend seemed to be highly affected by family separation and was counting days to join her family. The fact that Clover realized she did well in coping with separation by trying to enjoy the new experience when she compared herself to her friend denotes her understanding of the separation experience that the study abroad journey entails which helped her to gradually control her emotions and manage her stress. This agrees with the claim that “students who are systematic in coping and have an understanding of the cause of their emotion may have more success in their attempts to resolve their personal problems” (Akhtar and Kroener-Herwig, 2019, p.624). That is, coping with emotions resulted from separation differs across students and depends on their awareness of the reasons behind these emotions. Therefore, students should understand what they are struggling with and accept it before attempting to solve it.

Although she expressed her well performance in coping with separation, clover voiced that the stress of separation and homesickness sometimes control her as follows:

“I cry whenever I feel homesick, because this is how I express my anger, I release let's say, my anger, my stress, all the bad emotion. If I go into that emotion, the best thing to sort it out and just like release it in the

nicest way ever, is through crying. I cry if I felt stressed. So, nothing in terms of the family when I feel homesick because I talk to them, I will just like send them messages like mom, I love you, man enough for me. So, for example, I missed you or I send them my pictures. If I go outside, I was shooting everything, I just like send pictures like here I'm 90% of the time when I see those pictures attached to my father. He was like, right away, call me. And they got so happy. [...] Sometimes when I was on call them just like maybe crying a few tears” (Clover).

Clover shows above a feeling of homesickness as an undeniable fact of family separation and described it as bad emotion. She presented crying as the best strategy to externalise the negative energy and bad emotions resulted from homesickness and the stress of family separation. Additionally, Clover presented sharing her updates with her family through sending them pictures to show them how she is enjoying her time and discovering new things. Her family, from their part, asks her for video calls to see the environment of the host country and remotely live the new experience with her.

Likewise, Steven shared the following:

“In fact, last summer, I went back to Algeria. I got them all new passports and I was planning to bring them to the UK at least for a two weeks period or something, just for them to enjoy London or to enjoy the place where I am living here now... my sister, but none of that went according to plan because of COVID and so yeah... yeah, I do think about myself... but also think about my family when it comes to new experiences in life, which I want to share with them and when there is something that needs to be shared with them” (Steven).

Steven above illustrated how he is emotionally counting on his family while he is being in the UK. He explained that he had plans to bring his family to visit the UK but due to the COVID pandemic he was not able to do that. Steven also showed how he is thinking about his family in every new experience that worth sharing with them.

Then, Steven stated:

“If I were to stay here for the rest of my life, I would be more integrated in the Algerian community, or at least the Arab or Muslim community

who are living in the UK and that's a game changer I think... Yeah... I would not find difficulties into integrating to that kind of group, then when integrating to white, Christian, other kinds of groups, which may not have the same values as I do” (Steven).

Steven highlighted some important points that would help him to emotionally cope with living abroad. He emphasised that being in a community that shares the same values, ethnicity and religion would create a supportive atmosphere for coping when living abroad. He clarified that adapting to a community with different religion and culture encompasses several challenges. Illustrating by himself, Steven pointed out that the more individuals live abroad, the more they need to integrate with communities with whom they have shared beliefs and values to cope with feelings of foreignness.

Some female participants reported that they seek for emotional support from their closest family members to cope with stress and separation. For instance,

“All my family members are supportive. So, some, if I talk to anyone, they will be supportive but usually the one person that I talk everything to is my twin sister, or my mother. My twin sister, mostly, I think, because she is in the same age, she understands me. So, I can tell her everything without worrying. If I'm going to share something, I would have shared things with her” (Jane).

Here, Jane indicated that she mainly seeks support from her mother and twin sister. He presented her twin sister as the main source from which she gets emotional support. Due to the biological nature of being twins, Jane's twin sister understands and feels her more than other family members. As being twins, understanding and support were reciprocal between Jane and her sister. This made Jane share her experiences and stresses with her twin sister more than others and made the twin sister support Jane more than other family members.

In accordance with this view, Emily shared:

“I share my stresses and experiences with my sister because, as I told you, two of my sisters and one brother are married and I don't contact them always. That's why I used to call my home my either my father, my mother or my sister” (Emily).

Emily explained that she shares her life in the UK with her unmarried sister as she has daily contact with her along with her parents. As they have their own responsibilities and commitments, Emily does not contact her married sisters and brother as she does with the members in her family house. That is, maintaining contact with family members on daily basis allows Emily to share more experiences with them and receive more support.

Catherine also described how she shares her life in the UK with her family. She acknowledged:

“Most of the time I call my family and let them on the phone while I am and doing my stuff. So, I just stay connected to feel that I'm connected to them. Sometimes for example, my sister calls me when I study, what we do is she cooks or something and I study and we let the phone on hold, and you know what, when I leave the call connected with my family and hear their voices, I feel motivated, and I feel more concentrated and more protective” (Catherine).

Catherine stated that she opted for long video calls with her family to share their daily activities together. She indicated that having the sense of family around, even remotely, reassured her and made her feel secure. This had a positive impact on her mood and reduced her stress, which was reflected on her mental health and motivated her to study. That is, this emotional presence of Catherine's family on social media acted as an emotional support for her and minimize her stress of being separated from them.

Gill also reported a similar view:

“I share everything because I told you I trust only them. I only trust my family members, my mom, dad and sister” (Gill).

And added:

“If I am studying at home, I told you I just keep the messenger or the video call there. We talk and then they go and they just... I just know observe what they are doing and while I am studying, so yeah, maybe all day” (Gill).

Gill referred to sharing her stresses and challenges with her family members. Like Catherine, Gill also acknowledged her use of long video calls with family while studying and doing household chores to feel as if she were at home with her family.

This finding presented by the participants above which is about sharing stress with families back home and seeking emotional support from them as a strategy to cope with stress and separation is discussed in literature about international students. This is because in a similar study conducted by Saravanan, Mohamad, and Alias (2019) examined the coping strategies that international students use to manage depression and homesickness in Malaysia, it was found that international students tend to share their problems with their parents and families through social media and receiving emotional support from them had a positive impact on reducing their feelings of homesickness.

Correspondingly, some other students articulated that they prefer to share their stresses and insecurities with other Algerian students in the UK who are passing through the same experience. For example, one participant said referring to how she deals with stress *“when it's manageable. I try to talk to my family or friends and colleagues”* (Carol). Furthermore, Lisa, Emma and Catherine agreed on the same view as the following data extracts show respectively:

“I can express my feelings, emotions, and stresses to my friends here. They will understand me more because we are in the same situation”
(Lisa).

And:

“I will talk to my friends who are here, about like certain situation that I may face because I know they are here and maybe they are facing the same problem” (Emma).

And Catherine:

“I was always calling my friends to come and stay with me. My friends here in the UK and sometimes what I do is, I cook traditional things, and I share it with them” (Catherine).

Students' views above showed that sharing stresses with friends from the same community of Algerian students taking PhD in the UK worked for them as a strategy to cope with stress. That is, even if they do not share the same exact problems, but they do share the

same experience of studying abroad away from their family which gave them more chances to feel each other.

Carol also hinted to another strategy that worked for her to regulate her emotions and decrease her stress:

*“When it's constant during the week or the weekend, I usually like to go to the stock sanctuary when they give me a dog to take for a walk”
(Carol).*

Here, Carol introduced interacting with animals as another strategy to reduce stress of study and separation from family. This strategy would effectively work with students who love animals.

As for students' families, family members also revealed an awareness regarding the importance of dealing with the separation stress and emotions and the need to respond to them to decrease the negative effects of separation on their mental health. Family members almost shared similar views to those shared by students to emotionally cope with separation. They highlighted sharing experiences and occasions together via social media through which they support and encourage each other. For example, one brother stated about his sister:

“I would give her 8 out of ten for her coping to living in the UK. She managed to adapt to life there in the UK. She gradually did that because in her first year I would only give her 5 or 6 out of 10” (Nancy's brother).

Here, the brother indicated that his sister, Nancy, managed to adapt to live alone in the UK. However, this adaptation and coping was achieved gradually through time. Additionally, he also pointed out that the first year of separation was very difficult for Nancy. In another moment, he mentioned:

“We would prefer her to share everything with us, her stresses, her challenges, her experiences, at least we can emotionally support her. She is all alone there. She needs to have support more than other family members here” (Nancy's brother).

Nancy's brother expressed his view and the family's desire to know about the experiences that their daughter passes through in the UK. He noted that Nancy needs to have much support after she left to the UK especially when encountering challenges.

Ashley's brother talked about how his family shares their life with Ashley after she fled to the UK as follows:

“We share religious occasions and feasts... family gatherings with her through video calls. She remotely attends with us how we celebrate the feast and what we have prepared” (Ashley's brother).

And added:

“My mother daily talks with her and sends her pictures of our lunch, dinner and everything. My mother is always on a call with her [...] We share almost everything with her, updates of our family, neighbours, friends, everything” (Ashley's brother).

Ashley's brother above spoke about how his family sought to involve their daughter in their daily life events and special occasions that happened with them and with their relatives. He also highlighted the constant contact of his mother with Ashley. This makes Ashley feel more involved, as if she is present, in her family despite her distance, which works as emotional support for her.

Jane's twin sister talked about how Jane shared her experience in the UK with her along the following lines:

“Almost all nights, we talk, and we really share the stories, and she shares her day with me. But with my other sisters, like, once in a while she talks. She talks to my mother often, yes. But not with my father a lot. Maybe he is not here all the time [...] She shares everything with me. So, she tells me everything she does. Where she goes. She visits some places. She always comes to me and tells me about it. So, she shares everything with me. Like I said, because she's my twin, I feel like I had this experience. I really feel like as if we are both having this experience together” (Jane's sister).

Jane's sister shed light on the close relationship she has with her twin sister, Jane. The participant explained that she is the closest family member to Jane, with whom Jane shares her experiences, stresses, and challenges the most. She also pointed out:

“Yeah, it reflects on me too. I feel stressed as well and when she shares that stress with me. Of course, I don't let her know I am stressed too. I just try to comfort her and tell her that everything will be okay. And it breaks my heart that she's not here so I can give her a hug and, you know, just wipe her tears. But I always try to stay positive for her because I know she's there alone. And I'm here with the family” (Jane's sister).

Still with regulating emotions to cope with separation and stress, Jane's sister, in the extract above, acknowledged the impact of the stress and challenges Jane encounters in the UK on her. She mentioned that the only thing she can do for Jane is to support her emotionally and verbally. Jane's sister hinted to the lack of physical support that family member can provide to each other in the context of separation. This prompted Jane's sister to emotionally surround Jane with positive energy through providing her with positive thoughts and emotions. Like Nancy's brother earlier in this section, Jane's sister referred to the fact that students' families in Algeria still have each other while students in the UK have no family members with them, which makes them in need of more support.

This section discussed findings regarding emotional coping as a strategy to cope with the stress of taking a PhD in the UK for Algerian students, and with the stress of separation for students and their families back home. The data excerpts presented in this section revealed the participants' awareness of the importance of controlling emotions resulted from the challenging experiences to cope with stress and separation.

9.4. Avoidance coping:

This section presents and discusses the notion of avoidance as a coping strategy that was brought out by some participants. This finding is mainly presented by participants from the case of Algerian students taking PhD in the UK. Several Algerian students participating in this research demonstrated avoidance as strategy to cope with the stress they experience throughout their journey of taking a PhD in the UK away from their families and their home societies.

Nancy clearly introduced avoidance as a strategy to cope with stress and mentioned that she often depends on avoidance to cope with the stress of her being away from her family for almost two years. She voiced:

“I usually ignore stress, this is what I do, because I spent a period of almost two years now, hiding these things from my family, kind of internalising this inside myself that I no longer feel relaxed when I speak, you know, when I cope with stressors, because we have different coping strategies, among them, we have speaking to others speaking or speaking up out loud, so I ignore them. Now, basically, this is what I do, because I get used to not speaking about them. So, problem solving coping is another thing that I do, but not very much like avoidance one, because I feel like I reached the point where stress is part of my daily life, and I will function as if it doesn't exist, because it will be a waste of time for me to look around or to pay attention to this stress” (Nancy).

Nancy demonstrated that ignoring the reasons why she gets stressed and avoiding stress is the main strategy she uses to cope with her situation. With reference to family separation, Nancy stated that the fact of being away from her family for two years without sharing her stress of separation with her family was the stimulus for to opt for avoidance as a coping strategy, which led her to accept stress as an integral part of her journey in the UK. Nancy mentioned her preference of avoiding stress over attempting to solve the problem and address the stressors she faces. The finding that avoidance coping was plainly indicated by only one participant in this study goes in line with what has been found that avoidance coping is the least used coping strategy by international students in a study that examined perceived stress levels, health anxiety and coping styles in university students during the COVID-19 pandemic (Garbóczy et al., 2021).

Nancy also added:

“So, what's the point for me to spend time, just as the source of stress itself will not dissolve until overcome or get fixed or I would say get treated or dealt with until I came back to Algeria. So, I just ignore this is what I do ignore whether I try to do different things (...) But I don't want to address the problem, because now it's a problem that cannot be resolved” (Nancy).

Here, Nancy emphasised her coping through avoiding stress by not attempting to solve the problem resulted from the stressor she faces. This goes in line with the claim that “avoidance strategies are characterized by the absence of attempts to alter the situation” (Kausar, 2010, p.34).

Lucy shared a similar idea:

“I just feel that it is better to go outside and just sit in a park or in a garden, and just look at a lake or ducks in the water, smiling to people or looking at people passing by. Yeah, so just to forget about me, I am just being just being involved in nature” (Lucy).

Here, Lucy referred to her desire to escape from her difficulties and to ignore and forget about her stresses through immersing herself in nature. This helps in improving the individual’s relationship with nature and provides a peace of mind.

Likewise, Spencer mentioned:

“Now, I figured out like there are activities, that cannot help you to 100%, avoid the stress or overcome the stress but at least they decrease this feeling or decrease the burden of being stressed all the time” (Spencer).

And she kept on listing several activities that she sometimes does to keep herself away from the study-related stress that she has, such as going for a walk, to a park, or to the cinema, hang out with friends, discover new places, and then she concluded her talk by saying:

“Then. I am like, okay go back to study or whatever commitment you have” (Spencer).

Steven also introduced avoidance from a different angle, which is keeping oneself busy. He first articulated “*the coolest thing to move from one experience to another is to keep yourself busy*” (Steven), and then he added:

“So, the thing is to move off... the jump from one experience to another, to have your day plan and say, okay, today, I'm going to do this, do that, do that and once you do all those, you know, when you tick all the boxes in the day, then you wouldn't allow for, you know, that stress to sneak in and bring you down” (Steven).

Steven pointed out that keeping oneself busy through making good daily plans and striving to achieve them takes individuals out of the stress zone and prevent them from reflecting on stress. This result is in consistency with Saravanan, Mohamad, and Alias (2019), who found that international students tend to get themselves busy with different activities to refrain negative thoughts and feelings of missing family from controlling them while they are away from their families.

The data reported in this section presented findings regarding how Algerian PhD students in the UK used avoidance to cope with stress throughout their PhD journey in the context of family separation.

9.5. Positive thinking:

Positive thinking was a commonly held belief amongst participants that helped them to cope with separation. Data revealed participants' attempts to think positively to minimize the negative impacts of stress in the context of separation of Algerian students taking doctoral research in the UK who left their families in Algeria. On this matter, it has been proven in literature that there exists a connection that relates stress and positive thinking (Naseem and Khalid, 2010).

Participants' awareness of the positive influence of positive thinking on stress helped to cope with separation and its stress appropriately. This was shown in data through the participants' efforts to convince themselves with the bright side of the experience of taking PhD in the UK for Algerian students as well as their families back home. Participants' optimistic ideas they opted for to think positively were essentially centred around thoughts like focusing on the goals of this separation, convincing themselves of the temporary nature of separation to get the doctorate degree, relying on the fact that students are sponsored by the Algerian government. Accordingly, this section presents and discusses data regarding the influence of positive thinking on coping with stress and separation.

Positive thinking was referred to by participants many times throughout the interviews; for instance, Spencer said:

“I would try my best not to focus on like negative thoughts, I am here by myself, or I am away from my family, and as I mentioned, I try to do something else. First avoid thinking of it or bringing and recalling these negative thoughts. So, I just say, okay, it is an experience after all. There

is a day you will go back home, and you will miss this day in the UK. So, try to benefit from ... like, being in here. I would say that is it. So, just to reflect or try to do something I enjoy and avoid, like any negative thought. That would help” (Spencer).

Spencer here described how she sought not to let the negative feelings of separation control her by trying to transform her thinking into positive. She attempted to persuade herself by the temporary nature of this separation and she will eventually go home when she finishes her PhD and get her degree. Spencer also shed light on the importance of getting benefit from being in the UK and enjoying this experience.

Moreover, when talking about coping with being in the UK away from her family, Spencer rated herself and voiced:

“I would give it 70%. So, as I told you, I've never thought I can cope with such a feeling or with the fact of being away from my family or living away from my family. But when I get to this situation, I think I'm doing well” (Spencer).

This statement explains the expectation Spencer had before departing to the UK to start her PhD journey. The participant, after having almost 4 years in the UK (see sample dimension section), implicitly uttered that she gradually could manage to cope with living alone away from her family.

Similarly, Ashley mentioned the fact of temporary separation to alleviate her stress and her parents' stress in Algeria as well, as follows:

“I'm trying my best to cope with things, and I said, okay, I'm here just for a sense now it's almost two years and I'll be done. And when I tell that to my parents, I told them when they told me we miss you, when will you come, and sometimes I told them that okay, it's just a matter of time and I will be finished, and I will be there. Like I tried to give them somehow, to make them feel relieved. So, this is the only way how I can cope with things. I started giving them... it's not hope but it's a reality, like I will come I will travel, and you will see me” (Ashley).

The strategy that Ashley opted for to ease herself and her family in Algeria stands on the fact that her separation from her family is temporary for the sake of taking a PhD in the

UK. Despite that, Ashley's family were eager to see their daughter with them back home. What Ashley brought up here is her attempt to think positively and to spread that positivity among her family.

Emily was another participant who talked about study abroad in the UK as temporary as follows:

“It's all about convincing yourself that you are doing all of this for the benefit of your future to like, have a good career, good life. And all this is temporary, and everything will be as normal” (Emily).

Here, Emily acknowledged that her experience in the UK is temporary. She also focused on the target of this experience of getting the doctorate degree, to console herself. She used the future career as a motive for herself to move forward in her PhD journey and this would have had a positive impact on her mental health and reduced her stress of separation and homesickness.

Emily kept on with her talk in this way:

“The other point is that this chance is not granted or offered for everyone, especially in the hard situation, or life situation in Algeria, where most people are dreaming of being in Europe or other developed countries. So as an international student being in UK, like for only four years, so it's like biscuits, it shouldn't be that hard with, I mean, you must see the bright side of this experience. PhD abroad is only five or four years or less, and everything will be okay, and when you come back to Algeria, you will have a job. You will have a better situation. So, this is the ideas I'm trying to implement in my mind” (Emily).

Emily raised a very important detail about students who took part in this study. She stated that she is lucky to take her PhD in the UK as this is a dream for many people. This is because the PhD students in this study are sponsored by the Algerian government according to the agreement that the Ministry of Higher Education made with the UK (see context and background chapter). Furthermore, Emily affirmed that this experience is not permanent and her life with her family will be rekindled after finishing her PhD. Emily also shed light on securing a job position in the future as one of the positive motivating thoughts that she used to cope with her stress in the UK. This is because, as per the bursary sponsorship contract (2015),

students are required to work in Algerian universities when they come back home after finishing their doctoral research in the UK.

Still with thinking positively, Emma shared:

“I am comparing, just like to relax myself and to reduce my stress, like look to the first immigrants when they came here, and they found like difficult, so me complaining about not having that physical interaction... I find it like, kind of ridiculous... like just relax then, like you're in a better position than other people. Second thing is, like, I know like I might not be emotionally relaxed but at least like I am financially, socially relaxed. So, admit that, see the positive side of being here. Because if I focus on missing home, I think that would affect me in a negative way” (Emma).

Putting this into context, Emma was responding to a question on how she has managed to cope with the stress of being separated from her family. Ancient immigrants, as she justified, did not have social media and online means of contact to remotely see their families in their home countries and get emotional support from them, Emma felt herself lucky as being compared to immigrants in the past, and realized that she might be exaggerating in her stress of separation and claiming for physical support of her family, which is an integral part of the experience of study abroad. Emma, moreover, brought up the fact of being sponsored by the Algerian government and receiving her bursary from the Algerian government (Bursary Sponsorship Contract, 2015) as a preference for her in comparison with other international students who many of them are obliged to work to fund for themselves. These two advantages Emma is enjoying throughout her PhD journey in the UK acted as a stress-relief for her and helped her to maintain her positive thinking to cope with stress and console herself in moments of despair. This is referred to in research as positive cognitive restructuring which has been found as a coping strategy that self-compassionate people tend to use to cope with stressful events, where positive cognitive restructuring was explained by the individual's attempt to see the positive aspect of a stressful situation to minimize its negative outcomes, be optimistic and move towards positive thinking (Allen, and Leary, 2010).

Emma also mentioned other tips that she opted for to manage stress:

“Just recently, I started doing yoga and deep breath. But like, back in the days when I used to be just like stressed, I used to do self-talk a lot.

Like just thinking, for example, I will say, think Emma, nothing, it is like if you are stressed, or if you, you have an anxiety, then, there is no solution. So, I used to do self-talk, like, Emma... just concentrate, there is no solution, you can't go back. So, what is the point of me being stressful” (Emma).

Here, Emma continued her talk about coping with stress of study and separation. She emphasised on the need to accept and to acknowledge to the challenging situation of taking a PhD in the UK through talking to herself to convince herself with the reality she is in. In her statement, Emma articulated, in her self-motivation talks, that stress is not a solution for the challenge, yet it is an undeniable aspect of the experience. The participant also mentioned her use of yoga and deep breath in her moments of stress and to reduce her feelings of anxiety. This result is consistent with what has been found in the study that researched the application of yoga to reduce stress levels among students in an Indian context. It has been found that practising yoga helps individuals to make balance between their inner and outer worlds, strengthen their mental health to face and accept reality, and to be positive towards life experiences (Dubey, Sarva, and Singh, 2016).

Likewise, Rose mentioned:

“Some of the coping strategies is, for example, going to the gym, doing yoga. And, for example, when I wake up in the morning, and I start, I tried to do some work. And if I find that my mind is a bit cloudy, I'm not thinking. I'm not focusing. I start to reflect. So, reflecting, why do I think in this way, what makes me feel this way? And then when I know the reason, okay, then what should I do to improve my mood, for example, one of the strategies is let's go to the gym for 20 minutes or one hour. This is one strategy. If I miss my family, it's just yeah, call them. Talk to them” (Rose).

This extract of data reflects on the participant's attempts to be positive towards her stresses and challenges. Like Emma, Rose mentioned yoga and self-talk and reflection to reduce her stress. Rose, here, noted that self-reflection helped her to understand what she was struggling with and the reason behind it before attempting to solve it and overcome it. Rose tried to simplify her challenges, and then addressing them. Rose tried to listen to her feelings and respond to them appropriately in a positive way. She divided her stresses into small

challenges and attempted to solve them, such as calling family whenever missing them, doing yoga and going to the gym whenever she was unable to study.

According to Anne:

“I would say eight... I'm coping very well because it's like, sometimes, like you say, wake up, for instance, it's not a fairy tale. You need to rely on yourself. That's it. So sometimes I even write some stuff like to motivate myself, you need to rely on yourself, you need to focus on your studies. You don't need to care about anything else. Yeah, I'm trying to adapt” (Anne).

In her case, Anne mentioned that she used self-talks to motivate herself, however, she did not only opt for talks, but she also opted for writing her motivating thoughts to emphasise and embed them in her thinking.

Later, she added:

“Whenever I am upset, I go and talk to people. When I am upset, I go out, I have fun, and then like, I come back with a very, let's say, a new spirit, I become in a very good mood. So, I'm trying to help myself by myself” (Anne).

Anne implied here her attempts to regulate her mood and better her mental health through distracting her mind. She exemplified interaction with people as an effective way to refresh one's mind from her own experience and showed how she tried to help herself cope with stress by herself.

When asked about coping with family separation Nancy replied:

“I have accepted it and the thing that help me to just survive despite this absence of support is the fact that it's just temporary, we'll go back. So, I tried to convince myself in different ways, I will learn how to deal with stress by myself. I will learn how to keep my stresses silent as much as I can, so that I don't really pull myself into that cycle of speaking about problems and then getting more anxious about these problems. And then the problem is there, and you are inside the problem. So, for

me, it's better to go out and see the problem from a distance, but then live in the problem itself” (Nancy).

Nancy accepted family separation as an inseparable fact of study abroad experience. Nancy preferred to accept the fact that both separation from her family and absence of their support are just temporary during the journey of her PhD in the UK. She convinced herself to accept her problems as they are as part of the experience instead of making the whole experience revolves around the problems so that she can move on in her journey in the UK. In this regard, it has been said that “acceptance of the problem is very important in life, people have to accept their problems and take it as a challenge” (Baqtayan, 2015, p.486).

And then she elaborated:

“I don't want to overreact to stressors. I only react to stress when it's very high level because before I used to overreact even to low levels of stress because I know that someone is there for me to show me love and support, but now, I know that person doesn't exist. They are there. So, the option I like I have accepted the reality. I am here. I am by my own. My family is there. I will not send them anything that is going to make them concerned. I would only send them things that would make them feel comfortable. This is what I can say about family separation now” (Nancy).

And:

“It's something that I have to accept, and it is something that everybody else is going through. It is not just me. I had the chance to see a lot of international students who are coming from collectivist societies as well. So not to limit this to our own to only Algerian people. Chinese people are very collectivist, but they feel they've been homesick, they feel lonely, but you can see them like going after their goals and they are not really thinking that much about this homesickness, because it is part of the process. It is part of the study abroad experience” (Nancy).

Nancy elaborated her perceptions on family separation and stress. Nancy's awareness of the lack of family support in the context of separation made her accept the fact of living in the UK and being away from her family, and to take responsibility of her problems and

challenges in the UK without transmitting and sharing with her family in Algeria. To raise her acceptance, Nancy compared herself to other students from the wide community of international students in the UK and exemplified with Chinese students. Nancy denoted that coming from a collectivist society where family members tend to live together makes the separation experience harder but not impossible. She implied that homesickness is a common challenge for almost all international students despite their origins. Being aware of others facing the same challenges as her, Nancy raised her acceptance of the experience in the UK. In accord, a study done by Yue and Lê (2013) examined the coping strategies that international students adopted in an Australian tertiary context found that most of international students tend to use acceptance to cope with unchangeable stressful situations that have mainly resulted from cultural differences and mental health issues that encounter them like homesickness, anxiety, loneliness, and depression.

Even though family separation was the main challenge that affected students in the UK, not all of them struggled to cope with it. Jack talked about how well he has coped with being away from his family and said, *“I have managed to do that successfully”* (Jack). However, when asked whether he managed to cope with the study-related stress, he voiced:

“I was not expecting to go through so much stress in my PhD study [...] It is either you cope with that stress, or you fail” (Jack).

Here, Jack referred to the study-related stress as part of the PhD experience in the UK that needs to be accepted.

Still with positive thinking, Lucy elaborated on her tips:

“I try to google some inspirational speeches from people on the internet” (Lucy).

And:

“Sometimes, I question my presence here. I say maybe I shouldn't quit my job, and I go for this scholarship... but then I say, oh come on, this is something very good that you're doing. It just needs patience and time. So, it is just a matter of time and patience and the hard work, of course. [...] try to think about the positive things... about me being here. Think also about my achievements, in the previous years, and

think about people in Algeria and how happy they will be if I quit this scholarship” (Lucy).

And added:

“I’m not going to be successful. I am not going to make it. It is very difficult. I’m very far away I still have lots to do. But then, when you think that someone will be like super happy because of you being in Algeria, because you couldn’t cope... and my family, the other idea that comes to my mind is how disappointed my parents will be if I do this” (Lucy).

These data extracts are examples of motivating thoughts that Lucy thought of in her moments of despair. Like many other students in this research, Lucy attempted to console and convince herself that this separation experience is temporary and needs patience. She relied on a set of motivating facts to minimize her stress and encourage herself to pursue with her journey of taking a PhD in the UK amongst them: focusing on the positive aspects of this experience, thinking of her family happiness with her being a doctor and their disappointment if she quitted her scholarship, thinking of people happiness in Algeria if she gave up her PhD.

As for the families of Algerian students back home, some participants had similar beliefs to students that made them feel positive about the experience of having a child taking a PhD in the UK, which as a result, helped them to cope with the stress of separation and accept it.

Josie’s mother, among the family members, explained her view regarding coping with separation as follows:

“I guess the ability to cope with separation and the extent of coping with separation depends on family members’ personalities and personal differences” (Josie’s mother).

The participant brought up a very important point that explains the reason behind the students’ differences in their ability to cope and their choice of the coping strategies. Josie’s mother believed that some family members might find it easy to cope with separation than others depending on their personality. That is, coping with the experience of separation depends on the character of the students and their families, their way of thinking, and system of life before getting separated. This finding goes in line with the claim that “some coping strategies

may work effectively in some situation, but may not be suitable in another (Saravanan, Mohamad, and Alias, 2019, p.78).

Josie's mother also had a very positive vision on taking a PhD in the UK:

“For me, I was so happy for her to study in the UK right from the beginning of the scholarship. I love travelling and see and learn about different cultures. So, I always say to myself, let her enjoy and have new experiences. I always try to think positively to reassure Josie and myself as well” (Josie's mother).

Here, Josie's mother expressed her own belief of loving new experiences and discovering new places, cultures and societies. She affirmed her encouragement and support to her daughter to get this experience and attempted to be positive towards her.

Another positive view that could be considered as helpful for families to cope with separation is the fact of students adapting to life abroad. In her talk, Spencer's sister expressed:

“When the student has two or three years abroad there, you will know that he managed to cope with alienation, at least, you would say that he started to accommodate with living alone which is very reassuring” (Spencer's sister).

Here, the participant acknowledged that students' families in Algeria feel reassured when they see their children managed to adapt to life in the UK and started to cope with living alone away from their families. That is, students' ability of adaptation to the new experience in the UK is reflected on their families in Algeria.

Almost all family members in the study had a common belief that being a student sponsored by the Algerian government is a stress relief and a source of reassurance for them in Algeria. For example, one sister mentioned:

“When we reflect that you are sponsored by the government in this scholarship. That really consoles and reassures us” (Catherine's sister).

And another family member voiced:

“The government is taking her responsibility under any condition, through thick and thin, she is in the custody of the Algerian government. She has someone to take care of her” (Emily’s father).

Like many other family members, the two participants above, Catherine’s sister and Emily’s father, are conscious of the fact that being a governmentally sponsored student is one of the reassuring and comforting aspects of the experience of Algerian students taking doctoral research in the UK, which helps both family members and students to cope with separation. The participants here implied that they do not have to worry about their students’ tuition fees or living expenses, and in cases of unexpected situations that students may face and cannot manage to solve on their own, their sponsoring body, the Algerian government, will interfere to find a solution.

Ashley’s brother, talked about the same fact of how reassuring the fact of being a sponsored student by the Algerian government is for families in Algeria, and illustrated his view with an example from his sister’s experience in the UK along the following passage:

“I would give you an example, because she is under the authority of the Algerian government there, in the UK I mean, she had the chance to have a seat in the repatriation flight that was organized by the Algerian government during the COVID pandemic” (Ashley’s brother).

The same point was highlighted by Carol’s sister:

“As a sponsored student, Carol was given the chance to go back home in the repatriation flight organized by the Algerian government during the COVID-19 pandemic, if she was funding for herself and went to study abroad by herself, she might not have had that chance at that time like many other Algerians in the UK or in any European country” (Carol’s sister).

The example presented above by both participants, Ashley’s brother and Carol’s sister, justify why families of Algerian students consider getting the scholarship from the Algerian government as a stress-relief and a reassuring factor that helped both Algerian students in the UK and their families in Algeria to cope with separation.

Another instance of family members’ attempts to be positive towards the separation of their children is in Clover’s mother belief:

“When she has Muslim friends, even if they are not from Algeria, I feel reassured. Like Syrians, she used to live with Syrians. They were Arab Muslims, and it was good. She had a nice experience with them”
(Clover’s mother).

The participant asserted that the fact that her daughter lived with female students with whom she shared the same religious beliefs and principles acted as a consoling factor for her and made her positive towards her daughter’s experience in the UK as she could integrate herself in an environment somehow like the Algerian environment. Clover’s mother also reported:

“In the first year, I was so stressed and worried about her. However, when she got married and her husband joined her to live in the UK together, I felt less stressed as someone is there accompanying her”
(Clover’s mother).

Continuing with the factors that made family members feel positive about students UK experience, Clover’s mother mentioned one aspect that does not necessarily appear in all students’ cases but can be considered as a comforting aspect for families when it is found. In her case, Clover’s mother felt reassured and less stressed about her daughter, Clover, after she got married and started to live with her husband in the UK. This implies that Clover’s family realized that Clover is not alone anymore in the UK as she has a family member with her supporting her and sharing the experience in the UK with her.

This section presented the participants’ attempts to be positive towards the experience of separation. The data extracts showed the participants’ awareness of the importance of accepting the experience of separation to effectively cope with it. This was attained through seeking some positive attempts such as focusing on the positive aspects of having a fully funded scholarship by the Algerian government to take a PhD in the UK, accepting separation as of the journey, listening to motivational speeches.

9.6. Social media:

Another method of coping presented by all participants, which enormously helped Algerian students in the UK and their families back home to cope with stress in the context of separation, is the use of social media platforms. All research participants from both case studies, at different points of the interviews, came to an agreement that coping with separation

would not have been achieved without social media. They revealed an awareness of the crucial role of social media to emotionally cope with the feelings associated with separation from each other. Algerian students expressed their use of social media to seek support from their families. This is accordant with the assertion that “social media has the potential of helping the students sustain memories of their homeland and relationships with family or friends to help them adapt to their new environment and cope with challenges” (Ekundayo and Clear, 2018, p.116).

Participants showed the usefulness of social media in sharing their lives with each other to reduce the stress of family separation, get emotional support and maintain daily contact with each other. This agrees with Çömlekçi’s (2020) assertion that social media allow international students maintain contact with people from their home countries from whom they receive emotional support to cope and adapt with the host society. Using the most representative data from participants interviews, this section aims to present and discuss data relevant to the use of social media by Algerian postgraduate researchers in the UK and their families in Algeria.

Several participants acknowledged the significant role of social media helping them to cope with separation. Like many other participants, Jack reflected:

“Social media and coping with family separation Yeah, social media was and is still very helpful in making communication between me and my family easier, especially messenger, WhatsApp, Viber only...”
(Jack).

And he added:

“Most of the time video calls and I would say once... twice per day maximum twice sometimes the conversation lasts from 20 minutes to 45 minutes maximum” (Jack).

In the pieces of data above, Jack shed light on how social media was crucial in maintaining his relationship with his family. By listing the social media platforms, he uses the most to contact his family like WhatsApp, Viber and Facebook Messenger that allows him to virtually see his family, Jack emphasized his need and his family’s need to use video calls to talk to each other. Jack also pointed out to the need of contacting his family on daily basis with a duration of 30 to 45 mints for each call.

Another male participant also talked about the effectiveness of social media in his journey in the UK away from his family as follows:

“Very useful. Very, very useful. Well useful, but not so much useful in some respects, but still useful in that. So, the thing is, I use social media to talk to my family. We only talk on WhatsApp. We do the camera, which is a privilege for us, because there was a time when people did not have a phone or... Yeah, when technology was not that common. So yeah, being able to talk to my family face to face every day. That helps a lot” (Steven).

Steven here appreciated the use of social media, especially through video calls, to deal with his separation from his family. He highlighted WhatsApp as the most social media platform used by him and his family to check on each other.

The use of WhatsApp by Steven, Jack above and many other students who mentioned that when being interviewed as Algerian international students to get in touch with their families is in accord with the finding that WhatsApp was one of the most widely used social media platform by Chinese international students in Malaysia in a study that examined how the intensity of social media can affect the purpose of using social media with emphasis on the mediating role of cultural identity among Chinese international students in Malaysia (Zhao et al., 2022).

On the other hand, Steven pointed out to another aspect of using social media:

“But when it comes to other stuff, like for instance, there was a time I was just scrolling up on Facebook, and I'm in a group of the neighbourhood, they tell us about people who died in the neighbourhood and you know, when anything goes wrong, they just post stuff on that group, which makes me kind of stressful and makes me kind of want to go back home and take my family and move on square. Yeah, I think that is one way to put it but that is good, but that is also positive as well. Knowing what is going on in my neighbourhood can give me a sense of what the changes, which are happening, in the neighbourhood. So, when I go back home, I know what to expect and I know what questions I ask and so it makes it easier for me to adapt to the situation there” (Steven).

Although it is stressful for him to know about the bad events happening with people he knows and count for in like neighbours in Algeria, Steven expressed the usefulness of social

media in keeping him updated about the news of the environment he belongs to in Algeria, which, according to him, helps in how to react and deal with people after going back. This is conforming to Çömlekçi's (2020) finding that Facebook is the most widely used social media platform by international students to know about the recent events and news taking place in their home countries and societies, in his study that looked at what international students use social media for and how it affects them when adapting to a new culture and environment.

Katy also shared her view regarding social media in the context of separation:

“Excellent. I mean, it is the only reason why I am, as I told you, like, the other day when Facebook was down, and I could not contact them, and I was panicking. I was like, how am I supposed to talk to my family? I don't use Facebook page at all, I just use Facebook messenger to talk to my family every single day and I was like, I need to find another solution. So, I could be with my family because that's the only way that I am all right, because that is the only way I can know that they are okay, they are fine that nothing is happening to them” (Katy).

Katy voiced how important role social media plays in enabling her to contact her family and helping her to cope with separation from them. She emphasised that she mainly uses Facebook to stay in touch with her family. This goes with the claim that Facebook was often used to contact family and friends by African students in international distance education (Madge et al., 2019). Katy realized the effectiveness of social media in her journey in the UK in the context of separation at the moments when she was unable to get in touch with her family. This implies to the significant role that social media plays in building a link between students in the UK and their families in Algeria. She also expressed:

“I usually contact them through messenger, or WhatsApp and always video calls, yes. It is usually daily that I call them, or they call me” (Katy).

Like others, Katy asserted her use of video calls to maintain daily contact with her family.

Ashley talked about how useful social media is for her and her family in decreasing the separation stress:

“Thank God to social media, we are talking to each other. We are seeing each other like daily, I'm always on my phone. I'm always talking to them. But deeply, I really am aware that it is not the same thing. I mean, face to face, seeing my family face to face is something very different than seeing them behind screens. And this is another thing that I realized when I go back home” (Ashley).

Here, Ashley appreciated the role of social media in coping with separation. Although it is helpful, Ashley indicated that having regularly virtual contact with her family through social media does not replace meeting them, a fact that she realized whenever she joined them in Algeria. She also illustrated her belief with the case of her mother as follows:

“It does help it helps a lot. My mom is not like she doesn't know how to use messenger. She doesn't even know what Facebook is. But she learned how to make a video call. My mom doesn't go, she didn't ever go to school. She's illiterate but she uses messenger. She learns how to use messenger and how to record her voice and send it to me, how to see photos and she learned that for the sake of me” (Ashley).

In the extract above, Ashley reported how her mother, who is illiterate, gradually learned to use one of the social media platforms (Facebook messenger) just to check on Ashley and to have news and updates about her despite her unfamiliarity of social media. Ashley also kept talking about the role of social media in this way:

“Messenger most of the time and sometimes Viber. I'm using messenger because my mum gets used to it easily, but often Viber I use it to talk with other family members like my uncles and sometimes my dad also, yeah, (...) always video calls, sometimes for reasons they call me late at night and the light is off. I mean, it's gloomy. My mom said, no, something bad happens. I want to see your face. Try to get up from your bed and switch on the light to see if you are okay or not. Okay, I'm okay. So, video calls are the appropriate ones for them” (Ashley).

Here, Ashley listed Facebook messenger and Viber as the main social media platforms she uses the most to contact her family and relatives. Besides, she tightened on the use of video calls and justified this by her mother's serenity in doing so.

Correspondingly, in Jane's case, for instance, video calls were mainly used to contact her family members in the family house as she described:

“I mostly use Facebook or Viber. I would prefer WhatsApp but most of my family do not use WhatsApp. All of them use either Facebook or Viber. So, I mostly use those technologies to contact my family... and I use video calls most of the times [...] Usually, I initiate the video call with my parents, because my mother does not have a smartphone, and she does not like to use it. So, I have to contact my sister to talk to her because my sister... if she calls me like she talks to me. She does not give the chance to my parents to talk to me. I have to ask her specifically to give me my mother, or I do like a family group video call” (Jane).

Like Ashley and many other students, Jane was another participant who point up video calls through Facebook messenger and Viber as the most appropriate means to get in touch with her family in Algeria. She also noted that her parents' unfamiliarity of social media platforms and technology, which led them not to use smartphones, urged her to address her sisters to reach them. This is because WhatsApp, by which Jane contacts her parents, is only available on smartphones like Android phones, iPhone and blackberry (Malecela, 2016), which Jane's parents do not master to use. Besides, Jane referred to her option of group calls to enjoy time with all family members of hers. In this respect, she explained her view:

“My sisters live in different states, the married ones. So, I only get to talk to them altogether when they come to my parents' house. So, that doesn't happen very often, especially with COVID. They were also isolated, so they could not come to my parents' house. So, it started to become more distant. So, I do that, like once a week instead of the usual three times a week or two times. With other sisters, it is usually the daily thing that I do with them is texts or audio calls, but video calls are only when they are in my parents' house. I prefer video calls, so I get to talk to them somehow face to face but I don't get to do that a lot. Especially sometimes, we have problems with connection. So, I can't even get to talk to them on video because of a weak connection. I have a daily video call with my twin sister” (Jane).

Here, Jane justified her option of all-family group video calls to get the chance to see all her sisters (married and single) along with her parents. She explained that her use of video calls mainly to call her family members in the family house, whereas she uses texts and voice calls to check on her married sisters due to the challenging internet access her sisters sometimes encounter in Algeria. Jane also highlighted how the COVID-19 pandemic and its travel restrictions affected her virtual relationship with her married sisters in Algeria. She also emphasized her daily contact with her twin sister as a must. This implies the significant role of video calls in decreasing the stress of family separation between students in the UK and their families in Algeria.

With reference to the usefulness of social media in coping with family separation, Catherine attested:

“It's very useful to cope with them. If there is no social media, there is no family contact. They die and you die. No one will hear it. It's very difficult [...] I use messenger and WhatsApp mainly for video calls. Spontaneously, I just pick up on the video because I have to see them”
(Catherine).

This piece of data presented by Catherine supports other students' beliefs about the significant role social media plays in helping them to cope with separation stress. She described that neither her nor her family in Algeria can endure the separation experience without social media. That is, the family atmosphere and relationships are, to a great degree, maintained by social media in the context of Algerian students who take PhD in the UK and left their families behind in Algeria.

Several students also acknowledged social media as a key factor in coping with separation. For instance:

“Thanks to internet thanks to everyone that has contributed to have this amazing tool, that we are in very different countries, but we still see each other, talk to each other. Even though the physical presence is absent, but still very grateful of having this technology. [...] It is always through messenger video calls, no audio calls, without thinking, automatically video calls. I click on the video call button without even thinking or texting them, and if one of them calls without a video call, I

start thinking what's going on? Why you're not putting your video on? So, it makes me question” (Rose).

And:

“I can't imagine a world without social media. Especially when it comes to seeing them, they see, you share moments with them. If for example when I moved here in my house, I talked to my mom the first thing when I set my foot in this apartment and like I did a video call, I showed her the house, the neighbourhood because she was so stressed back then. So yeah, I'm so thankful for technology like Facebook messenger and WhatsApp. So, with my family, like my mother, my sisters and everything is definitely a video call, but maybe with friends, like when I talk with my friends in Algeria, no, we would always go for the audio call, like automatically. I don't know why. I never told them. They never say it to me. But we always go for the audio call. When it comes to family always like automatically, I hit the video button” (Clover).

Both participants above agreed with other participants regarding the role of social media in coping with the stress of their journey in the UK away from their families. They tighten the use of video calls as the most effective means of communication to share their life with their families. They both insisted that opting for video calls happens unconsciously. According to them, not seeing their families on cameras while having a call with family makes them feel doubtful about their families' situation. This finding emphasizes Çömlekçi's (2020) outcome that video conversations help international students to stay in touch and maintain constant contact with their families back home, especially through Viber and WhatsApp in which the latter is regarded as the master platform.

As for family members, they also gave prominence to social media as a fundamental aspect in coping with the separation of their students taking doctoral research in the UK. Nearly all family members adopted the same beliefs presented by students regarding the significance of social media in coping with separation. They essentially draw attention on how they used social media to share family experiences with students in the UK, and to remotely share the experience abroad with students. For instance:

“It's been two years or three years, and I'm still coping, the thing that makes it less painful is virtually calling her... the way that we call her. But if it was not the virtual communication, I don't think I would be able to cope at all. Virtually calling her, talking to her all the time, it makes me like less stressful ... knowing that she's doing well, she's good... in good health, and she's having fun. Maybe... she's doing well in her PhD, makes me more comfortable” (Emma's sister).

Here, Emma's sister explained the usefulness of social media in helping families in Algeria to decrease the separation-related stress. She highlighted that without social media, she might not be able to cope with the absence of her sister. She also demonstrated that the usefulness of social media manifested in getting reassured and updated about Emma, which would comfort the family and reduces their fears and stresses about Emma. At another point, she added:

“I usually call her, if she is not there, I leave her a message on every social media platform... if she is not on Facebook, I used to leave her a message only on Facebook but now, I leave her a message on WhatsApp because she uses it much” (Emma's sister).

In this extract, the participant showed her attempts in getting news and updates from her sister in different social media platforms using different options. Like other participants, the use of Facebook messenger and WhatsApp by Emma and her sister prevail over other social media platform, opting for video calls in the first place. Texts were mainly used to check on Emma when she is offline.

Equivalently, another family member expressed her use of texts as an alternative to video calls:

“Sometimes, if I did not see and talk to them on a video call, I just text them or send them a voice message, but we are always in contact with each other on daily basis” (Clover's mother).

The participant, here, described her endeavours to get in touch with her daughters who live abroad, Clover and her sister. The participant mentioned in the interview that she has another married daughter living in Egypt through which she experienced family separation for the first time before Clover's departure to the UK. Clover's mother pointed out to her need to

contact her daughters living abroad on daily basis. When she could not reach her daughters through video calls, the participant used texts and voice messages to contact them. This is to say, having daily contact with the family member who got separated from the family was a must for families, and the least families would do is through texting them.

Carol's sister, reported:

“We mainly use Facebook messenger, and sometimes Viber or WhatsApp to contact her. We always opt for video calls when we need to talk to her, whether was it me or any other family member, our preference always goes to video calls. Sometimes, our call lasts for hours, but the thing is we have to contact her and see her every day” (Carol's sister).

Here, carol's sister confirmed other participants' belief of unintentionally opting for video calls to communicate with students in the UK as this would help them best to share their life together and reduce the stress of separation. She also highlighted the use of Facebook messenger, Viber and WhatsApp as the main social media platforms used by her and her family to contact Carol, as these platforms can easily be used and learned by family members in Algeria. Additionally, Carol's sister assured on her family's need to approach Carol using social media on daily basis.

Like students, family members also expressed their gratitude to social media and its significant role in coping with separation. For example, amongst family members, these participants elucidated the following:

“Now, there are social media platform. We can talk with her, see her and share things with each other. This is really helpful to cope with separation” (Emily's father).

Also:

“When we see how the world is developing so fast and how travel become easier than before with the development of technology, we can communicate with each other, see and hear about each other whenever we want, and this minimizes the stress of separation” (Lisa's cousin).

And:

“Now, there are social media platform that we usually use to contact each other mainly Messenger and WhatsApp. we can talk with her, see her and share things with each other. This is really beneficial to cope with separation” (Catherine’s sister).

The data extracts above introduced by participants, Emily’s father, Spencer’s sister, Lisa’s cousin, and Catherine’s sister, acknowledged how positive social media was in reducing families’ fears and stresses in the context of them being separated from their students taking doctoral research in the UK. That is, social media helped both students and their families in Algeria to emotionally cope with separation through sharing events and occasions with each other and think positively about this experience of separation.

This section presented the participants’ perceptions regarding the use of social media in the experiences of Algerian students taking PhD in the UK who left their families in Algeria. This section showed the main social media platforms that students in the UK and families in Algeria used to communicate with each other, mainly those platforms that allowed them to have virtual meetings and that were easy for family members to use.

9.7. Chapter summary:

This chapter presented and discussed data related the participants’ strategies of coping with family separation and managing social stress in the experience of Algerian PhD students in the UK whose families remain in Algeria. Findings revealed that participants opted for different strategies to manipulate the stressful feelings they passed through throughout separation. As Muslims, they mostly relied on Islam and its practices and instructions to manage stress. Not only that, but participants also showed their attempts to regulate their emotions through sharing events of their life with each other, avoiding stress and being positive towards this experience. Both Algerian students and their families acknowledged the pivotal role of the technological advancement in coping with this experience.

Chapter Ten: General conclusion

10.1. Introduction:

This study aimed to understand the social stresses impacting Algerian postgraduate students during their doctoral studies in the UK and their families remaining in Algeria in the context of family separation. It examined the viewpoints, attitudes and how Algerian students and members of families perceived social stress and family separation, what they considered as stressors in the context of this study, and how they managed to cope with stress and separation. This final chapter of the thesis presents a general conclusion for the study. I first provide a summary of the study and its main findings. Then, I discuss the main contribution of this study to knowledge. Next, I highlight the main implications of the study in theory and practice. After that, the research's problems and limitations are acknowledged. Finally, I provide some recommendations and suggestions for possible further research.

10.2. Summary of the study:

This qualitative research sought to understand the social stresses that affected Algerian doctoral students during the period of their PhD studies in the UK along with their members of families who remain at home in the context of family separation. The study was guided by social stress theory which helped in shaping the status of Algerian students as a minority group among the wider community of international students in the UK. To achieve this, a social constructivist descriptive multiple-case study was employed, in which semi-structured interviews were used as a research tool to collect data. To address the research, aim and question that guide the study, semi-structured interviews, were conducted with 18 students and 11 members of their families. Most of the participants were females; only few males took part in the study. Family members of families of students involved some sisters, brothers, fathers, and mothers. In doing so, I attempted to comprehend participants' perceptions of social stress and the social stressors they came across each from their own perspective, and to learn about the strategies they used to cope with this situation. The following is a summary of the main findings that provide the answers to the research question and attain the research objectives.

To address the main research question of this study "*What are the social stresses affecting the families of Algerian students and students themselves during the period of their PhD studies in the UK?*", it was crucial to find out how these individuals perceive social stress first, which underlies the first objective of the study "*To understand how Algerian PhD*

students and their families back home perceive social stress and how they co-construct its definition". The second objective of the study, *"To understand what has been experienced throughout the family separation of Algerian families and their children in the UK that could lead to social stress"* also serves to answer the main research question. Accordingly, the research findings revealed that social stress, for students and family members, is originated from separation and study where all the stressors they encountered are separation-related and study-related. So, dimensions of the PhD like meeting deadlines, lack of data, supervision issues, and time limitation for the PhD completion were study-related stressors; and features such as health issues, losing family members and discrimination were caused from separation. Students and families emphasised how the COVID pandemic intensified these stressors and made them more real in their journey. Chapters 6 and 7 presented and discussed data regarding participants' perceptions of social stress and stressors in the context of this study.

As for the third research objective *"To find out how Algerian students and their families back home perceive and conceptualize family separation."*, the findings showed that participants have similar conceptualizations of family separation in very different ways, which were related to physical and emotional absence and presence. In doing so, some participants accepted to describe this experience as a family separation while others opposed that, yet they told me that missing the whole family is much harder than missing just one member. Another finding was that both students and family members talked about the psychological impacts of separation on their mental health. Findings in relation to the notion of family separation in this study were presented and discussed in depth in chapter 8.

With regards to findings related to the fourth research objective *"To learn about the coping strategies that Algerian students and their families back home tend to use to cope with family separation, manage stress and maintain their relationships."*, which fits with the sub-research questions of the study as follows: *"1. How do Algerian PhD students manage the social stresses they experience in the UK and cope with family separation"* and *"2. How do families of Algerian PhD students manage the social stresses they experience back home and cope with family separation?"*, the insights shared by the participants revealed that using social media, religion and having more positive views towards the experience were linked to better coping with stress and separation. Chapter 9 discussed the coping strategies used by participants in this study.

10.3. Contribution of the study:

This study aimed at providing an overall understanding of the social experiences of Algerian students taking doctoral research in the UK and their families who remain at home in Algeria, and how these experiences affected their relationship in the context of separation. This was accomplished through giving space to these students and their members of families to talk about their experiences and share their perceptions in the context of this study. Based on the collected data in this study presented in chapters (6,7,8,9), this qualitative research adds distinct contributions to the existing research. This section highlights the original contributions of this study.

This research is, according to my knowledge, the first to address the left-behind families of international students in general and Algerian students studying abroad in particular. This is due to, from one hand, previous studies in family research in migration contexts addressed the families of refugees who remain at home. From the other hand, most of previous studies that dealt with international students focused on students themselves and not their families. Still with research on families, this study would be the first to address families of Algerian students studying abroad as the emphasis was put only on students (Ghodbane, 2020; Guerriche, 2020; Sadoudi, 2021). Thus, the current study provides an original contribution to literature on family dynamics in Algeria who have members in other countries.

Even though the findings of this study might not be generalizable as the results of this study relate particularly to Algerian PhD students in the UK and their left-behind families, yet the study still contributes and adds knowledge to the wide research on international students in the world at macro level and students coming from the MENA (Middle East and North Africa) countries at micro level. This is because most of the past research studies that researched international students addressed students coming from Europe, America, Canada, and China, while there is a lack of research on international students coming from North Africa and Algeria.

Another significant point of contribution that this study offers is the conceptualizations of what “being socially stressed” and “being separated from family” are in study abroad contexts. According to the participants’ accounts in this study, separation appears to be an integral part of stress for international students coming from collectivist cultural backgrounds.

The study’s use of social stress to frame and view the experiences of Algerian students taking PhD in the UK whose families stay behind at home allowed for deeper and richer

understandings of how these individuals experience separation and its correlated challenges. The researcher here makes no claim that using social stress as a theory to understand the experiences of Algerian students as international students in study abroad contexts and the families left behind is the only approach to research this kind of experiences. However, the lack of research utilising the notion of social stress in relation to studying the experiences of Algerian students and families whose children take PhDs in British universities inside a British culture, which is a gap in knowledge, prompted the conduct of this study. That is, using a theory that has not been used much in research adds to the originality of this study and contributes to the wide literature about this theory.

10.4. Limitations of the study:

This research has successfully achieved its aims. It is worth mentioning that this study came across few challenges that could be taken into consideration when conducting future research.

One main potential limitation to this research is the researcher's position in this study and her assumptions which might led to a negative discourse and its implication for the research design and the findings. As previously said, my research was primarily motivated by my own experience of being separated from my family for the first time a few years ago as an international student put through a new cultural background. As a researcher, I shared some similar aspects with my participants in this study like language, religion and culture as we came from the same cultural background. This might make us perceive the study abroad experience as a separation of family somehow in the same way, as described by participants as El Ghorba (see section 6.2.1.1.) rather than looking into the experience from a more positive lens and this might imply a lack of critical distance. Besides, as the researcher is also an Algerian studying in the UK, this might have helped in the data analysis and in comprehending the various emotions that the student participants experienced and communicated. However, the researcher's lived experiences in the UK of family separation and personal and academic challenges as an international PhD student especially at the beginning of her research journey might have hindered her from understanding her fellow Algerian students' experiences objectively, despite her striving not to interfere her experience with the participants experiences, which might have introduced bias into the data interpretation, and thus, might have resulted in a biased negative lens in her positionality in this study. This negative lens might have resulted in the study as the study itself researched a sensitive topic like social stress,

where the latter is experienced by the study participants and the researcher herself. Thus, conducting such research by a different researcher who does not relate to the study by any means and external to the problem under investigation might result in a less negative discourse in the study.

Resource and time limitation represents another limitation for this study. A longer period would give the researcher the chance to interview more individuals. At the beginning of the study, I aimed to have a family member for each student to see how members of the same family (student and associated family member) view and experience separation and stress each from their own perspective. However, recruiting family members was very challenging and took me a lot of time due to the socio-cultural conception of the Algerian society that research is far from the society's real life and is only related to educational institutions, which made them afraid of taking part in the study. This has also led to some students' withdrawal of their willingness to participate. Therefore, I had to include some students in the research without necessarily having an associated family member. Alternatively, having two categories of participants and researching the same topic from two different angles at the same time could need lengthy periods of research as each case could represent a separate research project. This study, however, has successfully managed to research the same phenomenon across two groups of people.

Another limitation of the study was the COVID-19 pandemic which coincided the periods prior to the fieldwork, preparing for the data collection phase. This urged the researcher to conduct most of the interviews online and hindered collecting data face-to-face with most participants. This was the case for all members of families who were in Algeria and have been interviewed online by the researcher who conducted the research from the UK. Although students taking part in this study were in the UK, only few of them were able to have a face-to-face interview as it was not possible for others to do so. Hence, conducting internet-based research has in some way impeded the researcher from building rapport with the participants, but still it successfully allowed the researcher to collect the required data for the research.

One more limitation was the complexity of the term "social stress", as reported by both students and family members who found it challenging to convey their understandings of the concept itself than relating it to the context of the study (see section 6.2). This may be because both groups of participants received implicit rather than explicit explanations of the term in educational institutions which made them struggle to explain their perceptions. Nevertheless,

participants managed to engage with the interview and explain it according to their experiences in relation to this research.

While the focus of the study is a sensitive topic "social stress", another limitation to the study might lie in the fact that it has been conducted by a researcher who is considered a member of the same group of the study participants and shared many features with the study sample. That is, the researcher conducted, lived and got impacted by the sensitive topic examined in the study. Although this might give the researcher credit for conducting such research, but it also led her to encounter emotional and psychological challenges due to the nature of the research (see section 5.9.), which might make her in need of some systems of support throughout data collection and data analysis phases. This is because, through the course of the research, the researcher made sure to maintain and ensure the ethical responsibility of the researcher towards participants regarding the sensitive topic of stress, while this was not the case with the researcher herself.

As for the participants' safety, Patton (2015) says that, mostly for confidentiality and anonymity reasons, study participants can give information or share ideas with the researcher that they did not mean to, and thus, he argues that the interviewer should set up an "ethical framework" to address these issues (p.495). During the very initial phase of my analysis when I was listening to the interview recordings to familiarise myself with the data, I remember I came across one family member who shared much information regarding an incident he came across with his sibling, a student participant, which could make them both known for the Algerian readers and other participants. To evade this risk, I chose to contact the participant, and I explained the potential risks of using this information on their safety where the participant decided not to use this information in my study. I respected his decision, and I did not include this part of information from the transcribed interview. In another interview, I remember one participant got so emotional and sad from crying when she was talking about her uncle who passed away almost a year after she departed to the UK, and she could not even attend his funeral. At the time, I made sure to make the participant feel at ease during the interview through offering her several options. I asked her whether she wanted to end the interview, reschedule it for another time to be continued, or have a break until she feels fine and comfortable to carry on the interview with me. The participant asked for a 10 mins break then re-engaged in the interview. With the course of the interview, we tackled the point of consulting with the university counselling services in which I advised the participant to talk to in order to

deal with her stress and mental health. This point was also mentioned by several participants in interviews.

When ethics in social research are discussed, potential risks that could harm participants in any way are usually the main topics of discussion, along with strategies for avoiding them (Patton, 2015; Bryman, 2016; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018), the safety of researchers is, however, not given as much priority. Conducting research on sensitive topics is one example where potential risks are not generated on the participants only, but also on the researcher as well. My research study is one example that can illustrate that. As the researcher of this study, I got impacted by my study several times throughout my research journey. I recall myself getting too stressed whenever I got emotionally affected by a given interview and a participant reciting, sometimes with crying, a stressful experience she/he went through and communicated to me. Receiving participants' negative emotions and stressful challenges resulted in me dealing with and experiencing huge amounts of stress besides my personal challenges. This made me sometimes to leave gaps of almost two weeks between conducting one interview and another. Being exposed to social stress on daily basis, based on the nature of my research, made me to be unconsciously stressed and augmented my struggles. As a result, I had to refer myself, with the assistance of my supervisors, to the university counselling services to deal with my mental health and cope with my stress. Fortunately, the university staff and supervisors were understanding and supportive along with my friends and family and I could gradually cope with my challenges and manage my stress. This suggests a need to plan ahead not only about the ethical responsibility of the researcher towards the participants, but also about themselves when conducting research that investigates sensitive topic such as stress.

Although this study had few limitations, it nonetheless successfully offered a valuable understanding of the experiences of Algerian students in the UK and their families who remain at home in the context of separation.

10.5. Implications of the study:

10.5.1. Implications for universities:

The experience of international students is affected by several factors, which staff of the host university should be aware of. To maximize the benefits of study abroad for students, some factors were found in this study in relation to separation and conducting doctoral research.

To address the lack of knowledge of the academic context, host universities could plan PhD induction programmes to prompt self-instruction for students with teacher-centred educational background. This could include providing different workshops to address the necessary skills for academic research, for instance, academic English language, research methodology, and writing skills.

Host university staff are also encouraged to consider family separation as a serious issue for collectivist international students. Findings regarding the impact of family separation on students' mental health provide implication for host universities to offer more support systems for international students coming from collectivist social backgrounds. This could entail creating more workshops to raise awareness on mental health issues in study abroad contexts and how to deal with them. Host university staff could also organize regular checks for students' mental health and put emphasis on students leave requests due to mental health issues resulting from separation.

University staff are also encouraged to consider the ethical responsibility of the researcher towards themselves when dealing with sensitive topics such as stress through providing support mechanisms for researchers experiencing emotional challenges throughout their research journey. This could be maintained through advising experienced researchers to share their experiences of dealing with the impact of sensitive research studies on qualitative researchers regarding their positionality in the research with novice researchers. University staff can also offer sessions with counselling services for novice researchers researching sensitive topics.

10.5.2. Implications for Algerian students studying abroad:

Students are encouraged to participate in conferences and other academic events to gain an awareness of the academic culture of universities in the UK. It is equally the responsibility of the students to familiarise themselves with the academic culture of the UK, as this can enhance their capacity for learning. This could assist students to progress in their research and to keep themselves busy to decrease separation stress.

Students are also advised to get involved in social cultural events with other international students, not only Algerians, to widen their support system to address study stress and loneliness. This could help them to reflect more on their learning experience out of their comfort zone.

Students are also prompted to always refer to the university counselling and wellbeing services and systems of support when it comes to deal with their mental health. this also include attending the sessions offered by the university to raise awareness regarding mental health of international students like stress and depression.

10.5.2. Implications for families of Algerian students studying abroad:

Although they are also included in the experience, Algerian students' families who remain at home should pay careful attention to their students who study abroad and provide them with the sufficient emotional support to cope with separation. This implication stems from the findings that students are much more impacted by separation than their families, and from some students' belief that family support decreases with physical absence.

Findings of this research also provide implication for families of students willing to study abroad in the future to manage their expectations regarding separation and make them aware of the other angle of the experience. This also benefits students in Algeria who plan to study overseas.

10.6. Further research:

Based on the limitations listed earlier, some suggestions could be advised to conduct further research. First, to better understand the experiences of family separation of students and their left behind families in study abroad contexts, further research has to be conducted in other countries of destinations such as Canada, USA and other European countries. Future studies should also research other international students and members of families coming from collectivist backgrounds in different countries.

Future research could focus just on one perspective to research family separation. That is, two further studies could stem from the current study; one to research the social stresses experienced by left-behind families of international students, and another study could focus on international students in relation to separation. Future research could also focus on the factor of gender to understand how different the experiences of male and female international students in the context of family separation within study abroad settings. As for the left behind families of international students, further research could address parents of students only.

The conduct of this study was impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic. The latter was founded as an influencing factor that affected the experiences of Algerian students in the UK and their left-behind families. Thus, conducting further research on the impact of the COVID-

19 pandemic on individuals involved in study abroad settings, students and their families, could be constructive. Several recent research studies have been conducted to learn about the impact of COVID-19 on international students (Chen, Li, Wu, and Tong, 2020; Nguyen and Balakrishnan, 2020). More attention should be drawn on their left-behind families.

Interesting future research would have a comparative study between Algerian students who left their families to study in Arab-speaking countries and those who study in English-speaking countries. This could address the different cultural and religious aspects of students' process of adjustment with the host country and the coping mechanisms to cope with stress.

References:

- Abbou, F.Z. (2022) *The identities and lived/career experiences of Algerian female academics at universities: a feminist postcolonial perspective*. PhD thesis. University of Reading. Available at: <https://ethos.bl.uk/OrderDetails.do?uin=uk.bl.ethos.874868> (Accessed: 05 June 2023).
- Abu-Raiya, H. and Pargament, K. I. (2015) 'Religious Coping among Diverse Religions: Commonalities and Divergences', *Psychology of Religion and Spirituality*, 7(1), pp. 24-33.
- Achoui, M. (2006) The Algerian Family: Change and Solidarity. In J. Georgas, J.W Berry, F.J.R.V de Vijver, C. Kagitcibasi and Y.H Poortinga (eds.), *Families across Cultures: A 30 Nation Psychological Study* (pp. 243-250), London: Cambridge University Press.
- Adam, Z. and Ward, C. (2016) 'Stress, Religious Coping and Wellbeing in Acculturating Muslims', *Journal of Muslim Mental Health*, 10(2), pp. 3-26.
- Adisa, T.A., Baderin, M., Gbadamosi, G. and Mordi, C. (2019) 'Understanding the Trajectory of the Academic Progress of International Students in the UK', *Education + Training*, 61(9), pp. 1100–1122. Available at: doi:10.1108/et-08-2018-0177.
- Aflakseir, A. and Coleman, P. G. (2011) 'Initial Development of the Iranian Religious Coping Scale', *Journal of Muslim Mental Health*, 6(1), pp.44-61.
- Ahangar, M. and Khan, M. (2016) 'Social Intelligence of Adolescents of Nuclear and Joint Families: A Comparative Study', *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research*, 5(2), pp. 236-253.
- Aichner, T. and Jacob, F. (2015) 'Measuring the Degree of Corporate Social Media Use', *International Journal of Market Research*, 57 (2), pp. 257-276.
- Akhtar, M., Herwig, B. K., and Faize, F. A. (2019) 'Depression and Anxiety among International Medical Students in Germany: The Predictive Role of Coping Styles', *JPMA. The Journal of the Pakistan Medical Association*, 69(2), pp. 230-234.
- Akhtar, M. and Kroener-Herwig, B. (2019) 'Coping Styles and Socio-demographic Variables as Predictors of Psychological Well-being among International Students Belonging to Different cultures', *Current Psychology*, 38(3), pp. 618-626.

- Akram, H., Kamran, M., and Ahmad, N. (2020) 'An Examination of the Encountered Challenges of Pakistani International Students in China: A Case Study of First-Year Students', *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences (PJSS)*, 40(4), pp.1567-1576.
- Alaklabi, M., Alaklabi, J. and Almuhlaifi, A. (2021) 'Impacts of COVID-19 on International Students in the US', *Higher Education Studies*, 11(3), pp.37-42.
- Albatch, P.G. and Knight, J. (2007) 'The Internationalization of Higher Education: Motivations and Realities', *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 11(3/4), pp. 290-305.
- Algerian Ministry of Higher Education. (2014). *Bursary Sponsorship Contract*. Algiers.
- Alharbi, E.S. and Smith, A.P. (2018) 'Review of the Literature on Stress and Wellbeing of International Students in English-Speaking Countries', *International Education Studies*, 11(6), p. 22-44.
- Allen, C. (2019) 'Governmental responses to Islamophobia in the UK' in Zempi, I. and Awan, I. *The Routledge International Handbook of Islamophobia*. Routledge, pp. 397-407.
- Amankwaa, L. (2016) 'Creating Protocols for Trustworthiness in Qualitative Research', *Journal of cultural diversity*, 23(3), pp. 121-127.
- Aneshensel, C. (1992) 'Social Stress: Theory and Research', *Annual Review of Sociology*, 18 (1), pp.15-38.
- Aneshensel, C., Rutter, C. and Lachenbruch, P. (1991) 'Social Structure, Stress, and Mental Health: Competing Conceptual and Analytic Models', *American Sociological Review*, 56 (2), p.166.
- Anney, V. N. (2014) 'Ensuring the Quality of the Findings of Qualitative Research: Looking at Trustworthiness Criteria', *Journal of emerging trends in educational research and policy studies*, 5(2), pp. 272-281.
- Antonucci, T., Lansford, J. and Akiyama, H. (2001) 'Impact of Positive and Negative Aspects of Marital Relationships and Friendships on Well-Being of Older Adults', *Applied Developmental Science*, 5 (2), pp.68-75.
- Anyan, F. (2013) 'The Influence of Power Shifts in Data Collection and Analysis Stages: A Focus on Qualitative Research Interview', *The Qualitative Report*, 18(18), PP.1-9.

- Arain, M., Campbell, M., Cooper, C. and Lancaster, G. (2010) 'What is a Pilot or Feasibility Study? A Review of Current Practice and Editorial policy', *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 10(1), pp.1-7.
- Arthur, N. (2017) 'Supporting International Students Through Strengthening Their Social Resources', *Studies in Higher Education*, 42(5), pp. 887-894.
- Astalin, P. K. (2013) 'Qualitative Research Designs: A Conceptual Framework', *International journal of social science & interdisciplinary research*, 2(1), pp. 118-124.
- Baqutayan, S. M. S. (2015) 'Stress and Coping Mechanisms: A Historical Overview', *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(2 S1), pp. 479-479.
- Bartram, D., Poros, M.V. and Monforte, P. (1982) *Key concepts in migration*. London: SAGE.
- Bauder, H. (2012) 'The International Mobility of Academics: A Labour Market Perspective', *International Migration*, 53(1), pp. 83–96. Available at: doi:10.1111/j.1468-2435.2012.00783.x.
- Baxter, L., Henauw, C., Huisman, D., Livesay, C., Norwood, K., Su, H., Wolf, B. and Young, B. (2009) 'Lay Conceptions of "Family": A Replication and Extension', *Journal of Family Communication*, 9 (3), pp.170-189. Available at: doi:10.1080/15267430902963342.
- Baxter, P. and Jack, S. (2008) 'Qualitative Case Study Methodology: Study Design and Implementation for Novice Researchers', *The qualitative report*, 13(4), pp. 544-559.
- Bazrafkan, L., Shokrpour, N., Yousefi, A. and Yamani, N. (2016) 'Management of Stress and Anxiety Among PhD Students During Thesis Writing', *The Health Care Manager*, 35(3), pp. 231–240. Available at: doi:10.1097/hcm.000000000000120.
- Beaven, A. and Spencer-Oatey, H. (2016) Cultural adaptation in different facets of life and the impact of language: a case study of personal adjustment patterns during study abroad. *Language and Intercultural Communication*, 16(3), pp.349-367. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14708477.2016.1168048>. (Accessed: 23 May 2023).
- Belhocine, H. H. (2022) 'The Emigration of Algerian Students is a Lasting Loss Swarms benefit France L'Emigration des Etudiants Algériens est une Perte Durable. Les Essaims Profitent à la France', *Cahiers de Sociologie*, 10(01), pp. 88-107.

- Bellalem, F. (2012) 'Political History of Foreign Language Teaching in Algeria', *Working Papers*, pp.1-12.
- Belmihoub, K. (2018) 'English in a Multilingual Algeria', *World Englishes*, 37(2), pp. 207–227. Available at: doi:10.1111/weng.12294.
- Benouar, D. (2013) 'Algerian Experience in Education, Research and Practice', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 102, pp. 361–367. Available at: doi:10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.10.751.
- Benrabah, M. (2007) 'Language Maintenance and Spread: French in Algeria', *International Journal of Francophone Studies*, 10(1), pp. 193–215. Available at: doi:10.1386/ijfs.10.1and2.193_1.
- Benrabah, M. (2005) 'The Language Planning Situation in Algeria', *Current Issues in Language Planning*, 6(4), pp. 379–502. Available at: doi:10.1080/14664208.2005.10807312.
- Berezoug, H. (2021) 'The Socio-Cultural Impress on the Promotion of Self-Directed-Learning in Algerian Universities', *Arab World English Journal*, 12(3), pp. 216–231.
- Bhochhibhoya, A., Dong, Y. and Branscum, P. (2018) 'Sources of Social Support Among International College Students in the United States', *Journal of International Students*, 7(3), pp. 671–686. Available at: doi:10.32674/jis.v7i3.293.
- Blaikie, N. (2007) *Approaches to social enquiry*. 2nd edn. Cambridge: Polity.
- Blaikie, N. (2009) *Designing social research: The logic of anticipation*. 2nd edn. Cambridge: Polity.
- Boss, P. (2010) 'The Trauma and Complicated Grief of Ambiguous Loss', *Pastoral Psychology*, 59(2), pp. 137–145.
- Boado, H.C. and Ferrer, A.G. (2022) 'The Impact of Physical Separation from Parents on the Mental Wellbeing of the Children of Migrants', *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 48(10), pp. 2436–2454. Available at: doi.org/10.1080/1369183X.2021.1935670.
- Bonino, S. (2019) 'Discrimination against Muslims in Scotland' in Zempi, I. and Awan, I. *The Routledge International Handbook of Islamophobia*. Routledge, pp. 161-174.

- Bouguesri, I. and Nait-Brahim, A. (2021) ‘Ambiguous Subjectivity Within The Algerian Patriarchal Household: A Case Study Of Married Working Women In Mascara’, *Afak Ilmia Journal*, 13(03), p. 77.
- Bourke, B. (2014) ‘Positionality: Reflecting on the Research Process’, *The Qualitative Report*, 19(33). Available at: doi:10.46743/2160-3715/2014.1026.
- Bouzenoun, A. (2019) *The use of feature film clips (FFCs) in teaching English as a foreign language in Algeria*. PhD thesis. University of the West of Scotland.
- Boyd, D. M. and Ellison, N. B. (2007) ‘Social Network Sites: Definition, History, and Scholarship’, *Journal of computer-mediated Communication*, 13(1), 210-230. Available at: doi:10.1111/j.1083-6101.2007.00393.x.
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2013) *Successful Qualitative Research: a Practical Guide for Beginners*. London: SAGE.
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) ‘Using Thematic Analysis in Psychology’, *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), pp. 77–101. Available at: doi:10.1191/1478088706qp063oa.
- British Council (2014) Algerian Higher Education delegation visits UK. Available at: <https://www.britishcouncil.org/contact/press/algerian-higher-education-delegation-visits-uk> (Accessed: 15 December 2020).
- British Council (2014) Algerian Doctoral Initiative. Available at: <https://www.britishcouncil.dz/en/programmes/education/algerian-doctoral-initiative#:~:text=British%20Council%20Algeria%20is%20facilitating,Higher%20Education%20to%20UK%20universities> (Accessed: 15 December 2020).
- British Council. (2014) The start of a training session in English for the benefit of 14 teachers in preparation for the reopening of the British Council next September. Available at: <http://www.djazairess.com/ennahar/201097> (Accessed: 15 December 2020).
- Brown, L. (2009) ‘An Ethnographic Study of the Friendship Patterns of International Students in England: An Attempt to Recreate Home through Conational Interaction’, *International Journal of Educational Research*, 48(3), pp. 184–193. Available at: doi:10.1016/j.ijer.2009.07.003.

- Brumbaugh, C. C. and Fraley, R. C. (2010) ‘Adult Attachment and Dating Strategies: How Do Insecure People Attract Mates?’, *Personal Relationships*, 17(4), 599-614. Available at: doi:10.1111/j.1475-6811.2010.01304.x.
- Bryman, A. (2016) *Social research methods*. 5th edn. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Bryman, A. (2012) *Social research methods*. 4th edn. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Bulgan, G. and Çiftçi, A. (2018) ‘Work-Family Balance and Psychosocial Adjustment of Married International Students’, *Journal of International Students*, 8(2), pp. 1079–1107. Available at: doi:10.32674/jis.v8i2.133.
- Caidi, N., Ekmekcioglu, C., Chandra, P. and Jamali, R. (2022) ‘Socially-distant Fasting: Information Practices of Young Muslims during the COVID-19 Pandemic’, *Information Research: an international electronic journal*, 27. Available at: doi:10.47989/irisic2235.
- Cairns, D. (2014) *Youth Transitions, International Student Mobility and Spatial Reflexivity*. Springer.
- Campus France (2016) *The International mobility of African students* Available at: <https://www.campusfrance.org/en/resource/the-international-mobility-of-african-students> (Accessed: 11 January 2020).
- Chaker, S. (2001) ‘Berber Challenge in Algeria: The State of the Question’, *Race, Gender and Class*, 8 (3), pp.135-156.
- Chang, S. and Gomes, C. (2017) ‘Digital Journeys: A Perspective on Understanding the Digital Experiences of International Students’, *Journal of International Students*, 7(2), pp. 347-466.
- Chaouloff, F. (2013) ‘Social Stress Models in Depression Research: What Do They Tell Us?’, *Cell and Tissue Research*, 354 (1), pp.179-190. Available at: doi:10.1007/s00441-013-1606-x
- Chellia, H. (2018) ‘A Brief Overview on Students’ Mobility and its Impact on Second language Use’, *International Journal of Emerging Trends in Social Sciences*, 2(2), pp. 64–73. Available at: doi:10.20448/2001.22.64.73.
- Chen, J. H., Li, Y., Wu, A. M. S. and Tong, K. K. (2020) ‘The Overlooked Minority: Mental Health of International Students Worldwide under the COVID-19 Pandemic and beyond’, *Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, 54, p.102333. Available at: doi:10.1016/j.ajp.2020.102333.

- Chen, J.M. (2017) 'Three Levels of Push-Pull Dynamics Among Chinese International Students' Decision to Study Abroad in the Canadian Context', *Journal of International Students*, 7(1), pp. 113-135. Available at: doi:10.32674/jis.v7i1.248.
- Chen, A., Lin, Y. and Sawangpattanakul, A. (2011) 'The Relationship Between Cultural Intelligence and Performance with the Mediating Effect of Culture Shock: A Case from Philippine Laborers in Taiwan', *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 35 (2), pp.246-258. Available at: doi:10.1016/j.ijintrel.2010.09.005.
- Cohen, L. Manion, L. and Morisson, K. (2018) *Research methods in education*. 8th edn. London: Routledge.
- Coleman, J.A. (2006) 'English-medium Teaching in European Higher Education', *Language Teaching*, 39(1), pp. 1-14. Available at: doi:10.1017/s026144480600320x.
- Colley, H. (2007) Understanding Time in Learning Transition Through the Lifecourse', *International Studies in Sociology of Education*, 17(4), pp. 4277-443. Available at: doi:10.1080/09620210701667103.
- Coleman, J. (2015) 'Social circles during residence abroad: What students do, and who with', *Social interaction, identity and language learning during residence abroad*, 4, pp.33-52.
- Çömlekçi, M. F. (2020) 'Social Media Use Among International Students: Cultural Adaptation and Socialization'. *TRT Akademi*, 5(10), pp.668-685.
- Conti, R.P. (2015) 'Family Estrangement: Establishing a Prevalence Rate', *Journal of Psychology and Behavioral Science*, 3(2), pp. 28-35. Available at: doi:10.15640/jpbs.v3n2a4.
- Cope, D. G. (2014) 'Methods and Meanings: Credibility and Trustworthiness of Qualitative Research', *Oncology nursing forum*, 41(1), pp.89-91. Available at: doi:10.1188/14.onf.89-91.
- Costello, J. (2015) Students' Stories of Studying Abroad: Reflections upon Return. *Journal of International Students*, 5(1), pp.50-59. Available at: <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/159140/>. (Accessed 21 July 2023).
- Crafter, S. and Maunder, R. (2012) 'Understanding Transitions Using a Sociocultural Framework', *Educational and Child Psychology*, 29(1), pp. 10-18. Available at: doi:10.53841/bpsecp.2012.29.1.10.

Creswell, J. W. (2013) *Research design: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed method approaches*. 4th edn. London: SAGE.

Crișan-Mitra, C. and Borza, A. (2015) 'Internationalization in Higher Education', International Conference "Risk in Contemporary Economy". XVIth Edition at Galati (Romania), pp. 187-191.

Crowne, K. and Engle, R. (2016) 'Antecedents of Cross-Cultural Adaptation Stress in Short Term International Assignments', *Organization Management Journal*, 13(1), pp.32-47.

Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/15416518.2015.1129308> (Accessed: 30 May 2023).

Crum, A., Salovey, P. and Achor, S. (2013) 'Rethinking Stress: The Role of Mindsets in Determining the Stress Response', *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 104 (4), pp.716-733. Available at: doi:10.1037/a0031201.

Cullingford, C. (2017) 'Institutional Development and Professional Needs: Some Reflections', in *Professional Development and Institutional Needs*. Routledge, pp. 223–235.

De Mooij, M. and Hofstede, G. (2010) 'The Hofstede Model', *International Journal of Advertising*, 29(1), pp. 85–110. Available at: doi:10.2501/s026504870920104x.

Dinisman, T., Andresen, S., Montserrat, C., Strózik, D. and Strózik, T. (2017) 'Family Structure and Family Relationship from the Child Well-being Perspective: Findings from Comparative Analysis', *Children and Youth Services Review*, 80, pp.105-115. Available at: doi:10.1016/j.childyouth.2017.06.064

Dixit, K. (2020) 'A Study to Assess the Academic Stress and Coping Strategies Among Adolescent Students: a Descriptive Study', *Indian Journal of Applied Research*, 9(12), p. 28-29. Available at: doi: 10.36106/ijar.

Djoudi, M. (2018) 'Algeria', in Weber, A.S. and Hamlaoui, S (eds) *E-Learning in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) Region*. Springer. pp.1-25.

Doody, O. and Doody, C. (2015) 'Conducting a Pilot Study: Case Study of a Novice Researcher', *British Journal of Nursing*, 24(21), pp.1074-1078. Available at: doi:10.12968/bjon.2015.24.21.1074.

Dressler, W., Oths, K. and Gravlee, C. (2005) 'Race and Ethnicity in Public Health Research: Models to Explain Health Disparities', *Annual Review of Anthropology*, 34 (1), pp.231-252. Available at: doi:10.1146/annurev.anthro.34.081804.120505.

Dubey, P., Sarva, M. and Singh, P. P. (2016) 'The application of yoga on effective mind body and stress reduction among students', *Man in India*, 96(4), pp. 1163-1179.

Dunkley, M. (2009) 'What students are actually learning on study abroad and how to improve the learning experience', 20th ISANA international education association conference proceedings, pp. 1-4.

Dwairy, M. and Achoui, M. (2009) 'Adolescents-Family Connectedness: A First Cross-Cultural Research on Parenting and Psychological Adjustment of Children', *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 19(1), pp. 8–15. Available at: doi:10.1007/s10826-009-9335-1.

Edwards, C. (2018) *Social media and mental health*. England: Trigger.

Ekundayo, S. and Clear, A. (2018) 'An activity theory framework to explore social media and nostalgia as coping tools for international students'. International Conference on Learning and Teaching in Computing and Engineering (LaTICE), Auckland (New Zealand). IEEE Computer Society. 18-22 April. pp. 116-118. Available at: doi: 10.1109/LaTICE.2018.00013 (Accessed:17 January 2023).

Elliott, M. (2000) 'The Stress Process in Neighborhood Context', *Health and Place*, 6(4), pp. 287–299. Available at: doi:10.1016/s1353-8292(00)00010-1.

Elliot, D.L. and Kobayashi, S. (2018) 'How can PhD Supervisors Play a Role in Bridging Academic Cultures?', *Teaching in Higher Education*, 24(8), pp. 911–929. Available at: doi:10.1080/13562517.2018.1517305.

Etikan, I., Abubakar Musa, S. and Sunusi Alkassim, R. (2016) 'Comparison of Convenience Sampling and Purposive Sampling', *American Journal of Theoretical and Applied Statistics*, 5(1), pp. 1-4. Available at: doi: 10.11648/j.ajtas.20160501.11.

European Commission (2017) *Overview of the Higher Education System: Algeria*.

European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice (2015) *The European Higher Education Area in 2015: Bologna Process Implementation Report*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Available at: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2797/128576> (Accessed: 09 July 2019).

- Eurostat Statistics Explained (2019) *Migration and migrant population statistics*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Migration_and_migrant_population_statistics (Accessed: 11 July 2019).
- Fekih, M. (2020) *English as Foreign Language (EFL) teachers' perspectives on dyslexia in Algerian middle schools*. PhD thesis. University of the West of Scotland. Available at: <https://ethos.bl.uk/OrderDetails.do?uin=uk.bl.ethos.847530> (Accessed: 03 April 2022).
- Flick, U. (2007) *Designing qualitative research*. London: Sage.
- Flick, U. (2009) *An introduction to qualitative research*. 4th edn. London: SAGE.
- Flick, U. (2014) *An introduction to qualitative research*. 5th edn. London: SAGE.
- Fink, G. (ed) (2016) *Stress: Concepts, Cognition, Emotion, and Behavior*. Academic Press.
- Firang, D. (2020) 'The Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on International Students in Canada', *International Social Work*, 63(6), pp. 820–824. Available at: doi:10.1177/0020872820940030.
- Folkman, S. and Lazarus, R. S. (1980) 'An Analysis of Coping in a Middle-aged Community Sample', *Journal of health and social behavior*, 21(3), pp. 219-239. Available at: doi:10.2307/2136617.
- Forbes-Mewett, H. (2019) Mental health and international students: issues, challenges and effective practice. *International Education Association of Australia (IEAA)*. Available at: <https://www.ieaa.org.au/documents/item/1616>
- Gale, T. and Parker, S. (2014) 'Navigating Change: a Typology of Student Transition in Higher Education', *Studies in Higher Education*, 39(5), pp. 734–753. Available at: doi:10.1080/03075079.2012.721351.
- Garbóczy, S., Szemán-Nagy, A., Ahmad, M. S., Harsányi, S., Ocsenás, D., Rekenyi, V., Al-Tammemi, A.B. and Kolozsvári, L. R. (2021) 'Health Anxiety, Perceived Stress, and Coping Styles in the Shadow of the COVID-19', *BMC psychology*, 9(1), pp. 1-13. Available at: doi:10.1186/s40359-021-00560-3.
- Ghatol, S. D. (2017) 'Academic Stress Among Higher Secondary School Students: a Review', *International Journal of Advanced Research in Education and Technology*, 4 (1), pp.38-41.
- Gherzouli, I. (2019) 'Educational Reforms and Language Planning Quandary in Algeria: An Illustration with Arabization', *Sustainable Multilingualism*, 15 (1), pp.27-47.

- Gherzouli, I. (2019) 'Towards a Democratic Algerian Curriculum Development through Secondary School EFL Teachers' Involvement', *International Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*, 11(1), pp. 1-22.
- Ghiat, B. (2019) 'Women Managing Men Subordinates in a Males' society: The Case of Female Entrepreneurs in Algeria', *Open Journal of Women Studies*, 1(2), 35-40.
- Ghodbane, A. (2020) *The experience of student sojourners and their hybrid identity development while studying abroad: the case of Algerian PhD students in the UK*. PhD thesis. University of the West of Scotland. Available at: <https://ethos.bl.uk/OrderDetails.do?uin=uk.bl.ethos.835479> (Accessed: 03 May 2023).
- Giannelli, G. and Mangiavacchi, L. (2010) 'Children's Schooling and Parental Migration: Empirical Evidence on the 'Left-behind' Generation in Albania', *Labour*, 24, pp.76-92.
- Gindling, T.H. and Poggio, S. (2012) 'Family Separation and Reunification as a Factor in the Educational Success of Immigrant Children', *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 38(7), pp. 1155-1173.
- Golestani, B.N. (2011) *First Ramadan Away from Home, Al Talib*. Available at: <https://al-talib.org/ramadan-away-from-home/> (Accessed: 05 May 2023).
- Gomes, C., Berry, M., Alzougool, B. and Chang, S. (2014) 'Home Away from Home: International Students and their Identity-Based Social Networks in Australia', *Journal of International Students*, 4(1), pp. 2-15. Available at: doi:10.32674/jis.v4i1.493.
- González, J. J., Kula, S. M., González, V. V., and Paik, S. J. (2017) 'Context of Latino students' family separation during and after immigration: Perspectives, challenges, and opportunities for collaborative efforts', *School Community Journal*, 27 (2), pp.211-228.
- Goodsell, T.L. and Whiting, J.B. (2016) 'An Aristotelian Theory of Family', *Journal of Family Theory & Review*, 8(4), pp. 484–502. Available at: doi:10.1111/jftr.12169.
- Gordon, M. (2009) *A dictionary of sociology*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Gould, D. (2018). A study of cultural awareness and transformative learning through participation in study abroad. PhD thesis. Rowan University. Available at: <https://rdw.rowan.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=3610&context=etd> (Accessed: 03 May 2023).

Guerriche, A. (2020) *Intercultural identity development through study abroad programmes: an ethnographic case study of Algerian students in a UK university*. PhD thesis. University of Bath. Available at: <https://ethos.bl.uk/OrderDetails.do?uin=uk.bl.ethos.828304> (Accessed: 03 April 2022).

Guest, G., MacQueen, K. M. and Namey, E. E. (2011) *Applied thematic analysis*. Sage publications.

Haksever, A. M., and Manisali, E. (2000) 'Assessing Supervision Requirements of PhD students: The Case of Construction Management and Engineering in the UK', *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 25(1), pp.19-32. Available at: doi:10.1080/030437900308616.

Handa, N. and Fallon, W. (2006) 'Taking the Mountain to Mohammed: Transitioning International Graduate Students into Higher Education in Australia', *International Journal for Educational Integrity*, 2(2). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.21913/ijeiv2i2.89>.

Harvey, T., Robinson, C. and Welch, A. (2018) 'The Lived Experiences of International Students Who's Family Remains At Home', *Journal of International Students*, 7(3), pp. 748–763. Available at: doi:10.32674/jis.v7i3.297.

Hemer, S. R. (2012) 'Informality, Power and Relationships in Postgraduate Supervision: Supervising PhD Candidates over Coffee', *Higher Education Research & Development*, 31 (6), pp.827-839.

Higham, J. E., Ramírez, C. A., Green, M. A. and Morse, A. P. (2020) 'UK COVID-19 Lockdown: 100 Days of Air Pollution Reduction?', *Air Quality, Atmosphere & Health*. 14 (3), pp.325–332. Available at: doi:10.1007/s11869-020-00937-0.

Hiitola, J. and Vähä-Savo, V. (2021) 'Genres of Departure: Forced Migrants' Family Separation and Personal Narratives', *Nordic Journal of Migration Research*, 11(3), pp. 235-249. Available at: doi:10.33134/njmr.372.

Hirai, R., Frazier, P. and Syed, M. (2015) 'Psychological and sociocultural adjustment of first year international students: Trajectories and predictors', *Journal of counseling psychology*, 62(3), p.438. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/cou0000085> (Accessed: 29 May 2023).

- Hofstede, G. (1986) 'Cultural Differences in Teaching and Learning', *International Journal of intercultural relations*, pp. 10(3), 301-320.
- Holligan, C. (2013) 'The Cake and Custard is Good!' A Qualitative Study of Teenage Childrens' Experience of being in Prison', *Children and Society*, 29 (5), pp.366-376.
- Holmes, A.G.D. (2020) 'Researcher Positionality - A Consideration of Its Influence and Place in Qualitative Research - A New Researcher Guide', *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, 8(4), pp. 1–10. Available at: doi:10.34293/education.v8i4.3232.
- Hopwood, N., Alexander, P. Harris-Huemmert, S., McAlpine, L. and Wagstaff, S. (2011) 'The hidden realities of life as a doctoral student' in Kumar, V. and Lee, A. (eds.) *Doctoral education in international context: Connecting local, regional, and global perspectives*. Serdang: Penerbit Universiti Putra, pp.1-13.
- Hudzik, J. K. (2010) 'The economy, higher education, and campus internationalization', *International Educator*, 19(3), pp. 96-102.
- Hyldegård, J. S. and Hertzum, M. (2016) 'Coping with private and academic information needs abroad: An exploratory study of international students', SIG-SI Workshop on the Social Informatics of Work and Play at the ASIS&T. Annual Meeting 2016 of the Association for Information Science and Technology at Copenhagen (Denmark), 14-18 October. pp. 14-18.
- Jacka, M. and Scott, P.R. (2011) *Auditing social media: A governance and risk guide*. John Wiley & Sons. Online. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=6ymUej505x0C&pg=PA5&dq=there+is+no+single+recognized+definition+for+social+media&hl=fr&sa=X&ved=0ahUKEwiy9-ObkrXnAhUUm1wKHZg7CroQ6AEIKDAA#v=onepage&q=there%20is%20no%20single%20recognized%20definition%20for%20social%20media&f=false> (Accessed: 3 February 2020).
- James, N., and Busher, H. (2009) *Online interviewing*. London: SAGE.
- Jazvac-Martek, M., Chen, S. and McAlpine, L. (2011) 'Tracking the Doctoral Student Experience over Time: Cultivating Agency in Diverse Spaces' in McAlpine, L. and Amundsen, C. (eds) *Doctoral education: Research-based strategies for doctoral students, supervisors and administrators*. Dordrecht: Springer.

- Jindal-Snape, D., and Rienties, B. (2016) 'Understanding multiple and multi-dimensional transitions of international higher education students: Setting the scene', in *Multi-dimensional transitions of international students to higher education*. Routledge, pp.1-17.
- Johnson, A. G. (2000) *The Blackwell dictionary of sociology: a user's guide to sociological language*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Kandasamy, N. (2018) 'Unravelling Memories of Family Separation Among Sri Lankan Tamils Resettled in Australia, 1983–2000', *Immigrants & Minorities*, 36(2), pp. 143-160.
- Kaplan, A. and Haenlein, M. (2010) 'Users of the World, Unite! The Challenges and Opportunities of Social Media', *Business Horizons*, 53 (1), pp.59-68.
- Kaplan, A. and Haenlein, M. (2009) 'The Fairyland of Second Life: Virtual Social Worlds and How to Use Them', *Business Horizons*, 52 (6), pp.563-572.
- Karuppan, C.M. and Barari, M. (2010) 'Perceived discrimination and international students' learning: an empirical investigation', *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 33(1), pp. 67–83. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/1360080x.2011.537013>.
- Kausar, R. (2010) 'Perceived Stress, Academic Workloads and Use of Coping Strategies by University Students', *Journal of behavioural sciences*, 20(1), pp.31-45.
- Kaushik, V. and Walsh, C. A. (2019) 'Pragmatism as a Research Paradigm and Its Implications for Social Work Research', *Social Sciences*, 8 (9), p. 255.
- Kee, C. E. (2021) 'The Impact of Covid-19: Graduate Students' Emotional and Psychological Experiences', *Journal of Human Behavior in the Social Environment*, 31 (1-4), pp.476-488.
- Kelso, T., French, D. and Fernandez, M. (2005) 'Stress and coping in primary caregivers of children with a disability: a qualitative study using the Lazarus and Folkman Process Model of Coping', *Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs*, 5 (1), pp.3-10.
- Khammar, Z. and Dekoumi, B. (2022) 'Characteristics of Kinship in Algerian Society', *International Journal of Innovative Studies in Sociology and Humanities*, 7(10), pp. 9–17.
- Khatun, R. (2014) 'Analysis of the Causes of the Independent Movement of Algeria', *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 19 (6), pp.79-95.
- Kılıçoğlu, A. (2018) 'Qualitative Research for Educational Science Researchers: a Review of an Introduction to Qualitative Research', *The Qualitative Report*, 23 (4), pp.949-951.

- Kietzmann, J., Silvestre, B., McCarthy, I. and Pitt, L. (2012) 'Unpacking the Social Media Phenomenon: towards a Research Agenda', *Journal of Public Affairs*, 12 (2), pp.109-119.
- Kim, Y. (2010) 'The Pilot Study in Qualitative Inquiry', *Qualitative Social Work*, 10(2), pp.190-206.
- Kim, T. (2009) 'Transnational Academic Mobility, Internationalization and Interculturality in Higher Education', *Intercultural education*, 20(5), pp. 395-405.
- Kimura, H., and Nakajima, T. (2011) 'Designing Persuasive Applications to Motivate Sustainable Behavior in Collectivist Cultures', *PsychNology Journal*, 9(1), pp. 7-28.
- King, R. and Sondhi, G. (2017) 'International student migration: a comparison of UK and Indian students' motivations for studying abroad', *Globalisation, Societies and Education*, 16(2), pp.176-191. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14767724.2017.1405244> (Accessed: 21 June 2023).
- Kleres, J. (2011) 'Emotions and Narrative Analysis: A Methodological Approach', *Journal for the theory of social behaviour*, 41(2), pp.182-202.
- Knight, J. (2004) 'Internationalization Remodeled: Definition, Approaches, and Rationales', *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 8(1), pp. 5-31.
- Kosheleva, E.Y., Samofalova, E.I., Holtman, C. and Kopotilova, Y.E. (2015) 'Chinese Students in Russia: Causes of Migration and Basic Educational Behavioral Tenets', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 215, pp. 38-42.
- Krohne, H. W. (2002) 'Stress and Coping Theories', *International Encyclopedia of the Social Behavioral Sciences*, 22, pp. 15163-15170.
- Kumar, R. (2014) *Research methodology: a step-by-step guide for beginners*. 4th edn. London: SAGE.
- Kumar, V., Doshi, K. U., Khan, W. H. and Rathore, A. S. (2020) 'Covid-19 pandemic: Mechanism, Diagnosis, and Treatment', *Journal of Chemical Technology & Biotechnology*. 96 (2), pp.299–308. Available at: [doi:10.1002/jctb.6641](https://doi.org/10.1002/jctb.6641).
- Lacina, J. G. (2002) 'Preparing International Students for a Successful Social Experience in Higher Education', *New Directions for higher education*, (117), p. 21-28. Available at: [doi:10.1002/he.43](https://doi.org/10.1002/he.43).

- Lazarus, R. S. and Folkman, S. (1984) *Stress, appraisal, and coping*. Springer publishing company. Online. Available at : https://books.google.co.uk/books?hl=fr&lr=&id=i-ySQQuUpr8C&oi=fnd&pg=PR5&dq=lazarus+folkman+stress+appraisal+and+coping+1984+&ots=DfLMIqddQi&sig=yJMrhz8BTsJa_dW-OXsqKdu6me4&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=lazarus%20folkman%20stress%20appraisal%20and%20coping%201984&f=false (Accessed 24 May 2020).
- Lee, J., EunYoung, K. and vWachholtz, A. (2016) ‘The effect of perceived stress on life satisfaction’, *Korean Journal of Youth Studies*, 23(10), p. 29. Available at: doi:10.21509/kjys.2016.10.23.10.29.
- Lee, C., Sung, Y.-T., Zhou, Y. and Lee, S. (2017) ‘The Relationships Between the Seriousness of Leisure Activities, Social Support and School Adaptation among Asian International Students in the U.S.’, *Leisure Studies*, 37(2), pp. 197–210.
- Lefdahl-Davis, E.M. and Perrone-McGovern, K.M. (2015) ‘The cultural adjustment of Saudi women international students: A qualitative examination’, *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 46(3), pp.406-434. Available at: doi:10.1177/0022022114566680.
- Leigh, J.P. (2015) ‘Skilled Immigrants and the Negotiation of Family Relations During Settlement in Calgary, Alberta’, *Journal of International Migration and Integration*, 17(4), pp. 1065–1083.
- Le Roux, C. (2017) ‘Language in Education in Algeria: a Historical Vignette of a ‘Most Severe’ Sociolinguistic Problem’, *Language & History*, 60 (2), pp.112-128.
- Lewis, G.J. (1982) *Human migration: a geographical perspective*. London: Croom Helm.
- Li, G., Chen, W., and Duanmu, J.L. (2010) ‘Determinants of International Students’ Academic Performance A Comparison Between Chinese and Other International Students’, *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 14(4), pp. 389-405.
- Lincoln, Y.S. and Guba, E.G. (1985) *Naturalistic Inquiry*. SAGE.
- Liu, Q. and Turner, D. (2018) ‘Identity and national identity’, *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, 50(12), pp.1080-1088. Available <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131857.2018.1434076> (Accessed: 24 March 2023).

- Lundholm, E., Garvill, J., Malmberg, G., and Westin, K. (2004) 'Forced or Free Movers? The Motives, Voluntariness and Selectivity of Interregional Migration in the Nordic Countries', *Population, Space and Place*, 10, pp. 59-72.
- Mack, L. (2010) 'The Philosophical Underpinnings of Educational Research', *Polyglossia*, 19, pp. 5-11.
- Mackenzie, N. and Knipe, S. (2006) 'Research Dilemmas: Paradigms, Methods and Methodology', *Issues in educational research*, 16 (2), pp. 193-205.
- Madge, C., Breines, M. R., Dalu, M. T. B., Gunter, A., Mittelmeier, J., Prinsloo, P. and Raghuram, P. (2019) 'WhatsApp Use among African International Distance Education (IDE) Students: Transferring, Translating and Transforming Educational experiences', *Learning, Media and Technology*, 44(3), pp. 267-282. Available at: doi:10.1080/17439884.2019.1628048.
- Maes, S., Vingerhoets, A. and Van Heck, G. (1987) 'The Study of Stress and Disease: Some Developments and Requirements', *Social Science and Medicine*, 25 (6), pp.567-578.
- Maharaja, G. (2018) 'The Impact of Study Abroad on College Students' Intercultural Competence and Personal Development', *International Research and Review*, 7(2), 18–41. Available at: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1188735.pdf>
- Mak, A.S., Bodycott, P. and Ramburuth, P. (2015) 'Beyond host language proficiency: Coping resources predicting international students' satisfaction', *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 19(5), pp.460-475. doi:10.1177/1028315315587109.
- Malecela, I. O. (2016) 'Usage of WhatsApp among postgraduate students of kulliyah of education, International Islamic University Malaysia', *International Journal of Advanced Engineering Research and Science*, 3(10), pp. 126-137.
- Maleku, A., Kim, Y. K., Kirsch, J., Um, M. Y., Haran, H., Yu, M. and Moon, S. S. (2021) 'The Hidden Minority: Discrimination and Mental Health among International Students in the US during the Covid-19 Pandemic', *Health & Social Care in the Community*, 30 (5), p.e2419–e2432.
- Malterud, k. (2001) 'The Art and Science of Clinical knowledge: Evidence beyond Measures and Numbers', *The lancet*, 358, pp. 397-400.

- Mami, N. A. (2013) 'Teaching English under the LMD reform: the Algerian experience', *International Journal of Educational and Pedagogical Sciences*, 7(4), pp. 910-913.
- Maundeni, T. (2001) 'The Role of Social Networks in the Adjustment of African Students to British Society: Students' Perceptions', *Race Ethnicity and Education*, 4 (3), pp.253-276.
- Maudarbekova, B. and Kashkinbayeva, Z. (2014) 'Internationalization of Higher Education in Kazakhstan', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 116, pp. 4092-4097.
- Mazzarol, T. and Soutar, G.N. (2002) "'Push Pull" Factors Influencing International Student Destination Choice', *The International Journal of Educational Management*, 16(2), pp. 82-90.
- McDermott-Levy, R. (2011) 'Going alone: The lived experience of female Arab-Muslim nursing students living and studying in the United States,' *Nursing Outlook*, 59(5), pp. 266-277.
- McIntosh, J. C., and Islam, S. (2010) 'Beyond the veil: The influence of Islam on female entrepreneurship in a conservative Muslim context', *International Management Review*, 6(1), 102-108.
- McMahon, P. (2016) *A grounded theory of international postgraduate students in a British university: making the grade*. PhD thesis. Plymouth University. Available at: <https://ethos.bl.uk/OrderDetails.do?uin=uk.bl.ethos.686109> (Accessed: 03 May 2023).
- McMichael, C. (2002) "'Everywhere is Allah's Place': Islam and the Everyday Life of Somali Women in Melbourne, Australia', *Journal of Refugee Studies*, 15(2), pp. 171–188. Available at: doi:10.1093/jrs/15.2.171.
- Menaga, S. and Chandrasekaran, V. (2014) 'A Study on Academic Stress of Higher Secondary School Students', *Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies*, 2 (14), pp.1973-1981.
- Menaga, S., and Chandrasekaran, V. (2014) 'A study on academic stress of higher secondary school students', *Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies*, 2(14), 1973-1981.
- Meng, Q., Zhu, C. and Cao, C. (2017) 'Chinese international students' social connectedness, social and academic adaptation: the mediating role of global competence', *Higher Education*, 75(1), pp. 131–147. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-017-0129-x>.

- Merriam, S.B. (2009) *Qualitative research: a guide to design and implementation*. San Francisco: John Wiley & Sons.
- Merriam, S. B. and Tisdell, E. J. (2016) *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation*. 4th edn. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Miller, A., Hess, J., Bybee, D. and Goodkind, J. (2018) ‘Understanding the Mental Health Consequences of Family Separation for Refugees: Implications for Policy and Practice’, *American Journal of Orthopsychiatry*, 88 (1), pp.26-37.
- Mir, S., and Sarroub, L. K. (2019) ‘Islamophobia in US education’ in Zempi, I. and Awan, I. *The Routledge International Handbook of Islamophobia*. Routledge, pp. 298-309.
- Misirlis, N., Zwaan, M., Sotiriou, A., and Weber, D. (2020) ‘International Students’ Loneliness, Depression and Stress Levels in Covid-19 Crisis: The Role of Social Media and the Host University’, *Journal of Contemporary Education Theory & Research*, 4(2), p.20–25.
- Montgomery, C. (2010) *Understanding the International Student Experience*. Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Moskal, M. and Tyrrell, N. (2015) ‘Family Migration Decision-making, Step-migration and Separation: Children's Experiences in European Migrant Worker Families’, *Children's Geographies*, 14 (4), pp.453-467.
- Mossakowski, K. (2014) ‘Stress and Mental Illness’, *The Wiley Blackwell Encyclopedia of Health, Illness, Behavior, and Society*, pp.1-5.
- Moulds, M. L., Bisby, M. A., Wild, J. and Bryant, R. A. (2020) ‘Rumination in Posttraumatic Stress Disorder: A Systematic Review’, *Clinical Psychology Review*, 82, p.101910. Available at: doi:10.1016/j.cpr.2020.101910.
- Mourad, K. and Avery, H. (2019) ‘The Sustainability of Post-Conflict Development: The Case of Algeria’, *Sustainability*, 11 (11), p.30-36.
- Msengi, I. G. (2007) ‘Sources of Stress and Its Impact on Health Behaviors and Academic Performance of International Students at a Comprehensive Midwestern University’, *International Journal of Global Health and Health Disparities*, 5 (1), pp.55-69.
- Murray, L. and Barnes, M. (2010) ‘Have Families Been Rethought? Ethic of Care, Family and ‘Whole Family’ Approaches’, *Social Policy and Society*, 9 (4), pp.533-544.

Nada, C.I. and Araújo, H.C. (2018) 'Migration and Education: A Narrative Approach to the Experience of Foreign Students in Portugal.', *London Review of Education*, 16(2), pp. 308-324.

Nada, C. I., Montgomery, C. and Araújo, H. C. (2018) 'You went to Europe and returned different': transformative learning experiences of international students in Portugal', *European Educational Research Journal*, 17(5), pp. 696–713. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1474904118765334>

Naseem, Z. and Khalid, R. (2010) 'Positive thinking in coping with stress and health outcomes: Literature review', *Journal of Research & Reflections in Education (JRRE)*, 4(1), pp 42-61.

Nelly Trevinyo-Rodríguez, R. and Bontis, N. (2010) 'Family ties and emotions: a missing piece in the knowledge transfer puzzle', *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 17(3), pp. 418–436.

Newton, T., Handy, J. and Fineman, S. (1996) *Managing stress*. London: Sage.

Nguyen, O. and Balakrishnan, V. (2020) 'International Students in Australia – during and after COVID-19', *Higher Education Research & Development*, 39(7), pp.1372-1376.

Norton, J. and Brett, M. (2011) National Summit on the Mental Health of Tertiary Students.

Brett, M., J. Norton, and R. James. (2011) 'Healthy students, healthy institutions', National Summit on the Mental Health of Tertiary Students. (Melbourne) 4-5 August.

O'Donnell V.L., Kean, M. and Stevens, G. (2016) *Student transition in higher education Concepts, theories and practices*. Higher Education Academy.

O'Donnel, V.L., Tobbell, J., Lawthom, R., and Zammit, M. (2009) 'Transition to Postgraduate Study Practice, Participation and the Widening Participation Agenda', *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 10(1), pp. 26-40.

Office for National Statistics (2019) *Migration Statistics Quarterly Report: February 2019*. Available at: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/populationandmigration/internationalmigration/bulletins/migrationstatisticsquarterlyreport/february2019#:~:text=An%20estimat>

ed%20283%2C000%20more%20people%20came%20to%20the%20UK%20with,left%20the%20UK%20(emigration) (Accessed: July 10, 2019).

Office for National Statistics (2018) *Migration Statistics Quarterly Report: November 2018*. Available at: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/populationandmigration/internationalmigration/bulletins/migrationstatisticsquarterlyreport/november2018#non-eu-long-term-student-immigration-remained-broadly-stable-from-2013-to-2017> (Accessed: 10 July 2019).

Okhovat, S., Hirsch, A., Hoang, K. and Dowd, R. (2017) 'Rethinking Resettlement and Family Reunion in Australia,' *Alternative Law Journal*, 42(4), pp. 273–278.

O'Reilly, M. and Kiyimba, N. (2015) *Advanced qualitative research : a guide to using theory*. London: SAGE.

Orellana, M. L., Darder, A., Pérez, A., & Salinas, J. (2016) 'Improving Doctoral Success by Matching PhD Students with Supervisors', *International Journal of Doctoral Studies*, 11, pp. 87-103.

Osborne, C., & McLanahan, S. (2007) 'Partnership Instability and Child Well-being', *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 69(4), pp.1065-1083.

Ouadah-Bedidi, Z. (2018) 'Gender Inequity in Education in Algeria: When Inequalities are Reversed', *Journal of Education & Social Policy*, 5(2), pp. 84-105. Available at: doi:10.30845/jesp.v5n2a10.

Ozga, J. and Jones, R. (2006) 'Travelling and Embedded Policy: the Case of Knowledge Transfer', *Journal of Education Policy*, 21(1), pp. 1-17.

Papatsiba, V. (2006) 'Making Higher Education More European through Student Mobility? Revisiting EU Initiatives in the Context of the Bologna Process', *Comparative Education*, 42(1), pp. 93-111.

Papen, M., Niemand, T., Siems, F. and Kraus, S. (2017) 'The Effect of Stress on Customer Perception of the Frontline Employee: an Experimental Study', *Review of Managerial Science*, 3 (4), pp.725-747.

Park, B. and Lester, D. (2006) 'Social Integration and Suicide in South Korea', *Crisis*, 27 (1), pp.48-50.

Patton, M.Q. (2015) *Qualitative Research and Evaluation Methods: Integrating Theory and Practice*. Available at: <http://ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BB18275167>.

Pearlin, L. I. (1989) 'The Sociological Study of Stress', *Journal of health and social behaviour*, 30 (3), pp.241-256.

Pieper, J. Z., van Uden, M. H. and van der Valk, L. (2018) 'Praying as a form of religious coping in Dutch highly educated Muslim women of Moroccan descent', *Archive for the Psychology of Religion*, 40(2-3), pp.141-162.

Pietromonaco, P. R., Uchino, B. and Dunkel Schetter, C. (2013) 'Close Relationship Processes and Health: Implications of Attachment theory for Health and Disease', *Health Psychology*, 32 (5), pp.499–513.

Ploner, J. (2018) 'International students' transitions to UK Higher Education—revisiting the concept and practice of academic hospitality', *Journal of Research in International Education*, 17(2), pp.164-178. Available at: doi: 10.1177/1475240918786690.

Prescott, A. and Hellstén, M. (2005) 'Hanging Together Even with Non-Native Speakers: The International Student Transition Experience'. *Internationalizing Higher Education*. pp. 75-95.

Qadeer, T., Javed, M.K., Manzoor, A., Wu, M. and Zaman, S.I. (2021) 'The Experience of International Students and Institutional Recommendations: A Comparison Between the Students from the Developing and Developed Regions', *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. Available at: doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2021.667230.

Rabehi, A. (2021) *Investigating the status of intercultural communicative competence in Algerian middle schools: the case of the new curriculum of EFL*. PhD thesis. Lancaster University. Available at: <https://ethos.bl.uk/OrderDetails.do?uin=uk.bl.ethos.839109> (Accessed: 06 June 2023).

Rathakrishnan, B., Bikar Singh, S.S., Kamaluddin, M.R., Ghazali, M.F., Yahaya, A., Mohamed, N.H. and Krishnan, A.R. (2021) 'Homesickness and Socio-Cultural Adaptation towards Perceived Stress among International Students of a Public University in Sabah: An Exploration Study for Social Sustainability', *Sustainability*, 13(9), p. 4924. doi:10.3390/su13094924.

Reger, Jo. (2016) 'Transitions', *Gender and Society*, 30(1), pp. 5-8.

Reyes, M. (2008) 'Migration and Filipino children left-behind: A literature review', Miriam College, Women and Gender Institute. Paper prepared for the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF).

Rezig, N. (2011) 'Teaching English in Algeria and Educational Reforms: An Overview on the Factors Entailing Students Failure in Learning Foreign Languages at University', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 29, pp.1327 – 1333.

Ridley, D. (2012) *The literature review: a step-by-step guide for students*. 2nd edn. London: SAGE.

Ritchie, J., Lewis, J., McNaughton Nicholls, C. and Ormston, R. (2014) *Qualitative research practice: a guide for social science students and researchers*. 2nd edn. London: SAGE.

Robinson-Pant, A. (2009) 'Changing Academies: Exploring International PhD Students' Perspectives on 'Host' and 'Home' Universities', *Higher Education Research & Development*, 28 (4), pp.417-429.

Rui, J.R. and Wang, H. (2015) 'Social network sites and international students' cross-cultural adaptation', *Computers in Human Behavior*, 49, pp. 400–411. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.03.041>.

Sadoudi, Y. (2021) *Travelling to the West': voices of Algerian PhD students' transition to Britain*. PhD thesis. Canterbury Christ Church University. Available at: <https://ethos.bl.uk/OrderDetails.do?uin=uk.bl.ethos.862075> (Accessed: 03 May 2023).

Saeed, T. (2019) 'Islamophobia and the Muslim student' in Zempi, I. and Awan, I. *The Routledge International Handbook of Islamophobia*. Routledge, pp. 175-187.

Sakurai, T., McCall-Wolf a, F. and Kashima, E.S. (2010) 'Building Intercultural Links: The Impact of a Multicultural Intervention Programme on Social Ties of International Students in Australia', *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 27, pp. 6-8.

Saldaña, J. (2016) *The Coding Manual for Qualitative Researchers*. 3rd edn. London: SAGE.

Sapranaviciute, L., Padaiga, Z. and Pauzienie, N. (2013) 'The Stress Coping Strategies and Depressive Symptoms in International Students', *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 84, pp. 827-831.

- Saravanan, C., Mohamad, M. and Alias, A. (2019) 'Coping Strategies Used by International Students Who Recovered from Homesickness and Depression in Malaysia', *International journal of intercultural relations*, 68, pp. 77-87.
- Sarnou, H. A., Koç, S., Houcine, S. and Bouhadiba, F. (2012) 'LMD: New System in the Algerian University', *Arab World English Journal*, 3(4), pp. 179-194.
- Saubert, S.B. (2014) *A phenomenological exploration of the experiences of international students*. PhD thesis. University of Leeds. Available at: <https://etheses.whiterose.ac.uk/8614/> (Accessed: 03 May 2023).
- Savic, M., Chur-Hansen, A., Mahmood, M.A. and Moore, V. (2013) 'Separation from family and its impact on the mental health of Sudanese refugees in Australia: a qualitative study', *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Public Health*, 37(4), pp. 383–388. Available at: doi:10.1111/1753-6405.12088.
- Savignon, S. (2017) 'Communicative Competence', *The TESOL Encyclopedia of English Language Teaching*, pp.1-7. doi.org/10.1002/9781118784235.eelt0047.
- Savin-Baden, M. and Major, C.H. (2013) *Qualitative research: the Essential Guide to Theory and Practice*. London: Routledge.
- Saw, G., Abbott, W., Donaghey, J. and McDonald, C. (2013) 'Social Media for International Students – It's Not All about Facebook', *Library Management*, 34(3), pp.156-174.
- Sawir, E., Marginson, S., Deumert, A., Nyland, C. and Ramia, G. (2007) 'Loneliness and International Students: An Australian Study', *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 12(2), pp. 148–180. Available at: doi:10.1177/1028315307299699.
- Sayad, A. (2000) 'El Ghorba', *Ethnography*, 1(2), pp. 147–171. Available at: doi:10.1177/14661380022230714.
- Sayad, A. (2004) *The Suffering of the Immigrant*. Translated by D. Macey. Cambridge: Polity.
- Schartner, A. (2014) 'You Cannot Talk with all of the Strangers in a Pub': a Longitudinal Case Study of International Postgraduate Students' Social Ties at a British University', *Higher Education*, 69(2), pp. 225–241. Available at: doi:10.1007/s10734-014-9771-8.

Schwartz, S. and Meyer, I. (2010) 'Mental Health Disparities Research: The Impact of within and between Group Analyses on Tests of Social Stress Hypotheses', *Social Science and Medicine*, 70 (8), pp.1111-1118.

Scott, J. (ed.) (2014) *A dictionary of sociology*. 4 edn. Online. Available: <https://www.oxfordreference.com/view/10.1093/acref/9780199683581.001.0001/acref-9780199683581-e-2268?p=emailAu26r/YqocbzI> (Accessed: 26 July 2020).

Scotland, J. (2012) 'Exploring the Philosophical Underpinnings of Research: Relating Ontology and Epistemology to the Methodology and Methods of the Scientific, Interpretive, and Critical Research Paradigms', *English Language Teaching*, 5 (9), pp.9-16.

Selougui, S. (2019) *The Cultural Content of Algerian EFL Textbooks: Stakeholders' Perspectives*. PhD thesis. University of the West of Scotland. Available at: <https://ethos.bl.uk/OrderDetails.do?uin=uk.bl.ethos.848025> (Accessed: 03 May 2023).

Settersten Jr, R. A., Bernardi, L., Härkönen, J., Antonucci, T. C., Dykstra, P. A., Heckhausen, J., ... & Thomson, E. (2020) 'Understanding the Effects of Covid-19 through a Life Course Lens', *Advances in Life Course Research*, 45, 100360.

Sharma, R. (2013) 'The Family and Family Structure Classification Redefined for the Current Times', *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 2(4), pp.306-310.

Siddiqui, S. and Singh, T. (2016) 'Social Media its Impact with Positive and Negative Aspects', *International Journal of Computer Applications Technology and Research*, 5 (2), pp.71-75.

Shah, S.R. and Al-Bargi, A. (2013) 'Research Paradigms: Researchers' Worldviews, Theoretical Frameworks and Study Designs', *Arab World English Journal*, 4(4), pp. 252-264.

Shapka, J. D., Domene, J. F., Khan, S., and Yang, L. M. (2016) 'Online Versus In-person Interviews with Adolescents: An Exploration of Data Equivalence', *Computers in human behaviour*, 58, pp. 361-367.

Sharman, S., Roberts, A., Bowden-Jones, H. and Strang, J. (2021) 'Gambling in Covid-19 Lockdown in the UK: Depression, Stress, and Anxiety', *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 12. Available at: doi:10.3389/fpsyt.2021.621497.

Shively, C. and Willard, S. (2012) 'Behavioral and Neurobiological Characteristics of Social Stress Versus Depression in Nonhuman Primates', *Experimental Neurology*, 233 (1), pp.87-94.

- Silver, A. (2011) 'Families Across Borders: The Emotional Impacts of Migration on Origin Families*', *International Migration*, 52(3), pp. 194–220.
- Sinanan, J. and Gomes, C. (2020) "'Everybody needs friends': Emotions, Social Networks and Digital Media in the Friendships of International Students", *International Journal of Cultural Studies*, 23(5), pp. 674–691. Available at: doi:10.1177/1367877920922249.
- Smail Salhi, Z. (2008) 'Gender and Diversity in the Middle East and North Africa', *British Journal of Middle Eastern Studies*, 35(3), pp. 295–304. Available at: doi:10.1080/13530190802579707.
- Smith, R.A. and Khawaja, N.G. (2011) 'A Review of the Acculturation Experiences of International Students', *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 35, pp. 699-713.
- Søren Ventegodt, M. D., and Wiedemann, G. (2014) 'An Existential Theory of Stress', *Journal of Alternative Medicine Research*, 6 (1), pp.31-33.
- Stahl, N. A., and King, J. R. (2020) 'Expanding Approaches for Research: Understanding and Using Trustworthiness in Qualitative Research', *Journal of Developmental Education*, 44(1), 26-28, pp. 26-28.
- Stojanovich, L. (2010) 'Stress and Autoimmunity', *Autoimmunity Reviews*, 9 (5), pp. A271-A276.
- Suárez-Orozco, C., Bang, H.J., and Kim, H.Y. (2011) 'I Felt Like My Heart Was Staying Behind: Psychological Implications of Family Separations and Reunifications for Immigrant Youth', *Journal of Adolescent Research*, 26(2), pp. 222–257.
- Sullivan, C. and Kashubeck-West, S. (2015) 'The Interplay of International Students' Acculturative Stress, Social Support, and Acculturation Modes', *Journal of International Students*, 5(1), pp. 1–11. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.32674/jis.v5i1.438>.
- Sultana, S. (2017) 'Social Networking Sites (SNS) and Family Relationship: A Study on Youths of Dhaka City', *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 22 (04), pp.46-52.
- Sun, G.-Q., Wang, S.-F., Li, M.-T., Li, L., Zhang, J., Zhang, W., Jin, Z. and Feng, G.-L. (2020) Transmission Dynamics of covid-19 in Wuhan, China: Effects of lockdown and medical resources, *Nonlinear Dynamics*, 101 (3), pp.1981–1993.

- Sverdlik, A., Hall, N. C., McAlpine, L., and Hubbard, K. (2018) 'The PhD Experience: A Review of the Factors Influencing Doctoral Students' Completion, Achievement, and Well-being', *International Journal of Doctoral Studies*, 13, pp.361-388.
- Taha, N. and Cox, A. (2014) 'International students' networks: a case study in a UK University', *Studies in Higher Education*, 41(1), pp.182-198. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2014.927851> (Accessed: 29 April 2023).
- Tan, S. and Yip, A. (2018) 'Hans Selye (1907–1982): Founder of the Stress Theory', *Singapore Medical Journal*, 59 (4), pp.170-171.
- Tayyab, M. (no date) Ramadan Away from Loved Ones as an International Student | Amaliah, Amaliah. Available at: <https://www.amaliah.com/post/58993/lockdown-away-from-loved-ones-as-an-international-student-ramadan-muslim>.
- Teichler, U. (2017) 'Internationalization Trends in Higher Education and the Changing Role of International Student Mobility', *Journal of international Mobility*, 1(5), pp. 177-216.
- Teijlingen, E. and Hundley, V. (2002) 'The Importance of Pilot Studies', *Nursing Standard*, 16(40), pp.33-36.
- Thanh, N. C., and Thanh, T. T. (2015) 'The Interconnection between Interpretivist Paradigm and Qualitative Methods in Education', *American Journal of Educational Science*, 1(2), pp.24-27.
- Thoits, P.A. (2010) 'Stress and Health: Major Findings and Policy Implications', *Journal of Health and Social Behavior*, 51(1_suppl), pp. S41–S53.
- Thomas, P.A., Liu, H. and Umberson, D. (2017) 'Family Relationships and Well-Being', *Innovation in Aging*, 1(3), pp. 1- 11.
- Thomas, F. and Sumathi, G.N. (2016) 'Acculturative Stress and Social Support among the International Students: An Empirical Approach', *Sona Global Management Review*, 10(3), 61-72.
- Tiliouine, H. and Achoui, M. (2018) 'Family characteristics and family life education in Algeria' In: Robila, M. and Alan C. Taylor, A. (eds.) *Global perspectives on family life education*. Cham: Springer, pp. 117-133.

Tobbell, J., O'Donnell, V. and Zammit, M. (2010) 'Exploring Transition to Postgraduate Study: Shifting Identities in Interaction with Communities, Practice and Participation', *British Educational Research Journal*, 36(2), pp. 261-278.

Tobin, E. T., Slatcher, R. B., and Robles, T. F. (2013) 'Family relationships and physical health: Biological processes and mechanisms', in Newman, M. L. and Roberts, N. A. (eds.) *Health and social relationships: The good, the bad, and the complicated*, American Psychological Association, pp. 145–165.

Toyoshima, A. and Nakahara, J. (2021) 'The Effects of Familial Social Support Relationships on Identity Meaning in Older Adults: A Longitudinal Investigation,' *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12.

Toyokawaa, T. and Toyokawa, N. (2002) 'Extracurricular Activities and the Adjustment of Asian International Students: A Study of Japanese Students', *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 26, pp. 363-479.

Tran, L.T. and Vu, T.T.P. (2017) '“Responsibility in Mobility”: International Students and Social Responsibility', *Globalisation, Societies and Education*, 15(5), pp. 561–575. Available at: doi:10.1080/14767724.2016.1195729.

Treem, J., Dailey, S., Pierce, C. and Biffel, D. (2016) 'What We Are Talking About When We Talk About Social Media: A Framework for Study', *Sociology Compass*, 10 (9), pp.768-784.

Turner, H. and Turner, R. (2005) 'Understanding Variations in Exposure to Social Stress', *Health*, 9 (2), pp.209-240.

United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs (2019) *The number of international migrants reaches 272 million, continuing an upward trend in all world regions, says UN*, Online, Available: <https://www.un.org/development/desa/en/news/population/international-migrant-stock-2019.html> (Accessed: 24 December 2019).

United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division (2017) *International Migration Report 2017: Highlights*. Available at: <https://www.un.org/development/desa/pd/content/international-migration-report-2017-highlights> (Accessed: 24 December 2019).

United States Census Bureau (2020) *Statistical Definition of 'Family' Unchanged Since 1930* Online. The United States Census Bureau. Available: <https://www.census.gov/newsroom/blogs/random-samplings/2015/01/statistical-definition-of-family-unchanged-since-1930.html> (Accessed 28 Jan 2020).

University World News (2013) *International mobility of African students - Report*. Online. Available at: <https://www.universityworldnews.com/post.php?story=20130705203103913> (Accessed: 11 January 2020).

U.S. Library of Congress (1994) *Family and Household*. Online Available at: <http://countrystudies.us/algeria/58.htm>

Verbik, L., & Lasanowski, V. (2007) 'International Student Mobility: Patterns and Trends. *World Education News and Reviews*, 20(10), 1-16.

Walker, P. (2014) 'International Student Policies in UK Higher Education from Colonialism to the Coalition: Developments and Consequences', *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 18(4), pp. 325-344. Available at: doi:10.1177/1028315312467355.

Waller, V., Farquharson, K. and Dempsey, D. (2016) *Qualitative social research: contemporary methods for the digital age*. London: SAGE.

Wang, C.-C.D. and Mallinckrodt, B. (2006) 'Acculturation, Attachment, and Psychosocial Adjustment of Chinese/Taiwanese International Students,' *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 53(4), pp. 422–433.

Wang, N.T. and Li, L.Y. (2011) '“Tell me what to do” vs. “guide me through it”: Feedback experiences of international doctoral students', *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 12(2), pp. 101–112. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1469787411402438>.

Wen, M. and Lin, D. (2012) 'Child Development in Rural China: Children Left Behind by Their Migrant Parents and Children of Nonmigrant Families', *Child Development*, 83(1), pp. 120–136.

Wilmsen, B. (2013) 'Family Separation and the Impacts on Refugee Settlement in Australia,' *Australian Journal of Social Issues*, 48(2), pp. 241–262.

Wilmsen, B. (2011) 'Family Separation: The Policies, Procedures, and Consequences for Refugee Background Families', *Refugee Survey Quarterly*, 30 (1), pp.44-64.

Wilmsen, B. (2013) 'Family Separation and the Impacts on Refugee Settlement in Australia', *Australian Journal of Social Issues*, 48(2), pp. 241–262. Available at: doi:10.1002/j.1839-4655.2013.tb00280.x.

Winchester-Seeto, T., Homewood, J., Thogersen, J., Jacenyik-Trawoger, C., Manathunga, C., Reid, A. and Holbrook, A. (2013) 'Doctoral supervision in a cross-cultural context: issues affecting supervisors and candidates', *Higher Education Research & Development*, 33(3), pp. 610–626. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2013.841648>.

World Migration Report 2018 (2018) Online Available at: https://www.iom.int/sites/default/files/country/docs/china/r5_world_migration_report_2018_en.pdf (Accessed: 24 December 2019).

Wray, M., Colen, C., and Pescosolido, B. (2011) 'The sociology of Suicide', *Annual Review of Sociology*, 37, pp. 505-528.

Wu, H.P., Garza, E. and Guzman, N. (2015) 'International Student's Challenge and Adjustment to College', *Education Research International*.

Yadav, S. and Shukla, A. (2017) 'A Comparative Study of Moral Values among the Children Belonging to Nuclear and Joint Families of Lucknow District', *International Educational Journal*, 4(1), pp. 118-124.

Yahirun, J.J. and Arenas, E. (2018) 'Offspring Migration and Parents' Emotional and Psychological Well-being in Mexico,' *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 80(4), pp. 975–991.

Yang, M. (2007) 'What Attracts Mainland Chinese Students to Australian Higher Education', *Studies in Learning, Evaluation Innovation and Development*, 4(2), pp. 1-12.

Yeh, C. and Inose, M. (2003) 'International Students' Reported English Fluency, Social Support Satisfaction, and Social Connectedness as Predictors of Acculturative Stress', *Counselling Psychology Quarterly*, 16 (1), pp.15-28.

Yin, R, k. (2014) *Case study research: design and methods*. 5th edn. London: SAGE.

Yin, R, k. (2003) *Case study research: design and methods*. 3rd edn. London: SAGE.

Yue, Y. and Lê, Q. (2013) 'Coping Strategies Adopted by International Students in an Australian Tertiary Context', *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Educational Studies*, 7(2), pp. 25-39.

Zhao, W., Osman, M. N., Omar, S. Z. and Yaakup, H. S. (2022) 'Mediating Role of Cultural Identity in the Relationship between Social Media Use Intensity and Social Media Use Purpose among Chinese International Students in Malaysia', *Studies in Media and Communication*, 10(2), pp. 201-217.

Zhiheng Zhang, Z. and Brunton, M. (2010) 'Differences in Living and Learning: Chinese International Students in New Zealand', *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 11(2), pp. 124-140.

Appendices

Appendix A- Freedom of Information Request Email

Dear Sir,

My request is for data about the mental health of post graduate students, UK national and international. I would like the following please:

1. For the past 3 years the numbers declaring to you a mental health issue, e.g., depression.
2. Break these statistics, in point 1, down by gender and ethnicity please.
3. The systems of support they have available to use within Edinburgh Napier University.
4. The types of mental health issue reported by its frequency, and its name/category.

Kind regards,

Houda AGGOUN.

Appendix B- Glasgow Caledonian University FOI Response

Glasgow Caledonian University – Response

-data about the mental health of post graduate students, UK national and international. I would like the following please:

1. For the past 3 years the numbers declaring to you a mental health issue, e.g, depression.
2. Break these statistics, in point 1, down by gender and ethnicity please.

Please find attached tables for postgraduate UK and international students in response to Qs 1 and 2. The tables cover only those students who declared that they had ‘A mental health condition, such as depression, schizophrenia or anxiety disorder’ – the relevant HESA field. It is possible that there are some students who may have responded that they had ‘Two or more impairments and/or disabling medical conditions’ but there is no further breakdown of this field to determine if a mental health condition is one of those.

UK students

A mental health condition, such as depression, schizophrenia or anxiety disorder	2015/16	2016/17	2017/18
TOTAL	19	27	46
Female			
White	15	19	22
BME			5
Male			
White	3	8	18
BME			
Unknown	1		1

International students

A mental health condition, such as depression, schizophrenia or anxiety disorder	2015/16	2016/17	2017/18
TOTAL	4	5	8
Female			
White	1	1	3
BME	1	2	2

Unknown	1		
Male			
White	1	1	2
BME		1	1

3. The systems of support they have available to use within Glasgow Caledonian University.

Please see the link below:
<https://www.gcu.ac.uk/student/studentlife/healthandwellbeing/studentwellbeing/>

4. The types of mental health issue reported by its frequency, and its name/category.

There is no further drill down of mental health conditions to separate out individual conditions so we do not hold this information. As we do not record this information, the University is relying on an exemption in the Freedom of Information (Scotland) Act 2002 Section 17 (1) (b) Information not held.

Appendix C- University of Aberdeen FOI Response

Dear Houda Aggoun,

FREEDOM OF INFORMATION REQUEST FOI 2019-265

I refer to your email of 7 August 2019 requesting information relating to mental health.

Your request has now been considered under the Freedom of Information (Scotland) Act 2002, 'the Act'.

The following headcounts are for all registered students (Undergraduate, Postgraduate Taught, and Postgraduate Research) recorded with mental health difficulties in our Student Records System. These numbers exclude associate and visiting students. Students can update their information at any time during their studies.

Number of students declaring mental health difficulties:

ACADEMIC YEAR	HEADCOUNT
2016/17	355
2017/18	343
2018/19	320

Breakdown by gender and ethnicity:

ACADEMIC YEAR	FEMALE	MALE
2016/17	246	109
2017/18	237	106
2018/19	236	84

ETHNICITY	2016/17	2017/18	2018/19
Arab	2	3	3
Asian- Other	4	4	2
Bangladeshi	1	1	1
Black African	6	6	7
Black Caribbean	0	1	0
Indian	1	1	5
Mixed- Other	7	7	8

Mixed White- Asian African	1	1	1
Mixed White- Black African	4	2	2
Not known	1	3	6
Other	4	4	4
Pakistani	4	5	2
White	3	3	3
White- British	148	131	128
White- Irish	9	8	8
White- Other	81	84	67
White- Scottish	79	79	73

Our Student Records System only records a general self-declaration of ‘mental health difficulties’, there is no further breakdown into categories, such as depression. Please accept this message as notice under section 17(1)(b) of the Act that the information you have requested is not held by the University.

The University of Aberdeen has a number of ways to support students with mental health difficulties: Students can self-refer to counselling; visit the Student Advice and Support Team to speak to an advisor (they can also email or call); or discuss concerns with another member of staff (Personal Tutors or School Staff), who can refer a case or signpost them to appropriate help services. Students can also make use of self-help guides on our website and external sources of help to which we subscribe, such as accessing The Big White Wall.

Please see the following webpage for further information and links to guides.

<https://www.abdn.ac.uk/infohub/support/advice-and-support-office.php>

Should you be dissatisfied with this response, you have the right under the Act to request a review. A request for review must be made within 40 working days of the date of this reply. It must include your name and address for correspondence and specify the request for information and the grounds for dissatisfaction with the decision. Please send your request for review to our mailbox, foi@abdn.ac.uk. The University will respond to your request for a review within 20 working days of receipt of your request.

If you are unhappy with the outcome of the University's internal review, you have the right to appeal to the Scottish Information Commissioner within six months of the date of receipt of the University's review notice. Details on how to make an appeal to the Commissioner are available at www.itspublicknowledge.info/Appeal. Should you remain dissatisfied with the Commissioner's decision, you have a right of appeal to the Court of Session on a point of law.

Yours sincerely,

Mary Sabiston

Information Compliance Officer

University of Aberdeen

Appendix D- Edinburgh Napier University FOI Response

My request is for data about the mental health of post graduate students, UK national and international. I would like the following please:

1. For the past 3 years the numbers declaring to you a mental health issue, e.g, depression.

2018/19 28 PG students

2017/18 32 PG students

2016/17 27 PG students

*ethnicity to be updated

2. Break these statistics, in point 1, down by gender and ethnicity please.

2016/17

Gender:

25 females

10 males

Ethnicity:

White 24

Black 1

Asian 1

Other 1

2017/18

Gender:

20 females

12 males

Ethnicity:

White 25

Black 2

Asian 1

Other 4

2018/19

Gender:

18 females

10 males

Ethnicity:

White 26

Other 2

3. The systems of support they have available to use within Edinburgh Napier University.

The University provides support for student wellbeing in a number of ways across a number of teams. This work may not specifically be targeted at students requiring support with mental health issues but will benefit them should they wish to use those services. Additional information can be accessed via the links provided below, which are publicly available via the University website:

As part of the induction process:

<http://my.napier.ac.uk/New-Students/Next-Steps/Pages/Next-steps.aspx>

During induction and beyond:

<http://my.napier.ac.uk/Wellbeing-and-Support/Pages/Wellbeing-and-Support.aspx>

<http://my.napier.ac.uk/Careers-and-Development/Confident-Futures/Pages/Confident-Futures.aspx>

Please accept this as notice under s25 of the Freedom of Information (Scotland) Act 2002 that this information is otherwise accessible.

4. The types of mental health issue reported by its frequency, and its name/category.

The category recorded on the student's record system is 'Mental Health Condition', figures for this category have been provided in response to question 1 above.

This is not broken down any further, except for those students who choose to interact with student wellbeing & inclusion, who may have disclosed further detail.

Of those students who have sought support from wellbeing services, the following additional information is available:

Panic attacks 2

Panic and anxiety 2

Appendix E- Educational reforms in Algeria

1. Arabisation reform:

During the colonial period, Algeria was using French language as the language of government and education as this language was imposed by the French colonization. After independence in 1962, Algeria found itself in need of regaining its lost identity as an Arabic Muslim country which had been eliminated by the French colonialism (Rezig, 2011). Thus, Arabic was declared by the Algerian government as the national and official language in Algeria. By implementing the Arabisation reform, Algeria aimed to take out the linguistic and cultural aspects of the French colonization (Benrabah, 2005). Accordingly, it has been claimed that “in keeping with the spirit of the times, Algeria’s first president, Ahmed Ben Bella [1963–1965], instituted a policy of linguistic Arabization in primary schools” (Le Roux, 2017, p. 118).

In education, the main reform has been set after independence was the Arabisation reform for the sake of reviving the Arabic language. Beginning in 1962, the Algerian government worked to gradually increase Arabic sessions at all levels where all subjects were taught in Arabic while there was a decrease in the amount of time for teaching French; this strategy emphasised religion, national unity, and integrity (Benrabah, 2002 cited in Rezig, 2011). In 1966 and because of the lack of Algerian qualified teachers, the government sought to bring some skilled teachers in Arabic from the Middle East mainly from Egypt and Syria (Le Roux, 2017; Benrabah, 2005). Such a reform resulted in replacing French by Arabic language in schools as the standard language of instruction except for scientific subjects where French was used (Fekih, 2020; Selougui, 2019).

2. The Fundamental Schooling System reform:

The Fundamental Schooling System was introduced and applied in 1976 to combine the primary school with the middle school (9 years) where all the subjects apart from foreign languages were taught in Arabic (Bouzenoun, 2019). This reform resulted in the division of Algerian educators into two groups; those who supported teaching in French, the language of modernization, especially in scientific disciplines, and those who supported Arabic as a symbol of Algerian identity (Rabehi, 2021). English, however, was introduced to students as a foreign language class at the age of 13 in the middle school in that system. This was also objected by some teachers who opposed learning a foreign language at that age as it would be extremely difficult for students to speak it properly (Rezig, 2011). As a result, a suggestion that English language instruction should be offered to learners in primary education.

3. Teaching English in the Primary School reform:

In 1993 to promote teaching foreign languages to learners at early stages, primary school pupils were given the right to choose which foreign language they wish to study, English or French (Selougui, 2019). With this reform, English was introduced in the fourth grade of primary education in primary schools. Experts consider this to be a great change in foreign language teaching's history in Algeria (Daoud, 1996; Campbell, 1996 cited in Bellalem 2012). Unexpectedly however, the implementation of this reform in primary education has failed. This is because, learners' parents preferred teaching French than English as a first compulsory foreign language to their children in primary schools (Rezig, 2011; Benrabah, 2007). The reason behind that could be the use of French language by Algerians at that time because of the French colonization, which impacted their receptivity of a new foreign language. Accordingly, English was dropped from primary schools and was offered to students in middle schools' first year (Gherzouli, 2019).

Appendix G- Interview schedule for students

Thank you very much for accepting to take part in this interview. First, I confirm that your participation will totally remain anonymous, and your name will not be mentioned in the interview records.

Introductory questions:

1. Tell me, which part of Algeria are you coming from?
2. What ethnic group do you belong to?
3. What can you tell me about your family? How would you describe your family?
4. For how long have you been doing your PhD? How do you feel about it?

Social stress:

1. How would you describe yourself as an international PhD student?
2. What do you like the most about being an international student?
3. How have you found living away from your family so far?
4. How do you perceive stress in this context of your study abroad?
5. So far, what do you find the most challenging about your study abroad experience in the UK?
6. What do you usually do when you are stressed?

Family separation:

1. Can you explain what family separation is, in your own words?
2. How does family separation affect you?
3. What stresses you most about your family back home?
4. Thinking about family separation, in general, how well have you coped with it so far?

How did you manage to cope with it?

Appendix H- Interview schedule for family members (Arabic)

اسئلة المقابلة لأفراد الأسرة

شكرا جزيلاً على قبول المشاركة في هذه المقابلة. أولاً ، أؤكد أن مشاركتك ستبقى مجهولة تماماً ولن يتم ذكر اسمك في سجلات المقابلة.

أسئلة تمهيدية:

1- قل لي ، من أي منطقة في الجزائر أنت ؟

2- ما هي المجموعة العرقية التي تنتمي إليها ؟

3- ماذا يمكنك أن تخبرني عن عائلتك ؟ كيف تصف عائلتك ؟

4- منذ متى ابنك/ ابنتك/ اختك / اخوك يدرس الدكتوراه ؟

الضغوط الاجتماعية:

1- كيف تشعر حيال وجود ابن/ ابنة / أخت / أخ لك يدرس في الخارج؟ ما هو أفضل جزء/ شيء في ذلك ؟

2- كيف وجدت العيش مع فقدان او ابتعاد أحد أفراد عائلتك؟

3- كيف تنظر الى التوتر في سياق الانفصال عن ابنك/ ابنتك / أختك / أخوك ؟

4- حتى الآن، ما هو الشيء الذي تجده الأكثر صعوبة في انفصالك عن ابنك/ ابنتك / أختك / أخيك ؟

5- ماذا تفعل عادة عندما تشعر بالقلق والتوتر بشأن ابنك/ ابنتك / أختك / أخيك؟

الانفصال الأسري:

1- هل يمكنك وصف / شرح معنى ما هو الانفصال الأسري ، بكلماتك الخاصة ؟

2- كيف اثر عليك الانفصال العائلي؟

3- ما الذي يقلقك أكثر حيالهم ؟

4- فيما يخص الانفصال العائلي بشكل عام، كيف تعاملت معه حتى الآن؟

Appendix I- Interview schedule for family members (English)

Thank you very much for accepting to take part in this interview. First, I confirm that your participation will totally remain anonymous, and your name will not be mentioned in the interview records.

Introductory questions:

1. Tell me, which part of Algeria are you from?
2. What ethnic group do you belong to?
3. What can you tell me about your family? How would you describe your family?
4. For how long has your children been doing his/her PhD?

Social stress:

1. How do you feel about having a sister/ brother/ child studying abroad?
2. How have you found living missing a member of your family?
3. How do you perceive stress in this context of your study abroad?
4. So far, what do you find the most challenging about your being separated from your child?
5. What do you usually do when you are stressed?

Family separation:

1. Can you explain what family separation is, in your own words?
2. How does family separation affect you?
3. What stresses you most about them?
4. Thinking about family separation, in general, how well have you coped with it so far?

How did you manage to cope with it?

Appendix J- Ethics Approval

25/03/2021

Dear Houda Aggoun,

Your application 16256: Understanding the social stresses affecting Algerian PhD students in the UK during their PhD studies and their families back home in the context of family separation using social stress theory., submission 13499, has been approved by the Education and Social Sciences SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Iain McPhee

Appendix K- Consent form for students

Consent Form

University of the West of Scotland

School: Education and Social Sciences – Paisley Campus.

Researcher's Name: Aggoun Houda.

Study Title: Understanding the social stresses affecting the families of Algerian students and the students themselves during the period of their PhD studies in the UK in the context of family separation.

1. I hereby confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above research study. I also confirm that the researcher has answered all my queries about the research.
2. I understand that I voluntarily participate in this research study and I have the right to withdraw my participation at any time without giving reasons and without any consequences.
3. I consent to be a participant in the above-mentioned study.
4. I understand that I will participate in an online individual interview (and group interview if I show willingness to be involved in a group interview as well) and will be audio-recorded for this study.
5. I understand that all the recorded information I will provide for this research will last confidential and will not be available to public.

Name of participant:

Date:

Signature:

Name of Researcher:

Date:

Signature

Appendix L- Consent form for family members

استمارة موافقة

جامعة غرب اسكتلندا

الكلية: التعليم والعلوم الاجتماعية – بيزلي

اسم الطالبة: عقون هدى

عنوان الدراسة: فهم الضغوط الاجتماعية التي تؤثر على أسر الطلاب الجزائريين والطلاب أنفسهم خلال فترة دراستهم للدكتوراه في المملكة المتحدة في سياق الانفصال الأسري

أؤكد هنا أنني قرأت وفهمت ورقة المعلومات للدراسة البحثية المذكورة أعلاه. أؤكد أيضا أن الباحث قد أجاب على جميع استفساراتي حول البحث

أفهم أنني أشرك طوعا في هذه الدراسة البحثية ولدي الحق في سحب مشاركتي في أي وقت دون إبداء الأسباب ودون أي عواقب

أوافق على أن أكون مشاركا في الدراسة المذكورة أعلاه

أفهم أنني سأشارك في مقابلة فردية عبر الإنترنت (ومقابلة جماعية إذا أبديت استعدادا للمشاركة في مقابلة جماعية أيضا) وسيتم التسجيل السمعي لهذه الدراسة

أفهم أن جميع المعلومات المسجلة التي سأقدمها لهذه الدراسة ستكون و ستبقى سرية ولن تكون متاحة للآخرين

اسم المشارك

التوقيع

التاريخ:

اسم الباحث

التوقيع

التاريخ:

Appendix M- Participant Information Sheet for Students

University of the West of Scotland

School: Education and Social Sciences – Paisley Campus.

Research Study Title: Understanding the social stresses affecting the families of Algerian students and the students themselves during the period of their PhD studies in the UK in the context of family separation.

The research study is conducted by **Aggoun Houda**, an Algerian PhD student at the school of Education and Social Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland.

I would like to invite you to take part in this study, as your participation will be of a great contribution to the present research at micro level, and to research worldwide about international students and family separation at macro level.

What is the purpose behind this study?

The present research is aimed at understanding the stress- related social experiences of Algerian students in the UK in a study abroad context as well as their families back home in Algeria, and to know about family relationships and family separation in the context of these experiences. It seeks to explore how stressful the social life of families who are involved in the Algerian students' lives while studying abroad is, in addition to study the social life of the students themselves abroad when they are away from their families.

Do you have to take part in the research?

Participating in this research study is voluntary and choosing to take part in the research will not deprive participants from their right to withdraw the participation at any time without giving reasons and without any consequences.

What would participating in the research involve?

You will get involved in a 90-120 mints online semi-structured interview. The latter is mainly about your experiences of family separation and family relationships in the context of your study abroad in the UK while you are missing all your family members. That is, you will be interviewed about you experiences of the different stressful situations and their impact throughout your PhD journey in the UK as being separated from your family.

Why have you been invited to participate in the research?

You have to be an Algerian PhD student, sponsored by the Algerian government and taking a PhD course in a British university in the UK.

What are the possible risks of participating in the research?

No risks will arise to you from taking part in the current research except taking 1 to 2 hours of your time for the interview.

What will happen to the data you provided in the research?

The information provided by participants will be completely confidential and anonymous. The data will safely be saved within the university.

Please do not hesitate to ask any questions if you have some queries about the information written above. Thank you.

What is coming next?

If you have chosen to take part in this research, you will be given a consent form to sign to confirm your participation. The study is highly thankful for whomever devoted some time to read this information sheet whether they decide to take part or not.

This research study is governed by the ethical guidelines provided by UWS Ethics Committee and granted approval by the School of Education and Social Sciences Ethics Committee.

If you have any queries or want to direct a question for further information, please contact:

Professor Chris Holligan.

Researcher Contact Details:

Professor of Education

Houda Aggoun

School of Education and Social Sciences

School of Education and Social Sciences

University of the West of Scotland

University of the West of Scotland

Ayr Campus, University Avenue,

Paisley Campus

Ayr, KA8 0SR

Scotland, United Kingdom

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Appendix N- Participant Information Sheet for family members (Arabic)

وثيقة معلومات المشاركة لأفراد الأسرة

جامعة غرب اسكتلندا

الكلية: التعليم والعلوم الاجتماعية – بيزلي

عنوان الدراسة: فهم الضغوط الاجتماعية التي تؤثر على أسر الطلاب الجزائريين والطلاب أنفسهم خلال فترة دراستهم للدكتوراه في المملكة المتحدة في سياق الانفصال الأسري باستخدام نظرية الإجهاد الاجتماعي

يتم إجراء الدراسة من قبل **عقون هدي** ، طالبة دكتوراه جزائرية في كلية التعليم والعلوم الاجتماعية في جامعة غرب اسكتلندا.

أود أن أتشرف بدعوتكم للمشاركة في هذه الدراسة ، ذلك أن مشاركتكم ستكون ذات مساهمة كبيرة في تحقيق هذه الدراسة على المستوى الجزئي ، وفي الأبحاث في جميع أنحاء العالم حول الطلاب الدوليين والانفصال الأسري على المستوى الكلي.

ما هو الهدف من هذه الدراسة؟

تهدف هذه الدراسة إلى فهم التجارب الاجتماعية المرتبطة بالتوتر والمخاوف الاجتماعية لدى الطلاب الجزائريين في المملكة المتحدة في ظل الدراسة في الخارج وكذلك أسرهم في الجزائر ، ومعرفة طبيعة العلاقات الأسرية والانفصال الأسري في خضم هذه التجارب. تسعى هذه الدراسة أيضا إلى اكتشاف مدى توتر الحياة الاجتماعية لأسر الطلاب الجزائريين الذين يدرسون في الخارج ، بالإضافة إلى دراسة الحياة الاجتماعية للطلاب أنفسهم في الخارج بعيدا عن أسرهم.

هل يجب عليك أن تشارك في البحث؟

المشاركة في هذه الدراسة طوعية حيث ان اختيار المشاركة في البحث لن يحرم المشاركين من حقهم في التراجع و سحب مشاركتهم في أي وقت دون إبداء الأسباب ودون أي عواقب

على ماذا تنطوي المشاركة في البحث ؟

سوف تجري مقابلة شفوية لمدة حوالي 90-120 دقيقة على الانترنت . هذه المقابلة تعتمد أساسا عن تجاربك مع العلاقات الأسرية والانفصال الأسري المتعلقة بدراسة ابنك/ ابنتك/ اخوك / اخوك في الخارج في المملكة المتحدة حيث تفتقد العائلة فردا من افرادها. كما تتمحور المقابلة حول تجاربك في المواقف العصبية المختلفة التي مررت بها مع عائلتك وتأثيرها على حياتكم العائلية طوال رحلة الدكتوراه لابنك/ ابنتك/ اخوك / اخوك وكيفية تعاملك مع هذه المواقف

لماذا تمت دعوتك للمشاركة في البحث؟

يجب أن تكون فردا من أفراد العائلة لطالب دكتوراه جزائري ممنوح من الحكومة الجزائرية لدراسة الدكتوراه في إحدى الجامعات البريطانية في المملكة المتحدة لتشارك في هذه الدراسة

ما هي المخاطر المحتملة للمشاركة في هذه الدراسة ؟

لن تتجم أي مخاطر من مشاركتك في الدراسة الحالية باستثناء أخذ ساعة الى ساعتين من وقتك للمقابلة

ماذا سيحدث للمعلومات التي تقدمها في هذه الدراسة؟

ستكون المعلومات المقدمة من قبل المشاركين في هذه الدراسة سرية ومجهولة تماما وتستعمل لغرض الدراسة فقط. سيتم حفظ البيانات بأمان داخل الجامعة بدون ذكر اسمك في سجلات المقابلة. كما سيتم محو تسجيلات هذه المقابلة بمجرد الانتهاء من هذه الدراسة

من فضلك لا تتردد في طرح أي أسئلة إذا كان لديك بعض الاستفسارات بخصوص المعلومات المدونة أعلاه. شكرا على حسن تعاونكم

ما الذي سيأتي بعد ذلك ؟

إذا اخترت المشاركة في هذا البحث ، فستحصل على نموذج موافقة للتوقيع لتأكيد مشاركتك. الدراسة ممتنة للغاية لمن يكرس بعض الوقت لقراءة ورقة المعلومات هذه سواء قرروا المشاركة أم لا

تخضع هذه الدراسة للمبادئ التوجيهية الأخلاقية التي تقدمها لجنة الأخلاقيات في جامعة غرب اسكتلندا حيث منحت الموافقة من قبل لجنة أخلاقيات كلية التربية والعلوم الاجتماعية

إذا كان لديك أي استفسار أو سؤال للحصول على المزيد من المعلومات يرجى الاتصال بـ

البروفيسور

معلومات الاتصال بالباحث:

عقون هدى

بروفيسور في التعليم Chris HOLLIGAN

كلية التعليم والعلوم الاجتماعية

جامعة غرب اسكتلندا

عير ، اسكتلندا، المملكة المتحدة

كلية التعليم والعلوم الاجتماعية

جامعة غرب اسكتلندا

بيزلي ، اسكتلندا، المملكة المتحدة

Personal details withheld.

Appendix O- Participant Information Sheet for Family Members (English)

University of the West of Scotland

School: Education and Social Sciences – Paisley Campus.

Research Study Title: Understanding the social stresses affecting the families of Algerian students and the students themselves during the period of their PhD studies in the UK in the context of family separation.

The research study is conducted by **Aggoun Houda**, an Algerian PhD student at the school of Education and Social Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland.

I would like to invite you to take part in this study, as your participation will be of a great contribution to the present research at micro level, and at research worldwide about international students and family separation at macro level.

What is the purpose behind this study?

The present research is aimed at understanding the stress- related social experiences of Algerian students in the UK in a study abroad context as well as their families back home in Algeria, and to know about family relationships and family separation in the context of these experiences. It seeks to explore how stressful the social life of families who are involved in the Algerian students' lives while studying abroad is, in addition to study the social life of the students themselves abroad when they are away from their families.

Do you have to take part in the research?

Participating in this research study is voluntary and choosing to take part in the research will not deprive participants from their right to withdraw the participation at any time without giving reasons and without any consequences.

What would participating in the research involve?

You will get involved in a 90- 120 mints online in depth semi-structured interview. The latter is mainly about your experiences of family separation and family relationships in the context of your study abroad in the UK while you are missing all your family members. That is, you will be interviewed about you experiences of the different stressful situations and their impact throughout your PhD journey in the UK as being separated from your family.

Why have you been invited to participate in the research?

You have to be a family member of an Algerian PhD student who is sponsored by the Algerian government and take a PhD course in a British university in the UK.

What are the possible risks of participating in the research?

No risks will arise to you from taking part in the current research except taking an hour of your time for the interview.

What will happen to the data you provided in the research?

The information provided by participants will be completely confidential and anonymous. The data will safely be saved within the university.

Please do not hesitate to ask any questions if you have some queries about the information written above. Thank you.

What is coming next?

If you have chosen to take part in this research, you will be given a consent form to sign to confirm your participation. The study is highly thankful for whomever devoted some time to read this information sheet whether they decide to take part or not.

This research study is governed by the ethical guidelines provided by UWS Ethics Committee and granted approval by the School of Education and Social Sciences Ethics Committee.

If you have any queries or want to direct a question for further information, please contact:

Professor Chris Holligan,

Professor of Education

School of Education and Social Sciences

University of the West of Scotland

Ayr Campus, University Avenue,

Ayr, KA8 0SR

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Researcher Contact Details:

Houda Aggoun

School of Education and Social Sciences

University of the West of Scotland

Paisley Campus

Scotland, United Kingdom

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.